

SUDANESE LABOUR ACT 1997: “BEYOND TWO DECADES IN-
ACTION” A CRITICAL GAP ANALYSIS

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I hereby declare that I, Sulafa Gawish wrote this research entirely on my own and that it has not been presented in whole or in part in any prior application for any comparable academic award whatsoever. Unless otherwise stated by references or acknowledgement, this work submitted to UWS is completely mine.

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ABSTRACT

Purpose- To investigate the current Sudanese Labour Act of 1997 to assess its fitness for purpose.

Methodology- A Qualitative Strategy was used, involving critical opinions from a pool of experts in Sudanese Employment Regulations (selected through careful “non-random” judgmental sampling). In-depth semi-structured interviews were used to collect the data. The interviews were combined with a “Delphi Technique”, an interactive communication method to strengthen and confirm the findings. Finally, using “Thematic Analysis”, the data were carefully analysed and interpreted to make sense of the commonly shared meanings & perspectives led by Braun and Clarke’s 2006 Six-phase Guide.

Findings- Sudan-specific research was lacking. This justifies the criticality of the study and validates its relevance and urgency. The execution of the 1997 Act in the past 26 years has now proved it is inadequate for meeting business needs and ill-equipped for the twenty-first century. Furthermore, Sudan’s 1997 Act and complementary employment regulations are outdated and demand prompt attention and reform. They have shown a catalogue of failures. Not only is *Policy Reform* required, but so is *Institutional Reform*.

Limitations- The lack of previous research studies to rely on and support the investigation caused massive challenges. Sudan would benefit from additional research in this area. Most of the research was performed during COVID-19, and the data was gathered under difficult personal circumstances.

Originality & Value- An endeavour that is likely to be the first of its kind aimed at developing original knowledge, an area that has been significantly overlooked and understudied, hence attracting the attention of local scholars. The emerging themes will be extremely beneficial to both Sudanese Businesses and Policy Makers.

Practical Implication- It will enlighten Sudanese organisations, aid the development of robust HR policies, and inspire the Sudanese government to take proactive steps to reform for the benefit of the country.

Social implications- This subject has profound meaning to the working people of Sudan. It will promote good workplace practises, decent work, equality, and better working lives, an ambition shared by the ILO and the CIPD.

Keywords- Labour Law, Decent Work, Equality Act, ILO, Tripartite Committee, Labour Office

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I dedicate this work to my beloved country, Sudan, which has had no rest, and I pray for brighter days. And to the souls of my mother and father; and to my Husband Ahmed and my adored children, Omer, Tarig, Mustafa, Sameer, & Noon, who are the beat in my heart, the spark in my eyes, and the joy of my life.

Glossary of Abbreviations

ALO	Arab Labour Organisation
BBC	British Broadcasting Cooperation
CFR	Charter of the Fundamental Rights of the European Union
CIPD	Chartered Institute of Personnel and Development
CNN	Cable News Network
DPA	Dismissal Protection Act
DW	Decent Work
EDI	Equality Diversity and Inclusion
EEC	European Economic Community
EU	European Union
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HRM	Human Resource Management
HSE	Health and Safety Executive
ILC	International Labour Conference
ILO	International Labour Organisation
IMF	International Monetary Fund
ITUC	International Trade Union Confederation
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MDGs	Millennium Development Goal
MENA	Middle Eastern and North African

MSMEs	Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises
NEP	Sudan National Employment Policy
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisations
NIOSH	National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health
NPSIF	National Pension and Social Insurance Fund
OECD	Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development
OSHA	Occupational Safety and Health Administration)
PBUH	Peace Be Upon Him
PSMA	Personal Status for Muslims Act of 1991
R&D	Research and Development
SBEF	Sudanese Businessmen and Employers Federation
SLFS	Sudan Labour Force Survey
SWTUF	Sudan Workers Trade Union Federation
TA	Thematic Analysis
TFEU	Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union
UFW	Unacceptable Forms of Work
UN	United Nations
UWS	University of the West of Scotland

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CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

1.1. Introduction

Before the Industrial Revolution, employers had absolute sovereignty over how they governed their workers (Arthurs, 2011). Still, in the early years of the Industrial Revolution, laws emerged to protect the most vulnerable workforce from the wicked brutality and physical harm that was regrettably practised. It wasn't until the late nineteenth and early twentieth centuries that the first legislation was passed, and employment laws established simple structures focusing on collective problems (Arthurs, 2011). Since then, these rules and regulations have consistently developed, modernised, and updated to best suit humanity's progressing values and circumstances. Anglo-American societies have pioneered the development of employment laws and supported their progression.

History has successfully shown the value of labour laws and their impact on regulating our work environments. The World Bank confirms that labour laws increase stability, boost productivity, and serve as a safeguard for both workers and employers. Labour laws are integral to business because they protect workers' and employers' rights and regulate business activities. Still, they also create stable, favourable business environments that attract investment, contributing to economic growth and development. According to (Deakin, 2016), all historical and theoretical studies show that labour laws and regulations that protect workers positively impact economic growth and development.

The UK's Chartered Institute of Personnel and Development (CIPD) recommends that for effective employment regulations, all existing and fresh employment law components be scrutinised regularly to determine their fitness for purpose (CIPD, 2017). Like many African and Middle Eastern countries, Sudan unfortunately lags in developing and implementing effective labour laws. After gaining independence in 1956, Sudan naturally followed the lead of industrialised developed nations that paved the way for these practices. Customising and developing the laws they felt best fit their people, which they did very well initially; however, as an ancient Arabic proverb goes, "achieving glory is difficult, but maintaining it is even more difficult." The degree to which these principles were observed and enacted was also up to their discretion, perceptions, and social, political, and cultural practices.

1.2. The Research Problem

Labour law in many Middle Eastern and North African (MENA) countries is shaped by characteristics of the post-independence social contract. Each of these MENA nations has its history of labour law development, with varying labour market circumstances and contrasting legal and social protection systems; these laws are outdated, with some dating back to the 1960s in Kuwait and Lebanon, for example (Angel-Urdinola and Kuddo, 2010). Sudan does not differ from these nations; it faces further challenges and struggles. The first official sets of laws were released with reasonable momentum and were not as ancient as the nation. The diagram below illustrates the historical progression:

Figure 1:1 Time Series of Sudan Labour Laws Progression & Development

Source: (Original)

Following the 1981 Labour Relations Act, the Sudanese Labour Act of 1997 came into action. Since then, the legalisation has remained static for the last 26 years (a quarter-century), failing to keep up with changes in Human Resource practises and best practice international employment laws and regulations in the previous two decades. The Sudanese Labour Act 1997 may have responded reasonably to Sudanese labour market requirements and work challenges for the first five years. However, in 2005, following hands-on actual application, the researcher realised that this legislation was unsuitable. The researcher and many other practitioners have frequently met obvious core gaps in the 97 Act and found it challenging to resolve some fundamental daily workplace problems that are not supported by law. The law is out of date, out of touch and unfit to handle the issues of the twenty-first century, with all its significant changes and evolutions.

Since then, the researcher has continued to advocate for scrutiny and investigation that could lead to the effective incorporation of core best practice legislation. The researcher is determined to make a difference to her country and people in this critical area. Labour regulations not only protect workers' rights but also determine the flexibility in the labour market. They regulate interactions between employers, employees, unions, and other

employers' associations; they serve as a means of creating a more favourable environment for the creation of productive employment opportunities and the enrichment of social dialogue. International research affirms that, among other things, labour laws are an essential basis for a favourable investment climate. Unfortunately, a study conducted by the World Bank confirms all MENA firms surveyed believe that their labour regulations constitute a significant holdback in doing business (Angel-Urdinola and Kuddo, 2010).

1.3. Rational of the Study

From the beginning, the 1997 copy failed to convince even its caretaker. The latest version was barely different from the previous ones and lacked the effort to implement the required change. It is a continuation of the old rules established in the 1960s, 1970s, and beyond, with no substantial modification or resilience to the problems they bring. They were created to serve the Sudanese economy in the early 1960s (post-independence) when it was mainly built on agriculture and Agri-processing factories, and they still live in that era. Despite their adherence, the laws are not serving the expectations of small, medium, and large businesses across the country; they are all struggling with the application.

It is also worth mentioning that several attempts to upgrade the Act of 1997 on several occasions across the years; however, none of them were successful as the three partners who make up the governing body (Tripartite Committee) never saw eye to eye and never agreed to anything. As there was no consensus, all their attempted endeavours never took shape, and they never endorsed a copy comprehensive enough to serve all the aspects needed by the private sector for the 3rd millennium. An extensive copy merging all labour legislations into one unified Act highlighting the principal labour law rules of public order, binding rules that may not be violated, with the concept of equality visible and decent work principles at the heart of employment.

According to international best practice benchmarks, MENA countries, including Sudan, are defiantly lagging (there is no doubt about it); the laws that govern governance in employment are incompatible; for example, despite protective regulations, most MENA countries remain unprotected from unemployment hazards, trade unions (whether state or independent) hardly ever effectively represent workers, and law enforcement itself remains very weak in most of these countries (Angel-Urdinola and Kuddo, 2010). The same study concluded that changes or reforms to labour laws in MENA countries must coexist with changes to social protection

systems, such as social support networks, unemployment insurance, and other government-backed social protection policies (all backed by the government).

This means it is not just about labour regulations but a broader view of all the supporting mechanisms governing successful employment. The Sudanese workplace requires new, robust, and fully rejuvenated employment laws; modern organisations are operating in Sudan today, as well as others who intend to invest in Sudan soon and require modern, just laws to operate effectively; for this reason, we must reinvent the rules to address the challenges and make Sudan an appealing investment hub.

The starting point is to discuss the fundamental challenges and gaps that are missing in the 1997 Act: problems areas such as Equality, Diversity & Inclusion, Harassment, flexible contractual Agreements, Data Protection, Health & Safety, and numerous others besides all other corresponding social protection legislations that work hand in hand with the Act such as minimum wage policies, unemployment protections, trade union representations, and the enforcement of the law itself. The 1997 Labour Act, as well as the complete employment system, requires urgent attention and reform. No study has set a precedent; nothing has been done scientifically to identify the issues and best explain how to fix the problem.

Thus, there is a need for this study to identify this gap and consider the issue in widely accepted international best practice ideologies and frameworks. This study aims to critically examine and investigate the current Sudanese Labour Act, last updated in 1997 (a quarter-century ago), to assess its fitness for purpose. It introduces the problem, reflects on it in global best-practice ideologies and contemporary frameworks, and makes valuable recommendations that can effectively contribute to any forthcoming policy change & reform or any development endeavour shortly. It is based on the following straightforward and concise research questions and objectives.

1.4. The Research Direction

The study aims to investigate the current Sudanese Labour Act of 1997 to assess its fitness for purpose. It sets out to do so by answering three questions and achieving three objectives, as stated in the table below:

Table 1:1 “The Research Direction”

Research Aim	Research Questions	Research Objectives
<i>The aim of this research is to investigate the current Sudanese Labor Act of 1997 to assess its fitness for purpose.</i>	<i>What are the key aspects of the Sudanese Labor Act?</i>	<i>To identify the key aspects of the Sudanese Labor Act.</i>
	<i>What challenges can be identified within the Act in the context of international best practices?</i>	<i>To assess the critical challenges the Sudanese Labor Act faces in light of international best practices</i>
	<i>What strategies can be in place to ensure the Sudanese Labor Act meets the twenty-first century needs?</i>	<i>To identify the strategies and techniques for updating the Labor Act in order to suit Sudan's current HR needs.</i>

Source: (Original)

1.5. The Research Process

This research project is data-driven, and the researcher adopts an inductive approach while she studies the Sudanese Labour Act of 1997 and develops a theoretical explanation as the data is collected and examined. According to (Saunders *et al.*, 2015), an inductive approach may be challenging to implement and may not provide triumph for an inexperienced researcher! However, this will probably happen if the researcher rushes through the data-gathering process without scrutinising it to see if any common patterns emerge. For this reason, the researcher carefully analysed the data as and when it was obtained and developed a logical framework to guide the study from the beginning. Qualitative research mainly relies on semi-structured in-depth interviews to acquire data, data that is exploratory, descriptive, explanatory, and evaluative, making it a dual-purpose study.

It is a social problem which includes crucial perspectives from a pool of carefully chosen professionals and experts in the field (a cautious “non-random” judgemental selection process was used). The data is meticulously collected, presented, and summarised verbally through in-depth semi-structured interviews. The interviews were combined with the “Delphi Technique,” a structured, interactive communication technique, to strengthen the data and confirm the findings. Finally, with considerable sensitivity and receptiveness to the data’s dynamic and complex character, it is analysed and interpreted meaningfully using “Thematic Analysis” to observe, clarify, and make sense of the commonly shared meanings and

different points of view. Below is the research process/ framework developed by the researcher.

Figure 1.2 The Research Process

Source: (Original)

1.6. Research Organisation

The author divided this study into nine chapters.

Chapter One: Introduction

Chapter Two: Literature Review Part I (*Origins & Background*)

Chapter Three: Literature Review Part II (*The Evolution of the Employment Relationship*)

Chapter Four: Methodology Part I (*The Framework*)

Chapter Five: Methodology Part II (*Analysing the Data Thematically*)

Chapter Six: Analysis & Discussion Theme I (*Key Aspects & Features*)

Chapter Seven: Analysis & Discussion Theme II (*Major Issues & Challenges*)

Chapter Eight: Analysis & Discussion Theme III (*Strategic Direction & Way Forward*)

Chapter Nine: Conclusion & Recommendations

1.7. Ethical Considerations

All relevant access concerns have been thoroughly examined considering the nature of the study, and all necessary and appropriate ethical considerations and protocols have been ensured in line with and in compliance with the principles of UWS's Research Ethical Committee. All ethical considerations regarding honesty, transparency, respect, confidentiality, anonymity, and safeguarding relationships are considered. In addition to the researcher's credibility, that is never compromised! All work is rigorously governed by the University of the West of Scotland's four major ethical principles for research with Human Participants (2016) as set below:

- Autonomy, Veracity & Informed Consent
- Privacy & Confidentiality
- Justice & Inclusiveness
- Benefits & Harms

Furthermore, the researcher is cautious and mindful of safeguarding data protection and equality when dealing with others and thus adheres to other regulatory standards that effectively apply to research, such as

- The Data Protection Act
- The Freedom of Information Act
- The Equality Act of 2010

CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW PART I

(Origins & Background)

2.1. Introduction

Sudan is one of Africa's most imperative nations, sandwiched between two great powers, Egypt and Ethiopia, bordering the Red Sea in a volatile region. (International Crisis Group, 2019). Sudan is a hugely diverse country; it is the residence of a vast variety of ethnic groups, rich with culture, religion, and languages. Between 1999 and 2010, Sudan's economic growth was primarily driven by oil production. However, the independence of South Sudan in 2011 led to a need for diversification and short-term austerity measures. Sudan lost 75% of its oil output, 55% of its fiscal income, and two-thirds of its foreign exchange profits because of this irreversible shock (ILO, 2014). Despite the substantial oil revenues, Sudan has adopted an unsustainable development route, consuming a significant portion of its wealth because of its focus on expenditure and importation rather than production and exportation (Lee, 2012).

Figure 2.1 Important Historical & Political Events

Source: (Original Inspired by an Article in the BBC World Africa 2019)

Figure 2.2: Sudan GDP Growths

According to official World Bank data, Sudan's (GDP) was worth 26.11 billion US dollars in 2020.

The GDP value of Sudan represents only 0.02 per cent of the world economy!

Sudan's GDP averaged 18.61 Billion Dollars from 1960 to 2020, with a peak of 65.63 Billion Dollars in 2010 and a minimum of 1.31 Billion Dollars in 1960.

Source: (World Bank)

Figure 2.3 Sudan Annual Growth Rate

Sudan's (GDP) annual Growth Rate decreased from 2.50 per cent in 2019 to -8.40 per cent in 2020.

Source: (tradingeconomics.com -Sudan Central Bureau of Statistics)

Figure 2.4 Sudan Unemployment Rate

Unemployment in Sudan rose to 17.70 per cent in 2020 from 16.80 per cent in 2019.

Source: (ILO)

Figure 2.5 Sudan Population Size

According to the United Nations (UN) data and estimations, Sudan's 2020 midyear population was around 43.85 million in 2020.

Source: (World Bank)

According to the International Monetary Fund (IMF) data, non-oil real GDP growth fell to 4.6 per cent in 2012, indicating a broad-based fall in economic activity. This financial crisis occurred when Sudan's high population growth rate resulted in a very young population; young people between 15 and 29 comprise more than 51 per cent of the working-age population. The International Organization for Migration 2011 estimated and expected Sudan to have 880,000 and 1,330,000 economic migrants, with more than 50% settling in Saudi Arabia and only a tiny percentage headed to Western nations (Al-Tohami, 2011).

2.2. The Economy and Employment

Sudan is heavily reliant on natural resources and a few major commercial partners. As the agriculture sector's contribution to GDP rose from 31.2% in 2010 to 34.1% in 2011 and was projected to rise to 39.4% in 2012, the service sector's contribution to GDP was about 43% (African Economic Outlook, 2012). Agriculture's value added increased by 9.3% in 2018 and was anticipated to increase by 15% in 2012. Agriculture employs over half of the country's workforce, accounting for nearly 45% of total employment. The service sector employs around 40% of the workforce, while the industry employs about 15% (Sudan Labour Force Survey- SLFS, 2011). Due to the reduction in oil production and related processing

operations, the industrial sector, including mining, accounted for 23% of GDP in 2011 and fell to 15.9% in 2012 (ILO, 2014).

Figure 2.6 GDP by Sector

Source: (African Economic Outlook 2012)

Figure 2.7 Employments by Sector & Gender

Source: (Sudan Labour Force Survey, 2011)

Based on the fieldwork and a Thematic Paper performed via ILO programs led by Ahmed Abou El-Yazeid in 2013 (Sudan's Small and Medium Companies), the estimated total number of micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs) in Sudan in 2013 was about 600,000. They officially employ less than 1.5 million people, about 20% of the total number of employees in Sudan. This indicates that the informal shadow economy employs a substantial proportion of the Sudanese workforce.

The Ministry of Human Resources Development and Labour, according to the ILO (2014) records, has attempted to determine the number of working poor using the latest Labour Force Survey results; one of the metrics chosen for the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) is the percentage of employed people living below the poverty line (working poverty rate). According to its recent estimates, over 30% of working people in Sudan live in homes that are below the poverty threshold despite their employment and income. This study has significant policy implications, as it proves that having a job in Sudan does not mean it is meant to escape poverty for many workers.

Therefore, policymakers must work hard, pay close attention to the quality of employment produced in the economy and people's earnings, and make serious efforts to align the two; people work to make a living and thrive, not to go through struggles, strive and barely survive!

2.3. Gender Inequalities

The ILO's employment statistics confirm the apparent gender gap in the Sudanese employment market. Men have over three times the employment-to-population ratio as women (61.4% versus 19.6%). Young Sudanese women have the same relative labour market disadvantages as males in their optimum working years. The gender gap unfolds at a younger age (15-24) when young males have a job rate of 28.9% and young women have a job rate of 11.4%.

Figure 2.8 Labour Force Participation Rate Age-group and Gender

Source: (Sudan Labour Force Survey, 2011)

2.4. Labour Reform Challenges

Sudan is currently confronted with both quantitative and qualitative labour market obstacles. The efficacy of measures adopted to assist people’s transition to “*decent employment*” is influenced by the institutional framework regulating the labour market and how governmental policies are designed and managed. The ILO analysed data on the Sudanese labour market in 2014 and found that it points to three broad areas of policy ambitions that could shape job creation and development in Sudan:

- i. The role of macro-economic and industrial policies on employment creation through funding for small and micro-enterprises, together with the social economy
- ii. Education and Training strategies and their significance to the labour market demand to enhance employability.
- iii. Labour market legislation and structures that seal the gap between demand and supply for labour and the protection and safeguarding of employees’ interests.

Sudan’s National Employment Policy (NEP), according to the ILO, should establish and foster a “Decent Work” vision for economic growth and recovery. In this context, the NEP and other stakeholders should go into great detail about the various aspects of employment

endorsement that play a role in national policy, such as the protection of the fundamental rights and principles at work, as well as other rights involving working conditions, such as wages, occupational safety and health, social security, and working hours; the employment relationship, and labour management and the protection of migrant and foreign workers, public-sector labour working conditions, and social dialogue techniques (ILO, 2014).

2.5. Sudan Labour Laws Progression & Development

After gaining independence in 1956, Sudan, like many African and Middle Eastern colonies, naturally followed the lead of industrialised developed countries that paved the way for these practices. Customising and developing the laws that they believed well suited their people, they did; however, as an old Arabic saying goes: *“Reaching glory is difficult, but what’s more difficult is maintaining it”*. The extent to which these rules have been followed and implemented was also left to their judgement, perceptions, and cultural practices. In many MENA countries, labour legislation is shaped by specific features of the social contract established in the post-independence era. Each of these MENA countries has its history of labour law development, with differing labour market conditions and contrasting legal and social security systems; these laws are outdated and some root back to the 1960s, for example, Kuwait and Lebanon (Angel-Urdinola & Kuddo 2010).

Sudan does not differ from these countries and is overwhelmed by its challenges and struggles. The first official sets of laws were published with relatively fair momentum and were not as ancient as the nation. The illustration below shows the historical progression.

Figure 2.9 Time Series of Sudan Labour Laws Progression & Development

Source: (Original)

Following the 1981 Labour Relations Act, the **Sudanese Labour Act of 1997** came into action. Since then, legalisation has been static for the last 25 years (a quarter of a century); it has not coped with any changes in human resource practices and best practices in

international employment laws and regulations that have occurred in the last two decades. With all its significant changes and evolutions, it is certainly not equipped for the 21st century. At some point in time, maybe within the first five years, the Sudanese Labour Act of 1997 may have been the answer to the needs of the Sudanese labour market and employment challenges. However, in 2005, after hands-on practical application, it came to the researcher's attention and understanding that this legislation did not fit the purpose. Upon everyday application, the researcher and many other practitioners have regularly encountered apparent gaps in the *97 Act* and found it challenging to resolve some fundamental everyday issues in the workplace that are not backed up by the legislation.

Fundamental gap areas include *Equality, Discrimination, Bullying, Harassment & Sexual Harassment, Diversity & Inclusion and Data Protection*. Since then, the researcher has continued to battle for scrutiny and investigation, effectively incorporating core best practice legislations. She is determined to make a difference to her country and people in this critical area. Labour regulations do not just protect workers' rights but also largely determine the amount of flexibility the labour market has, regulate the interactions between employers, employees, unions and other employers' associations, and serve as the means of establishing a more favourable environment for the creation of productive employment opportunities and enrichment of social dialogue. International knowledge confirms that, among many other factors, labour regulations constitute an essential foundation for a favourable investment climate. Unfortunately, a study conducted by the World Bank affirms that all MENA firms surveyed believe that their labour regulations are a significant holdback in doing business (Angel-Urdinola and Kuddo, 2010).

2.6. A Global Perspective

Anglo-American societies have been at the forefront of developing employment laws and advocating for continuous improvement. According to a CIPD report on employment regulations in the UK (2017, p.4), "*All aspects of existing and proposed employment law need regular and careful scrutiny to assess whether they are fit for purpose.*" In June 2013, **ILO** recognised protecting workers from *unacceptable forms of work (UFW)* as one of the most essential practices and the top critical priority of the organisation in the years 2014 & 2015. These unacceptable forms of work have been described by the ILO as "*comprising conditions that deny fundamental principles and rights at work, put at risk the lives, health,*

freedom, human dignity and security of workers or keep households in conditions of poverty” (ILO, 2013, para. 49). Furthermore, in 2017 the ILO communicated its breakthrough five-year strategy (Fundamental Principles & Rights at Work Strategy 2017-2023) underpinned by a theory of change that reproduce the essential meaning of the 1998 Declaration on Fundamental Principles & Rights at Work and the 2008 Declaration on Social Justice for a Fair Globalisation. This strategy is based on four intertwined change categories (Public Policies & Governance, Empowerment & Representation, Partnerships & Advocacy and Knowledge & Data Fig. 2).

Figure 2.10 ILO-Fundamental Principles and Rights at Work

Source: (ILO, 2019)

The principles are a clear baseline and threshold that protect and promote practical labour standards, one that can be used as a benchmark to see where countries like Sudan, for example, fit in terms of these principles. Developing countries have freed their economies in the past three decades by reducing regulations, privatising, and promoting market linearisation. Nevertheless, they have also designed and strengthened their labour laws and regulations (Coslovsky, 2014), making a clear, significant suggestion for constant maintenance (solid, robust labour regulations) under all economic circumstances.

Sudan's labour act is outdated, has been static for over two decades and is by far not equipped for the challenges of the 21st century. Sudan must thus follow the lead of other developing nations and work hard quickly and continuously to cope with contemporary developments in Labour regulations and level up their human resource practices. The researcher has the required experience, skills, competence, and connections to lead this research and formulate valuable recommendations to add value to her homeland.

2.7. Understanding Labour and Employment Laws

According to (Davidov and Langille, 2011), labour law is considered in crisis! How did that alarming status come to be when we consider labour law a warrior in history and a saviour of all times? They believe that many scholars have widely attacked labour laws for holding back the desired efficiencies, flexibilities, and progress. Despite this criticism, one cannot deny its value to the business world in governance and controls. Yes, people seek elasticity and autonomy, but imagine if we had to operate without these laws; complete chaos is the answer! The World Bank, in its 2015 *Doing Business Report*, stated that it is undoubtedly essential and needful to have employment regulations in place; without doubt, these are to protect not just employees from inconsistencies, uniformed practices, injustice, and clashes but also defend employers and help create effective contractual relationships between the two parties.

The World Bank confirms that labour laws increase stability, enhance productivity, and act as a protection shield for workers and employers. All historical and theoretical studies indicate that labour laws and regulations to protect workers have positive economic growth and development outcomes (Deakin, 2016). Deakin recommends that labour laws be perceived as “developmental institutions” that symbolise the global rise of capitalism and the transition to free market economies rather than parameters that hold the business back. Hyde (2006) described labour and employment laws as a collection of regulatory techniques and the set of values correctly applied to any market; if left unregulated, it will undoubtedly cause socially inferior and minimal outcomes, as economic actors are individuated and cannot overcome collective action problems.

Labour Law is considered a distinct field on its own, and one of the most essential starting points for understanding labour law is the “*Universal Declaration of Human Rights*”

adopted by the United Nations in 1948, which identifies many of the characteristic objectives of labour law:

“Everyone has the right to work, to free choice of employment, to just and favourable conditions of work and protection against unemployment. Everyone, without any discrimination, has the right to equal pay for equal work. Everyone who works has the right to just and favourable remuneration, ensuring for himself and his family an existence worthy of human dignity, and supplemented, if necessary, by other means of social protection. And everyone has the right to form and to join trade unions for the protection of his interests”

(UN Article 23 P. 48)

Furthermore, *The International Labour Organisation Declaration* adopted in the year 1998 laid out clear ***Fundamental Principles and Rights at Work*** that are built on four fundamental categories or principles of rights and entrust all members to respect and promote these principles; these are the four categories:

- *Freedom of association and the effective recognition of the right to collective bargaining.*
- *The elimination of forced or compulsory labour.*
- *The abolition of child labour.*
- *And the elimination of discrimination regarding employment and occupation.*

The ILO needed to pilot these international priority guidelines worldwide, focusing on the critical, core and most widely accepted labour rights worldwide. It is considered a basic guideline and a fair means of governance for all. The declaration is respected and well-regarded by many. It is a giant leap forward for practical, manageable, and globally accepted labour rights, which can be effectively incorporated into local legislation and beyond border trade agreements (Hyde, 2006).

2.8. Why Sudan Labour Laws?

There are so many controversial employment issues in ***Sudan***, such as the minimum wage limit, for example, and how adequate and frequently it is updated, with inflation levels being very high and on a constant rise. These are disproportionate to the realities workers face besides the poor working conditions most must bear with, let alone the levels of inequality, discrimination, and social injustice. All these and beyond need urgent attention and have been neatly identified by the ILO as UFW, referred to as any working conditions that contradict

the basic principles and rights at work, putting people's lives at risk, affecting their health, limiting their freedoms, dignity & humanity, and safety; or fail to maintain households in acceptable conditions away from poverty (ILO, 2013). The initiative is well-regarded, one that recognised the importance of enhancing contemporary working lives in the early twenty-first century.

According to (Fudge and McCann, 2015), global comparative reports argue it has become equally evident to politicians and researchers that countries around the world, like Sudan, have noticeable patterns of working people who struggle and overwhelmingly drift away from "*decent work*". That's why it's crucial that this research investigates the level to which the Sudanese labour law caters for such inequalities and vulnerabilities and whether it is robust enough to align these global objectives and priorities to Sudan, a piece that fits within the global puzzle and demonstrates actions of UFW. We must also narrate our investigation of relevant studies and explore the options regarding context, applications, and lessons learned.

After surveying many research papers (Djankov and Ramalho, 2009), they published a study from 2004 to examine the effect of employment laws in developing countries. The study covered around 87 countries (*Eastern European, West African, and Latin American*). To strengthen their findings, they included a complete analysis of cross-country correlation. Because of their work, they revealed that because of rigid employment laws, developing countries have larger informal sectors and suffer from substantial unemployment issues, especially among youth and women. They also struggle with increased urban poverty and lower rates of startup businesses. They believe their research needs further empirical support from similar countries that have not been studied to comprehend further and confirm their findings. This avails the opportunity and room for additional research, especially in countries like Sudan, which are not mentioned in their conclusions.

Moreover, other studies of countries with closer cultures and similar circumstances, like MENA conducted by (Angel-Urdinola and Kuddo, 2010), provided the general background and the main features of *Employment Regulations* in this region and unveiled findings that are quite like the situation of the Sudanese Labour Act. First, these countries are lagging according to international best practice benchmarks; the laws that stipulate governance are not compatible; for example, despite the presence of protective regulations, most countries in MENA continue to be unprotected from unemployment hazards, trade unions (whether state

or independent) hardly ever symbolise workers effectively and the law enforcement itself remains very weak in most of these countries (Angel-Urdinola and Kuddo, 2010).

The study concluded that developments or reforms in labour regulations in MENA countries must go parallel with developments in social protection systems such as social support systems, unemployment insurance and other social protection policies championed by the governments. They also discovered that MENA trade unions still have strong political influence and support the status quo of post-independence public agreements, making it rather difficult to reform and a far-reaching process. Like the situation in Sudan, “deliberate negligence”, which backs and supports personal gains, is an obvious highlight, leading to a continual decline in the social and economic well-being of the people of Sudan.

Therefore, inevitably, one reviews the current Sudanese Labour Act of 1997, which never got the privilege of proper scrutiny in modern Sudanese history following recent global legislative developments. Mitchell, Petra, and Gahan (2014) issued “*The Evolution of Labour Law in India*”, which examined the trends and developments in Indian Labour Laws through time. Their work embarked on a survey of the literature on the grounds, investigating initially the various times in which Indian labour law has changed up to date. It examines the extent to which the Indian labour law schemes can be regarded as achieving its two fundamental goals: “the protection of labour” and “the maintenance of industrial harmony”.

They came to find that Indian labour law resembles the labour law of developed industrial nations. It has comprehensive legislation covering the minimum employment standards, social security, work-related health and safety issues...etc. They cover trade union regulations and their actions, set the guidelines/structure, and settle manufacturing disagreements favouring the general interest. Unfortunately, these fantastic regulations officially only cover a small portion of the Indian society and workforce and neglect the rest, showing an apparent malfunction of the system. Hence, they conclude for effectiveness; one must seek a versatile multipurpose approach to labour regulations for India (Mitchell *et al.*, 2014), a lesson learned by the researcher and an eye opener approach to considering a more robust and inclusive strategy for Sudan.

2.9. The Significance of Employment Laws...Why Govern?

According to (Djankov and Ramalho, 2009), free labour markets are predominantly imperfect, and this is the logic behind the interventions led by governments in the labour markets. As a result, there is a rift in the employee/employer relationship and characteristically, employers exploit workers unfairly, creating apparent inefficiencies. For this reason, greater power must float on top of employers; otherwise, vulnerable groups will be taken for granted. This is demonstrated by the unfair discrimination practised on deprived and vulnerable groups, payment of low salaries, and unlawful terminations for employees who eventually are supported and taken care of by the governments. They can also suppress employees and force them against their will to work long hours, threatening them with job loss and humiliation.

They also fail to secure workers against the likely threats of disability, sickness, and death. Governments try to govern the fragile employment relationship within the free market to address perceived injustice and inequality. Across the world, nations have developed an array of legal systems to safeguard the rights and interests of workers and employees, protecting their livelihoods and hence shielding the larger population, ensuring a bare minimum standard of living deserved by all (Djankov and Ramalho, 2009).

2.10. Dignity at work

To enjoy a decent, fulfilled life, people need to have dignity at work, so working with dignity is a prerequisite to realise that fulfilment. Despite the tremendous struggles and challenges workers face daily, they exert their utmost effort to perform at their best and deliver the maximum outcome and results, taking pride in what they do. They do that while facing humiliation from their bosses and sometimes even their colleagues (Hodson, 2001). We believe that workers must be protected from abuse at work and cared for by governments by developing and providing the appropriate rules and regulations that defend them and act as a safety net throughout their working lives.

The researcher sympathises with workers as one of them and knows what it could be like. One might naively assume that dignity is established by default and by the implied daily standards of mutual value and respect. Nonetheless, in the brutal, cruel, messy, and materialistic world of work, the reality is entirely different, and dignity appears to be threatened. Dignity is significant for our well-being and enormously impacts employee

fulfilment and job satisfaction, but it is jeopardised for many reasons (Sayer, A., 2007). The perception of oneself and respect relies massively on the treatment of others, especially those we meet and associate with regularly; although work is not the sole moral game we encounter in our lives, however for those employed, it is of fundamental meaning and working with dignity and self-respect makes a massive difference (Calhoun, 2003).

The historian E. P. Thompson 1963 argued that most political struggles, including the emergence of the Labour Movement itself, were not just about gaining wealth and realising materialistic advantages but were pursuing recognition and respect (Thompson, 1963; Sennett and Cobb, 1973). Dignity matters, it needs to be discussed and championed by further research and critical management studies (Sayer, 2007). Let's take, for example, "*Bullying and Harassment*", two forms of brutality and injustice that are constantly struggled, resisted and escaped in the workplace. The British writer Andrea Adams (1992) brilliantly developed the phrase "*Workplace Bullying*", which was immediately recognised by people across the world, people who could easily relate to the term and know what it means (Namie G. and Namie R., 2009).

In developed countries like the United Kingdom and the United States, *harassment* is illegal by state and federal laws and *bullying* cuts across its boundaries; it is harassment described by Gray and Ruth Namie, 2009 in their book "*The Bully at Work: What You can do to stop the hurt and reclaim your dignity on the job*"-status-blind harassment. The National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health (NIOSH) 2005 summoned a particular intervention covering workplace "*Aggression*" and workplace "*Violence*". It recognised bullying as an official form of workplace violence (Namie, G. and Namie, R., 2009).

Across the world, people experience the same brutal humiliation and indignity with no consequences. It is not referred to, referenced, or revealed by anyone; it is hardly mentioned. The fact of the matter is that the words "Bullying" and "Harassment" are two examples of workplace injustice and inequality that don't even exist literally in the Arabic dictionary, let alone in its Labour Laws, specifically referencing and referring to the Sudanese Labour Act of 1997 that does not mention a word in relevance!

2.11. A Historical Perspective

The official regulation of employment did not come into action until the Industrial Revolution. Before that, regulating employment was not a subject that occupied the hearts and minds of legislators (Floyd et al., 2017). Religious morality and personal principles might

have guided people's practices with labour issues or not. For instance, there were arbitrary attempts to govern and control employment that were tracked back to the year 1351 in England following the Black Death of 1348-1349, an epidemic that swiped the world, causing massive loss of lives, especially in Europe and England and said to have killed one-third of Europe's population (Gottfried, 2010). The effects hit the English population drastically, creating a vast void and shortages in the labour market.

In collaboration with the English parliament, King Edward III created "*The Statute of Labourers Law*" to solve the problem. It was initiated to protect sovereignty and prosperity by attempting to control the Labour market. The law stipulated wages and working conditions for employees, prohibiting any request or offerings towards increased wages beyond the pre-plagued standards determined by the government (Booth, 2018). Hence, limiting workers' freedom of movement forced them to work or face imprisonment, a seed responsible for creating the "*Master-Servant*" relationship. Later imported to the colonies in Asia and Africa!

On the other hand, in the Arabian Peninsula, Islamic rulings governed workers' rights and the entire employment relationship in the Seventh Century. Islamic values preserve workers' rights, and many articles prove that, for example, the practice of labour itself is worship and a virtuous endeavour; Islam educates that all people are created equal and must be valued and treated equally (Arshadul, 2018). Therefore, in employment terms, the objective of Islam is the protection of workers from harm and exploitation, and it advocates maintaining self-dignity.

2.12. How Islamic rulings governed the employment relationship:

We can see that Islam has highlighted the significance of equality and prohibited discrimination long before it was written in the equality acts of Western nations and before the United Nations' "Universal Declaration of Human Rights" came into action. Moreover, apparent evidence for that, Allah said in the Holy Quran:

"O mankind! We created you from a single (pair) of a male and a female, and made you into nations and tribes, that ye may know each other (not that ye may despise (each other)). Verily the most honoured of you in the sight of Allah is (he who is) the most righteous of you. And Allah has full knowledge and is well acquainted (with all things)" (Al-Hujurat 49: 13).

In addition, the Prophet Mohamed, *peace be upon him* (pbuh), guided Muslims through the employment relationship, prohibiting discrimination and addressing diversity. In his last speech, he said:

“O people, indeed your Lord is one and your father is one. Behold, there is no superiority for an Arab over a non-Arab, nor for a non-Arab over an Arab, nor a white person over a black person, nor a black person over a white person, except through piety” (Musnad Ahmad, 2012).

Furthermore, Islamic practices are very strict with workers’ compensation for their services (Musannaf, 2017). It highlights not just their right to sufficient compensation but even prompt compensation, which is specified by the Messenger of Allah Mohamed (pbuh) when he said:

“Give employee his/her wage before the sweat is dry on him.”(Majah & Muhammad, 1993)

And on another occasion said:

“The rich, despite his riches, cannot delay payment to the worker, for it is a crime” (Bukhari, 1997)

This calls for not upholding workers’ rights and promotes timely compensation for their efforts. Similarly, determining basic minimum wage, fairness in remuneration, and equality in living align with Islamic principles (Arshadul, 2018). Historical Islamic stories tell that Omer Ibn El-Hattab used to fix the wages of the military workforce. During his leadership, wages were revised based on several criteria for fairness, such as *performance, longevity, and expertise* (Abu Dawud, 2008).

He also determined workers’ salaries with the city’s general conditions, personal needs, and circumstances. Also evident is the well-known practice where the Prophet Mohamed (pbuh), when granting the war spoils (Ghanimah), rewarded personnel with families double that of unmarried individuals ((Majah & Muhammad, 1993). The examples can go on and on; nonetheless, because of the limitations and constraints of this research, one must put the exemplifications to a limit.

The researcher mainly aspires to unveil the reality of Islamic philosophies and reveal that Islamic civilization is unique in sophistication and that Islamic countries like Sudan missed an excellent opportunity for guidance. They had a chance to benefit from this solid,

remarkable foundation and valuable principles to develop a strong foundation for building world-class competitive laws that would underpin their local Labour & Employment Regulations. It could have easily created an endured legacy and even paved the way for others.

2.11. The Legal Origins

The “legal origins” hypothesis argues that the origins of the legal systems guide nationwide regulatory styles, initially first claimed in company and financial laws (La Porta *et al.*, 1998), then recently applied to Labour law (Botero *et al.*, 2004). According to the “legal origins hypothesis”, systems or countries with common law history origins developed gradually over time based on old customs and standard practices are more likely to create efficient company governance/norms, more than their civil law counterparts who rely on laws created and imposed by politicians. For example, the solid legal systems in the UK are based on English Common Law and those in the USA (Deakin *et al.*, 2007).

Unfortunately, countries like Sudan did not follow their common laws and have politically embedded the legal laws inherited from colonisation. They did that “blindly” without securing the necessary foundation to support their adaptability and sustainability. Therefore, from this stage and the perspective of contemporary Islamic Studies, the researcher strongly recommends further research and focusing on Islamic employment relations following the teachings of Islam regarding the justice of employment and employment regulations.

Most Arabic African and Islamic countries followed the lead of colonisation, and Sudan was one of them. They found themselves in challenging situations burdened by colonisation, too oppressed to think creatively and adapt quickly. They are too overwhelmed once again to even review them to cope with the challenges of the current day, which is another mismatch weighing the people in their everyday lives.

2.13. The Industrial Revolution and the Labour Movement

2.13.1. The Industrial Development and Revolution

In the early years of the Industrial Revolution, labour reforms emerged and gradually strengthened to protect the young and vulnerable from the brutal exploitation of capitalists (Davidov and Langille, 2013). In the UK (England), a pioneer in industrialisation and the world leader in the Industrial Revolution movement, various events took place that forever changed the lives of people on the island, overseas, across Europe, and the entire globe.

According to The Encyclopaedia Britannica 11th edition and the writings edited by Hugh Chrisholm, in the year 1784, an awful fever outbreak took place close to Manchester where this outbreak became a trigger to an explosion of public opinion regarding the dangers and hazards and terrible work conditions that young children had to expose themselves to while serving the in-cotton mills.

Following the scandal, a local inquiry led by Dr Thomas Percival who, under the Jurisdiction of Lancashire, managed to pass the first historic step towards the protection of workers and Labour Legislation in 1802 named the *“Health and Morals of Apprentices Act”*. The act was mainly developed to protect young workers shoved into work in these heavily machined factories and mills without the appropriate education and skills. Also, against the unlimited work hours, they were forced to work against their will and fragile little bodies that couldn't cope with this inhumane brutality, let alone the horrific working conditions they had to deal with and become intertwined in. The Act limited their working hours to only 12 hours per day and prohibited the night shifts! And so, finally, young apprentices were trained, accommodated on an excellent night's sleep, fed and dressed!

By the end of the 19th century, as of the Encyclopaedia Britannica, a combination of a comprehensive set of employment regulations was in place in England, and people's attention began to focus on workers' health and safety and compensation for injuries was brought forward. In 1841, women and girls were excluded from underground work, and the **Mines and Collieries Act** excluded boys under ten. Then, in 1843 and beyond, the Board of Health started inspecting and producing yearly reports covering the health and safety industrial situation, eventually producing fines for noncompliance. In 1874, breakthrough legislation was passed to mandate management training and certification by the government institution following a series of examinations and assessments.

This was to qualify and assure the accessibility of the skills and competence required for adequate personnel in the coal mining industry. The main aim was to safeguard health and safety issues at work and reduce the incidents and accidents caused by incompetence and the lack of scientific knowledge and expertise. In the researcher's opinion, this was the first step towards the birth of *scientific management* and acknowledging the vital need for daily control and qualified supervision, leadership, learning, and development. The same progressive development in labour regulations in England followed in other industrial countries in the late 19th Century. Countries like France, Germany, and North America adopted similar systems to

diminish the apparent abuse in their factories. By the end of the century, England had developed and compiled a complete inclusive set of regulations (Encyclopaedia Britannica).

2.13.2. Labour Movement

An Early Labour Movement Worth Acknowledging...

1830 was the birth of socialism, a fresh discipline and modern school of thought inspired by the thinking of people like Robert Owen in the UK and St Simon and Fourier in France. It was also the birth of democracy, institutions and the forces of working-class solidarity, unity, and cohesion. These pioneers strongly denounced the forceful aggressiveness and competitiveness created by the ruthless individualism of the Industrial Revolution. Their efforts represented the workers as human beings, advocating for fairness, freedom, self-respect, and social justice (Mishra, 2012). It was a century of continued struggle, twinge and sacrifice that did not go to waste; it proudly resulted in the birth of new ideologies based on the harmony, unanimity, and solidarity of the working class worldwide.

These fresh ideas led to the evolution of “*Labour Laws*” and associations that promoted anti-exploitation of labour and the emergence of laws that shielded and protected the worker (Mishra, 2012). They also brought people from all over the world together, who shared the same struggles and pains and knew they were the creators of wealth and deserved better in the workplace. These workers spend the end of the nineteenth century organising and uniting.

This movement then grew bigger and bigger. According to (Rodgers *et al.*, 2009), it then witnessed an international progression, forming the ***International Working Men’s Association in 1864***, targeting the working class’s liberation, protection, and development. As a result, trade unions emerged, representing workers’ rights and becoming the voice they never had. International efforts started to take shape and structure; official bodies known as the *First International* occurred between *1864 and 1871*, the *Second International* from 1872 to 89, and the *Third International* from *1889 to 1919*.

The efforts of the Second International were second to none; it was exemplary because the *association united and demanded an eight-hour working day and a 48-hour working week in 1889*. This became the first mandate adopted by the International Labour Conference that brought people from across the globe together and became the cornerstone of the ***International Labour Organisation ILO*** (Rodgers *et al.*, 2009). Another date worth

mentioning is the *1st of May 1886, which saw the birth of the International Labour Day*, a day representing unity, fairness, and justice for labour rights worldwide (Mishra, 2012).

2.14. The International Labour Organisation (ILO)

The ILO is an institution collectively created more than a century ago. It is one of the world's oldest International Organisations. Headquartered in Geneva, Switzerland, it has weathered two world wars: a cold war, a severe global downturn, a series of recessions, a quadrupling of its membership, and global capitalism (Helfer, 2006). According to Hughes and Haworth, 2013, the *ILO was born in 1919* with solid aspirations closely tied to and linked with developing and enhancing universal dimensions that aim to regulate extreme variations created by the industrial labour markets aspiring to improve working conditions and workers' lives.

It has always been at the forefront of battling and supporting social matters and promoting labour standards. It famously preached in the *Philadelphia Declaration* that "*labour is not a commodity*"; thus, it earned a reputable global position and even a Nobel Peace Prize for its fiftieth anniversary in 1969. Every summer, over 3000 representatives from across the world gather in Geneva for the *International Labour Conference (ILC)*, where they spend two weeks discussing various critical labour matters, social policy, and procedural issues (Standing, 2008).

Despite its longevity and historic position, the ILO remains a well-established institution with one of the most effective triple decision-making structures, with balanced representations from governments, employers, and employees worldwide; yet it remains one of the most respected progressive, forward-thinking, and contemporary institutions. It has broad links, diverse representation, inclusivity, and a well-represented international presence. Nevertheless, the association is criticised for its minimal influence. It is seen to have a trivial impact on modern global economic governance and control and its inability to systematically ensure membership consistency and effective compliance with its vast number of core conventions (Hughes and Haworth, 2013).

The ILO developed principles and created standards intended for national regulatory systems, allowing room for general interpretations and the ratification or rejection of these standards. As a result, the Organisation was not positioned to advocate for a particular type of welfare state capitalism (Standing, 2008). This also applies to two current social research concerns: the variant of capitalism and the legal roots of national capitalism (Ahlering and Deakin,

2006). According to Standing (2008) , the ILO's approach was favourable to the determination of several variants of capitalism; the purpose was to restrict labour-based competition so that different systems based on other legal origins could easily co-exist.

The beginning began with the function and focus of identifying frameworks and boundaries for the employer/employee relationship. It was not primarily structured to become a knowledge-based agency or a technical corporation. However, it did issue a few significant publications in response to unemployment issues and poverty in developed countries in the mid-thirties. It facilitated impactful surveys that revealed critical, informative data and statistical realities related to family income, budgets and living standards. Almost half a century later, they were used as a core baseline for statistical measures (Standing, 2008).

Since its development in 1919, the ILO has made three significant fundamental achievements. First, it was a rallying cry for the post-war period. It embodied a systematic attempt to circumvent the labour market as an institutional device to reduce the commodity character of labour relationships by spreading standards around the world, praising "tripartism", and assisting the so-called "*backward*" countries to introduce legislation along lines developed in "*advanced*" countries.

The year 1944 brought the *Philadelphia Declaration*, where the ILO's founders, Governments of countries coming out of World War two (those who won the war) together with employers and trade unions came together and issued a public statement of values and principles which constituted the ILO Philadelphia Declaration, it included a paragraph made of one line sentence which says, "***Labour is not a commodity***". The ILO's mission was to regulate national labour markets to protect employees, primarily focusing on male workers working full-time, particularly unionised jobs (Standing, 2008).

Furthermore, throughout its history, the ILO has successfully focused on activities beyond the labour market. It has always fought for *more significant labour standards* to encourage economic progress and *promote social fairness and peace*. Although peace has been interrupted several times since 1919, the ILO's efforts to protect vulnerable workers, reduce unemployment, and promote freedom of association are acknowledged as contributing to democracy and social stability. For this reason, in 1989, the ILO was awarded the *Nobel Peace Prize* (Charnovitz, 2000).

The ILO renewed and revitalised itself after issuing the *Declaration of Fundamental Principles and Rights at Work* (Standing, 2008). On June 18, 1998, the Eighty-Sixth International Labour Conference of the UN occurred. The ILO approved the Declaration on Fundamental Principles and Rights at Work (the “ILO Workers’ Rights Declaration”). The ILO Workers’ Rights Declaration, along with its size for follow-up processes, was adopted by the ILO Governing Body on November 19, 1998, and it binds the ILO’s 174 member countries to four basic labour and employment law principles. Those fundamental ideas and principles, as stated in the Declaration, are enshrined in the ILO’s seven basic conventions on workers’ rights:

Figure 2.11 The ILO’s Four Basic Labour & Employment Law Principles of 1998

Source: (Coxson, 1998)

Given the changing nature of work and labour in globalising labour markets and the archaic governance structure of the ILO, the essential fundamental question is whether the ILO can transform itself into an effective development organisation (Standing, 2008). Baccaro and Mele, 2012 argued that during the 1990s, the ILO recognised that its standard-setting approach was in trouble and swiftly responded by implementing significant governance-related organisational changes. It turned away from norms and towards general affirmations of fundamental ideas, or “*soft law*”. It began to investigate innovative ways to involve other organisations in the social classification movement, Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs) and civil society organisations in developing and implementing the ILO policies.

It also explored publishing quantifiable metrics of labour standard compliance, such as a comprehensive *decent work index*, to inspire public interest and track national and enterprise achievements toward the ILO's aims. While the move to soft law was successful, the attempt to open the organisation up to private monitoring schemes and civil society was met with fierce internal opposition and ultimately abandoned. Attempts to develop quantitative indicators have yielded only sporadic and late results. (Baccaro and Mele, 2012).

As multinational trade agreements boomed across the world accompanied by increased unregulated labour markets, trade unions, growing labour organisations, women's organisations, and other Nongovernmental Organisations began to call for the rescue of a translucent mediator, a democratically reliable independent international organisations working in the social field and global systems and techniques focusing on enhancing workers' lives (Vosko, 2002).

Of course, the obvious answer was the ILO, the organisation that has gone a long way, is well-established in the field and has already paved the way. Despite the variation in character and structure of these global social justice struggles and the differences in the primary goals of the players driving them forward, they miraculously come together collectively, sharing an increased awareness of the failing and weakening of labour rights and standards worldwide. Consequently, the ILO decided it was inevitable for the organisation to rethink its role under globalisation and engage in activities that would fulfil this pressing need. Indeed, this was a priority for the ILO as it was constantly criticised and accused of sustaining the domination of capitalism, especially American capitalism, during the Cold War and for ignoring the dilemma of disadvantaged workers in the global economy (Cox, 1980; Vosko, 2000; Whitworth, 1994).

In response, the ILO embraced a new platform and took on a new turn of action, the road of *“Decent Work”*, an intelligent effort to mediate the tensions among and between the stakeholders; precisely speaking the stress caused by the ILO's support for global capital lead by industrialised countries and the increasing pressures created by the loud voice of trade unions, women organisations and other NGO demanding radical improvements to the lives of marginalised workers (Vosko, 2002), and rightly they did.

The idea of *“decent work”* can contradict the ILO's new podium. *The ILO uses the term metaphorically to highlight the terrible need for enhancing the working circumstances of all people: those paid and unpaid, those working in formal and informal sectors via attempts of*

re-regulation and the growth of social and labour securities (Vosko, 2002). According to ILO's 1999 official stage, the "Decent Work" agenda is redirecting its focus and emphasis way further beyond the scope of a narrow set workforce:

"The ILO is concerned with all workers. Because of its origins, the ILO has paid most attention to the needs of wage workers- the majority of them men- in formal enterprises. But this is only part of its mandate, and only part of the world of work. Almost everyone works, but not everyone is employed. Moreover, the world is full of overworked and unemployed people. The ILO must be concerned with workers beyond the formal labour market-with unregulated wage workers, the self-employed and home workers. The participation of the informal sector in total employment has reached almost 60 per cent in Latin America. In Africa, the informal economy accounted for over 90 per cent of new urban jobs during the past decade."

(ILO: 87th Session -Geneva, June 1999)

2.15. In Pursuit of Decent Work

"Every person at work or looking for work, whatever his or her country, occupation or skill level, has a notion of what "decency" at work stands for" (Anker et al., 2003, p.147)

2.15.1. Measuring Decent Work Using International Statistical Indicators

The ILO has tried to introduce and promote the concept of decent work and has made it its sole focus and centre of attention since 1999:

"Opportunities for women and men to obtain decent and productive work in conditions of freedom, equity, security and human dignity"
(ILO, 1999, p. 3)

This became an objective close to the heart, and the ILO showed a genuine global commitment towards its achievement. The organisation considers decent work not only as a means of life and a critical component of long-term development but also as a worthwhile critical goal. (Anker, R., Chernyshev, I., Egger, P. and Mehran, F., 2003).

Because work occupies a large portion of one's life regarding time, social integration, and personal self-esteem, excellent employment is unquestionably a vital aspect of one's overall quality of life. Furthermore, for many people, productive Labour is also their primary source of income.

"Every person at work or looking for work, whatever his or her country, occupation or skill level, has a notion of what "decency" at work stands for" (Anker et al., 2003, p.147).

However, (Anker *et al.*, 2003) and other researchers are asking what precisely it is. Decent work means what? How can we assess and measure it to enable us to observe the “**decency**” of various occupations, businesses, and countries to monitor and compare them against one another? Richard Anker then led a team of researchers to help establish decent work and suggest some lean statistical indicators to measure decent work, where relevant data can be available in different countries worldwide and can be used to set future priorities and help eliminate shortfalls of decent work. This study was done as part of the work of the Statistical Development and Analysis Unit at the International Labour Office Geneva in October (2002).

These indicators make it easy for countries to see where they stand regarding decent work and where they can effectively measure, control, and compare their indicators. Most importantly (Anker *et al.*, 2003) argue that these indicators need not be only used for countries, but they must be relevant to and easy to communicate to the average person in the street. Below are ten generic characteristics they used as a starting point four plus six. These are the general characteristics of work that people worldwide consider fundamental elements of decent work. They have elected indicators that followed and met the four criteria shown below:

Figure 2.12 Four Criteria for Elected Indicators

Source: (Original)

2.15.2. Conceptual Dimensions of Decent Work

Table 2.1 ILO's General Characteristics of Work

<i>That people from around the world considered as fundamental and essential elements of "Decent Work."</i>		
1	Opportunities for work	<i>The need for all persons (men and women) who want work to be able to find work, since decent work is not possible without work itself. The underlying concept of work is a broad one, encompassing all forms of economic activity, including self-employment, economic unpaid family work and wage employment in both the informal and formal sectors</i>
2	Work in conditions of freedom	<i>Underscores the fact that work should be freely chosen and not forced on individuals and that certain forms of work are not acceptable in the 21st century. It means that bonded labor and slave labor as well as unacceptable forms of child labor should be eliminated as agreed by governments in international declarations and labor standards. It also means that workers are free to join workers organizations.</i>
3	Productive work	<i>Is essential for workers to have acceptable livelihoods for themselves and their families, as well as to ensure sustainable development and competitiveness of enterprises and countries.</i>
4	Equity in work	<i>Represents workers' need to have fair and equitable treatment and opportunity in work. It encompasses absence of discrimination at work and in access to work and ability to balance work with family life.</i>
5	Security at work	<i>Is mindful of the need to help safeguard health, pensions, and livelihoods, and to provide adequate financial and other protection in the event of health and other contingencies. It also recognizes workers' need to limit insecurity associated with the possible loss of work and livelihood.</i>
6	Dignity at work	<i>Requires that workers be treated with respect at work and be able to voice concerns and participate in decision-making about working conditions. An essential ingredient is workers' freedom to represent their interests collectively.</i>
<i>Source: (Anker, et al-Working Paper No. 2. 2003 p.2)</i>		

2.15.3. Statistical Indicators of Decent Work

(Anker, et al., 2003) His team then complimented the ten aspects of decent work with a comprehensive list of eleven indicators (11 groups of indicators); the list below summarises

the essential features of decent work in economic and social contexts. This last set of indicators is meant to represent the features of the economy and the people that serve the economy as a framework for defining the levels, trends, and sustainability of decent employment.

The 11 Groups of Indicators

Figure 2.13 11 Groups of Indicators

Source: (Anker et al., 2003)

The team divides Each suggested indicator group (Anker et al., 2002) into sub-group indicators and possible indicators and measurements that require longer planning and further development.

The Table below exemplifies these in more detail:

Table 2.2 Groups of Indicators in Detail

Group Indicators	Possible Subgroup Indicators
1 Employment opportunities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Labor force participation rate ➤ Employment-population ratio ➤ Unemployment rate ➤ Youth unemployment rate ➤ Time-related underemployment rate (“Decent hours”) ➤ Share of wage employment in non-agricultural employment ➤ Employee-specific unemployment rate ➤ Youth unemployment to total population ratio
2 Unacceptable work	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Employee-specific unemployment rate ➤ Youth unemployment to total population ratio ➤ Children not in school by employment status (percentages by age) ➤ Children in wage employment or self-employment activity rate (percentages by age) ➤ Children not in school by employment status (percentages by age) ➤ Children in wage employment or self-employment activity rate (percentages by age) ➤ Children in hazardous work (percentages by age) ➤ Children in worst forms of child labor (percentages by age) ➤ Forced labor (extent by type)
3 Adequate earnings and productive work	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Inadequate pay rate (percentage of employed earning less than one-half of median earnings or an absolute minimum, whichever is greater, by status in employment) ➤ Average earnings in selected occupations ➤ Excessive hours of work (“Decent hours”) ➤ Time-related underemployment rate (“Decent hours”) ➤ Employees with recent job training (percentage with job training during last 12 months provided or paid for by employer or state)
4 Decent hours	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Excessive hours of work (percentage of employed persons working more than hours threshold, by status in employment) ➤ Time-related underemployment rate (percentage of employed population working less than hours threshold, but available and wanting to work additional hours) ➤ Atypical or Asocial work hours
5 Stability and security of work	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Tenure less than one year (percentage of employed persons who have held their main job/work for less than one year, by age and status in employment) ➤ Temporary work (percentage of employees who classify their job as temporary) ➤ Perceptions of future job security ➤ Measures of intermittency of employment

6	Balancing work and family life	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Employment rate for women with children under compulsory school age (ratio to the rate for all women aged 20-49) ➤ Excessive hours of work (discussed in “Decent hours”) ➤ Effective incidence and duration of job/employment protection for mothers and fathers, both publicly mandated and privately provided. ➤ Incidence, duration, and average level of monetary benefits for maternity and paternity, both publicly mandated and privately provided. ➤ Flexibility of work and accommodation of family needs (e.g., hours, sick child leave, bringing children to workplace, access to telephone for personal use) ➤ Quality, availability, and affordability of formal childcare arrangements, including public subsidies and tax policies. ➤ Workplace issues connected with population ageing
7	Fair treatment in employment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Occupational segregation by sex (percentage of non-agricultural employment in male-dominated and in female-dominated occupations, and index of dissimilarity) ➤ Female share of employment in managerial and high-level administrative occupations (ratio to female share of non-agricultural employment) ➤ Female share of non-agricultural wage employment (see under “Employment opportunities”) ➤ Female/male wage or earnings ratio, selected occupations (see under “Adequate earnings”) ➤ Female/male ratios or differences for the other suggested indicators (see under other headings) ➤ Other major forms of discrimination are based on religion, ethnicity, migrant status, national origin, etc. ➤ Harassment ➤ Autonomy
8	Safe work environment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Fatal occupational injury rate (per 100,000 employees) ➤ Labor inspection (inspectors per 100,000 employees and per 100,000 covered employees) ➤ Occupational injury insurance coverage (percentage of employees covered by insurance) ➤ Excessive hours of work (see under “Decent hours”) ➤ Health insurance coverage (see under “Social protection”) ➤ Occupational stress and injury rates

9	Social protection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Public social security expenditure (percentage of GDP, separately for total, health services and old-age pensions) ➤ Public expenditure on needs-based cash income support (percentage of GDP) ➤ Beneficiaries of cash income support (percentage of poor) ➤ Share of population over 65 years benefiting from a pension ➤ Share of economically active population contributing to a pension fund ➤ Average monthly pension (percentage of median/minimum earnings) ➤ Occupational injury insurance coverage (see under “Safe work”) ➤ Health insurance coverage
10	Social dialogue and workplace relations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Union density rate ➤ Collective wage bargaining coverage rate ➤ Strikes and lockouts (per 1,000 employees) ➤ Employer-employee relations and grievance settlement procedures ➤ Participation in workplace decision-making ➤ Percentage of women among union members and union officers ➤ Union member participation in union elections and decision-making ➤ Union participation in public policymaking ➤ Information sheets (and possibly indicators) on restrictions on freedom of association and the right to bargain collectively
11	Economic and social context of decent work	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Output per employed person (purchasing power parity level) ➤ Growth of output per employed person (total and manufacturing) ➤ Inflation (consumer prices) ➤ Education of adult population (adult literacy rate, and adult secondary school graduation rate) ➤ Composition of employment by economic sector (agriculture, industry, services) ➤ Income inequality (ratio of top 10 per cent to bottom 10 per cent for income or consumption) ➤ Poverty (percentage of population subsisting on less than US\$1 or less than US\$2 per day) ➤ Informal economy employment (percentage of non-agricultural or urban employment)

Note: Gender issues are mostly handled by monitoring disparities between men and women for indicators that are gendered. Female-male discrepancies provide suitable gender indicators in virtually all cases since all components of decent labor are important for both men and women.

Source: (Anker et al.-International Labour Review 2003 p.155-168)

Key	
Data believed to be available or is expected to become available in the relatively near future.	Black
Possible indicators and measurement approaches that require longer planning and/or further development.	Brown

In conclusion, the team of researchers stress that these suggested and agreed-upon set of decent work indicators may not be perfect, and they acknowledge the fact that they have proposed a mere selection of indicators, intentionally keeping it reasonable and concise. Since they believe this makes it simple and easy for both the ILO and countries/governments to measure a wide range of decent work apprehensions with the limited resources accessible. In the researcher's view, she finds it uplifting to have a universal set of measures at our fingertips and to encounter a consolidated common platform combining a set of agreed-upon diverse standards/ indicators to position and work from. Indeed, a trustworthy and reliable framework to benchmark, measure, and control us against; remember what Peter Drucker said in 1954: "*What gets measured gets managed*".

2.16. Conclusion

Formal employment regulations were only enacted after the Industrial Revolution, guided by religious morality and personal principles. In England, for example, the Statute of Labourers Law was created in 1351 after the Black Death, while Islamic rulings in the Arabian Peninsula emphasised equality and prohibited discrimination. The late 19th century saw the birth of scientific management and socialism, which marked the beginning of democracy and working-class solidarity. Pioneers like Robert Owen, St Simon and Fourier criticised the aggressiveness of the Industrial Revolution, advocating for fairness, freedom, self-respect, and social justice. Labour laws and associations evolved to promote anti-exploitation and protect workers, while trade unions emerged to represent their rights and become the voice they never had.

Labour laws have evolved since the Industrial Revolution, with Anglo-American societies pioneering the development of employment laws. Studies show that labour laws and regulations positively affect economic growth and development. Deakin (2016) suggests viewing labour laws as developmental institutions symbolising the global rise of capitalism and the transition to free market economies. The International Labour Organisation (ILO), one of the world's oldest international organisations, was created over a century ago and has made significant achievements. It has fought for post-war labour markets, promoted tripartism, and regulated national labour markets to protect employees, primarily male workers in full-time work, particularly unionised jobs. Despite its longevity and historic position, the ILO remains a well-established institution with broad links, diverse representation, inclusivity, and a well-represented international presence. Nevertheless, critics argue it lacks significant influence and effectively ensures membership consistency and compliance with core conventions.

The Universal Declaration of Human Rights and the ILO are critical foundations for understanding labour law. The ILO's Declaration emphasises core labour rights, such as freedom of association, collective bargaining, and elimination of forced labour. It has also fought for social fairness and peace. In 1989, the ILO was awarded the Nobel Peace Prize for its efforts. The ILO has been promoting decent work since 1999, aiming to provide opportunities for both men and women to work in conditions of freedom, equity, security, and human dignity. Researchers are exploring the definition of decent work and its measurement to establish lean statistical indicators for monitoring and comparing different occupations, businesses, and countries. Having a global set of measurements at our fingertips

is uplifting and gives us a trustworthy and dependable framework to benchmark, measure, and govern ourselves against.

The Sudanese Labour Act 1997, enacted after the 1981 Labour Relations Act, has been stagnant for over 25 years, failing to adapt to changes in human resource practices and international employment laws. It has not been adequately equipped for the 21st century, notably inequality, discrimination, bullying, harassment, diversity, inclusion, and data protection. Sudan faces high inflation and poor working conditions, decreasing social and economic well-being. The ILO has identified Unfair Working Conditions as a need for urgent attention. Notwithstanding the scarcity of literature, this research investigates Sudan's labour law's ability to address these issues, highlighting the missed opportunity for Islamic countries like Sudan to develop world-class competitive laws under their local Labour & Employment Regulations. The researcher advocates incorporating best practice legislation and further research on Islamic Employment Relations.

CHAPTER THREE: LITERATURE REVIEW PART II (*The Evolution of the Employment Relationship*)

3.1. Introduction

This chapter focuses mainly on reviewing the literature on labour laws in Europe and Sudan. In Europe, the researcher starts by taking the *British Equality Act of 2010* as a helpful model and best practice benchmark, which successfully consolidated all grounds for discrimination into a single standardised law. Then, the historical progression of the European Union Laws led to the groundbreaking *Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union* (CFR), a legally binding proclamation in 2000 which encompasses provisions central to European Labour Law and industrial relations, including freedom of association, collective bargaining, workers' rights, and occupation of choice. And a systematic overview of German employment laws, including individual and collective employment laws. Its comprehensive, distinct and progressive nature makes its application an actual role model for other countries. Finally, the chapter ends by thoroughly illustrating the Sudanese Labour Law of 1997 in full detail and, at the very end, discusses the gaps in the literature.

3.2. The British Equality Act 2010

Linda Dickens 2007 highlights the significance of discrimination and equality in employment as an unquestionable matter; indeed, the call goes beyond mere employment opportunities and chances into broader areas such as education, immigration, health, and labour market policies. Today, there is a vital need to implement mainstream equality measures and legislation effectively. Drawing workplace boundaries can be challenging, particularly in understanding and influencing what happens in the workplace in terms of discrimination and inconveniences.

Great Britain has tried to address the shortcomings of the British equality law by re-evaluating and tightening enforcement mechanisms. It is also necessary to refrain from antiquated laws that reflect the priorities and realities of a bygone epoch and focus on providing a better match to the modern contemporary character of today's employment and associate employers. Hence, it illustrates an improved understanding of the nature of discrimination, the structural causes of disadvantage, and legislative options for promoting fair representation, equality, and diversity (Dickens, 2007).

The British Labour Government 2010 succeeded in passing “The Equality Act 2010”. This was one of the last measurements they made before losing office in May 2010. The Birth of the Equality Act in Great Britain resulted from long years of campaigning by equality specialists and Human rights activists. The Act was welcomed by all governmental parties and received remarkable support and commitment from all. It covered England, Wales, and Scotland, effective October 2010 (Hepple, 2010).

Previous British anti-discrimination Acts and Regulations were simplified and systematised (applicable to the public sector). The Equality Act of 2010 repealed the Sex Discrimination Act of 1975, the Race Relations Act of 1976, and the Disability Discrimination Act of 1995 (Fell and Dyban, 2017). The Equality Act of 2010 successfully consolidated all grounds for discrimination into a single law, standardised definitions, and ideas and included new criteria and concepts (Lockwood, Henderson, and Thornicroft, 2012). The act’s essence is making discrimination against persons with a “*protected characteristic*” illegal under the Equality Act of 2010. According to the British Equality Act of 2010, nine characteristics fall under legislative protection (Fell and Dyban, 2017):

Figure 3.1 Characteristics under Legislative Protection

Source: (Original-based on the British Equality Act 2010)

According to (Bob Hepple, 2010), the British Equality Act can be a helpful model and standard for other nations. Countries seeking to implement a comprehensive equality law enforced by a single commission that defines and applies terms such as discrimination, harassment, and victimisation to all protected characteristics. Despite this recommendation, legal models cannot be easily transferred from one country to another without customisation. Before implementing and enforcing equality legislation, it is crucial to consider the adopting nation's distinctive historical, political, and socioeconomic factors (Bob Hepple, 2010).

3.3. Labour Laws in Europe

The European Union (EU):

When the six founding European countries (*Belgium, France, Germany, Italy, Luxembourg, and the Netherlands*) united (Weiss, 2017) and joined membership in 1957, formulating the *European Economic Community (EEC)*, European Labour Law was not part of the Treaty's agenda then. The members' focus was mainly on establishing a common market among and between them, and they were concerned primarily with establishing market freedoms that incorporate the free movement of capital, goods, and services, as well as developing and growing businesses. This is the essence of the treaty, which is still valid today. The only challenge is it did not focus then on the social dimensions, which are also valid today and eventually became an integral part of the Treaty.

In the beginning, the fundamental vision of the original Treaty assumed that social progression would automatically fall into place once the Common Market was established. Of course, this didn't happen just like that. The first baby step in this social progression was the guaranteed free movement of workers with equal treatment from the host country, which was all an indirect economic aim of market freedom, and the optimal development of the common market and further development have taken place since then (Weiss, 2017).

The European Union today has undergone several stage developments since its formation and progressively expanded its social and labour reforms into more compatible and applicable legislations that were relevant to the time and the European Union's relationship and circumstances. Below is a brief outline of the significant event occurrences and legislative developments that took place extracted from Professor Manfred Weiss's "Introduction to European Labour Law", 2017:

Table 3.1 EU Labour Law Stages of Development

EU Labour Law Stages of Development	
Social Action Program (SAP)	<i>A resolution adopted in 1974.</i>
Single European Act	<i>A successful amendment and innovative solution for the European Labour Laws introduced in 1989 by the Commission's President Jacques Delors.</i>
Community Charter of the Fundamental Rights of Workers	<i>A legally non-binding statement agreed by the Member States in December 1989</i>
Social Protocol of the Treaty of Maastricht of 1992	<i>A powerful amendment to the legislation promoting the EEC as a single market with a broad viewpoint and perspective. The Social Protocol not only greatly increased the EC's legislative powers in the area of labour law, but also unaltered till now successfully managed to exist</i>
Amsterdam Treaty/Lisbon Treaty	<i>Incorporated in the Amsterdam Treaty of 1998 and is now a component of the Lisbon Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU), which has been in effect since 2009.</i>

Source: (Original-Based on Weiss, 2017)

The European legislature has since then been greatly influenced and authorised to “take the necessary measures to fight discrimination based on **gender, race or ethnic origin, religion or belief, disability, age, or sexual orientation**”. This empowerment extends way beyond the sphere of work and vocation. To sum up, notwithstanding the expansion of legislative powers in the field of labour law, the hurdles to legislation in this sector remain significant (Weiss, 2017).

Figure 3.2 EU Social & Labour Reform Stages of Development & Progressive Growth

Source: (Original Inspired by the Writing of Professor Manfred Weiss's 2017)

3.4. The Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union

In 2000, the Charter of the Fundamental Rights of the European Union (CFR) was declared a symbolic proclamation before being included in the Lisbon Treaty and becoming legally enforceable for the EU Countries (Weiss, 2017). The EU Charter contains provisions that are central to European Labour Law and industrial relations; rights such as freedom of association, the right to collective bargaining and collective action, workers' right to information and consultation within the enterprise, freedom to choose an occupation and the right to work, prohibition of child labour and prohibition of forced labour are well stipulated in the charter (Bercusson, 2006).

Below is an extraction of the articles relevant to Labour legislation extracted from the *European Union Charter of Fundamental Rights* as written in the *Official Journal of the European Union* "Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union (2012)" and tabulated in table 3.4.

Two essential lessons should be noted when examining the social and labour aspects of the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights, which were agreed upon in Nice in December 2000. The economic and political backdrop shapes fundamental labour and social norms. Their substance shifts in response to economic and political conditions. Second, social and labour rights progress when connected to policies promoting European integration and when included in the Community's integration agenda. The Charter is groundbreaking because it embraces conventional civil and political rights and many social and economic rights in a single list of fundamental rights (Bercusson, 2006).

Table 3.2 EU Labour Legislation Articles

<p>I. Protection of personal data (Article 8)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ <i>Everyone has the right to the protection of personal data concerning him or her.</i> ➤ <i>Such data must be processed fairly for specified purposes and based on the consent of the person concerned or some other legitimate basis laid down by law. Everyone has the right of access to data which has been collected concerning him or her, and the right to have it rectified.</i> ➤ <i>Compliance with these rules shall be subject to control by an independent authority.</i>
<p>II. Freedom of assembly and association (Article 12)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ <i>Everyone has the right to freedom of peaceful assembly and to freedom of association at all levels, in political, trade union and civic matters, which implies the right of everyone to form and join trade unions for the protection of his or her interests.</i> ➤ <i>Political parties at the European level contribute to expressing the political will of the citizens of the Union.</i>
<p>III. Freedom to choose an occupation and right to engage in work. (Article 15)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ <i>Everyone has the right to engage in work and to pursue a freely chosen or accepted occupation.</i> ➤ <i>Every citizen of the Union has the freedom to seek employment, to work, to exercise the right of establishment and to provide services in any Member State.</i> ➤ <i>Nationals of third countries who are authorized to work in the territories of the Member States are entitled to working conditions equivalent to those of citizens of the Union.</i>
<p>IV. Non-discrimination (Article 21)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ <i>Any discrimination based on any ground such as sex, race, colour, ethnic or social origin, genetic features, language, religion, or belief, political or any other opinion, membership of a national minority, property, birth, disability, age, or sexual orientation shall be prohibited.</i> ➤ <i>Within the scope of application of the Treaty establishing the European Community and of the Treaty on European Union, and without prejudice to the special provisions of those Treaties, any discrimination on grounds of nationality shall be prohibited.</i>
<p>V. Equality between men and women (Article 23)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ <i>Equality between men and women must be ensured in all areas, including employment, work and pay.</i> ➤ <i>The principle of equality shall not prevent the maintenance or adoption of measures providing for specific advantages in favour of the under-represented sex.</i>

VI. Workers' right to information and consultation within the undertaking (Article 27)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ <i>Workers or their representatives must, at the appropriate levels, be guaranteed information and consultation in good time in the cases and under the conditions provided for by Community law and national laws and practices.</i>
VII. Right of collective bargaining and action (Article 28)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ <i>Workers and employers, or their respective organizations, have, under Community law and national laws and practices, the right to negotiate and conclude collective agreements at the appropriate levels and, in cases of conflicts of interests, to take collective action to defend their interests, including strike action.</i>
VIII. Protection in the event of unjustified dismissal (Article 30)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✳ <i>Every worker has the right to protection against unjustified dismissal, under Community law and national laws and practices.</i>
IX. Fair and just working conditions. (Article 31)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ <i>Every worker has the right to working conditions which respect his or her health, <u>safety</u> and dignity.</i> ➤ <i>Every worker has the right to limitation of maximum working hours, to daily and weekly rest and an annual period of paid leave.</i>
X. Prohibition of child labour and protection of young people at work (Article 32)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ <i>The employment of children is prohibited. The minimum age of admission to employment may not be lower than the minimum school leaving age, without prejudice to such rules as may be more favourable to young people and except for limited derogations. Young people admitted to work must have working conditions appropriate to their age and be protected against economic exploitation and any work likely to harm their safety, health or physical, mental, moral, or social development or to interfere with their education.</i>

Source:

Official Journal of the European Union-Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union-2012 C 326/397- C 326/402)

Individual employment law governs the relationships between employees and their employers, whereas *collective employment law* governs employee representation and organisation, as well as the rights and responsibilities of employee representatives. Furthermore, the employment legislation in Germany is not unified into one labour code. The primary sources of German employment law include federal legislation, case law, collective bargaining agreements, works council agreements, and individual employment contracts (Employment Law Overview Germany 2021-2022).

Germany is a country governed by civil law. As a result, its legal system relies heavily on written laws, such as the Constitution, codes, and laws. There are separate state laws, and each state has its constitution in addition to the federal constitution and statutes. Federal legislation controls most aspects of German employment and labour law. Historically, however, there hasn't been a single employment and labour law code. Jurisprudence is significant in this area of law since the applicable legislation is scattered over several statutes, and statutory gaps are filled by jurisprudence. This makes understanding and applying German labour and employment law challenging for employers and employees (Kirchner and Morgenroth, 2018).

There has been some talk about adopting one unified labour code to cater to German employment regulations by combining and incorporating all codes. However, the project was disregarded and shelved, and introducing it back to the table in the near or mid-term is quite improbable (Employment Law Overview Germany 2021-2022).

Below is a detailed overview of the German Labour laws as broken down and explained by Tobias Pusch and Verena Braeckeler-Kogel, both qualified German Lawyers specialising in German Workplace Law and operate *Pusch Wahlig Workplace Law Labour Law Attorneys*, a leading German employment and labour law firm.

JUVE named Pusch Wahlig Workplace Law Employment Law Firm of the Year in Germany in 2008 and 2011 and the newly formed "Gründerzeit-Award" in 2009. The award went to law firms that have made significant market achievements quickly and have grown exceptionally dynamically. Pusch Wahlig Workplace Law was named Employment Law Firm of the Year in Germany by JUVE in 2017. 2017, the organisation was also awarded the Azur Award for "Diversity". Chambers, Best Attorneys, Who's Who Legal, The Legal 500, and JUVE have all named partners of the company as outstanding employment lawyers in Germany (Employment Law Overview Germany-2021-2022).

The researcher is keen to see what makes German law distinct, robust, and an actual role model for countries that are serious about governing labour laws and want to make a difference and visibly affect the lives of their people.

3.5. A Comprehensive Overview of the Current German Employment Laws

(A summary extracted from “Employment Law Overview Germany 2021-2022”)

By: (Pusch, T. and Braeckeler-Kogel, V. 2021)

I. The Hiring Practices

Germany has several legal restrictions on background checks, application and interview questions, and discrimination issues. Background checks are not legally required, and employers have limited authority to conduct them without employee consent. Application and interview questions are restricted to essential information for establishing a working relationship, such as basic credentials. Personal issues like pregnancy, age, race, sexual identity, ethnic origin, religion, trade union involvement, or serious handicap issues are not permitted.

The General Equal Treatment Act aims to remove unfair treatment of employees based on race, ethnicity, gender, religion, handicap, age, or gender identity. This law applies during recruitment, restricting job postings and candidate selection. Advertising for a “young, dynamic team member” might imply age prejudice.

Data privacy and protection are crucial in the hiring process. The Federal Data Protection Act and General Data Protection Regulations limit personal information usage for job-related purposes, such as formulating hiring decisions or conducting dismissals or terminations. Starting November 21, 2019, the “Second Data Protection Adaptation and Implementation Act EU” made it necessary to designate a business data protection officer if 20 people are routinely participating in processing personal information.

II. The Employment Contracts

The employment contract must include vital contractual terms, such as name, address, starting date, duration, location, working hours, nature of work, compensation, remuneration, leave days, notice period, and any relevant collective bargaining agreements. The trial period cannot exceed six months, with a minimum notice period of two weeks. The Dismissal

Protection Act is not applicable during this period, which is the first six months of employment.

The employer's notice period varies depending on the employee's tenure, ranging from four weeks for workers under two years of service to seven months for those with twenty years and beyond. These extended notice periods apply to terminations led by the employer unless specified otherwise. Employees can terminate their contract with a four-week notice to the 15th or end of the calendar month. Collective agreements can specify longer or shorter notice periods.

III. Working Conditions

The German labour laws outline minimum working conditions, salary, minimum wage, and the Remuneration Transparency Act. These conditions are determined by statutes, collective bargaining agreements, and works council agreements and must not differ from the employee's employment agreement to their harm. The Posted Workers Act dictates that sectors such as mail services, construction, and commercial cleaning must adhere to precisely always defined minimum working conditions. These conditions include maximum work periods, minimum rest time, minimum paid holiday entitlements, overtime, health benefits, safety and hygiene in the workplace, maternity leave parental entitlements, youth protection, non-discrimination policies, travel remuneration, accommodation, and meal costs for workers away from their home for work reasons.

Salary is determined by mutual contractual agreement with limited freedom, with any salary below two-thirds of the standard usual wage considered invalid. A constitutional, statutory minimum wage of 9.50 EUR/hour applies to all workforces above 18 in all sectors, with some sectors, like construction, having a higher minimum wage because of special collective bargaining agreements. The Vocational Training Act grants a statutory minimum monthly salary of 515 EUR/calendar month for trainees in their first training year, which increases by 18% in the second year and goes up to 40% in the fourth training year.

The Remuneration Transparency Act gives individuals the right to access information relevant to compensation, but only the average remuneration of a similar comparison group must be revealed. Employees have the right to know the criteria determining their remuneration, the comparable remuneration, and the average/mean comparable remuneration paid to the similar/comparable group.

Maximum working hours/week are 8 hours/day (Monday to Saturday) and 48 hours/week, with regular daytime hours may be extended up to 10 hours but not exceeding an overall average of 8 hours/week in 6 consecutive months or 24 weeks. Under all circumstances governed by German law, employees must be assured a continuous, uninterrupted rest period of 11 daily hours.

Overtime pays and charges are not explicitly controlled by law but are governed by collective bargaining agreements, employment agreements, and works council agreements. Creating overtime compensation reimbursed by the typical salary for regular employees is not feasible. Employees have the right to comment and suggest improvements to their managers for aspects related to health and safety. They can file a complaint if their employers fail to meet the minimum defined safety and protection standards. They also have the right to ask/insist on better, safer, and healthier working conditions and claim compensation if these are not adhered to. Protection from retaliation is protected by law if the claim is genuine and a valid violation of workplace health and safety has taken place.

IV. Anti-Discrimination Laws

The General Equal Treatment Act in Germany provides comprehensive protection against discrimination based on various factors, including race, ethnicity, gender, sexuality, age, disability, religion/beliefs, etc. The Act prohibits discrimination in employment, self-employment, occupational professions, recruitment conditions, and working conditions. It also covers harassment, sexual harassment, and instructions to discriminate.

German legislation protects employees against harassment, particularly sexual harassment, which is considered illegal under German law quarterly. Harassment occurs when someone engages in unwelcome behaviour with the intent or effect of compromising the person's dignity and producing an intimidating, hostile, degrading, or offensive feeling. This includes unsolicited sexual actions or demands, sexually explicit physical contact, sexually explicit statements, and the uninvited displaying or public exhibition of sexual material.

Employers have a comprehensive organisational obligation to protect their workers from discrimination harm. They must take necessary actions to highlight unacceptable discrimination and shield employees from discrimination caused by colleagues and third

parties. They must provide reasonable accommodations, such as written warnings, transferring employees to different locations, or ending employment contracts. Additionally, the organisation must develop and implement a grievance system that is accessible for victims to file and track their complaints.

Remedies for Employees who suffer discrimination in the workplace are entitled to file a complaint and record their grievance following the organisation's complaints policy. They have the right to compensate and can pursue all remedies and damages. The responsible employer is accountable for any damages and compensation. A written claim must be submitted within two months of the discrimination incident. Suppose discriminatory behaviour occurs during the recruitment process. In that case, the victim may be entitled to monetary compensation of up to a three-month salary even if the organisation has not officially recruited them. In 2016, a gender quota of 30% was implemented for new supervisory and managerial positions in businesses registered or subject to board co-determination. The aim was to increase the representation of women in leadership and senior roles.

V. Pay Equality Laws

The statutory minimum wage in Germany ensures fair salaries for all employees in all industries, and the Remuneration Transparency Act provides access to remuneration information. However, the Act does not enforce claims for equal remuneration based on such information. Employees have the right to challenge remuneration, seek damages or payment for losses resulting from unfair treatment, and may rely on evidence based on the information obtained. Employers that do not pay the statutory minimum wage may be charged.

The Minimum Wage Act covers all relief measures, processes, and tangible employment actions, but employees cannot demonstrate a breach of non-discrimination and fair treatment in many situations. As a result, there has been a shortage of substantial equal pay lawsuits based on the Remuneration Transparency Act. However, as this Act is a relative newcomer to German labour law, the legal implications may take some time to manifest.

VI. Social Media & Data Privacy

The employer has the right to determine whether employees can use the company's internet facility, phones, or email system for personal purposes during or after working hours. Employees are not legally permitted to use the organisation's internet for private use without

seeking permission. If an employee breaches the restriction on using work equipment for personal gain, the employer may give a warning and, in some cases, terminate the employment contract.

The rights of employers in monitoring, accessing, and reviewing employees' electronic communications depend on the organisation. The employee's correspondence may be subject to legal access and tracking if the employer does not permit private use. If personal use is allowed, the employer may be classified as a telecommunication services provider, subjecting the organisation to more stringent regulations, including criminal prosecution for accessing or ordering third parties to access staff members' correspondence beyond what is required for safety purposes.

The Federal Data Protection Act and the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) both support the principle of prohibiting the handling of personal data except in conditional situations when legally permitted by law under special agreements like a collective bargaining agreement or a works agreement. A worker can still express their permission for specific data processing. Still, it must be distinct from all other agreements and informed of the purpose of the data processing intentions and the ability to cancel it with future effect in writing.

Employees are required not to compromise the employer's legitimate interests, including not revealing internal information or resolving any internal concerns directly. If a worker fails to meet this commitment, the employer can sue for damages and terminate the employment contract. In some cases, breaches of this kind may even be considered a legal felony.

VII. Termination of Employment Contracts

The German employment law outlines the grounds for termination, which can be ended by mutual consent, or a notice issued by one party. There are two types of dismissal protection: general protection and special protection. Special protection is given to employees with disabilities, pregnant individuals, and works council members. The Dismissal Protection Act (DPA) significantly limits employers' ability to freely fire an employee, especially if a corporate body has more than ten employees and the employee has worked in the same business entity or establishment for six continuous months without interruption.

In the event of a severe violation of written agreements, any party has the right to terminate the employment agreement immediately, and no notice period is required. Suppose the company employs more than 20 people. In that case, collective dismissals may require developing a social plan and attempting to harmonise interests with the works council in case of an “operational change of business.”

If the DPA is in effect, termination is only legitimate if it is “socially justified,” which can be justified on three grounds: person-related reasons, conduct-related reasons, and pressing operational requirements. Person-related reasons include prolonged absence due to sickness and diminished working capability, while conduct-related reasons involve deliberate or gross negligence. Pressing operational requirements makes it impossible for the employee to continue working for the company.

The notice must be submitted in writing and signed by a legally authorised employer representative. The employee has the right to appeal their dismissal, and they must submit a complaint to the relevant labour court within three weeks of receiving the termination notification. If the dismissal is unlawful, the employee is entitled to reinstatement and uninterrupted pay from the organisation.

VIII. Disability Protections

Employees with severe disabilities in Germany are entitled to several benefits, including protection from dismissal, authorisation from a governmental body, and a meeting with their representation. They may claim part-time work, if necessary, because of their disability, and those who are significantly impaired may refuse to work overtime. Working conditions must be arranged to accommodate the limitations of the disabled individual, and only unreasonable organisational measures may be denied by the employer. If a business has over 20 workers but does not employ a certain number of disabled individuals, they must pay compensation.

Severance payments can be made at the end of employment in various situations, such as contractual severance payouts included in the employment agreement, parties agreeing on a severance payout to resolve a termination dispute, or if the court finds that continuing employment would be unbearable for either the employer or the employee, the job is terminated alongside payment of severance. Severance payments can also be included in a social plan agreed with the works council in line with collective redundancy.

To calculate severance, labour courts often use the (non-binding) formula below, which is widely integrated into separation settlements and social plans:

Monthly gross pay multiplied by years of service multiplied by factor x

X is usually a factor of 0.5 to 1.5, while it can be lower or greater based on the circumstances, industry, and location in Germany.

Separation agreements are rare because of the robust protection against dismissal, and even individuals safeguarded from dismissal can establish one without obtaining approval from authorities. In most cases, the firm will provide a severance package to persuade the employee to embrace voluntary separation.

Remedies for employees seeking to challenge wrongful termination in Germany are limited to reinstatement, with the employer bearing the responsibility of evidence confirming the termination's legitimacy. If the dismissal is found invalid, the employee gets reinstated, and most dismissal protection cases are negotiated in return for a severance payout in effect.

IX. Whistleblower Laws

In Germany, whistleblowing is not a standard practice, but employees are expected to disclose misconduct as part of their duties of good faith. The Trade Secrets Act, which implements the European Directive on the Protection of Trade Secrets, has legalised the term "trade secret" for the first time. Trade secrets are only protected if owners have adopted proper confidentiality precautions under context. Whistleblowers are not protected from dismissal but are subject to strict regulations. Proportionality is addressed where whistleblowing was "proportionate," requiring employees to report misconduct internally before reporting it.

X. Restrictive Covenants

Restrictive covenants are legally binding agreements between employers and employees that prohibit them from working for a competitor during an employment relationship. In Germany, the power to add a restrictive covenant in an employment contract is restricted by statutory law. A post-contractual restrictive covenant is only legally enforceable if it is in writing, authentic, and meets certain conditions. These conditions include the agreement

being in writing, the employer having a genuine commercial interest in the covenant, the employee's legitimate interests not being compromised, the covenant being for a maximum of two years, and the company offering compensation equivalent to at least 50% of the employee's previous total earnings for the duration of the covenant.

Labour courts can enforce restrictive covenants if legally agreed upon, providing injunctive relief and reimbursement for any losses incurred by the employer. However, demonstrating, and quantifying damages can be challenging for employers.

Employees have a legal right to work for the employer, and the organisation cannot unilaterally release them without valid justification. Employees are usually freed from their obligation to work after obtaining a termination notice until the expiry of the relevant notice period. The employer can deduct any remaining holiday time from the release, and the employee must not engage in any competing activity during the release.

XI. Transfer of Undertaking

The Civil Code (Sec. 613a) governs the transfer of an enterprise, business, or part of a business to a new owner, including mergers, splits, and asset transfers. It also aligns with the EU Directive (2001/23/EC) on "acquired rights" or "transfer of undertakings." The European Court of Justice and the German Federal Labour Court define an undertaking as an economic entity that maintains its identity despite the transfer. All transferor staff is automatically transferred to the transferee with the same terms and conditions as their employment agreements.

Employees must be informed in writing about the transfer, its grounds, context, social and legal implications, and any additional measures anticipated by the transferee. They have the right to object to the transfer of employment within one month of receiving a proper information letter. The right to object can only be waived years after the transfer if the information letter does not comply with legal standards.

The transferee is responsible for all rights and responsibilities stemming from the employment contracts at the time of the transfer, as well as the transferor's pension liabilities to the affected employees. However, the transferee is not required to identically treat transferred and existing employees.

XII. Trade Union and Employers' Associations

Trade unions play a crucial role in negotiating collective bargaining agreements, while employers' associations are established by industry sectors and locations, with national and state boards. They are the equivalents of trade unions in negotiating and finalising these agreements. Constitutional law protects labour unions' establishment, operations, and democratic processes. Collective bargaining agreements can be reached with a single employer or an employer's association, with the same direct and binding impact on individual employment relationships as statutory law if certain conditions are met: the employee is a member of the applicable trade union, the employer is a member of the relevant employers' association, the Federal Ministry of Labour and Social Affairs declares the collective bargaining agreement legally binding, or the employment contract stipulates the application of a particular collective bargaining agreement contractually.

XIII. Employee Benefits

The Social Security Codes govern Germany's social security system and cover various aspects, such as health insurance, unemployment insurance, nursing care insurance, pensions, and accident insurance. Both employers and employees pay half of the social security payments, with employers contributing their part besides the wage. Employees can choose from various statutory health insurance policies, with contributions split evenly between the employer and the employee.

Required leave includes holidays and annual leave, maternity and paternity leave, sickness leave, disability leave, and other required or typically provided leave(s). The number of public holidays varies by federal state, with the minimum being ten in Berlin, Lower Saxony, and up to twelve in Bavaria and Saarland. Paid maternity leave is offered to female employees for six weeks before and eight weeks following childbirth, with extended leave for multiple births, premature births, or disabled children.

Employees have the legal right-to-work part-time while on parental leave unless pressing business circumstances prohibit it. Pregnant employees, apprentices, interns, and students completing compulsory internships are protected from dismissal under the Maternity Protection Act throughout pregnancy and for four months following birth. Women experiencing a miscarriage after the 12th week of pregnancy are also shielded from termination for the next four months. Terminating an employee when they are protected from

dismissal will only be allowed in extraordinary circumstances, with prior authorisation from the appropriate governmental authorities.

Sickness leave is available after four weeks of employment, with the employer paying the employee's regular salary if the employee is ill multiple times in a calendar year. However, this benefit is restricted if the employee was not out sick for more than six months for the exact cause or if twelve months have passed since the first sickness. Small businesses with less than 30 individuals may use an apportionment method that permits sick pay to be repaid. Disability leave is granted to seriously disabled employees after six months of employment. Other required or typically provided leave depends on individual negotiations or is included in collective bargaining agreements/works council agreements.

The German pension system consists of the public retirement insurance system, business pension schemes, and private individual retirement investments. The public retirement insurance system has always been "pay-as-you-go," with current pensions paid from current premiums paid by those who have not yet retired. Business pension plans comprise around three-fifths of the workforce, while individual retirement investments are becoming increasingly significant and subsidised by the government. Retirement used to start at 65 years old, but it is now progressively being raised to 67 years old.

In summary, Germany's social security system, healthcare, and other required or typically provided leave options ensure fair compensation and benefits for employees.

(Source: Pusch, T. and Braeckeler-Kogel, V. 2021. Employment Law Overview Germany-2021-2022-knowledge.leglobal.org)

3.6. The Sudanese Labour Act of 1997

In 1997, the Labour Act of 1997 (as it is known) went into effect, regulating employment in Sudanese Private Organisations. It replaced the Manpower Act of 1974 and overturned the following acts:

1. The Manpower Act 1974
2. The Industrial Relations Act of 1976
3. The Industrial Safety Act of 1976
4. The Individual Labour Relations Act 1981

It defines employment organisation (including provisions for women and juveniles), service contracts and wages, working hours and leave, termination of employment, after-service benefits, and various other provisions. It also specifies who is exempt from the act, including domestic servants, agricultural workers not employed in organisations that process agricultural products, and casual workers (World Bank Report, 2021).

3.6.1. Exemptions

According to Article (3) of the Sudanese Act of 1997, the following ten categories or groups of people are exempted from the applications of this Act:

EXEMPTIONS
The Members of the Judiciary
The Counsels of the Ministry of Justice
Persons of Disciplinary Forces
Persons of National Security Organ
Persons employed in the federal and state governments and public corporations governed by special laws
Domestic Servants
Agricultural workers
Members of the employer's family
Casual workers
Any class of persons, the Ministry Council may declare by an order Exempt

The Sudanese Labour Act of 1997 is Sudan's chief law and legislation governing labour relations. It is the most important document and is used by all private sectors. Under this act, the Federal Minister of Labour has the right and authority to issue further regulations, orders, regulations, and guidelines to carry out the Act's provisions.

Furthermore, besides the Act, Sudan follows the following provisions:

- I. The **Organisation of Non-Sudanese Employment Act of 2001**- guidelines for foreigners working in Sudan.
- II. The **Minimum Wages Act of 1974** - minimum pay guidelines.
- III. The **Social Insurance Act of 1990** - standards for social security.

As summarised by the Investment Guide 2015, The Act comprises 127 different sections: Manpower, Organisation of Employment, Employment of Women and Minors, Contracts of Employment, Wages, Advances and Other Payments, Hours of Work and Leave, Termination of Contract of Employment, Severance Pay, General Provisions, Industrial Safety and Labour Disputes and Stages of Settlement are among the 127 sections divided into the 14 chapters of the Act. Below is a summary of the Act and its respective chapters.

3.6.2. Summary of the Sudanese Labour Act 1997

Table 3.3 Summary of the Sudanese Labour Act 1997

1	Chapter Two	Establishes a Manpower Federal Committee
2	Chapter Three	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Governs employment agencies, private employment agencies, recruitment, apprenticeships, and registration of workers. <i>Sudanese looking for jobs outside of Sudan shall obtain permission to do <u>so</u></i>
3	Chapter Four	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Covers the employment of women and young workers. Forbids the employment of women during night hours (except in administrative or health-care work) and in hazardous or arduous working conditions. Prohibits the employment of children (defined as persons less than 12 years of age) and the employment of young persons (individuals under 16 years of age) in specified tasks. Hours of work for young workers shall be seven hours per day and one hour of paid rest.
4	Chapter Five	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Caters for employment contracts.
5	Chapter Six	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Covers wages: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> wages shall be paid in cash, except for allowances for food, fuel, housing, transportation, and clothing, which may be paid in kind.
6	Chapter Seven	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Observes matters related to hours of work and leave, including overtime, paid leave, and annual leave. Women workers shall be granted a maternity leave of eight weeks (four weeks before and after confinement) for each year of service. Also caters for Hajj leave and Idda leave (mourning leave for a Moslem widow)
7	Chapter Eight	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Covers matters regarding termination of employment and redundancy.
8	Chapter Nine	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provides for severance pay, including seasonal workers.
9	Chapter Ten	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Contains general provisions regarding penalties, validity of contracts with successor employers, and labor inspection. Establishes a National and District Council for Labor Relations
10	Chapter Eleven	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regards occupational safety matters, including registration of factories, safety inspectors, notification of accidents, and the establishment of safety committees in factories employing 500 or more workers.
11	Chapter Twelve	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Labor disputes are covered in this chapter. Section 101 states that court cases involving people preparing to act in response to a labor dispute will be dismissed unless the planned action is a "crime" as defined by law.
12	Chapter Thirteen	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cover the settlement of labor disputes through negotiation and mediation. Section 124 rule out the partial or full stoppage of work
13	Chapter Fourteen	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Final provisions are covered in chapter fourteen. Abolishes the following acts: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The Labor Force Act 1974 Industrial Relations Act 1976 Industrial Safety Act 1976 The Individual Labor Relations Act 1981
<i>Source: (The Labor Act 1997, Ministry of Justice, Sudan)</i>		

A Probationary Period:

Apart from any training time, it must not exceed three months. Suppose a contract of employment is not for a set amount of time, and the probationary period passes without one party terminating the contract. In that case, the agreement is for an unlimited period. Any employment contract extending more than three months must be specified in writing; nonetheless, if there is no legal agreement, the employee may show their rights via any method of accessible evidence.

Termination of the Employment Contract:

An Employment Contract may be terminated with or without notice under specified conditions, such as committing multiple violations or for economic or technical reasons. Employees may also end their employment contract without prior notice to the employer for the following reasons.

Working Hours:

Working hours are officially 48 hours per week or 8 hours per day. Fasting employees and nursing mothers will have their working hours shortened by one hour during Ramadan and for two years from a child's birth. Employers who hire expatriates must train Sudanese and submit a training and "Sudanisation" plan to the Minister for approval under the Organisation of Employment of Non-Sudanese Act, 2001.

Social Insurance:

Insurance with the National Social Insurance Fund is mandatory; each employer must subscribe to the Fund, as must their personnel. The legislation compels every firm to withhold 8% of each employee's salary, add 17% to that wage, and pay 25% to the National Social Insurance Fund as a social insurance deposit.

Minimum Wage:

As per the latest data wageindicator.org, 2021, the Sudanese Ministry of Finance has recently announced lifting the minimum wage for civil servants to SDG 3,000 Sudanese Pounds (equivalent to 6.72 US Dollars) on 4th of March 2020; however, the official minimum for the private sector remains at 425 Sudanese pounds (SDG) per month (equivalent to 0.95 US Dollars)! These figures are unrealistic for a country where the cost of living does not react to the mentioned figures. It is pretty amusing and sad that decision-makers continue to ignore the fundamental human element in their formulas and the people's livelihood. Government after government, they all continue to keep a blind eye far from reality when it comes to

fundamental human rights and inset to humiliate the people of Sudan, who dwelled in constant poverty and despair. Sudan has also ratified all the key International Labour Organisation ILO treaties safeguarding workers' rights. Unfortunately, labour laws are not consistently implemented, and they fall short of international norms in practice.

Additionally, expatriate employees must have legitimate residency and work permits or risk being deported and jailed.

(Investment Guide 2015 – Sudan www.africalegalnetwork.com)

3.6.3. Summary of the Ratified Acts

Table 3.4 Summary of the Ratified Acts

According to the Constitution Decree No. 3 of 1995, the National Council has passed, and the President of the Republic of Sudan has ratified the following Act:

PART I: PRELIMINARY PROVISION	PART II: THE MANPOWER	PART III: ORGANISATION OF EMPLOYMENT	PART IV: PROVISIONS RELATING TO WOMEN AND JUVENILES	PART V: CONTRACT OF SERVICE	PART VI: WAGES, LOANS AND OTHER EMOLUMENTS	PART VII: WORKING HOURS AND LEAVES	PART VIII: TERMINATION AND EXPIRY OF THE CONTRACT OF SERVICES	PART IX: AFTER SERVICE BENEFITS	PART X: MISCELLANEOUS PROVISIONS	PART XIV: GENERAL PROVISIONS
Repeal and saving	The Commission and its constitution	Establishment of employment exchange	Requirement for employment of women	Writing of the Contract	General provisions about payment of wages	Normal working hours and Females working hours	Termination of Contract of Service by Notice	Calculation of the gratuity	Work Regulations and Penalties	Amendment of schedules
Exemption	Function of the Commission	Private employment exchange and employment exchange agencies	Hours of work of women	Types and Terms of Contracts	The Deduction for Absence	Overtime work	Termination of the Contract of Service in the case of repeated contravention	Termination of Contract of Service by the worker	Keeping of Workers Records	Penalties
Interpretation	Financial resources	Prohibition of employing unregistered persons	Employment of juveniles	Contents of the Contracts of Service	Loans	Annual leaves	Appeals	Gratuity of the Seasonal Worker	Validity of Contract of Service with the successor	Power to make Regulations and rules
Repeal and saving	The Commission and its constitution	Furnishing particulars	Medical Examination for Juveniles	Terms inconsistent with the provisions of this Act	Travelling Allowance	Official Occasions and holidays	Termination of the Contract of Service without notification to the worker	Additional of the period of the previous service	Prohibition of enforcing certain contract	
		Nomination of employment	Hours of work of the juvenile	The work that differs from that agreed upon	Expenses of Transportation.	Traveling leave	Termination of the Contract of Service without notification to the employer		Payments payable on the death of the worker	
		Notification of the employment exchange of appointment	Fixing the conditions and regulations concerning the juveniles in a conspicuous place	Presenting of Contracts	Statement of entitlements.	Maternity leave	Referring of disputes to the Commissioner Referring of disputes to the Commissioner		Inspection	
		Employment of Sudanese abroad	The Commissioner's notification	The receipt of depositing the papers of the worker and his certificates as to payment of wages	Violability of reconciliation, discharge, or waiver	Sick leave	Reduction of the number of workers for economic and technological reasons		Labor Relation Council	
		Inspection and investigation	The termination of the juveniles' contract of service			Al-eda leaves (Widow Mourning Period)	Termination of the Contract of Service with notice by the worker		Priority of entitlement of the workers	
		Training of workers	Establishment and Constitution of the Special Committees			Alhaj leave	Termination of Service when the worker is on a journey or voyage connected with his employer's business		Exemption from the Judicial fees	
		Training Contract				Al-eda leaves (Widow Mourning Period)	Certificate of Service		Lapse of right by prescription	
		Termination of training contract							Conditions of Service and better Benefits	

Source: (Compiled, edited, and translated by Curtis F. Doebbler and Rifaat Osman Makkawi

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3.7. Women and Employment Laws in Sudan

Sudan's Islamist government, which came to power in 1989 in a coup led by Omar Al-Basher, has legally secured women's equal freedom to work. However, Sudan is regarded as one of the "worst" countries in terms of legislative restrictions on women's economic empowerment (Jensenius and Nunez, 2019). The Muslim Family Law of 1991, which mandates wives to seek their husbands' permission before working, is by far the most severe legal limitation observed in research on Sudanese women's employment.

In Sudan, women continue to encounter significant challenges in achieving the equal rights established in international human rights legislation. The way Islamic law has been interpreted is among the most fundamental barriers to gender equality (An-Naim, 1990). Since the Islamization of 1983, new laws have been established based on an interpretation of Islamic standards to preserve the culture and customs that subordinate and oppress women, such as the *Personal Status for Muslims Act of 1991* (PSMA). The culture and norms that subordinate women have been inextricably linked to the unnecessary, discriminatory interpretation of Islamic Shari'a laws.

In an "enlightened construction" of the Qur'an and Sunna, the same comprehensive protections provided in international human rights texts, such as the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, can be found. As a result, developing fresh knowledge of the interpretation of Islamic norms is an essential milestone for women from now on. The rewriting, understanding, and interpretation of Islamic law in a way that is consistent with women's equality is crucial. It will not only assist women in their quest for equal rights precisely within the Islamic faith, but it will also reduce opposition to the application of international human rights standards. Furthermore, when international human rights standards effectively incorporate and complement cultural values that promote equality, they have a better chance of succeeding (Halim, 2019).

Asma Abdel Halim (2019) argues that Sudanese laws are biased towards women, and international law adherence is non-existent. Evidence law, Criminal Law, Muslim Personal Status Law, and Civil Procedure Law are all deliberately discriminatory and gender

imbalanced. Therefore, international law is perhaps Sudan's most reasonable window and the only source for legal reforms. However, because Sudan has refused to ratify or implement international agreements that prohibit discrimination against women, applying international law for such an ambition involves tremendous challenges. According to the fifth census, women's labour participation in Sudan remained lower than men's (2008). According to its figures and statistics, the share of female breadwinners has more than doubled, rising from 12% in 1993 to 28% in 2008.

In metropolitan regions, women have a greater economic inclusion rate than in rural areas. Even though the Interim Constitution of 2005, the Labour Act of 1997, and the National Civil Service Act of 2007 give certain protections for female workers, numerous women work in areas not covered by social insurance. The National Civil Service Act of 2007 and its corresponding regulations stipulate equal pay for equal work, the right to be recruited and promoted based on qualifications, merit and achievements, the right to maternity leave, a mourning period (Iddah), reduced working hours for nursing moms, and the restriction of involving women in dangerous work.

Furthermore, the statute promotes open competition in the hiring process for public office positions. Article 19 of the Labour Act of 1997 prohibits women from working in jobs that are dangerous, exhausting, or hazardous to their health, such as carrying weights or allocating women to undertake jobs that require them to work underground or underwater or jobs that expose them to poisonous materials or temperatures that are higher than the normal bearable limits. Article 3 of the same Labour Act excludes domestic workers from any of its provisions (Sudan.unfpa.org., 2018).

Figure 3.3 Salary Comparisons by Gender

Source: (Salaryexplorer.com)

On September 4th, 2000, the Islamic government in Sudan, headed by the Governor of Khartoum, issued Decree Number 84 for the year 2000, which prevented women from working in petrol stations, restaurants, and hotels under the umbrella of protecting Sudanese culture and religion from the West. Women's employment rights, which had been achieved in the 1950s, were compromised (Bakr, 2019). Sudan's human rights representatives and labour affiliates denounced the ban and criticised the governors' bizarre move. The Governor of Khartoum, Majzoub al-Khalifa, at the time, defended his call and argued that by preventing women from working in public places in the capital where they are in constant and direct contact with men, he is protecting and preserving their superior status in line with Islam and Sharia laws (BBC World, 2000).

But Sudanese women did not take no for an answer and fought a battle that distinguished them from their counterparts in the reign; not defeated, they held their heads high. The experiences of Sudanese women who fought against this decision were explored by Bakr (2019) represented by 23 women she interviewed, women who lived the struggle and collaborated with local and multinational organisations to fight for what's theirs. These women accessed and reinterpreted International UN publications in support of their cause and their collaboration and trust in their multinational relationships.

Their global endeavour successfully influenced Human Rights Watch to denounce the Decree on September 8, 2000, and the Constitutional Court in Khartoum to put it on hold. This

historical battle of persistent Sudanese women is believed to have highlighted the value of recognising the significance of local context as a source of knowledge generation capable of promoting women's transnational resilience worldwide (Bakr, 2019).

Figure 3.4 Revolutionary Women of Sudan

Source : (issafrica.org, 2019)

3.8. The Right to Organise and Collective Bargaining

The International Trade Union Confederation (ITUC) is a global organisation whose principal purpose is to develop, promote and protect workers' best interests via international collaboration among trade unions, global advocacy, and lobbying within key international bodies (ITUC, 2021). The International Trade Union Confederation, the Trade Union Advisory Committee, and many other United Nations specialised institutions, such as the ILO, collaborate regularly. The ITUC collaborates with the primary goal and intention of protecting trade unionists when fundamental human and labour rights are infringed, as these rights may harm workers' well-being (Fredette, 2019). In 1998, ILO issued the Declaration of *Fundamental Principles and Rights at Work*, in which member nations pledged to observe and promote the ILO's conventions, which are legally binding international treaties (Flanagan, and Gould, 2003). Sudan is one of these nations that has pledged to do so.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Please contact the author for further information.

Figure 3. 5 ITUC Global Rights Index

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Please contact the author for further information.

Source: (ITUC Global Rights Index, 2021)

The ITUC Global Rights Index specifies a score from 1 to 5 for nations based on their commitment and compliance with collective labour rights. The rating does not reflect the country's economic progress, size, or location. Because of the regime's inability to protect workers' rights, a high score implies that workers in that region have no right to collective bargaining. The image above shows the worldwide scores of member nations by region, highlighting information on worker harassment, deprivation of freedoms, and bans on union membership (Fredette, 2019).

The MENA region, of which Sudan is a part, ranked the *world's worst for workers'* rights in 2021 and the years before. The average score for countries in the MENA is **4.50**, rising from **4.44** the previous year. The survey is an eye-opener; it also extends its output to compute the

violations of workers' rights in the region, as shown in the figure below (ITUC Global Rights Index, 2021).

Figure 3.6 Violations of Workers' Rights in the Middle East and North Africa

Source: (2021 ITUC Global Rights Index)

According to the (Middle East Solidarity Magazine, 2020) issued by menasolidaritynetwork.com, Sudan's revolution overthrew Dictator Omar El Bashir, yet workers still fight for their fundamental right to organise. Sudan Labour Bulletin activists are in the lead in building consensus for their continued battle for work dignity. Sudan's workers' movement arose as a natural outcome of British operations experienced in the region. The first strike in Sudan was organised by forest workers in 1908, and it was then followed by subsequent smaller strikes afterwards. The relatively tiny working class's self-consciousness eventually found voice in the widespread workers' unions that arose in the mid-1930s.

The Kenana sugar plant workers' strike of 2020 set a record for the length of a strike. Earlier in 1948, the first trade union law was adopted, and the General Federation of Trade Unions was established in 1950. The Railway Workers' Union, the Port Workers' Union, the Textile Workers' Union, the Doctors' Union, and the Teachers' Union were all significant trade unions in Sudan's history. Following Omar El Bashir's entry into power in 1989, a committee was set up to eliminate political opponents of the administration from their positions. The

group published what they named “*The Public Good Law.*”. *Labour* and political activists were unjustly detained and fired from their positions. Trade unionists were fired and replaced with government supporters. The dictatorship quickly established its corporate trade unions and federation and adopted new legislation criminalising strikes (menasolidaritynetwork.com 2020).

Figure 3.7 Sudan Uprising 2019

Source: (springmag.ca.,2021)

Sudan has ratified the ILO’s Convention No. 87, which protects workers’ freedom to organise. However, it has not been applied in practice. “The government’s rhetoric on trade union rights is absolute nonsense”, they say. The current troubles confronting the Sudanese labour movement include but are not limited to the workforce’s main demands for a healthy working environment, better pay, and the ability to organise without the fear of being harassed by employers.

Developing local associations that champion workers’ interests and reforming laws that handicap the labour movement, particularly the “**1997 Labour Code**”, which has resulted in the arbitrary dismissal of hundreds of employees since this government gained power, are among the many challenges faced by the Sudanese workers (menasolidaritynetwork.com 2020).

3.9. Gaps in the Literature

There is not a single study, research paper, book, or other type of relevant writing on the topic of the “Sudanese Labour Act of 1997.” The Act is available as a document, but no previous author has thoroughly researched it. There were a couple of student researchers who

discussed Article 56 of the Act, which covers redundancies and unfair dismissal, and they were written in Arabic and were not published in an authorised journal or website; the researcher obtained them from personal contact and one of the core participants in this research, but none were relevant. As a result, not a single search engine generated a study or paper on the Sudanese Labour Act of 1997. The researcher found only one PhD thesis that might have been somewhat relevant, titled “The Regulation of Labour and the State in Sudan” (A Study of the Relationship Between the Stage of Social and Economic Development and the Autonomy of Labour Relations Law), written by El Siddig Abdelbagi Hussein at the University of Warwick School of Law in October 1986. Unfortunately, a decade before the 1997 Act was even published! Generally, Sudan is very under-researched, and literature is scarce.

This study made significant contributions to filling this gap by providing empirical evidence to the literature. The researcher has addressed this research void through this endeavour, but it cannot be said that it has been discussed thoroughly. The researcher successfully addressed the critical aspects of the Sudanese Labour Act of 1997 by identifying key areas, such as its features, administration, relevant institutions, and policymaking. And discuss and assess the critical challenges the Sudanese Labour Act faces while considering international best practices. The researcher was also able to thoroughly cover the challenges faced by implementing the 1997 Act and partially cover some of the most relevant concurrent acts that work in conjunction with the Act.

Finally, the researcher created and suggested strategies and methods for updating the 97 Act and generally improving and promoting employment laws in Sudan. This study is probably the first of its kind and an excellent starting place for other researchers to take it from here and further explore this critical research topic and take it to the next level.

3.10. Conceptual Framework

Figure 3.8 *Conceptual Framework*

Source: (Original)

The researcher developed the above conceptual framework as a foundation for the entire research project. It is clear from the literature review that the Sudanese Labour Law has not been adequately studied. The literature is void; thus, this study is a step towards bridging that

gap. Best practice frameworks have been identified and discussed; the ILO principles and frameworks, at the foremost, are based on dignity and fundamental human rights principles. The international employment legislations of leading countries have also been studied and reviewed as a potential benchmark. Ultimately, the Sudanese Labour Law of 1997 and the challenges identified are thoroughly discussed and analysed. The legal system of Sudan and the cultural contexts and values matter in the process and are kept at the heart of all the discussions as they influence the relevance. The conceptual framework considers the context when examining the shortcomings in the Sudanese Labour Law of 1997 and developing expert recommendations for reform.

3.11. Conclusion

The British Labour Government passed the British Equality Act in 2010, addressing the shortcomings of previous anti-discrimination laws focusing on contemporary employment and employer characteristics. Nine characteristics fall under legislative protection under the Act. This serves as a model for other countries aiming to adopt an integrated concept of equality law enforced by a solitary commission. It defines discrimination, harassment, and victimisation, expands positive duties on public authorities, increases government agency responsibilities, and permits more positive action situations. In addition, the European legislature has empowered itself to combat discrimination based on various factors. The Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union (CFR) was a symbolic proclamation in 2000 legally binding for EU countries.

It includes provisions central to European Labour Law and industrial relations, such as freedom of association, collective bargaining, workers' right to information and consultation, occupation choice, work rights, prohibition of child labour, and forced labour. The CFR is groundbreaking in encompassing both civil and political rights. Furthermore, German employment law is divided into individual and collective employment laws, with federal legislation controlling most employment and labour law aspects. Civil law governs the country with separate state laws and constitutions. Jurisprudence plays a crucial role in this area as it fills statutory gaps and applies scattered legislation across several statutes. This makes understanding and applying German labour and employment law challenging despite its comprehensive, distinct and progressive nature, which is another actual role model for other countries.

The Sudanese Labour Act of 1997 replaced the Manpower Act of 1974. The Act consists of 127 sections, including Manpower, Organisation of Employment, Employment of Women and Minors, Contracts of Employment, Wages, Advances and Other Payments, Hours of Work and Leave, Termination of Contract of Employment, Severance Pay, General Provisions, Industrial Safety and Labour Disputes and Stages of Settlement. Exemptions include domestic servants, agricultural workers, and casual workers. The Act also outlines minimum pay guidelines for foreign workers in Sudan, including a minimum wage of SDG 3,000 for civil servants and 425 SDG per month for the private sector, equivalent to 6.72 US Dollars/month! Sudan faces severe legislative restrictions on women's economic empowerment, with the Muslim Family Law of 1991 being the most severe. Sudanese laws show bias against women and do not adhere to international law. Evidence, Criminal, Muslim Personal Status, and Civil Procedure Laws are discriminatory and gender imbalanced. Applying international law to legal reforms in Sudan presents significant challenges.

The International Trade Union Confederation (ITUC) is a global organisation that aims to protect workers' rights through international collaboration among trade unions. In 2021 and previous years, Sudan, part of the MENA region, has ranked as the world's worst for workers' rights. Sudan's workers' movement emerged because of British operations in the area, with the first strike in 1908 organised by forest workers. Workers in Sudan established the General Federation of Trade Unions in 1950, including significant unions such as the Railway Workers' Union, Port Workers' Union, Textile Workers' Union, Doctors' Union, and Teachers' Union. Sudan recently ratified the ILO's Convention Number 87 but has not implemented it in practice. Current challenges for the Sudanese labour movement include a healthy working environment, better pay, and the freedom to organise without fear of harassment.

Finally, this study provides essential empirical evidence on the "Sudanese Labour Act of 1997," addressing key aspects, assessing challenges, and suggesting strategies for updating and improving employment laws in Sudan. It is the first of its kind, significantly contributing to the scarce literature on the subject. The lack of relevant research creates an evident gap, which firmly supports the study's necessity and validates the intervention's significance and urgency.

CHAPTER FOUR: METHODOLOGY Part I (The Framework)

4.1. Introduction

Individuals engage in research as an endeavour to discover or find out things. In this characterisation, the terms “*in a systematic way*” and “*to find out things*” are crucial (Saunders *et al.*, 2019). (Ghuri and Grnhaug, 2005) Stress the term “Systematic,” meaning proper research relies on logical relationships rather than mere beliefs. The researcher intends to clarify the purpose of this research vividly by systematically selecting and collecting the relevant data that support the outcome of this research and mindfully interpreting this data to produce a valid, valuable, and meaningful result.

This business research aims to create tangible, practical and applicable business value for first-hand users and beneficiaries, all the users and custodians of the Sudanese Labour Act, workers, employees, employers, local & international organisations, and the government that regulates the legislation. According to (Easterby-Smith *et al.*, 2008), four components combine to make business and management research a unique field of study and focus. The fact is that managers/researchers are inclined to build on the knowledge of others and will only embrace research that promises to generate personal and commercial value. The fact that most managers/researchers tend to be well informed and have the correct calibre equips them to carry out the research. And finally, the stipulations for the research must have real practical applications. This suggests it must either include the possibility of taking an action or consider the practical implications of the results.

4.2. Revisiting the Research Aims, Objectives and Questions

This research follows a straightforward and concise set of research questions and objectives stated below:

Table 4.1 Research Aims, Objectives & Questions

Research Aim	Research Questions	Research Objectives
<p><i>The aim of this research is to investigate the current Sudanese Labor Act of 1997 to assess its fitness for purpose.</i></p>	<p><i>What are the key aspects of the Sudanese Labor Act?</i></p>	<p><i>To identify the key aspects of the Sudanese Labor Act.</i></p>
	<p><i>What challenges can be identified within the Act in the context of international best practices?</i></p>	<p><i>To assess the critical challenges the Sudanese Labor Act faces in light of international best practices</i></p>
	<p><i>What strategies can be in place to ensure the Sudanese Labor Act meets the twenty-first century needs?</i></p>	<p><i>To identify the strategies and techniques for updating the Labor Act in order to suit Sudan's current HR needs.</i></p>

Source: (Original Source)

4.3. “Methodology”, “Method”, “Methods!”

In this chapter and throughout the study, the phrase “**Research Methodology**” or “**Research Method**” will be used interchangeably, meaning the same thing, referring to the theory of *how the research project is undertaken*. However, the word “**Methods**”, which is entirely different from the former two, is used to identify the *techniques and procedures* chosen for collecting and analysing the research data (Saunders *et al.*, 2007). “*Research methods may be understood as all those methods/techniques used for conduction of research; thus, refer to the methods the researcher uses in performing research operations (Kothari, 2004, p.7).*”

Research methods refer to all the tools and techniques the researcher deploys when investigating the research topic. Because the goal of this research, like all other applied research, is to discover a solution to a specific problem (in our case, the **Sudanese Labour Act of 1997**), the accessible data and the unknown features of the problem must be related to a solution to be attainable (Kothari, 2004). We must make this distinction early to avoid confusion and misunderstanding in the future. The researcher starts by discussing “**Methodology**” first, creating clarity for the term and an understanding of its parameters and will dive into the “**Methods**”, tackling its scope later in the chapter.

According to (Wilson, 2014), the research **methodology** refers to the strategy & overall approach, which includes everything from the theoretical application to the data collection & analysis techniques used to conduct the entire research. A research methodology is a systematic technique for methodically solving a research problem. It may be considered the

science that studies how academic research is conducted. The researcher develops the various phases to investigate the research topic and the rationale behind each. Because methodology varies from problem to problem, the researcher makes informed decisions and creates the approach that best suits her concern.

Therefore, it could safely be stated that research methodology has multiple facets and that research methods are a component of the methodology. The methodology includes a broader spectrum of issues beyond the research methods. Hence, when speaking about research methodology, the researcher doesn't just talk about the research methods; nonetheless, she also considers the rationale behind the methods used in the context of the research project and precisely justifies why she has used one method or technique over another; so that the research findings can be effectively evaluated by the researcher as well as others. The researcher will also be able to answer questions such as why this research has been undertaken, how the problem was defined, what sort of data was collected, what method was deployed, how the data was analysed and why a particular data analysis technique was chosen. Many additional questions should be answered (Kothari, 2004).

Furthermore, the researcher's methodological decisions were also impacted by the amount of time in hand, the deadline for the research project, the researcher's knowledge skills and previous experiences, the University of the West of Scotland's (UWS) regulations, the Supervisor's inputs, access issues, ethical considerations as well as the researcher's insight and her preferences (Blaxter *et al.*, 2010).

4.4. The Methodological Framework "*The Blueprint*"

After grasping the research methodology, it is time to embark on a reliable framework to help develop a practical roadmap or blueprint for the research journey/methodology the researcher intends to follow, i.e. develop the appropriate methodology that best suits the nature of this research and help answer the research questions in hand. According to Melnikovas (2018), the methodology is an extensive research strategy that specifies how the research project is conducted. It comprises a collection of ideas and philosophical assumptions that determine how researchers think about the research questions and the choice of research methods. The research methodology section for the research project helps ensure that the tools, techniques, and underlying philosophy are aligned and consistent.

The technique of research methodology development based on Saunders *et al.* theoretical idea, the famous "research onion," is a lengthy list of the significant layers or steps that must

be fulfilled to develop a sound methodology (Raithatha, 2017). The research methodology starts with the definition of the main philosophy, followed by the selection of approaches, methods, and strategies, as well as the establishment of time horizons, all of which led to the research design, i.e. the primary techniques and procedures for data collection and data analysis (Melnikovas, 2018). Saunders *et al.*'s research onion helped the researcher develop a solid foundational understanding and create a vision for the comprehensiveness and richness of the research methodology,

The researcher then chooses to embrace the **“Honeycomb”** (Wilson, 2013), which is less popular but very simple and effective, and the researcher feels more comfortable with its structure and is more confident with its application. The Honeycomb of Research Methodology (Wilson, 2013), elaborated further in the chapter, tends to explore and examine each part of the research method separately, not necessarily in a sequential pattern. The *honeycomb* places the methodology at the heart, surrounded and supported by each of the components that make up the research endeavour, formulating a solid bond around the methodology- holding it tight together. Each component forms an independent, versatile unit that can be separately acknowledged, valued, and thought about and is also worth exploring individually and among the methodology.

Therefore, the methodology is shaped by its outer components that make up the complete research methodology, shaping the entire research. The researcher likes to know that the components of the research methodology will always remain visible in her mind, forming a vivid mental image posing firmly as she navigates back and forth in the research journey from one compartment to the other without having to drop a “layer” during the process and the complete picture “blueprint” always remains vivid and accessible.

4.4.1. The Honeycomb (Wilson, 2014)

Wilson combines the six critical elements of research, making up the central focus points of the methodology diagrammed in one consolidated illustration, which acts as a *comprehensive framework*: combining all essential concepts of the study in contemplation of the relationship among and between all six concepts. Wilson called it a **“honeycomb”** for its resemblance to a beehive tightly knit to fit together, effectively gearing up all six elements logically engineering every process; the diagram below illustrates the framework. This research methodology follows Wilson’s fascinating framework (2014).

As discussed, another option could have been used, which is the research onion (Saunders *et al.*, 2019), just as well; however, the honeycomb approach considers the reality of the research thinking process that might not necessarily take a linear style and is multifaceted; the researcher may choose to tackle any of the elements at any stage in the research process as opposed to the onion layered format, which perceives a more sequential pattern (Wilson, 2014). Nevertheless, the researcher primarily intends to rely on (Saunders *et al.*, 2019) to reference the valued and much-appreciated literature, concepts and understanding. The diagram below summaries the research methodology and the discussion that follows:

Figure4.1 Honeycomb Research Methodology

Source: (Original Based on the Honeycomb of Research Methodology-Wilson, 2014)

4.5. Philosophy

Research philosophy is a term used to refer to the *system of beliefs and assumptions* related to the development of knowledge and the nature of knowledge (Saunders *et al.*, 2019) on which the research foundation is based. The development of knowledge in a particular field, for example, in this research project, involves the development of new knowledge by addressing the *Sudanese Labour Laws*, which hence involve many beliefs and assumptions, whether consciously aware or unaware of them (Burrell and Morgan 2016).

The research philosophy, according to (Saunders *et al.*, 2019), can be expressed from three perspectives, views or assumptions:

- A. ***Epistemological Assumptions***- assumptions about human knowledge and what constitutes valid, legitimate knowledge (*what*)
- B. ***Ontological Assumptions***- assumptions about the nature of realities encountered in the research (*what and how*)
- C. ***Axiological Assumptions***- the ways and the extent to which the researchers' values and ethics influence the research process.
- D.

To distinguish between these assumptions, one needs to understand the two opposing extremes related to the three philosophical assumptions "Objectivism" & "Subjectivism":

A. Objectivism:

Objectivism is a natural science approach that views the social world as external to researchers and social actors. It endorses realism, believing social phenomena exist like physical entities in the natural world. Objectivists aim to understand the social world through tangible, quantifiable facts, establishing law-like generalisations about universal social reality. They strive to avoid personal values that may distort their conclusions, as social entities and actors exist separately. Throughout a rigorous scientific study process, they remain detached from individual views and values (Saunders *et al.*, 2019)

B. Subjectivism:

Subjectivism, a philosophical approach that combines arts and humanities, suggests that social actors' perceptions and actions shape social reality. It adopts nominalism conventionalism, which asserts that researchers and other social actors create the structure and patterns of social phenomena through language, conceptual categories, perceptions, and behaviours. Nominalists believe that the social world has no underlying reality beyond what individuals assign to it and that various realities are more meaningful than a single universal reality (Burrell and Morgan 2016).

Social phenomena are constantly changing because of the dynamic nature of social interactions. Researchers must scrutinise situations, considering historical, geographical, and socio-cultural settings. Subjectivist researchers focus on multiple viewpoints and perspectives to account for diverse social experiences and realities.

They argue that they cannot separate themselves from their values and beliefs, as they actively use data to reflect on and challenge their views. They openly admit, proactively reflect, and include these arguments in their studies, ensuring a comprehensive understanding of social phenomena (Saunders *et al.*, 2019).

This research endeavour aims to develop knowledge of Sudan's labour/employment laws and the Equality Acts. The knowledge the researcher embarks on may not be as dramatic as creating a new theory of motivation, for example; nonetheless, despite the humble and simple aspiration of solving this problem, "*bridging the gaps of the Sudanese Labour Act*" may seem it certainly contributes to the development of new knowledge in a field of great contextual significance. It intends to develop new knowledge in an area significantly overlooked and understudied in Sudan. The philosophy the research adopts constitutes critical assumptions and considerations, indicating how the writer perceives and views the world (Saunders *et al.*, 2019).

The research philosophy is generally associated with the author's beliefs in knowledge development. However, the researcher undertakes the study and will be influenced by her perceptions of what constitutes knowledge, which comes naturally and subconsciously (Burrell and Morgan 2016). Yet, grasping the research philosophy is essential, as it affects how the researcher conducts the study (Wilson, 2014). According to Mark Easterby-Smith *et al.* (2002), there are three reasons why understanding philosophical matters is helpful. For instance, it can assist in the clarification of the research design. This includes thinking about the sort of evidence that will be required, as well as how it will be collected and analysed. Second, understanding philosophy can help determine which designs are most effective. Finally, philosophical knowledge can assist researchers in identifying and adapting research designs to the limitations of various subjects or knowledge structures. In essence, comprehending research philosophy is essential because it encourages the researcher to consider her position as a researcher.

4.5.1. Epistemology

Epistemology refers precisely to the *nature of knowledge*, meaning how we visualise our surroundings. The central concern epistemology seeks to comprehend is what is *acceptable knowledge* in the field of understudy (Saunders *et al.*, 2019). It refers to the assumptions regarding knowledge, what constitutes reasonable, valid, and legitimate knowledge, and how we may communicate it to others (Burrell and Morgan 2016). The research's view is that

what is considered necessary in this study is adopting assumptions, opinions, and specific individual contextual meanings to add value to the field.

Looking into the nature of this research, we can confirm that it is **not** “*natural science*”, and it cannot be compared to natural science in any form or shape; for this reason, the researcher does not intend to adopt an approach comparable to that of the natural scientist (**Positivism**); therefore, the epistemological approach is *defiantly not positivist*. Positivism always takes an objective stand in research, and the researcher is usually detached from their study; however, in this research situation, the researcher preferred to take an **active role** in the study, taking an in-depth look into the subject of Sudanese Labour and Employment Laws without detaching the researcher’s beliefs and some relative personal biases. The purpose of the study is **not** to *generalise findings* and be genuinely objective but to *interact, participate* and be *actively engaged* with the research participants throughout the research process (Wilson, 2014).

Therefore, the nature of this research theme is a **social science** covering a business issue that is relatively complicated to be tackled and measured in line with other natural sciences; consequently, the writer is bound to adopt the role of an “*interpretivist researcher*”. **Interpretivism** is “*an epistemology that supports the view that the researcher must enter the social world of what is being examined*” (Wilson, 2014, p.10). It is essential to explain the researcher’s relationship to the chosen topic and problem area under investigation; it is an area of immense professional, practical experience and personal understanding. This is an area of specialisation the writer cannot personally detach from and has a close relationship with the variables under investigation and will be involved in the interpretation and understanding of its realities (the truth is the researcher is part of this reality). The researcher interacts with social actors within their cultural settings to analyse and understand the data. This certainly involved **observations** and **interpretations** that are *qualitative and subjective*.

The researcher has a profound comprehension and active engagement in this research topic, primarily attributable to the inherent character of the subject matter. This is a consequence of the researcher’s extensive exposure and prior experiences accumulated over the years in this field. Hence, the participants and the writer are both relying on each other and working alongside each other in steering the research investigation, i.e. it is a collaborative, participatory and interdependent relationship which embraces a paradigm or philosophy of an **interpretivism** approach (Wilson, 2014). If, however, for any reason, the researcher was not certain of the philosophical approach to follow, being not entirely certain of the nature of

knowledge (*where this does not apply to this research project*) and felt that it was swinging in between the two extremes of *Positivism* and *Interpretivism*, the researcher would have then followed a ***Pragmatism Approach***.

The *pragmatic* paradigm recognises the relevance of both the physical and social worlds and does not associate itself with any one philosophical viewpoint. Pragmatist researchers concentrate on the investigation of the problem's "what" and "how" (Creswell, 2003). While mixed methods may be employed with any paradigm, pragmatism is the most common paradigm for mixed methods social research enquiry (Greene, 2007). Pragmatists prioritise the research problem and questions and adopt the methods they believe are most effective in obtaining the most meaningful results from their investigations (Wilson, 2014).

4.5.2. Ontology

Ontological assumptions shape how the writer perceives and approaches the research study; the author's ontology decides how the world of business and employment regulations and best practice Equality Acts are seen from the writer's point of view. Hence, the researcher chooses what to study and what to research (Saunders *et al.*, 2009). Making the ontology in this study subjective- ***Subjectivism*** is nominal and a socially variously constructed reality which adopts assumptions of the researcher, as well as opinions and specific individual background meanings to add value to the field of employment laws application in Sudanese organisations; consequently, adding value to the socioeconomic wellbeing and making an effective contribution in Sudan. The writer's passion and involvement in the subject matter significantly impact its critical analysis and findings. Conversely, if not objectively handled, it may be a drastic pitfall.

Turner and Pirie (2016) have described these fatal pitfalls. They argue that within their long years of experience with research students, they have repeatedly seen researchers' struggles in critically analysing subject areas to which they are individually attached. They make use of their comprehensive understanding of subject matters. They are encouraged by their solid past experiences and their strength and capability in accessing data and information, let alone their familiarity with the subject. They were, subsequently, becoming deeply involved! *"However, as a result of this involvement in the subject area, students often face the pitfall of being unable to form an objective opinion, thus impacting the analysis of the research topic, and as such, they can be prone to producing overly descriptive, even biased work as a result"* (Turner & Pirie 2016 p.2).

The issue of the Labour, Employment & Equality Acts in the context of Sudan has deep, profound meaning and relevance to the researcher to the extent that the proximity of the subject matter and immense relevance are thought to hinder the validity and threaten the project with tremendous subjectivity. Therefore, the researcher has made an extraordinary effort to detach and take a careful, conscious, objective stand throughout the project, not to jeopardise the research's validity, reliability, and quality of *findings*.

4.5.3. Axiology (*Biased*)

According to Saunders *et al.* (2019), *axiology* is the impact of values and ethics in research. Axiology can be defined as “*a branch of philosophy that studies judgments about value*” (Saunders *et al.* 2007, p. 110). It is concerned with the researcher's perception and the role this perception plays in the research (the role of values in the inquiry); our values play a vital role in the entire research process (Wilson, 2014). One of the most essential axiological judgments for a researcher is whether the researcher desires to see the influence of the researcher's values and beliefs on the study as positive. As a result, the researcher must determine how to deal with one's values and those of the individuals behind the investigation.

For example, one might believe that their values are the guiding rationale for all actions and that while unquestionably integrating these values during the process, it is critical that one openly acknowledges and reflects on them as conducting and writing the research (Heron, 1996). Choosing one topic over another implies that the researcher considers one more valuable. Therefore, the research philosophy approach and the data collection techniques chosen merely to reflect the researcher's values (Saunders *et al.*, 2019). Saunders argue that the influence of values on choices is absolutely in place; the researcher chose this topic because she considers it to matter the most to her, her people and her country.

Furthermore, the researcher's choice of research methods reflects her values, ethics and personal principles; it also demonstrates the value of the research itself, its significance and what it means to the researcher (the research methods selected are discussed in full detail later in the chapter).

Therefore, regardless of the standpoint, articulating one's values and beliefs as a foundation for making choices and decisions about what research to conduct in the first place and how to undertake it demonstrates the researcher's axiological ability and competence (Heron, 1996). This research is not value-free; the researcher is fully involved with her values and beliefs

embedded in and interdependent with her research. As an “*interpretivist*”, the researcher’s values are built-in and incorporated throughout the research process, from collecting the data, interpreting it and presenting the findings.

For example, the nominated sample of experts is a targeted selection of Human Resource and labour law experts (around 9) whom the researcher knows, trusts their judgment, believes they have the right competence for the task and are expected to add value to the research. This is not left to chance but a cautious, judgmental sampling process. Therefore, this is non-random, and the researcher’s values are openly visible and explicitly communicated. The researcher tries to produce integral and credible results throughout this process.

Figure 4.2 Philosophy Undertaken

Source: (Original)

4.6. Theoretical Development and Contribution

Before discussing the research approach, the second cell in the honeycomb framework, it is vital to begin by understanding the word *theory* and the researcher’s role in developing a *theoretical* attempt. According to (Saunders *et al.*, 2015), a good theory should include not only the “*what*” and “*how*” parts to establish fundamental variables and describe the nature

of their association (cause and effect), but it must also apply “*logical reasoning*” to explain why the relationship exists in the first place. ‘*Logical*’ because the researcher is searching for compelling evidence to justify “why” and “reasoning” because logic will be grounded on what is already known about the “what” and “how”. Once a reasonable explanation has been created, the theory may be used to predict new outcomes by modifying the factors on which the theory is based, such as who the theory applies to, when and where it applies.

Kelly (1955) claims that everyone trying to tackle the day-to-day challenges confronted by all addresses the task similarly, just as any scientist. Both create and test hypotheses constantly, and their concepts are modified. Both organise their findings into schemata (conceptual frameworks), which are then classified into theories and are a system of wider schemata. Kelly believes researchers require schemata and ideas like these to make sense of the world. People would be overwhelmed by the amount of irrelevant information they had to remember without organizing frameworks. People employ theory in their daily lives and occupations without realizing it (implicitly).

One must not be intimidated by “theory” since it is deeply embedded in our daily lives. Acknowledging its significance implies making it explicit if it is implicit in all day-to-day decisions and actions. The relevance of theory in research must be recognized; hence, it must be made explicit. Understanding how theory is created is significant when formulating research questions and objectives. Each research endeavour will aim to either test a theory or develop one. This research project would have been theory-driven and used a deductive approach if the researcher wanted to take a defined theoretical stance that could be verified via data gathering. However, this research project is data-driven and takes an ***inductive approach*** since the researcher studies a topic and creates a theoretical explanation as the data is collected and analysed; these approaches are further explained in the coming section of the research approaches (Saunders *et al.*, 2015).

While anticipating a theoretical explanation to emerge, the researcher is certainly not expected to develop a groundbreaking idea that will lead to an entirely new way of thinking in business or management! Not all theoretical contributions seem the same, and the three-tiered categorization of theories is comforting. **Grand theories**, such as Newton’s theory of gravity, Darwin’s theory of evolution, or Einstein’s theory of relativity, are typically under natural scientists’ jurisdiction. Those could be compared with **Middle-range theories**, which

lack the potential to transform how researchers think about the world yet are still indispensable. This category includes several well-known theories on human motivation.

On the other hand, most researchers are preoccupied with Substantive ideas that are limited to a specific period, sites around the world, a particular group or population, or a specific problem. *Studying the gaps in Sudan's labour and employment laws is an example of developing a substantive theory*. Despite its limits, several of these “substantive theories” with similar assumptions may eventually lead to “middle-range theories”. As a researcher, expanding the understanding of the surrounding world by generating “substantive theories”, however modest they may seem, is a *bold* statement, but it is *true* (Saunders *et al.*, 2015)!

Figure 4.3 Grand, Middle-range, and Substantive Theories

Source: (Saunders et al., 2015)

4.7. Research Approach

The second cell in the honeycomb structure contains the **Research Approach** compartment. As discussed, the research includes the application of theory, which may or may not be mentioned in detail in the research design stage. However, the actual substance of the theory is reached at the end using the results of the research findings. The philosophy the researcher chose to follow earlier determines the approach later used to create the theory or justify the reasoning behind the findings. Likewise, the approach chosen impacts the design and research methods the researcher decides to undertake (Babbie, 2010).

According to Saunders *et al.* (2019), theory development may be approached in three different ways or approaches: “*Theory Deduction*”, “*Theory Induction*”, and “*Theory Abduction*”. When the researcher examines what is undertaken in terms of these three

approaches, it may be categorised that these undertakings take three logical categories respectively: “*Theory Testing*”, “*Theory Building*”, and “*Theory Modification*” (Aesanetwork.org). With deduction, a theory and hypothesis or hypotheses are created, and a research strategy is then designed to test this hypothesis. With induction, data is collected, and a theory is developed or built based on the data analyses. With abduction, data is used to investigate a phenomenon, discover themes, and explain patterns, as well as develop a new or modify an existing theory that is then tested, typically with further data collection (Saunders *et al.*, 2015). The three approaches (deduction, induction, and abduction) are explained further and summarised in the table below:

Table 4.2 Deduction, Induction & Abduction (*from reason to research*)

	Deduction	Induction	Abduction
Logic	In a deductive inference, when the premises are true, the conclusion must also be true	In an inductive inference, known premises are used to generate untested conclusions	In an abductive inference, known premises are used to generate testable conclusions
Generalizability	Generalizing from the general to the specific	Generalizing from the specific to the general	Generalizing from the interactions between the specific and the general
Use of Data	Data collection is used to evaluate propositions or hypotheses related to an existing theory	Data collection is used to explore a phenomenon, identify themes and patterns and create a conceptual framework	Data collection is used to explore a phenomenon, identify themes and patterns, locate these in a conceptual framework and test this through subsequent data collection and so forth
Theory	Theory falsification or verification	Theory generation and building	Theory generation or modification; incorporating existing theory where appropriate, to build new theory or modify existing theory

Source (Saunders *et al.*, 2015, p. 145)

The research in hand follows an **Inductive** approach; as explained, inductive is defined as “*a theory-building process, starting with observations of specific instances, and seeking to establish generalisation about the phenomenon under investigation*” (Hyde, 2000 p. 83). Following an inductive approach, this research starts by seeking observations about the

research problem (the existing Sudanese labour law of 1997 with its current state and evident gaps). To add value, contribute to developing a new theory (a new set of missing laws that must be incorporated to bridge these gaps). Therefore, data will be collected first and then analysed in pursuit of the findings to develop a theory, i.e., the project begins with observations and ends with theory (theory follows the data), not the other way round as in deductive approaches where one starts with a theory or hypotheses and ends with a set observation (Wilson, 2014). Furthermore, there is no room for existing theory modification with further findings, so this research cannot follow an *abductive approach*.

There is an evident gap in the literature for a study championing the situation of Sudan, so the author embarks on this piece of research. Moreover, the researcher has a strong background and experience in the area of understudy and is considered a subject matter expert with first-hand experiences and applications, which will facilitate the research endeavour. This qualitative research deals with qualitative data (qualitative will be explained later) collected in the form of semi-structured interviews, which is one reason the research follows an *inductive approach*. It follows a more flexible structure to allow room for changes as the research develops, and there are no concerns about generalising the findings (Saunders et al., 2007), which is why it follows an inductive approach. The findings are intended for a particular contextual setting that is not necessarily applicable to other settings; thus, generalisation is not intended. Nevertheless, the research approach and findings will guide and benefit other researchers with similar purposes in Sudan and the region.

4.8. Quantitative or Qualitative?

Quantitative research methods, at their most basic level, are devoted to gathering and analysing structured data that may be represented in quantifiable numerical forms (Matthews, R. and Ross, E., 2010). One of its primary objectives is to create precise and reliable measures that can be analysed statistically. According to (Goertzen, 2017), “*Quantitative Research*” is highly successful in answering the “what” and “how” scenarios because it concentrates on data that can be quantified. The results generated by quantitative research tend to reveal patterns, trends, and behaviours. However, it is necessary to realise that they don’t explain why individuals think, feel, or act the way they do. Put another way, quantitative research identifies trends across data sets or study groups but not the motivations underlying the observed actions. To cater to this knowledge gap, “Qualitative research”

methods such as focus groups, interviews, or open-ended survey questions are successful alternatives for filling these knowledge gaps (Goertzen, 2017).

Quantitative researchers gather data and analyse how one data item relates to the other. They employ numerical data and, in most cases, systematic and predefined research goals, conceptual frameworks, and designs (Punch, 2005). As a result, they deploy approaches that are anticipated to yield quantifiable and, if feasible, generalisable results. Researchers who take a *qualitative approach* are more interested in learning about people's perspectives on the world. They question the existence of social *facts* and the applicability of a *scientific* approach to dealing with people.

Moreover, Punch (2005) highlighted one key distinction: qualitative research employs non-numeric and unstructured data. Usually, it includes research objectives and techniques that are more general at first and eventually grow more targeted as the study develops. There are times, however, when qualitative researchers use quantitative methods and contrariwise. It all depends on the information the researcher seeks (Bell, J., 2010).

Furthermore, (Saunders *et al.*, 2016) argue that the distinction between numeric data (numbers) and non-numeric data is one way that is often used to differentiate quantitative research from qualitative research (words, images, video clips and other similar material). In this context, the term "*quantitative*" is frequently used to refer to any data-collecting method (such as a questionnaire) or data analysis method (such as graphs or statistics) that creates or uses numerical data. Conversely, "*qualitative*" is commonly used as a synonym for any non-numerical data-gathering approach, such as an interview or data processing procedure, such as classifying data. Therefore, quantitative and qualitative research are two extremes of a continuum that can sometimes be combined in practice, resulting in research designs that may mix methodologies in various ways (Saunders *et al.*, 2016).

According to (Saunders *et al.*, 2016), *quantitative research* is often connected with positivism, especially when data collection procedures are predefined and highly structured. In addition, quantitative research is generally affiliated with a *deductive approach*, in which data is used to test theories. It may, however, integrate an inductive approach, in which data is utilised to create theory. A single data collection method, such as a questionnaire and a matching quantitative analytical procedure, may be used in a quantitative research design (*mono-method quantitative research*). More than one quantitative data collection method and

an appropriate analysis procedure may be used in a quantitative research design (*multi-method quantitative research*); see the diagram below:

Figure 4.4 Methodological Choices

Source: (Saunders et al., 2016)

Experimental and survey research strategies are commonly linked with quantitative research. A survey research strategy is typically used in quantitative research and involves questionnaires, structured interviews, or perhaps structured observation. An *interpretative philosophy*, on the other hand, is usually connected with *qualitative research* (Denzin and Lincoln 2011). It is interpretative, as researchers must make sense of people’s subjective and socially constructed interpretations of the phenomena under investigation.

This kind of research is called “naturalistic research”. It is so named because it requires researchers to work in a natural environment or study context to build trust, involvement, participation, access to meanings, and reach in-depth knowledge. Like quantitative research, qualitative research may also be used within realism and pragmatic ideologies (Saunders *et al.*, 2016). Various sets of qualitative research begin with an *inductive approach* to theory development, where a naturalistic and emergent research strategy is used to create a theory or generate a deeper theoretical standpoint beyond the currently existing literature. On the other hand, some qualitative research strategies begin with a *deductive approach*, in which qualitative procedures are used to evaluate an existing hypothesis (Yin, 2014).

In practice, much qualitative research employs an *abductive approach* to theory building, in which inductive and deductive conclusions are produced and tested repeatedly during the study. Furthermore, a qualitative research design may employ a single data collection technique, such as semi-structured interviews, and a qualitative analysis procedure to

complement it (*mono-method qualitative research*). More than one qualitative data collection technique and associated analytical method may be used in a qualitative research design (*a multi-method qualitative study*); see the diagram above. Qualitative research is linked with several different strategies. While they all have shared ontological and epistemological foundations and traits, each strategy embraces its purpose, scope, and set of methods. Action research, case study research, ethnography, grounded theory, and narrative research (storytelling) are some of the most popular qualitative research methods.

4.9. Strategy

Generally, a strategy is a plan of action to achieve a specific goal. Hence, a research strategy may be considered the plan used by the researcher to address the research questions and objectives. The methodological connection between the philosophy and the succeeding data collection and analysis methods chosen (Denzin and Lincoln 2011). Based on the research questions set for this research and the *inductive approach* selected, the suitable research strategy, in this case, is a **Qualitative Strategy**. It is also worth mentioning that this is a *social* issue dealing with opinions from a pool of chosen experts and non-numerical data.

According to (Have, 2004), qualitative research is characterised by an essential feature related to the primary data collected and results presented and summarised as verbal expressions, in contrast to quantitative data, usually given in numerical forms. Have further explains the meaning by identifying another critical feature of qualitative research: the researcher's effort to search deep for buried meanings, non-obvious qualities, multiple interpretations, implied associations, and hidden voices. Raigin (1994) differentiates between qualitative and quantitative techniques by saying that most quantitative data techniques are "*data condensers*" while quantitative methods are "*data enhancers*".

It is important to note that the researcher did not undertake a qualitative strategy to avoid dealing with numbers and statistical findings; nevertheless, due to the nature of the data collection protocol and the absence of theory relevant to these research questions. Qualitative research in social sciences, particularly in management and business contexts, is valuable and reliable; it is just as good and essential as the most vigorous quantitative research techniques and must not be perceived as an easy substitute for "statistical" quantitative techniques (Creswell and Poth, 2016).

Figure 4.5 Choice of Philosophy Determines
Research Approach & Strategy

Source: (Original Based on Wilson, 2014)

4.10. Design

According to Bryman and Harley (2011), “a research design provides a framework for the collection and analysis of data” (Bryman & Harley, 2011 P. 40). They argue that the research design nominated for the research project stipulates the decisions made and priorities given to a wide range of dimensions in the research process. Wilson (2014), however, puts it in simpler terms and defines research design as a *plan or detailed framework* that is set to guide the researcher throughout the research process to achieve the research objectives. It is essential to mention that the research design is determined by the research philosophy previously embarked on; it helps clarify it, decide which works better and identify and adapt designs following the subject area understudy and knowledge structures (Easterby-Smith *et al.* 2002). A critical plan for answering the research questions, as explained, is the design.

Furthermore, stressing and appreciating the significance of clearly defining the research questions can never be overstated. It consists of specific goals and objectives originating from the research questions specifying the source from which the researcher collects the data, how she collects and analyses this data and discusses the ethical issues and the challenges faced in the process, such as accessing the data, time issues, location, and resources. Above all, it

must indicate that the researcher has addressed all aspects of the selected research design. The first methodological choice is effectively choosing to undergo a *qualitative technique* of study, which is the broad research strategy. This choice requires a distinct combination of elements to achieve the consistency and coherence the researcher seeks in the research design (Saunders *et al.*, 2015).

According to (Rowley, 2002), a research design consists of the research questions, the proposal, units of analysis, the reasoning that connects the data to the proposal and the criteria for interpreting the results. (Blumberg *et al.*, 2005) similarly argue that the essentials of research design are that it is an activity and a time-based plan, as mentioned earlier, it is persistently founded on the research questions, it determines the sources and types of information to be used, *it is the framework that defines the relationships between the variables* in the study, and each research activity is outlined in the design. After understanding the scale of the research design, it is essential to distinguish between the *types of research studies* by recognising the *actual purpose* of the design before revealing the different options of research design available at our fingertips and which one/s is most appropriate for answering the research questions.

4.10.1. The Purpose of the Research Design:

The objectives of the search massively determine the type of research study. This researcher, for example, aspires to research an area known to have received little attention from local Sudanese scholars. For example, The researcher could have wanted to examine how one variable affects another, which she did not. Either way, this research project will directly impact or dictate the research design adopted (Wilson, 2014). Research can be pursued (designed) to fulfil and accomplish one of the following purposes: either an *exploratory*, *descriptive*, *explanatory*, or *evaluative* purpose or a *combination* of these (the table below summarises the purpose of the research).

Table 4.3 Purpose of Research

Exploratory Studies:	Descriptive Studies:	Explanatory Studies:	Evaluative Studies:	Combined Studies:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exploratory study is a powerful tool for discovering what's going on and obtaining insights into a subject of research by asking open-ended questions. • Exploratory research questions are likely to begin with the words such as “What” or “How” (questions used to gather data in order investigate a problem, issue, or a situation). • An exploratory design is highly valuable if we want to clarify our knowledge of a problem, situation, or phenomena, such as if we are not sure what it's all about. • An Exploratory study can be performed in a number of different ways. A literature search, interviews with ‘experts’ in the field, in-depth individual interviews, and focus group interviews are just a few examples. • Because of their exploratory character, these interviews are likely to be unstructured, depending on the value of the contributions of 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Descriptive research is used to create an accurate profile of certain events, people, or circumstances. • Descriptive research questions are likely to start with, or include the words: “Who”, “What”, “Where”, “When” and “How” • Questions about events, characters, or circumstances that we ask throughout the data collection stage are likely to begin with, or incorporate, the words: “Who”, “What”, “Where”, “When” and “How” • Descriptive research can be used as a follow-up component to exploratory research or as a groundwork to an explanatory study. Prior to collecting data, we must have a clear understanding of the phenomena on which we intend to gather information. • Work that is overly descriptive should generally be avoided. The researcher is expected to go a little farther by making conclusions from the facts they are describing, as 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Explanatory research is defined as a study that establishes causal connections between variables. Explanatory research questions are likely to begin with or include the words “why” or “how.” • Questions asked during the data collection stage to provide an explanation are likely to begin with, or contain, the words “Why” or “How” • Explanatory studies are aimed at investigating a scenario or an issue in order to understand the relationships between the variables. • To achieve a clearer picture of the relationships, the data can be subjected to statistical methods like correlation. As an alternative, qualitative data may be gathered to understand and clarify why things are the way they are. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evaluative research is used to measure how well something works. • Questions that intend to examine responses are likely to begin with the word ‘How,’ or include the word “What” as in “To What Extend”. • In business and management, evaluative research is focused on determining, for example the effectiveness of a firm’s or organization's strategy, a specific policy, a program, project, or procedure. • The questions we ask to get an evaluative perspective during the data collection stage are likely to begin with, or incorporate, words like “What” “How” or “Why”. • The researcher could be interested in making comparisons between situations, events, people, countries, or timeframes as part of the evaluative research, therefore we might ask questions like “Which”, “When” “Who”, or “Where”. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In its design, a research study can combine multiple purposes. • This may be accomplished by incorporating mixed methods research into the research design, which allows for a mix of exploratory, descriptive, explanatory, and evaluative research. • Alternatively, a single technique study design can be implemented in a way that allows for several purposes to be accomplished.

<p>the individuals participating to drive the research's next stage.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exploratory research has the virtue of being responsive to change and flexible. • While exploratory research may begin with a broad focus, it will narrow as the study proceeds. 	<p>well as refining their data evaluation and idea synthesizing capabilities, to more advanced competencies beyond mere precise description.</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Asking these questions allows us to evaluate the effectiveness of different elements; evaluative research will therefore allow us to better understand, evaluate and compare performance in this way. • Evaluative research may generate a theoretical contribution by emphasizing not only "how successful" something is, but also "why," and then comparing that explanation to contemporary ideas (existing theory). 	
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Source: (Saunders et al., 2015)

This qualitative research relies mainly on semi-structured interviews to support the data collection, which is exploratory, descriptive, explanatory, and evaluative, i.e., a combined purpose study!

4.10.2. Different Types of Research Design

Figure 4.6 Types of Research Design (Options)

Source: (Original Derived from Wilson, 2014)

As seen in the illustration above, many research design options exist. The research philosophy determines this selection; accordingly, the research design suited to achieve the objectives is *Comparative Design*, where two or more groups are compared on one variable, which is a measurable characteristic (Wilson, 2014). Here, the researcher compares written documents “Sudanese Labour Act of 1997” to relevant elected best practice standard documents of contemporary international employment standards & best practice Equality Acts to highlight the existing gaps and challenges. A comparative study is essential for measuring where the Labour Act stands regarding global standards.

It compares “like” with “like”; the researcher does not investigate specifics of countries that distinctly surpass Sudan regarding social and economic progression and mismatch its cultural makeup, making the comparison invalid and unreliable. Nevertheless, the comparison lies between what Sudan is currently practising and what the world community is advocating for and has together agreed constitutes the minimum threshold for all nations in terms of ensuring the fundamental human right for good practice in the workplace, the dignity of workers and good working lives (a benchmark relevant and intended for all).

4.11. Data Collection (Generation)

Mason (2002) made an insightful distinction between *data sources* and the *methods* used for generating data from those sources. The researcher believes this is a necessary beginning and an important distinction before proceeding further in detail. Despite her efforts, Mason argues that this distinction will probably get muddled in the future; nonetheless, it is a valuable start (Mason, 2002). Based on Mason's idea, one may consider "*people*" as the *data sources* because they are the banks of essential knowledge, experiences, emotions, or otherwise. Nonetheless, there may be a much broader range of methods through which one might consider collecting data from these people, such as observing them, talking to them, or video recording them, collecting items they have created, such as their writings, or asking them to create something specific, such as a journal or issue some pictures. In this respect, the data sources are the situations or occurrences from or through which one believes data may be created. Thus, the researcher must consider whether they might develop data from this source. Hence, the *tactics and strategies* she must deploy to do this are regarded as *data-generating methods* or techniques.

Thinking about data sources and techniques in this manner doesn't imply considering data as an already existent reserve of knowledge, ready to be acquired and unaffected by our judgments as researchers. Of course, many qualitative researchers would disagree with that, and Mason (2002) chose to use the word data "*creation*" instead of "collection", intending to reflect the much broader spectrum of interactions that qualitative research entails between the researcher, social environment, and data. Most qualitative points of view would reject the notion that a researcher can be an impartial and neutral collector of information about social settings; hence, she believes it would be more practical and realistic to speak about generating rather than collecting data. Instead, the researcher is constantly proactively building knowledge about that reality, using the principles and techniques drawn from or reflecting their epistemological stand. Hence, this researcher would not just determine where to go for data in a collectable condition. Instead, the researcher also determines how to get the most data from the selected sources using intellectual, analytical, and interpretive abilities, i.e., effectively generating data!

4.11.1. Sourcing the Data

Social scientists use a variety of data-gathering techniques to gather information. Experiments and quasi-experiments are essential sources of data for many reasons. They

usually feature a study design that allows for robust research hypotheses. Furthermore, structured questionnaires are another significant data-gathering method since they generally collect information on many variables from a large and representative sample of respondents. Finally, the data collection technique in a qualitative research design typically entails capturing a significant quantity of data from a small, selected group (sample) utilising in-depth interviews, observations, or focus groups (Boeije and Hox, 2005).

Data can be classified into two types: primary data and secondary data. According to (Boeije and Hox, 2005), “**Primary data**” are data collected/generated specifically for the research topic in hand, employing techniques customised to the research topic. New information is added to the current repository of social knowledge each time primary data is gathered. This material generated by other academics/researchers is progressively being made accessible for reuse by the broader research community; it is then referred to as “**secondary data**”.

The researcher will use primary and secondary data for this comparative study. The **secondary data** used constitutes all previously written documents relevant to the research, whether directly related to the core of the investigation or indirectly related in the form of the literature reviewed to underpin the research. The researcher uses textbooks, academic journals, different Internet websites, abstracts, reports, theses, catalogues, dictionaries, bibliographies, encyclopaedias and various policies and legislations. **Primary data** is at the heart of this research, and it is core to answering the research questions and achieving its objectives. It is related to the information and inputs gathered and generated from a pool of expert participants. The researcher collected the data herself; this data was collected using **interviews**, mainly **semi-structured interviews**. The researcher couldn't rely on secondary data for one important reason: its limitation and, in this case, absence!

The Sudanese labour law situation is a topic that is largely overlooked and severely understudied. Furthermore, the data that might be available is not specific to Sudan and generally focuses on African countries, predominantly North African and Middle Eastern countries, that, yes, somewhat resembles the situation of Sudan; however, Sudan has a unique set of circumstances that such broad generalisation is far from applicable to its character. Finally, the researcher chooses to embark primarily on Primary Data to produce original, reliable work that is targeted, tailored, and specific and could be easily applicable to Sudan. Therefore, the data generated for this research is original and unique. Despite its cost, challenges and apprehension, the researcher is confident this is the best way forward.

4.11.2. The Interviewing Process

Research interviewing is a structured conversation where the interviewer establishes rapport and asks precise questions, allowing the interviewee to respond and listen attentively. This method enables the researcher to delve deeper into the responses (Saunders *et al.*, 2015). Wilkinson and Birmingham (2003) define interviews in research as more than just conversations; they are used to gather detailed information about a specific issue or subject matter. It is worth mentioning that “*interviews are not an easy option*” (Wilkinson and Birmingham, 2003, p. 43). The researcher must make informed efforts to gain insight by extracting information from the targeted respondents one-on-one. Interviews, when conducted correctly, can provide valid, reliable, and credible data that aligns with the research questions and objectives. (Saunders *et al.*, 2015). To achieve that, the researcher utilised *semi-structured interviews*, a flexible technique that combines structured questions with room for respondents to elaborate and raise significant issues. This approach provided insights into participants’ beliefs and attitudes, utilising verbal and nonverbal cues (Wilson, 2014).

Structured interviews, also known as quantitative research interviews, according to Saunders *et al.* (2015), are conducted using pre-arranged, standardised questions. These interviews are read aloud and recorded on a predetermined schedule, with pre-coded responses. While socialisation may occur, questions are asked precisely and in the same tone to avoid biases. *Semi-structured* and *in-depth interviews* are non-standardised, while *qualitative research interviews* are commonly used. Researchers start with a list of ideas and critical questions, but how they are handled and implemented varies depending on the study setting.

Depending on the discussion’s dynamic, the sequence of questions was sometimes modified and altered. Furthermore, given the nature of events within certain situations, the researcher needed to keep asking questions to fully explore the research questions and objectives due to the nature of the questions and the subsequent discussions. Data was collected via an audio recording of the dialogue and the researcher’s written notes. The interview session included some statements to initiate the conversation, a list of cues to stimulate and expand the discussion, and some remarks to conclude it, in addition to the list of topics and questions covered (Saunders *et al.*, 2015).

4.11.3. Conducting the Interviews

The researcher conducted the interviews herself in relatively long and deep focused discussions that took place remotely with the aid of interactive technological communication techniques thanks to Zoom and WhatsApp. Despite the enormous geographical barriers, the researcher felt great proximity and connection with her participants; they were all very keen and passionate about the subject, had a duty of care and felt responsible for contributing. The researcher had an excellent chance to focus on the discussion and actively listen to engage and probable the interviews.

Almost all participants were comfortable expressing their views in their mother tongue language “Arabic” which is also the researcher’s first language, although all participants were proficient English speakers. The researcher encouraged the participants to speak at ease and was confident that this enriched the conversation and gave them the comfort and relief they needed to focus on expressing their ideas and thoughts without boundaries or losing any crucial meanings in the conversion effort.

The good thing is that the researcher was very keen on listening to the audio recordings right after the discussion and, on some occasions, more than once. This was necessary for the researcher to understand the data and what the participants had to say; the researcher wanted to feel comfortable and familiar with the data. Each interview had its element of ingredient, uniqueness, and flavour. Every time the researcher discovers something new and exciting looks forward to the subsequent discussion (this will be discussed further in the Data Analysis section).

4.11.4. The Participants

The Sudanese Labour Law Experts and Practitioners were selected from a pool of close networks of professionals mostly known and accessible to the researcher. The criteria for their selection were based on their qualifications, years of experience (not less than 20 years), and reputation in Sudan. Based on the researcher’s previous knowledge and relations in the workplace, almost all the experts were already known to the researcher and were contacted directly by the researcher. A few participants snowballed using the knowledge of the targeted experts and their trusted recommendations and databases.

4.11.5. Seeking Consent

These discussions were conducted and recorded only after consent. The idea of autonomy recognises everyone has the freedom to choose their path. It is at the heart of the requirement

for free and informed consent. The researchers' information to the participants was sufficiently informative, relevant, and correct. Consent was freely provided and was revocable. There was no excessive influence or compulsion, such as disproportionate rewards or disincentives for refusing to consent. Ensuring all participants were fully aware of the research purpose and methods was critical. All participants were given enough time to think about the facts and decide whether to participate.

4.11.6. Reaching Saturation

Input and information were gathered and generated from 9 expert participants. An average of 90-180-minute sessions were conducted on an average of 2–3 time sessions per participant. They are a reputable representation of Sudanese professionals with years of expertise (20 years and above) in human resources management, employment regulations, and the practical application of the Sudanese Labour Act of 1997.

After analysing three in-depth interviews, the data revealed tremendously informative and satisfying information. The researcher reached code saturation at five interviews and saturation at seven interviews, allowing the researcher to uncover a massively relevant and wide range of thematic themes.

However, the researcher proceeded with the nine predetermined interviews to attain richness and meaningful saturation, a stage at which reaching a deeply textured understanding of the intended meanings and issues (Hennink *et al.*, 2017). It was challenging to secure a number beyond what has been considered for this study because of the scarcity of the calibre required for the study and to safeguard the credibility and reliability of the research findings, conclusions, and recommendations.

4.11.7. Challenges Faced

Some of the biggest challenges are geographical distance barriers and the impossibility of face-to-face communication. The hectic schedules of these high-profile participants and interviewees presented another challenge; it was challenging and occasionally stressful to plan the appointments with them. Due to pressing business needs, several meetings had to be called to an end and rescheduled. Additionally, there was a time difference issue because of how widely scattered the participants were throughout the different continents, which made it challenging to schedule mutually favourable meeting times. Additionally, due to COVID-19 and the unpredictable nature of the virus, some meetings had to be postponed. Finally, despite

their efficacy, the depth of the dialogues occasionally resulted in long, exhausting sessions, and sometimes technological restrictions were also encountered.

4.11.8. The Delphi Technique

In addition to the interviews, the researcher used a *Delphi Method* to strengthen the data and confirm the findings. A structured, systematic, interactive communication technique (Rowe and Wright, 1999). It was used to collect and refine the judgments of the panel of experts using a series of data collection and analysis techniques combined with feedback; the process stopped when the research questions were answered (Skulmoski *et al.*, 2007). Initially, the researcher identified and prioritised the acts under investigation and went back and forth to confirm each expert participant's suggested recommendations and findings in face-to-face remote meetings. The number of times was situational, depending on the amount of information gathered, the level of understanding and the relevance & reliability of the data collected. Therefore, this was determined in the final stage of the data collection.

The Delphi technique, developed in California in the 1950s by Rand Corporation, is a research method that aims to shape group opinions and discussions through questioning and judgment. It eliminates interpersonal interactions as a determining factor in decision-making, allowing for consensus on specific issues and policy decisions that represent the aspirations and perspectives of a given group (Goodman, 1987). It is considered a more practical approach than conventional group meetings (Rowe and Wright, 2001). Furthermore, it enhances group discussions by facilitating diverse perspectives and understandings while minimising negative aspects like overbearing, thereby improving the effectiveness of these discussions. (Grime and Wright, 2016). A group research method involves anonymity, repetition, controlled feedback, and statistically aggregated responses (Rowe and Wright, 2001).

In its most basic form, it *asks a group to answer a series of questions on a single issue anonymously*. A facilitator then combines the replies into a summary of the group response, sometimes with explanations for the responses included (Rowe and Wright, 2001). According to (Belton *et al.*, 2019), *individuals are then given the option of submitting a modified response or resubmitting their original response after evaluating the diversity of replies received*. This loop and controlled feedback process continue over several "rounds" until a *consistent pattern of replies develops*, such as a clear **consensus or broad agreement** within the group or a strong disagreement. (Belton *et al.*, 2019) then go further and present a

thorough six-step approach to support the execution of a successful Delphi technique in any situation. The table below summarises their proposal:

The Six Steps of a Successful Delphi Application

Table 4.4 Six Steps to Successful Delphi Application

STEP 1	Setting up the Delphi process (Goal of the exercise & number of Experts)
STEP 2	Developing question items and response scales (Main Issues
STEP 3	Software delivery choice (Paper/Pen, Email or Web)
STEP 4	Providing feedback panellist
STEP 5	Preventing and dealing with panellist dropouts (Communicate)
STEP 6	Analysing and presenting the Delphi Data (Integrate the Data)

Source: (Belton et al., 2019, pages 2-4)

4.12. Data Analysis

After securing the data, it is time to discuss how it was analysed. Qualitative research analysis is defined as an analysis that produces findings, concepts, and hypotheses that are not reached by statistical methods (Glaser, 1992). Qualitative analysis (involves a variety of non-numerical data sources, such as observations, spoken words, written text, and visual data (Glaser, 1992). In this research, the analysis involved data in the form of spoken words and written text. Since researchers need to make sense of the subjective and socially constructed interpretations expressed by individuals who participate in the research concerning the phenomenon being investigated, qualitative research is usually associated with an *interpretivist philosophy* (Saunders et al., 2015). According to social constructionism, partially shared meanings and realities are contingent on people's perceptions and interpretations of events around them.

Therefore, qualitative data are more *dynamic, fluid, and sophisticated* than quantitative data since meanings in qualitative research are derived from social interaction. Hence, to be meaningful, the analysis and interpretation of this data must be sensitive and receptive to these qualities (Saunders et al., 2015). Furthermore, qualitative data is likely characterised by its complexity and depth because of the researcher's ability to investigate a topic as authentically as possible. Thus, a distinction may well be formed between the "*thin*" abstraction or explanation that primarily arises from quantitative data gathering and the

“*thick*” or “*comprehensive*” abstraction or description associated with qualitative data collection (Brekhus *et al.*, 2005). This implies that the quality of qualitative research is determined by the interplay between data collection and data analysis, which enables the exploration and clarification of meanings (Saunders *et al.*, 2015).

A famous quote from Halcom’s Laws of Inquiry made great sense in scientific enquiry and data analysis (Bricki and Green,2007): “It wasn’t curiosity that killed the cat. It was trying to make sense of all the data curiosity generated”. So, the data collected has no value if the researcher fails to make sense of it all, no matter how rich. Analysing the data and “Making sense” is our upcoming challenge and will be discussed in the next chapter; it is the heart and essence of successful research methods and probably the greatest challenge of all (Patton, 2002).

4.13. Conclusion

Drawing on the philosophical assumptions, it is worth mentioning the qualitative nature of this research, which covers a relatively complicated business problem in Sudan (employment regulations) in which the writer assumes the role of an interpretivist researcher. A handpicked team of professionals worked with the researcher to pursue the project, making it a collaborative, participatory, and interdependent effort based on an interpretivism epistemological paradigm. The study is deeply rooted in the ontological assumptions that govern the researcher’s perspectives and perceptions of employment legislation and best practice Equality Acts. As a result, the ontology is nominally “subjective,” intending to add value to the field of employment regulations & their application in Sudanese enterprises and contribute broadly to Sudan. As a result, the Axiology is “biased” since this is not a value-free study, and the researcher is fully engaged in the research, with values and beliefs embedded and interdependent.

It follows an “inductive approach,” first gathering observations about the Sudanese Labour Law of 1997 in its current state to add value by contributing to developing a new theory, i.e. advocating for a better approach to bridge this gap. The strategy employed is a “Qualitative Strategy,” as it is a social issue involving critical opinions from a pool of carefully selected Human Resource & Labour Law experts (a cautious “non-random” judgmental sampling process) who have the necessary expertise and have contributed significantly to this research. This was not done by chance but rather through a deliberate judgmental sampling process, and the researcher’s values are openly visible and explicitly communicated throughout.

Through in-depth semi-structured interviews, original targeted primary data is collected, presented, and summarised as verbal expressions.

Finally, a combined purpose study and a comparative research design are used to collect exploratory, descriptive, explanatory, and evaluative data. Furthermore, the interviews are combined with the “Delphi Technique,” a structured, interactive communication technique to strengthen the data and confirm the findings.

CHAPTER FIVE: METHODOLOGY PPART II

(Analysing the Data Thematically)

5.1. Introduction

Qualitative data analysis is perhaps the most challenging aspect or course of action. Nonetheless, it's a great experience to witness and an enjoyable one, too. Patterns will indeed develop, and the researcher can draw them out. Among all the different arguments and discussions, a few distinct ones are meaningful and have memorable conclusions. There are numerous approaches to analysing qualitative data. One of the particular approaches the researcher had the option of opting for at the beginning of the research is a process called *Content Analysis*, “a way of systematically converting text to numerical variables to qualitative data analysis” (Collis and Hussey 2003 p.250).

Despite its suitability, however, the researcher found that content analysis has a main drawback, which is that the frequency counts may include words out of context or words with multiple meanings-with inconsideration to their meaning (Wilson, 2014); this is particularly tricky with the Sudanese labour Laws material, which can be very challenging with other international material which could lead to unintentional loss of meanings leading to drastic results. Another comprehensive limitation argued by Wilson is the tremendous time consumption challenge that qualitative researchers face when using qualitative data analysis. Their ability to consume a significant amount of time requires patience and persistence from the researcher. Both former characteristics are abundant in the researcher's traits; however, the most crucial facet, “time”, is unfortunately scarce, so the researcher has entirely refrained from the process.

Hence, the researcher can use a thematic, descriptive approach or go further in-depth with the investigation. Therefore, for this research, the researcher decided that a “**Thematic Analysis**” is sufficient as it is for most applied undertakings (Bricki and Green, 2007) and so embarks on it for its popularity, flexibility, and accessibility. Braun and Clarke (2012) define Thematic Analysis as a technique for systematically identifying, organising, and interpreting patterns of meaning (themes) in a data set.

5.2. Thematic Analysis

Procedures for deploying Thematic Analysis as a qualitative technique only started to be released in the 1990s (Aronson, 1994); nevertheless, qualitative researchers have labelled their approach to analysis as “*thematic*” without an apparent reference to a particular approach, with both pre-and post-specific procedural guidelines (Terry, Hayfield, Clarke and Braun, 2017). Considering this complication, Virginia Braun and Victoria Clarke classified Thematic Analysis as: “*a poorly demarcated and rarely acknowledged, yet frequently utilised qualitative analytical framework*” (Braun and Clarke, 2006, p. 77).

It is regarded as a terrible “branded” technique because it doesn’t seem to exist as a “labelled” analysis like other techniques, such as Narrative Analysis and grounded theory. In this regard, it is frequently not stated clearly as the analysis technique. At the same time, Virginia & Victoria believe that much analysis is thematic but represented as something else, such as content analysis (Meehan *et al.*, 2000) or not labelled as any technique. On the other hand, recognition has also expanded for other notable accounts of TA techniques written before Braun and Clarke’s, such as the work of Boyatzis, 1998. However, Terry *et al.*, 2017 argue that there is still considerable misunderstanding and relative confusion when understanding what Thematic Analysis really is and whether it even refers to something in particular!

The primary objective of **thematic analysis is to look for common themes or patterns in the data set** (the interviews). The researcher classifies (codes) the qualitative data using thematic analysis to search for themes or patterns further investigated following the research questions (Saunders *et al.*, 2019). To conduct this analysis, the researcher carefully navigates all the data collected from the interviews to unleash the common issues that reoccur and then identifies the key ideas that incorporate all the points of view and perspectives gathered (Bricki and Green, 2007).

5.2.1. Why Thematic Analysis?

Thematic Analysis offers excellent flexibility in the application, which the researcher is seeking and a primary reason for this selection. The flexibility is relevant and applies to the choices made regarding *theoretical assumptions*, *research questions*, *data gathered*, and *data analysis* (Terry *et al.*, 2017). It enables the investigator to see and make sense of common or shared meanings and perspectives by concentrating on the meaning across the data collection. The goal of Thematic Analysis is not to find unique and distinctive meanings

and experiences located exclusively within a particular data piece; it is a technique of recognising and making sense of what is familiar to how a topic is spoken or written about. Below is a list of unique features that make Thematic Analysis an excellent choice for selection and an opportunity the researcher effectively embraces.

Table 5.1 What Makes Thematic Analysis Unique

What Makes Thematic Analysis Unique
It is Flexible
Simple, easy to comprehend & execute
Accessible to researchers with little or no prior knowledge of qualitative research
Results are usually accessible to the broader public
Effective technique for using participants as collaborators while working within the framework of participatory research
Meaningfully summaries key aspects of a huge collection of data
Provides a “deep description” of the data set
Draws attention to patterns and discrepancies in the data set
Generates unexpected findings
Enables both behavioral and social data analyses
Leads to the creation of qualitative analyses that can assist in the development of legislation and policymaking

Source: (Original Based on the Advantages of Thematic Analysis

(Braun and Clarke, 2006)

On the other hand, (Terry *et al.*, 2017) argue that what is common isn't always relevant or significant. The patterns of meaning that thematic analysis permits the researcher to uncover must be relevant to the subject and research question under investigation, even if the question becomes evident during the analysis, as in some qualitative research, analysis generates the answers to those questions. Data collection can reveal a wealth of patterns; effective analysis aims to find those that address a specific research question (Braun and Clarke, 2012).

5.2.2. The Procedure & Application

In contrast to other approaches, the nature and flexibility of using thematic analysis make it relatively straightforward to apply. Instead of spending a lot of time adopting a more sophisticated approach to qualitative analysis per their stringent guidelines, the researcher focused on ensuring the analysis was thorough and rigorous (Saunders *et al.*, 2019). Practically speaking, and according to (Saunders *et al.*, 2019), Thematic Analysis is not a linear process; this method does not follow a straight line. Instead, it is more likely to happen concurrently and recursively, where the researcher analyses the data as it is gathered, then goes back over previous data and analysis and refines how the researcher coded and categorised subsequently collected data, hence looking for analytical themes.

The main steps according to (Saunders *et al.*, 2019) that take place during the process are four significant steps:

- Becoming Familiar with the Data
- Coding the Data
- Searching for Themes & Recognising Relationships
- Refining Themes & Testing Proposition

Undertaking the Thematic Analysis: The Approach, Process & Procedure:

The author adopted a popular thematic analysis technique, widely known and used by many qualitative researchers, the contemporary technique created by **Virginia Braun and Victoria Clarke in 2006**. Since the publication of their phenomenal work in 2006, which then became a landmark, *Thematic Analysis* has taken a considerable turn, become extremely popular in the research arena and has been welcomed into the qualitative literature as a reliable, recognisable, and credible method of analysis; Thematic analysis thanks to Virginia and Victoria is officially “named & claimed” (Terry *et al.*, 2017)!

5.2.3. Virginia Braun & Victoria Clarke (2006) Six Steps

The data gathered for this research is analysed using the Thematic Analysis technique, guided by and following Braun and Clarke’s (2006) Six-phase Guide to Performing Thematic Analysis, a commonly used version of Thematic Analysis. It is essential to recognise that these guidelines for qualitative analysis, as Braun and Clarke put it, are precisely that! They are not fixed rules; when following these core principles, they should be flexible to suit the

research questions best and accommodate the data (Patton, 1990). In addition, as discussed earlier, analysis is not a straightforward linear process in which one phase is followed by the next. Instead, movement back and forth between stages occurs more frequently in a circular format, a process that evolves through time and should not be hurried at all (Ely *et al.*, 1997).

Figure 5.1 Six-Step Process

Source: (Braun and Clarke, 2006 p. 87)

5.2.3.1. Step One: The Researcher Starts by Familiarising with the Data

Right after every interview, the researcher listened to the recorded data repeatedly, sometimes four or five times, to translate and transcribe the data accurately and effectively into written formats. This process was long and time-consuming, but in doing so herself (carefully, deeply, and vigilantly), the researcher spent generous time engaging with the data, taking notes, reading, and rereading the content, hence familiarising herself with every little piece of detail. The researcher made a great effort, to the best of her knowledge, to conduct the

transcription with a very high level of accuracy, integrity, and detail. This effort is to preserve the truthfulness and originality of the meetings conducted and secure the validity and reliability of the data collected.

Even though it may seem tedious, time-consuming, and occasionally dull, transcription can be a great way to begin getting acquainted with the data (Riessman, 1993). Moreover, some scholars even claim that it should be recognised as a critical process of data analysis within interpretive research methodologies (Bird, 2005) and acknowledged as an interpretative act, where meanings are established, as opposed to just a robotic act of placing spoken sounds on paper (Lapadat and Lindsay, 1999). The researcher indeed finds the process time-consuming but not tedious; it is an eye-opener and surprisingly very enjoyable!

Overall, the data gathered is rich and extensive; in just about any case, the researcher needed to familiarise herself with the depth and breadth of the information by fully immersing herself in it, which she vigorously did. Immersion typically entails “repeated reading” of the information and “active reading “of the material, looking for patterns and meanings (Braun and Clarke, 2006).

5.2.3.2. Step Two: Generating the Initial Codes

Braun and Clarke (2012) compare “**Codes**” to “building bricks”, arguing that codes are the building blocks constructing the analysis. When examining a house made of bricks with a tile roof, the walls and roof serve as the themes, and the individual bricks and tiles serve as the codes. Coding is, therefore, a systematic technique for categorising data with similar meanings. They label each data unit within the data item, and the text in the transcripts is marked with a code that symbolises the meaning of that particular extract. This process aims to make each piece of data of interest to the researcher available for further analysis (Saunders *et al.*, 2019).

Codes define and label a data characteristic likely to be relevant to the research questions. *Latent* or *semantic* dimensions of meaning can be coded according to (Braun and Clarke, 2012); these codes provide an interpretation of the data’s substance that goes beyond the connotations of the participants. These latent interpretive codes revealed meanings deeply hidden behind the semantic surface of the content. The process of **coding** only started after the thorough and intensive reading process. The researcher read the complete data set word by word more than once, and this assisted in the generation of exciting ideas and contributed to the identification of the well-anticipated patterns (Braun and Clarke, 2006)

The data generated, or transcripts contained a considerable amount of valuable data that is extensive and complex. It contained the essence of diversified experiences, thoughts, ideas, beliefs and values of well-informed, impactful experts and professionals. Without coding this data, the researcher finds it difficult to grasp and comprehend its meanings and insights. Accordingly, coding was a critical and vital step for managing the data to organise and retrieve it under the associated/relevant codes. This step required the researcher to break down the original data items/transcripts and regroup the bits and pieces of data with similar meanings together (*meaningful groups*) so they can be examined in conjunction with other groups of identical pieces of information in the data set (Saunders *et al.*, 2019).

DATA		
A Code	A Word	A Short Phrase
A Coded Extract	A Unit of Data	
A Unit of Data <i>(determined by its meaning)</i>	A Number of Words A Sentence (s)	A Line of a Transcript A Paragraph
<i>Some Units of data Overlapped & Coded using more than one Code!</i>		

Source: (Saunders *et al.*, 2019)

How much to code and from where?

- How much depends on the research approach and research questions. Using a **deductive approach** means the researcher starts with a framework of codes generated from a previous conceptual or theoretical work and applies these previous codes. On the other hand, in this analysis, the researcher used an *inductive approach*, where unquestionably everything is coded. The researcher sought to investigate and explore all possible meanings in the data to guide the direction of the research. This was quite challenging as it required a great deal of time coding every unit of data (line by line) (Saunders *et al.*, 2019).
- Nevertheless, this research was necessary, as it is an exploratory study that seeks to discover hidden meanings. The research questions helped the researcher determine the relevant codes to steer the research in the right direction and avoid any temptations of scope creep! This does not mean the researcher did not use any predetermined codes; the existing literature and particular questions predetermined some of the codes the researcher had previously in mind and wished to code around (Braun and Clarke,

2012). Therefore, the researcher has undergone a hybrid approach in coding where most of the codes are “**data-driven**” and some are “**theory-driven**”.

Figure 5.2 Sources of Codes

Source: (Saunders et al., 2019 p. 655)

Coding can be done manually or with a computer or a software program, for example, Kelle (2004) and Seale (2000). The researcher was in favour of conducting it manually, but due to the massive amount of data, chose to perform it with the aid of a straightforward software tool called **Delve**; it is a simple online qualitative analysis tool that organizes the data and complies with it in one place and gives the researcher the autonomy to work with the data without interference freely, it just organizes it. It facilitates the process, bringing the data visibly closer to the fingertips.

With **Delve**, the data is in hand, and the researcher controls the actions and decisions more. The researcher did not use other well-known software such as NVivo, ATLAS.ti, and MAXQDA because of the required complexity and sophistication. She was more comfortable working with the data, doing all the shuffling, cutting, pasting and processing on her own with very little assistance from **Delve**, as she wanted to make sure not to miss a word in the process. She is familiar with the data, understands the meanings, and does not want third-party interference; a party does not comprehend the data as well as the researcher and is not as acquainted with it as she is.

Furthermore, the researcher is not technically skilled in using advanced computer software programs and is not confident. Sure, the researcher could have trained and developed herself in the programs; unfortunately, she could not afford to spend extra time doing so and was thus much more comfortable and confident with **Delve!**

The Codes:

Everything was coded; the researcher had to review the coded data regularly to ensure it corresponded to the research direction and questions. The researcher focused on all the relevant codes (including new emerging ideas) and compiled the applicable ones, giving each a number and listing them, as shown in the table below. The researcher did not work with all these codes in the next stage (*Searching for Themes*) but decided which ones to eliminate, how, and why in step three.

Table 5.2 Initial Codes

<i>Code No</i>	<i>Code Name</i>	<i>Code No</i>	<i>Code Name</i>	<i>Code No</i>	<i>Code Name</i>
001	21 Century Challenges	032	Domestic Workers	063	Ministry of Work - Relationship
002	Abided By	033	Effort to Develop/update the 97 Act	064	Modern Day Slavery
003	Access	034	Employee Protection	065	Notes & Notes SG
004	Access Issues	035	Employment Contracts/Agreements	066	Organisations (private sector) & the Application
005	Accessibility	036	Empowerment	067	Over-time
006	Accountability	037	Equality Discrimination & Social Injustice	068	Pensions
007	After Service Benefit	038	Ethics & Integrity	069	Performance Management
008	Application	039	Exploitation	070	Political Constrains
009	Areas that Need Urgent Attention	040	Fair Pay	071	Privacy & Confidentiality
010	Authority	041	Flexible Work	072	Probation Period
011	Available Support	042	Fundamental Principles & Rights at Work	073	Problems/Issues
012	Awareness	043	Gaps & Shortcomings	074	Protecting The Most Vulnerable
013	Best Practice & International Standards	044	Gender Issues	075	Recommendations
014	Beyond the Formal Sector	045	Global Objectives And Priorities	076	Regulations

015	Bulling & Harassment in the Workplace	046	Governance	077	Skills /Calibre
016	Change & The Revolution	047	Government Role/Priorities	078	Social Injustice
017	Clarity (Interpretations)	048	Health and Safety	079	Social Insurance
018	Collective Issues/Trade Unions	049	ILO	080	Social Protection
019	Communication & Dialogue	050	Important Notes from Participants	081	Speciality Committees
020	Consequences	051	Inspection	082	Strategies
021	Consistency & Alignment	052	International Workers	083	Training &Development
022	Core Characteristics of Work-Sudan	053	Investment Climate	084	Tripartite Committee
023	Corruption	054	Islamic Practices	085	Unacceptable forms of Work
024	Cost of Living	055	Key Aspects & Features	086	Unemployment Benefits
025	Coverage	056	Labour Courts	087	Unfair Dismissals
026	Covid19/Pandemic	057	Labour Offices	088	Vulnerable Groups
027	Culture	058	Legal Issues	089	Women
028	Decent Work	059	Lessons Learned	090	Work Life Balance
029	Decent Work Meaning in Sudan	060	Marginalized Groups	091	Work Place Boundaries
030	Development	061	Measures	092	Worker Vs Employer Relation
031	Disciplinary Actions	062	Minimum Wage	093	Working Conditions

Source: (Original)

5.2.3.3. Step Three: Searching for Themes & Relationships

This phase began after all the data had been coded and collated (gathered). The software facilitated collating the data to fit together and apply to each code and, hence, the theme. After the researcher had developed this considerable list of codes identified across the data set, it was time to start the third step. This phase refocuses the study on “**themes**” rather than codes, entails grouping the various codes into suitable themes and assembling all relevant coded data extracts inside these identified themes (Braun and Clarke, 2012). The researcher analysed the codes, considering how the different codes might connect to generate a broader underlying topic.

According to (Saunders *et al.*, 2019), “A Theme” is a broad category that includes multiple connected codes representing a significant concept to the research questions. A theme can also be a **single code** that denotes an idea *raised to the level of a theme* because it acquires universal significance to the research questions. Finding themes is a significant step in compressing the original data, involving first coding and then assembling the coded data into logical categories or themes.

The *number of codes* the researcher should deal with at this point varies greatly. Some researchers suggest using up to 30 codes. Another advice is to generate as many codes as needed to interpret every relevant meaning in the data. This could mean creating several hundred codes, if not more! According to Saunders *et al.* (2019), they argue against the idea of imposing a fixed number of codes on data. Therefore, the number of codes generated should be correlated to the meanings the researcher is interested in, genuinely wants to investigate in the data set, are relevant to the research approach and the research question, and are enormously essential in adding value to the overall research inquiry.

The researcher decided to take (Saunders *et al.*, 2019) recommendation and did not force the data into a predetermined mould of a definite number of codes and chose to let the data fall naturally in place as needed to create a meaningful study. In addition, the researcher always considered the research questions, aim, and objectives when analysing the data (Saunders *et al.*, 2019).

Sorting the Codes into Themes

In line with (Braun and Clarke 2012) direction, on a separate “*Sticky Note*,” the researcher sorted the codes into piles of different themes and gave each theme a different colour. The table below illustrates these themes:

Figure 5.3 Sticky Notes

Source: (Original)

Table 5.3 Codes Sorted into Themes

<i>What are the key aspects of the Sudanese Labor Act?</i> <i>Theme One: Key Aspects</i>	<i>What challenges can be identified within the Act in the context of international best practices?</i> <i>Theme Two : Local & International Challenges</i>	<i>What strategies can be in place to ensure the Sudanese Labor Act meets the twenty-first century needs?</i> <i>Theme Three: A Strategic Direction & the Way Forward</i>
1-Legal Issues & Practices	1-Speaking The Same Language	1-Strategic Direction & Way Forward
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Compliance (Abided By) • The Employment Law • Labor Courts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lac of Consistency & Alignment • Lac of Clarity (Interpretations) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recommendations • Strategies and Approaches
2-Key Aspects and Features	2-Major Issues and Challenges	2-Effort Needed for Development
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organizations (private sector) & the Application <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Application ◦ Coverage • Features • International Workers • Investment Climate • Privacy & Confidentiality • Unfair Dismissals • Performance Management • Disciplinary Actions • Probation Period • Training & Development • Health and Safety 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 21 Century Challenges <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Change & The Revolution • Corruption <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Exploitation ◦ Modern Day Slavery • The Employment Contracts/Agreements • Skills /Caliber 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop/Update the 97 Act • Development
	3-The Sudanese Labor Offices	3-Sudan & Best Practice/International Standards
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Labor Offices Described • Specialty Committees • Inspection • Authority & Empowerment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Best Practice & International Standards • ILO • Global Objectives And Priorities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Fundamental Principles & Rights at Work ◦ Unacceptable Forms of Work ◦ Core Characteristics of Work-Sudan ◦ Working Conditions in Sudan • Decent Work <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Decent Work Meaning in Sudan 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Flexible Work • Work Life Balance • Covid19/The Pandemic
	4-Compensation	

<p>4-Access and Communication</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engagement • Access Issues <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Accessibility ◦ Access • Worker Vs Employer Relation • Awareness • Communication & Dialogue 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Minimum Wage • Over-time • Fair Pay • Cost Of Living • Social Insurance <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ After Service Benefit ◦ Pensions 	
<p>5-Culture & Gender Issues</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gender Issues <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Women • Culture • Ethics & Integrity • Islamic Practices 	<p>5-Limitations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gaps & Shortcomings • Problems/Issues • Lessons Learned <p>6-Social Protections/Injustice</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social Protection Issues & Problems • Beyond the Formal Sector <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Unemployment Benefits • Available Support <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Marginalized Groups ◦ Domestic Workers ◦ Vulnerable Groups ◦ Protecting The Most Vulnerable ◦ Employee Protection • Work Place Boundaries <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Bulling & Harassment in the Workplace • Equality Discrimination & Social Injustice <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Social Injustice ◦ Areas that Need Urgent Attention 	
<p>6-Government & Governance</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Government Role/Priorities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Political Constrains ◦ Ministry of Work - Relationship • Governance <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Regulations ◦ Measures ◦ Accountability ◦ Consequences • The Tripartite Committee • Collective Issues/Trade Unions 		

Source: (Original)

5.2.3.4. Step Four: Reviewing the Themes

This step started after establishing a group of potential themes, and it entails the *refinement* of those named themes. It also became clear to the researcher at this phase that some nominated themes aren't themes as there isn't enough data to support them; furthermore, some themes fused into one another to form a separate theme, while others needed to be broken down into further distinct themes. In this situation, it was essential to consider Patton's (1990) dual criterion assessing categories of internal homogeneity and exterior heterogeneity, meaning that no data should belong to more than one group or fall between two categories. Data within themes can genuinely overlap; however, there should be clear

and easy distinctions between them (Braun and Clarke, 2012). This step consists of two stages of *reviewing and refining* the themes: the flow chart below summaries these stages:

Figure 5.4 Thematic Refinement Process

Source: (Original Framework: Inspired by Virginia Braun & Victoria Clarke, 2006)

According to Braun and Clarke (2012), researchers need to be cautious not to get overly excited about endless re-coding because coding data and creating themes might be an infinite process and may continue indefinitely. So, it is hard to advise and give a definitive suggestion

on when to stop, but if the refinements aren't contributing anything significant, then that is probably the right time to quit! Now, the researcher has a good idea and a solid understanding of the different themes, what they mean, how they fit and relate to one another, and the broader narrative they convey about the data and can progress to the next stage.

5.2.3.5. Step Five: Defining & Naming the Themes

Now that the researcher has a satisfactory thematic map of the data, the fifth stage begins. In this phase, the researcher worked thoroughly to create and develop the topics to provide and analyse the data included inside each of them. The researcher “defined and refined”, and by *define and refine*, Virginia & Victoria mean establishing the “essence” of what each topic is all about in addition to the themes as a whole and determining what part of the data each theme captures. This process required tenacity in the application, and the researcher did not forget the Dos and Don'ts while doing so:

Table 5.4 Defining & Naming Themes- Dos & Don'ts

Dos	Don'ts
Go back to the collated <i>data extracts</i> for each theme	Do not <i>stretch</i> or attempt to get a theme to do too much
Organize the data into a <i>coherent & logically consistent</i> account with accompanying narrative	Do not have it <i>too diverse</i> and complex
Determine what is <i>interesting</i> about the data and why	Do not <i>just paraphrase</i> the content of the data extracts
Write <i>a full analysis</i> for each individual theme	Do not <i>overlap</i> too much between themes
Identifying the <i>story</i> told by each theme and consider <i>how it fits</i> into the bigger picture	Do not have the story <i>drifted away</i> from the research direction or questions
Think about the <i>themes individually</i> , as well in relation to the <i>other themes</i> and <i>sub-themes</i> (<i>themes-within-a-theme</i>)	Do not overlook the <i>hidden meanings</i> and take the discussion at face value

Source: (Original Idea Based on the Suggestions of Braun & Clarke, 2006)

By the end of this phase, it was extremely crucial to clearly understand the themes and what they aren't. One way to examine this was to see if the researcher could define the scope and substance of each theme in a few sentences. If not, that topic might need further refinement. While the researcher had already given the themes functional titles earlier, this was the time to think seriously about the *final names* in the final analysis. These names were *brief and*

snappy, giving the reader an immediate sense of the theme (Braun and Clarke, 2012). Below are the actual names used in the report:

Table 5.5 Final Refined Themes & Subthemes

<i>Theme One: Key Aspects and Features</i>	<i>Theme Two : Major Issues & Challenges</i>	<i>Theme Three: Strategic Direction & Way Forward (Meeting the Twenty-first Century Needs)</i>
A Historical Perspective	How well is the Act coping?	Fundamental Principles and Rights at Work
Private Sector Organizations: Application & Abidance	Lack of Clarity Consistency and Alignment	International Standards
The Practical Application	“What doesn’t get measured doesn’t get managed”	Protecting workers from Unacceptable Forms of Work
Organizational Compliance: Abidance and Inspection	Remuneration	A Decent Work Strategy
Government & Governance	Minimum Wage	Understanding & Measuring Decent Work
The Role of the State	Salary Breakdown, Overtime & Other Benefits	What effort is needed to establish decent work in Sudan?
A Ministry in Limbo	Social Protection (Safety Nets)	A Communication Strategy
The Tripartite Committee	National Pension and Social Insurance Fund	Occupational Safety and Health
Incompetence and Corruption	Beyond the Formal Sector	
Underdeveloped Reform	Protecting the Most Vulnerable	
The Labour Offices	Workplace Boundaries	
Role, Ability and Credibility	Equality Diversity and Inclusion	
Lack of Consistency and Flexibility	The Employment Contract	

Source (Original)

5.2.3.6. Step Six: Producing the Report

Although this was the last step of the analysis involving the creation of the report that went into the analysis chapter, it was not a standalone phase that the researcher started and ended in the very end. It required much effort and progressive refinement, which took place throughout the analysis process and even before that. The table below summarises what Braun and Clarke (2006) have identified as critical actions for producing a quality report.

Unlike in quantitative research, which requires first complete data analysis and then the write-up begins, here writing and analysis went hand in hand, from the informal initial note-taking and memo-writing stage to the more formal processes of analysis and report writing,

just as described by Braun and Clarke (2012); writing and analysis are indeed inextricably intertwined where themes relate logically and meaningfully in every way and where applicable build on previous themes hence telling a coherent, eloquent story about the data.

Table 5.6 Critical Actions for Producing a Quality Report

The Final Report	
The Write-up	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tells the Compelling Complex Story of the Data • Convincing to the reader in terms of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Value ○ Validity • Provides Sufficient Evidence of the Themes within the data • Sufficient Data Extracts to indicate the Theme's Existence • Needs to Go Beyond just providing data
The Analysis <i>(write-up including data extracts)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Concise • Coherent • Logical • Non-repetitive • Interesting
The Extracts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pick Vivid extracts/examples <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ The point's Essence ○ Avoid Complexity ○ Avoid Passive Phrasing • Easily Identifiable example of the issue • Extracts must be Integrated within the analytic narrative • Thoroughly Illustrates the Story(data)
The Analytical Narrative	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Must go Beyond the Data Description (fact summary) to <i>making an argument</i> answering the research questions

Source: (Original Summary based on Braun & Clarke (2006) producing the Report)

5.2.4. Limitations of Thematic Analysis

Thematic Analysis is not flawless, like all other qualitative research methods. As discussed earlier, it is widely used but is poorly “demarcated & claimed” (Braun and Clarke, 2006). Research scholars like Terry *et al.* (2017) criticised thematic analysis for not being a particularly distinct method but rather generally involving searching for patterns, similar to many other research approaches. Most of the other drawbacks are caused by the poor execution of analysis or inadequate research questions rather than a pure setback or complication with the approach itself; this is how Braun and Clarke (2006) defend the

approach. They further highlight that its known flexibility is both a blessing and a curse. The researcher well agrees with that and experienced the dilemma in her execution.

Because the method is flexible, it permits a wide variety of analytical alternatives, which implies the existence of a vast range of potential ideas /issues stated about the data. While this flexibility is considered a huge advantage, it may well be a drawback because it makes developing precise rules for an elevated analysis challenging, and it might paralyse the researcher when deciding which elements of the data to focus on.

Another essential point to remember is that if the thematic analysis is not applied within a well-established theoretical framework that grounds the views expressed by the analysis, it will have limited interpretive value beyond plain description. Finally, additional drawbacks emerge when a thematic analysis is compared to other qualitative analytical methods. Unlike narrative or other biographical approaches, the researcher cannot maintain a sense of coherence and discrepancy across any single account, and these discrepancies and commonalities among the various narratives may be informative. The plain thematic analysis does not allow the researcher to make statements about linguistic use or the perfectly alright functionality of the conversation (Braun and Clarke 2006).

5.3. Access Issues & Ethical Considerations

With all the participants in this study, the researcher employed the published and attached “Consent Form” provided in the appendix and proudly adhered to the Ethical Values and Principles of the University of UWS. The idea of autonomy recognises everyone has the freedom to choose their path. It is at the heart of the requirement for free and informed consent.

The researcher’s information to the participants was sufficiently informative, relevant, and correct. Consent was freely provided and was revocable. There was no excessive influence or compulsion, such as disproportionate rewards or disincentives for refusing to consent. Ensuring potential participants knew the research’s purpose and methods was critical. All the participants were given adequate time to think about the facts and decide whether to participate.

All ethical considerations took place regarding honesty, transparency, respect, confidentiality, anonymity, safeguarded relationships, and the researcher’s credibility, which is never

compromised. All work was strictly guided by the USW's four main ethical principles of research with Human participants (2016):

- Autonomy, Veracity & Informed Consent
- Privacy & Confidentiality
- Justice & Inclusiveness
- Benefits & Harms

5.4. Conclusion

Analysing qualitative data is challenging but enjoyable, with various approaches available. The author uses the popular “Thematic Analysis” technique to analyse and interpret the data meaningfully, with great sensitivity and receptiveness to its dynamic and complex nature, following the contemporary technique developed by Braun and Clarke (2006), referred to as the “Six-phase Guide to Performing Thematic Analysis,” a widely used version of Thematic Analysis, to code and generate the themes. It offered great flexibility in application, allowing the researcher to observe, clarify, and make sense of the common shared meanings and perspectives across the data collection.

Coding can be done manually or with a computer or software program. The researcher used a simple online qualitative analysis tool called Delve, which allows the researcher to work with the data manually without interference, making it more comfortable to work with the data without third-party interference. The researcher coded and reviewed the data regularly to ensure it aligned with the research direction and questions. Compiled relevant codes and listed them, deciding which ones to eliminate. Then, the focus is on “themes” rather than codes, grouping the various codes into suitable themes and assembling all relevant coded data extracts inside these identified themes.

In conclusion, the researcher coded the data, analysed the codes, and refined the themes to ensure they were relevant and meaningful to the research. The production of the report was the last step in the analysis process, and it required a lot of effort and progressive refinement throughout the analysis process. Writing and analysing are inextricably intertwined, as themes logically and meaningfully relate, building on previous themes to tell a coherent and eloquent story about the data. By following the Six-Step Process, the researcher gained a deeper understanding of the data and developed more effective strategies for analysing the findings. The researcher finds thematic analysis a reliable and credible method of analysis

that was effectively applied to answer the research questions. Limitations of thematic analysis include its lack of distinctness, poor execution of analysis, inadequate research questions, and limited interpretive value beyond plain description. The flexibility of the method allows for a wide variety of analytical alternatives, but it may also make developing precise rules challenging.

The writer's enthusiasm and involvement in the subject may have influenced its critical analysis and, thus, the research findings. As an "interpretivist," the researcher's values and beliefs shape the entire research process, including data collection, data analysis, and the final presentation of the findings and recommendations. However, throughout this process, the researcher makes every genuine effort to preserve the study's objectivity and ensure the development of integral, candid, and credible results.

Finally, ethical considerations were taken regarding honesty, transparency, respect, confidentiality, anonymity, safeguarded relationships, and the researcher's credibility. The work adhered strictly to the University of UWS's four main ethical research principles with human participants (2016): autonomy, veracity & informed consent, privacy & confidentiality, justice & inclusiveness, and benefits & harms.

CHAPTER SIX: ANALYSIS & DISCUSSION THEME I

(Key Aspects & Features)

6.1. Introduction

This chapter and the following two chapters will present a detailed analysis and a thorough discussion of the findings as primary data collected and collated from the interviews conducted in meetings between the researcher and the high-profile participants selected for this study. The *Primary Data* generated for this research is original and unique, meticulously gathered for this study. By employing the qualitative research method of Thematic Analysis discussed in Chapter Five, this study addresses the research aims, questions, and objectives below.

The Research Direction

Research Aim	Research Questions	Research Objectives
<i>The aim of this research is to investigate the current Sudanese Labor Act of 1997 to assess its fitness for purpose.</i>	<i>What are the key aspects of the Sudanese Labor Act?</i>	<i>To identify the key aspects of the Sudanese Labor Act.</i>
	<i>What challenges can be identified within the Act in the context of international best practices?</i>	<i>To assess the critical challenges the Sudanese Labor Act faces in light of international best practices</i>
	<i>What strategies can be in place to ensure the Sudanese Labor Act meets the twenty-first century needs?</i>	<i>To identify the strategies and techniques for updating the Labor Act in order to suit Sudan's current HR needs.</i>

Source: (Original)

Drawing back on the philosophical assumptions, it is worth reminding the reader of the qualitative nature of this research as social science covers a business issue that is relatively complicated and where the writer adopts the role of an “interpretivist researcher”. Interpretivism, according to (Wilson, 2014), is “an epistemology that supports the view that the researcher must enter the social world of what is being examined” (Wilson, 2014, p.10).

Research around the Sudanese Labour Act of 1997 was scarce; hence, the researcher extracted primary data from nine intensive interview sessions, coded the data and extracted *three significant themes and thirty-four subthemes*, developing a solid argument and a robust

interactive discussion between the participants and the researcher. In this chapter, the researcher focuses on the first theme, “Key Aspects and Features”, which further binds the following thirteen subthemes (highlighted column). Starting with a historical overview and then focusing on the application in the private sector, the government institutions, and the state’s role, i.e., the ministry and the labour offices.

Table 6.1 Final Refined Themes & Subthemes I

<i>Theme One: Key Aspects and Features</i>	<i>Theme Two : Major Issues & Challenges</i>	<i>Theme Three: Strategic Direction & Way Forward (Meeting the Twenty-first Century Needs)</i>
A Historical Perspective	How well is the Act coping?	Fundamental Principles and Rights at Work
Private Sector Organizations: Application & Abidance	Lack of Clarity Consistency and Alignment	International Standards
The Practical Application	“What doesn’t get measured doesn’t get managed”	Protecting workers from Unacceptable Forms of Work
Organizational Compliance: Abidance and Inspection	Remuneration	A Decent Work Strategy
Government & Governance	Minimum Wage	Understanding & Measuring Decent Work
The Role of the State	Salary Breakdown, Overtime & Other Benefits	What effort is needed to establish decent work in Sudan?
A Ministry in Limbo	Social Protection (Safety Nets)	A Communication Strategy
The Tripartite Committee	National Pension and Social Insurance Fund	Occupational Safety and Health
Incompetence and Corruption	Beyond the Formal Sector	
Underdeveloped Reform	Protecting the Most Vulnerable	
The Labour Offices	Workplace Boundaries	
Role, Ability and Credibility	Equality Diversity and Inclusion	
Lack of Consistency and Flexibility	The Employment Contract	

Source: (Original)

6.2. A Historical Perspective

Like many African and Middle Eastern colonies, Sudan naturally followed the lead of industrialised developed countries that paved the way for employment practices after gaining independence in 1956. They believed in customising and developing laws that suited their people, and indeed they did. The nation’s first official rules were not as old as they were, but

they were published with a fair amount of momentum. The historical development is exemplified in the illustration below:

Figure 6.1 Time Series of Sudan Labour Laws Progression & Development

Source: (Original)

“You have to understand that 1997 Laws are a continuation for the laws that were initiated in 1948; they are almost the same thing, with just very little changes here and there, nothing major. Changes in the number of days, wages, and so on; but no changes in the heart. It was targeting the old labors, manual workers & industry workers; has nothing to do with modern employment (does not serve doctors, engineers, teachers, and bankers....they have no place in the law...).The law applies to them but the laws are irrelevant to them” (Participant Six-MAK)

“In my opinion ... it is very clear that it has been written to serve an industrialized sector, the old cotton factories, Aljazeera Agricultural project and other manufacturing and assembly lines. I believe it does not cater for the diverse sectors that we currently have in Sudan. Let’s take for example the laws governing shifts in Sudan they are different for Women & Men (putting in mind the intention to protect women workers from night shifts ...etc); but how can these laws be applied to other sectors that demand women working night shifts by profession and other sectors that cannot afford to do that such as telecommunication and other wide service sectors.... the law is very outdated!”(Participant One-EOS)

The data clearly show that the Sudanese Labour Act of 1997, which is currently in effect in the Sudanese public sector, is an actual continuation of the old laws, those developed in the Sixties and Seventies and beyond, with no real substantial change and endurance to the challenges they bring. The Sudanese public sector developed these laws to serve the economy during the early 1960s, when they were primarily based on the agricultural industry and Agri-processing factories. During this time, policymakers worked to diversify the economy by developing new lines of production in the industry and introducing new cash crops besides cotton as the primary source of foreign exchange earnings in Sudan. Afterwards, newer investments, particularly in textile, spinning, weaving, and tanneries, as well as fertilisers, sugar, and food processing, occurred in the 1980s (Dagdeviren and Mahran, 2004).

Participants understood that the policies developed to regulate labour activities back then spoke well to the old industries, and the sound of the 1997 Act still hints at a substantial sum of terminologies applicable to the assembly lines and even the earlier arrangements of crop export. The same act used to serve employment in today's contemporary Sudanese corporations, including telecommunications, consumer, financial services and even the oil & gas industries, with very little adaptation.

“... it addresses industries that are no longer functioning and talks about obsolete things... all the amendments that were made the least that I can say were just appearances and touchups and nothing more and nothing core! Reorganizing the numbers, removal or change of wording (some words were removed because the meaning was different or not clear). But genuine amendments as such for the laws to cope with or match the needs of the era never happened! When it was updated in 1997, I believe it was done with very little effort, the people in charge of the so-called amendments 25 years ago made no studies, no effort to manage or cope with the needs back then in 1997”...All that happened was a change in naming, numbers, built points, scheduling, change in names of committees, reordering; but a core change or amendment to the essence of the regulations or new updates needed did not take place even back then in 1997” (Participant Five- SEI)

The participants confirm that little has been done to make the much-needed difference and change, even in the 1990s, let alone the twenty-first century. The participants who were familiar with the previous acts noticed this and believed the changes to the 1997 Act were ineffective and insignificant. They all agreed that updates mainly involved minor changes in the wording, numbers, figures, general structure, and organisation rather than significant changes (much needed for the era). However, the initial laws drafted then deserve recognition for being pioneers in the Arab and Gulf countries. Sudanese experts also played a significant role in the creation and advancement of their laws.

“Generally speaking, initially, there was a very strong law for collective bargaining and Sudan was very advanced in this area one day there were very strong labor unions in Sudan. You can't imagine the strength of the Railway Union and how powerful they were (they were a standalone empowered state and legislator). But now, not having the right laws in place and the political instabilities and interferences weakened the area very much and you can easily say that they are nonexistent. This means Sudan was progressing in the 1960s far beyond what it takes place today! Once again Sudan was way advanced in the creation of laws to the extent it was exceeding the Arab World, especially the Gulf Nations and we contributed massively in drafting their laws back then”(Participant Five- SEI)

However, as an old Arabic proverb goes, “Achieving glory is difficult, but maintaining it is even more difficult.” The extent to which these rules were followed and implemented was also up to their discretion, perceptions, and cultural practices. Labour legislation in many

MENA countries is shaped by specific features of the post-independence social contract. Each of these MENA countries has its history of labour law development, with varying labour market conditions and contrasting legal and social security systems; these laws are outdated, with some dating back to the 1960s, for example, in Kuwait and Lebanon (Angel-Urdinola and Kuddo 2010). Sudan shares many of the same issues and problems as these nations and is even more burdened.

6.3. Private Sector Organisations: Application & Abidance

The Practical Application:

“For example, in Sudan, there are around 1000 Private Recruitment agencies (just over 1000), and 241 are registered under the Sudanese General Intelligence Agency (all of these companies 241 are exempt by a presidential decree from the application of the Act of 1997. I witnessed a case where they terminated all their staff with no legal rights and when the workers came to take legal action, they discovered that they had no legal rights as the company employing them is exempt from the implementation of the law by a letter from the president! This is all happening today in Sudan so many companies; so many companies are invited and have permission to do what they like!!!...foreign investors by law can be exempted ..., take for example the African University they are exempt by a presidential decision; because you can do that, the Sudanese laws support these exemptions”

(Participant Six- MAK)

The Labour Act of 1997, which governs employment in Sudanese private organisations, took effect in 1997, replacing the Manpower Act of 1974 and repealing the following Acts:

The 1974 Manpower Act
The Labour Relations Act of 1976
The Industrial Safety Act of 1976.
Individual Labour Relations Act of 1981

It specifies employment organisation (including provisions for women and minors), service contracts and wages, working hours and leave, termination of employment, after-service benefits, and various other provisions. It also specifies who is not subject to the act, such as domestic servants, agricultural workers not employed in organisations that process agricultural products, and casual workers (World Bank Report, 2021). From the data, it is necessary to understand how it applies to the different Sudanese organisations, how it serves them, and to what extent it is abided by.

“The Practical application over the past 25 years has proved that the 97 Act is currently not coping with the needs. I can see that from my personal experience with all the NGOs I am working with. The law is simply not coping with the needs and expectations of these organizations. Especially when it comes to the employment relationship and the type of contracts needed. The types of contracts they usually require are based on the nature of activities they run and normally use across the world-are not supported by the Act. And hence the struggle occurs. This has even affected their budgets and their ability to provide finance to make the necessary compensations that they owe the workers legally in courts (due to their lack of understanding and the gaps in the Act). Regarding other big companies and organizations in the private sector, they are also dreadfully complaining of its incompatibility with their needs (not coping) and the huge injustice in the Act especially in the relationship between the employee and employer relationship as if it was a Catholic Marriage that is not possible to break unless with very complex arrangements” (Participant Eight-HEH)

The data reveals the enormous challenges of the application in the private sector and the struggles the participants have encountered in their long years of service in different Sudanese organisational settings. Laws are not meeting the expectations of small, medium and large corporations nationwide; they are all struggling with the application. Participant Eight spoke about the employment relationship itself, how the contractual relationship is not fit for purpose, and how it is not wide enough to cater to the diverse needs of the different businesses and multinational organisations operating in Sudan.

These organisations have to make tough decisions to work around this shortcoming (this is a significant area that emerged in the study, which the researcher gives considerable room for discussion later in the chapter). Furthermore, the issue of clarity is also a massive challenge in the application, which has also been discussed thoroughly.

“I can say that all the big companies and organizations are committed and abiding by the legislation, despite the fact that it is crippling and handcuffing in so many ways...Big companies were brand conscientious...On the other hand, small companies in the private sector have so many ways for fraud and room for manipulating the laws; and honestly speaking I do not blame them for that...The labor act of 1997 does not support the economical needs of small businesses, employers and entrepreneurs under the challenges of the economical situation in Sudan. I saw many small companies crumble with former employee entitlements and payments, some of which was miss managed to start due to their lack of understanding and experience with the legislation and others were genuine as the laws do not differentiate between small start-ups or well-established businesses and have no support whatsoever for small businesses, in terms of concessions or financial support”

(Participant Five- SEI)

Small businesses are suffering the most; according to the data, the 1997 rules apply across the board with limited or correctly no consideration to the size of the business; this cripples small

businesses and start-ups and even scares entrepreneurs away from ventures, as the burden of their failures can be massive and way beyond their capacity and capital investments. They tend to work around the laws to find, sometimes even illegally, ways to protect their small margins and safeguard their businesses from collapsing because they know when they fall, no one is there to pick them up. Big companies have no choice; they cannot afford to go to court and ruin their reputation; they protect their brand names because they can afford to do so.

On the other hand, government-led private businesses, yes, government “Private Businesses” and any other foreign investor the government chooses can do what they like; they can indulge themselves with concessions and permissions to not abide by the law as the law itself says it loud and clear in Article (3) Exceptions No. j: “Any class of persons, the Ministry Council may declare by an order that they are exempted totally or partially from the provisions of this Act” (Sudanese Labour Act 1997 p.3). The examples below, explained by “Participant Six”, exhibit the situation:

6.4. Organisational Compliance: (Abidance and Inspection)

“In my experience to a degree, we followed it and ensured that we complied with it even though it was old and outdated” (Participant Nine-RFU)

“Of course, I was obliged to abide by the regulations of all three offices” (Participant Three-MOS)

“Finally, I can say for myself and the majority of companies in Sudan, the law is abided by as no one wants to go to court and face all the hassle and waste of time” (Participant Five- SEI)

Once again, the response of almost all participants indicates that public sector organisations do abide by the labour law of 1997 and as discussed earlier, big companies are the ones with the most adherence and the argument for that is being keen to preserve their reputation and avoid legal disputes and hassles, something smaller organisations might have the stomach for. Another significant point is that the laws provide the minimum baseline as they are written.

Of course, organisations can exceed that should they opt to deliver better quality regulations for their human resources above the basic threshold. The issue of knowledge and skills constantly arises throughout the data and underpins the effective implementation of the laws. Unfortunately, all respondents have agreed that there is a massive challenge in the capability of the people implementing the regulations and those responsible for governing the implementation. The discussions below clearly highlight this point, and the researcher will designate a separate section to discuss the matter further in the chapter.

“I can’t say that the 1997 Act is fully abided by because the legislation provides the minimum requirements in the working relationship between the employer and employee, this minimum is a bare minimum that is not sufficient for a decent life hence, taking, for example, the minimum wage; it is a disgrace and is far way far from being realistic by all measures, so in this context, it is not practical for any successful business to follow this absurd measure and guarantee sustainability, it just doesn’t make sense. Even these measures as I said before are meant to be inspected regularly by the labour office inspectors (which integral part of the legislative procedures) but this process itself is not activated for economical reasons” (Participant Two-MZK)

However, according to the data and the evidence provided by most participants, not all the laws are activated as they should be, and some are not enforced as written and as the authorities intended. A recurring theme in the data from participants who claim that a significant aspect of the Act of 1997 and a critical procedure that is supposed to be taking place is ineffective. This is the **“Inspection”** process outlined in Article (69) of the 1997 Act as follows:

“For the achievement of the purposes of this Act, the competent labour office or any person authorized by the competent authority may enter during working hours into any place whenever he has the reason to believe that there is work in that place, in which one worker or more are employed and he may ask the employer or any responsible person on his behalf to give any information for the implementation of the provisions of this Act. The employer or the responsible person or the worker shall give such information whenever possible. The competent authority may call the employer or any person acting on his/her behalf or the worker at the labour office to settle any matter for the implementation of the provision of this Act”

(Article 69- Sudanese Labour Act 1997)

The inspection function may have taken effect at the beginning of the implementation of the Act or in some specific instances where need be; however, according to the responses below, it is evident that it has not been implemented as it should. Despite the controversial debate, a core critical function does have significance in promoting sustainable compliance (Pires, 2008). Rigid implementation and enforcement are not advisable as they might create resentment; however, loose negligence and infringement are just as dangerous. Stringent enforcement breeds resentment and a refusal to collaborate with regulated firms, failing to produce the necessary incentive for firms’ attitudes to change.

Finally, it fosters a culture of resistance and defensiveness in firms, triggering them to avoid penalties by treating the “symptoms” (violations) rather than the “disease” (production

process) or by employing minimum compliance strategies, i.e., compliance with only the strictly required measures (Bardach and Kagan, 1982).

A body of research on British factory inspectors in the first half of the nineteenth century emphasises pedagogy and persuasion as frequently used to bring businesses into compliance (Field, 1990). It is essential to highlight that organisations are not against inspection; they are open to that but argue that the authorities are not activating the process as they should.

“Since I have started working with this Act for more than 20 years I have realized that there are certain Articles at the end of the Act (Articles related to the penalties) which are completely frozen ... I asked all the lawyers I know and even Judges why these Articles are not activated no one has an answer” (Participant Eight-HEH)

“The Inspection is not activated in the Ministry of Labour; blamed under the umbrella of lack of resources” (Participant Four- LME)

“I worked for 20 years and saw no one inspecting” (Participant Seven –AAB)

“But what can I say? This is probably the government's least important priority right now; if auditing health and education isn't a priority, why would it audit private employers on the implementation of the labour act?! It is a sequence or chain of corruption with a domino effect... You halted the unions, you halted the inspection, you violate people's rights” (Participant Five- SEI)

According to Piore and Schrank (2006) , labour inspection might constitute the vehicle for a much broader approach to economic development, one that brings firms up to the standards imposed by their regulatory obligations rather than bringing regulatory commitments down to the productivity levels characteristic of firms”. However, it seems that “Inspection” is not the only frozen process in the Act. The lack of consequences highlighted by “Participant Eight” (i.e. no penalties) indicates that other significant articles mentioned in the act are not actively practised. Consider the following three areas, as highlighted by Participants Eight and Six:

First, the recruitment process, in which all applicants must be registered in government recruitment offices from the start (which never actually existed in practice), and positions must be advertised through these offices, as well as the selection process; and only if applicants are not available should the recruitment process deviate (See Article 12 on Nomination of Employment).

The second example is employment contracts, how they must be administered through labour offices, and the requirement that a copy of each employment contract be filed in the

corresponding labour office. Finally, there are the employee health checks that never happen as well. None of these activities currently occur in any business setting in Sudan.

“Let’s take Recruitment, for example, according to the legislation the candidates must be selected through the public labour recruitment office, the applicants must be registered there in the labour offices initially and if chosen then the recruiter needs to go back and confirm their appointment if successful. And if the recruiter failed to find suitable candidates an opening must be advertised in the newspapers and finally, biannual reports are issued ...none of these activities takes place in reality they by no means did!...“Public Employment Offices” (not one office was ever established since 1997” (Participant Six- MAK)

“Any contract for more than three months should be written and three copies issued (employee copy, employer copy and a copy for the labour office) and made through the labour office. Which is part of the legislation (Article 28) - unfortunately in the practical sense these procedures are not practically implemented as they should; they are missing from the actual day-to-day implementation...The job itself should not have been advertised unless it was done through the labour offices, all of that does not happen” (Participant Eight-HEH)

Furthermore, both respondents agreed to highlight a particularly peculiar issue: these laws are not essentially that binding, and labour offices have no binding force over businesses in any way. A point that is not fully understood is how they can be legally binding and nonbinding! The issue is related to the authority that labour offices have.

The **Labour Offices** are the primary authorities enforcing the Labour Act. Can you believe that these offices, which are supposed to oversee and govern the implementation, are weak bodies with little impact, no authority to enforce the application, and are not empowered to enforce anything? The chapter further examines this topic as the researcher investigates the labour offices more extensively. Furthermore, “Participant Four” and “Participant Six” emphasised the fact that the “Executive Regulations Document” that was supposed to accompany the Act in 1997 was never actually issued. As a result, there is a great deal of disparity and inconsistency in the application, and all the participants have unanimously agreed that they all struggle with the lack of consistency across the board, so the researcher designated a separate section to discuss this.

“In addition, the role of the labour offices is very passive, they have no authority and most of the time makes no difference. All they do is receive the complaints and collect the fees. And their decisions are not binding and must still be taken to court (they have no binding power). To be honest, they are usually more of an obstacle, and sometimes we do not even consider taking it as a step as we know they can do nothing and I take my problem straight to court and completely overlook them (without them even knowing). While they should have played an active role in investigating the issues, checking the standard and specifications to make sure everything is in line and acting as a real regulatory body in collaboration with the Industrial Safety and the written act” (Participant Eight-HEH)

“...and most important the Regulations are not in place.....The regulation part should be drafted and part of the Act –it was never done when it should have to accompany the 1997Act...The 1997 act is a combination of four different acts (none of which has regulations neither the old four nor the 1997)!” (Participant Six- MAK)

6.4.1. Government & Governance

The Role of the State

According to the UN, the rule of law is a governance principle in which all persons, institutions, and entities, public and private, including the State, are accountable to laws that are publicly endorsed, equally enforced, and independently arbitrated, and are consistent with international human rights norms and standards. It also necessitates measures to ensure adherence to the principles of supremacy of law, equality before the law, accountability to the law, fairness in the application of the law, separation of powers, decision-making participation, legal certainty, avoidance of arbitrariness, and procedural and legal transparency.

This definition reflects the *thick*, meaningful version of the rule of law, which includes justice and human rights respect. And *thin*, strict versions engaged in the existence of the law “*accessible, stable, clear, and universal rules*” and its ***administration***, especially the court’s independence, fairness, and access to justice. The rule of law primarily seeks to prevent injustice, especially abuse of power. Respect for the rule of law also contributes to the creation of a climate favourable to peace, security, equality, development, and the exercise of liberties (Oette and Babiker, 2014)

“In general, ministries take the lead in initiating any updates and creating the vision; in this case, the Ministry of Labour takes the lead and, in collaboration with the Ministry of Justice, creates the necessary legal context; unfortunately, I believe this has been missing in the last 30 years... Before that, and especially at the beginning/middle of the 1990s, there was a very active period in which all of these laws and many more were written, and then everything came to a halt! For example, criminal laws from 1991, personal status laws from 1991, and then 1997 the labour law...now everything is a mess and there is huge disparity...even the states are inconsistent in their application of laws and are developing their own laws! Some have even opted to repeal the 1997 Labour Act (for example in South Darfur)” (Participant Eight-HEH)

“With the current conditions in Sudan, the labour ministry should be the top priority; however, it is at the bottom of the priority list! Economic rights are neglected, but political issues are addressed (for example the Electoral Commission is in place)” (Participant Six-MAK)

The discussion shows that the Ministry of Labour, Sudan’s primary custodian for developing and implementing labour laws, is currently in limbo. The Ministry of Labour in Sudan is one of the government departments responsible for setting and overseeing the implementation of the Labour Law and other equivalent employment standards in addition to human rights and social protection.

It is also responsible for the governance and compliance of these laws and standards. It has been neglected for quite a while, lacks resources and capabilities, and is not prioritised as it should be on the government’s agenda. It has been abandoned for many years, and the recent political constraints have aggravated the situation. In general, Sudan’s entire legal system is in disarray. It may have seen better days; however, the current situation reflects an ageing system that cannot meet the country’s current needs and is on life support.

The institution meant to guide the recovery in this situation, the Ministry of Labour, responsible for setting the vision, leading the change, bringing the parties together, and overseeing the implementation of labour laws, is in despair! A significant threat to the entire nation. This nation has shed much blood in the name of *“freedom, peace and justice”*, a nation dreaming of stability and reform, a dispirit nation struggling to make ends meet, and urgently calling for help.

A Ministry in Limbo

The data reveals the ministry’s current position in the face of current political challenges; it is no secret that the situation has not improved despite all the obstacles, including urgency, criticality, and vital needs. According to the (WHO, 2022), Sudan has been embroiled in conflict for most of its post-independence history, and its deep-seated political issues create

the most severe threat to its prosperity. It is currently led by a transitional government, an agreement reached between the armed forces and civilians following the 2019 revolution.

"During my tenure as Labour Minister, we were all very eager to revisit all of the laws and update them to comply with International Standards and Treaties. It was critical for the transitional government to revisit all laws in order to achieve social justice and secure a life of dignity in Sudan if it was to bring about change and a revolution. The transitional government was committed to social development in order to effect this changeIn terms of the Labour Ministry; the biggest obstacle to change was the ministry itself, which lacked the capacity and aptitude to make the change happen. The second issue was the decision makers, who were represented by the Tripartite Committee (this is a committee responsible for everything related to any kind of change in legislation) and the relationship between all three parties, who never agreed, and the sudden political change which diluted their composition beyond doubt affected the relationship" (Participant Four-LME)

Three and a half years after Sudan's military overthrew the authoritarian leader Omar Bashir in response to prolonged protests, political divisions and the military's current leadership are preventing the country from electing a civilian government to lead the country to political stability. This year has seen an even worsening economic crisis and violent communal clashes, accompanied by peaceful resistance and grassroots campaigns for the restoration of democracy. Sudan's complex crisis resembles that of many fragile states in the "global south": a weak state incapable of meeting its people's basic needs, military dictator rule across its regions and populations facing hunger or famine as COVID and the Russia-Ukraine war intensify economic burdens (United States Institute of Peace, 2022).

"...Furthermore, prior to the pandemic, there was a major setback that slowed things down, and that was the following: part of the transitional government task was to get rid of all previous bodies through the Dismantling Committee, which was in charge of dismantling all previous established unions, and part of that was the Tripartite Committee body. This slowed progress because there was no official body representing these faces other than the assigned steering committees established by the government, and these bodies were not elected bodies (not legitimate delegated committees -selected by the new government and were not elected) and thus could not represent the people and hence were unable to take any actions" (Participant Four-LME)

Indeed, the situation in Sudan is not normal; however, neither is the administration responsible for administering the labour laws, and it is pretty evident that these shortcomings did not just happen overnight. It took years of negligence and incapacity. There is no justification for skill shortage in an institution accountable for building capability and workforce nationwide.

There has been a recent effort to turn things around, but how can life-long damage be repaired in two years? Two years that never came to an end. Why is it that whenever a Sudanese person dreams a beautiful dream before the dream comes to an end, they wake up to a horrid, gloomy, shocking nightmare?

6.4.2. The Tripartite Committee

The Ministry of Labour partners in decision-making with two other bodies: the *Sudanese Businessmen and Employers Federation (SBEF)* & *Sudan Workers Trade Unions Federation (SWTUF)*, forming the “Tripartite Committee”. Each of these bodies is meant to represent independently their respective units autonomously. However, according to the (ILO, 2011) country report, the representation is a political government appointed and controlled! This committee develops reviews, decides all the changes and updates and mandates everything related to employment in Sudan.

The Dismantling Committee (responsible for dismantling all preceding bodies) assigned by the transitional government dismantled all previously established unions, including the Tripartite Committee. As a result, no official legitimate body has represented these faces, so there has been no decision-making. This further halts the state and causes further calamities within the more significant crisis.

Sudan’s democratic transition has been hampered by political insecurity, which has slowed the progression of governance and the reform of the rule of law, and a desperate economic situation, which aggravated public outrage and organisational instability. The government failed to implement critical institutional and legal reforms outlined in the August 2019 constitutional agreement, such as forming a transitional legislative council and committees addressing peace, transitional justice, and corruption (Human Rights Watch, 2021).

6.4.3. Incompetence and Corruption

The data paints a gloomy picture, signifying a political shadow that overwhelms the governmental institutions responsible for developing, implementing, and supervising the application of effective employment standards. Corruption and power struggles all over the place distract from implementing fair, just and reliable endeavours.

“Unfortunately, the majority of Ministers assigned to the Ministry of Labour are politically appointed and lack the technical background or competence required to make a difference and lead the much-needed and deserved change. All they care about is hiring new employees and firing existing ones” (Participant Seven-AAB)

“Government officials are corrupt in many ways; they take advantage of their positions and use their power to levy taxes and impose regulations on simple labourers such as wagon manual workers in open markets and kiosk sellers with no repercussions” (Participant Six-MAK)

One might argue that the financial constraints are the overwhelming burden on the people of Sudan and the real crippling factor. As (Singh and Zammit, 2004) argue, the real reasons that developing countries cannot implement labour standards quickly are not because their governments are corrupt or perverse but mainly because of the structure of their economies and their economic circumstances. The main issue is, therefore, not whether developing countries should have labour standards but rather what these standards should be and what the best way of implementing them is.

“Generally speaking, the SBEF possess enormous influence and are abusing their power manipulating the laws to their advantage-the situation in Sudan, in my opinion; can be simply described as modern-day slavery! Sudanese businessmen are aggressively taking control of the labour market... Why should they decide the minimum wage when it is a completely irrational and wrong practise that does not exist in any country in the world (conflict of interest)?...The tripartite committee relationship is an exploitative relationship that benefits these businessmen, and it is in their best interests that the labour act remains in limbo. There is clear evidence that the tripartite committee is not impartial and is biased towards the business men's association (Employers Union), as well as evidence that the committee's office is located in the facilities of the Employers Union, despite the fact that it should have been a stand-alone independent entity functioning without prejudices. In any case, no one knows who is in charge for the time being and after 2019 (after the revolution) and the committee has been dissolved! As a result, nothing tends to happen!” (Participant Seven-AAB)

The answer is simple: deploying the right people is the best and only way. The skills and calibre assigned to a specialised and strategic function like the Ministry of Labour, which is expected to collaborate with diverse local and international calibre while adhering to best practice labour standards, is insufficient.

Kuruvilla and Verma (2006) believe that it is crucial to take into account the function of national governments. They recognise that the failure of national governments to enforce their legislation adequately has created the problem that current approaches are attempting to solve. However, they believe that national governments should not only be viewed as the source of the problem but also as part of the solution. This is because national governments

provide significant advantages in improving labour standards. National governments (and subsequently regional, sub-regional, and local governments) have more resources and better access to all workers and workplaces in various industrial sectors than any private sector system, NGOs, or international organisations.

Nothing will happen unless the government gets its act together. The solution is in the hands of the decision-makers. The lack of competent people with the necessary technical know-how, knowledge, skills, and behaviours is devastating. Furthermore, there is a great deal of laziness, dereliction of duty, and lack of focus. There is no justification for a government official to be a trader, buying and selling at the expense of fulfilling the main job description; they can make way for someone more capable, keen, and enthusiastic. It is not fair to the Sudanese people to have political leaders who have conflicting priorities and manipulate the rules for their gain, violating all ethical and moral codes.

The constant shambolic, chaotic, aimless approach and greedy barbarian behaviours have sadly transformed Sudan (a great nation- one day as fierce as the lions it breeds) into something else, making it look ludicrous among its peers!

*“The problem is that the people working in the ministry have become so complacent that they are unwilling to change even the most basic things around them. Let me tell you a story that happened during one of my first rounds in the ministry. I received a complaint from one of the departments that they have a huge problem...all the files have been eaten by rats, and they want me, the minister, to solve this problem for them. I couldn't believe my ears when I heard the request! I inquired as to when the administration manager was available and why you had allowed this to happen for so long until you had lost all of the files. This is an incredible level of content and passivity. It was difficult for me to comprehend how the ministry in charge of working conditions could not ensure a healthy and safe working environment for itself”
(Participant Four-LME)*

6.4.4. Underdeveloped Reform

From the conversations, it became apparent that there is no transparent, systematic approach followed by the government and the Tripartite Committee for reviewing, assessing, and updating the 97 Act since its development. It has been static for the last 25 years without evidence of change. The committee responsible for acting, deciding, and leading the change is rarely in action. Therefore, the entire system of reform is broken, and the challenge does not just lay in the law itself, which requires urgent attention, but in the institutions in charge of doing so.

“The 1997 Act has not seen any changes despite the fact that it contains numerous mistakes, print mistakes, gaps, and is incapable of coping with global changes or even the local legal reforms that have occurred in Sudan over the years. Of course, from a legal perspective, having the laws for a long period of time is not a problem; the issue is having them without any amendments or updates” (Participant Seven-AAB)

“Any work in this area is heavily reliant on the Tripartite Committee; they determine any progress, change, or development in this area. The problem is things take longer than they should because they never see eye to eye and are frequently faced with challenges or in conflict! As a result, they do not progress and have no set routine for updates and development. In theory, they should have constant regular reviews, but in practise, this is not the case! And the evidence is that the 1997 act has remained unchanged since 1997!” (Participant Four-LME)

Davis and Trebilcock (2001) argue that, in terms of legal reforms, developing nations should not just solely concentrate on passing or adopting appropriate substantive bodies of law or regulation intended to support the specific notion of advancement that drives them. Instead, the empirical data suggests it is relevant to emphasise *reforms* that improve the quality of institutions responsible for enacting laws and regulations and those responsible for administering and or enforcing those laws and regulations once they are passed.

“I know there was a committee formed eight or nine years ago to review the 1997 Act, and I know it has made some effort to upgrade the labour act, possibly more than once; I believe they have created a draft (but I have not seen anything). I can't say they have a specific structure or mechanism for doing so, and we haven't seen any findings, and nothing has been communicated to us, so I'm not sure what it has accomplished. My guess is that the initiative came from the private sector, but this is just my personal speculation” (Participant Three-MOS)

“At some point, some changes have been proposed; however, the Tripartite Committee never agreed to anything, and thus no change occurred over time. We tried to bring people together recently during my tenure and form task forces or review current laws and make the necessary changes. In fact, there was a very productive initiative made by the Sudanese HR Managers Association and they came up with good proposals for change, and we welcomed their suggestions and contribution and said why not make them part of the committee task force, which we did; unfortunately, their initiative was unsuccessful” (Participant Four-LME)

According to international best practice benchmarks, MENA countries, including Sudan, are lagging; the laws that govern governance in employment are incompatible; for example, despite the presence of protective regulations, most MENA countries remain unprotected from unemployment hazards, trade unions (whether state or independent) hardly ever effectively represent workers, and law enforcement itself remains very weak in the majority of these countries (Angel-Urdinola and Kuddo, 2010).

The same study concluded that changes or reforms to labour laws in MENA countries must coexist with changes to social protection systems, such as social support networks, unemployment insurance, and other government-backed social protection policies (backed by

the government). This means it is not just about labour laws but a comprehensive outlook of all the supporting means regulating effective employment. Hence, there is so much work to be done, but what if the government is constantly in conflict, and the representatives (Tripartite Committee) that help create policy, administer its reform and facilitate progress are never in harmony or reach a conclusion? There seem to have been some unstructured attempts over the years, but these attempts never produced any formal official output for anyone to acknowledge or hold on to.

Suppose you ask anyone who applies the law and uses it daily. In that case, they will tell you they have never seen any changes, and nothing was communicated. In contrast, others may say they have heard of some newly issued proposals but haven't seen anything tangible or official. They all wait with great anticipation, hoping for a miracle to happen. Another significant issue that has emerged from the discussion is the lack of involvement of stakeholders in the process. They are never involved; communication channels are haphazard and rely on individual effort. They are not heard and excluded from discussions or policy formulation, although they are on the ground daily and aware of the issues. Some have led private initiatives, and the transitional government attempted, but failed, to bring the parties together.

Furthermore, it is claimed that the tardiness and malfunction are not accidental but rather the result of "deliberate negligence," which supports and fosters personal gains of free enterprise, or, more specifically, the Sudanese Businessmen and Employers Federation. A key factor contributing to Sudanese citizens continued decline in social and economic well-being. Businesspeople have a moral responsibility towards Sudan and should act accordingly.

6.4.5. The Labour Offices

These offices are located across the country and are in charge of administering the implementation of the Labour Act on behalf of the Ministry of Labour. They serve as the primary point of contact between the employer and the employee and are responsible for resolving and reconciling any conflict. They are also in charge of conducting reviews, audits, and inspections; we know the inspection is not activated; however, the inspectors are still there "in charge" of handling inspection in these labour offices across the various organisational settings and sectors and the coordination of activities among and between HRM Departments throughout the private sector.

The administrative and regulatory component is central to its function, determining its success or failure. Regulation is frequently viewed as a tool for constraining and embedding human behaviour, but it could also be used to prevent undesirable outcomes; this could also play an empowering and affirmative role (Baldwin *et al.*, 2012). According to the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), better regulation could underpin growth and strengthen resilience by improving economic and social welfare prospects (OECD, 2012).

The ILO defines labour administration as “public administration activities in the field of national labour policy” in its Labour Administration Convention, 1978 (No. 150). This covers all aspects of labour policy, including employment policy, labour law, social protection, and industrial relations, as well as its institutions, activities, and results. Although the Labour Administration Convention does not define a national labour policy, it is generally acknowledged that it encompasses all labour-related issues, such as the protection of employment and working conditions, the promotion of equal opportunity, and fundamental principles and rights at work (Standing, 2008).

The only conceptual framework for labour administration that is universally acknowledged is provided by the Labour Administration Convention and the accompanying Recommendation, 1978 (No. 158). The Convention and the Recommendation are typical promotional standards in that, despite having an apparent normative content, they primarily offer policy guidelines and objectives that must be given concrete form in particular measures tailored to national circumstances. They are based on the idea that if a country does not have a capable and effective labour administration to monitor the advancement of labour laws and regulations, adopting those laws and regulations may be ineffective (Heyes and Rychly, 2013).

“Another significant fact is that these offices do not report to the ministry (Labour Ministry), but rather to the state offices. Let’s just think about it for a moment: if the ministry wants to establish a relationship with the ILO and effectively develop international standards in Sudan, how can they work with labour offices to implement these strategies if they do not report to them? The same is true for government schools (I know that from Adeel Almadaris- the CSR Corporate Social Responsibility initiative lead for several years)... dividing the schools and renting out the classrooms as shops; government schools with acres of land have been cut and rented to make money, and the funny thing is that this money does not go back to the school; it goes to state offices!” (Participant Five-SEI)

“More importantly, labour offices are part of the state/province offices rather than the Ministry of Labour (which is a huge contradiction and huge challenge). This distances it from what is going on there; it lacks the necessary links, measures, and statistics to refer to” (Participant Four-LME).

The participants revealed that the labour offices do not report to the Ministry, the sole entity responsible for applying labour laws and all other technical knowledge associated with labour issues. This is a pronounced structural flaw and administrative weakness. The offices serve the ministry and are the direct link between the ministries, the people, and the organisations they serve. They accordingly represent the ministry and reflect the community yet have no reporting line; they report to the state offices, a non-specialised entity that probably understands nothing about labour issues.

It is unclear why there are no solid reporting lines between the two entities, despite the direct link from a national strategic and objective standpoint and a technical and know-how point of view. How will these offices obtain the necessary leadership and competencies (Knowledge, Skills, and Behaviours) required to function effectively, and who will lead them? Where will the direction come from, and where will the strategies, global international standards, and objectives that align them with the rest of the world come from, such as the state offices?

6.4.6. Role, Ability and Credibility!

It is crystal clear from the discussion that the labour offices lacked three significant components: **competence**, **power**, and **integrity**. They do not have the necessary skills and abilities to add value and support the private sector as anticipated. They have very limited or no legal background and transfer all issues to court without any influence to attempt to resolve the matters. Their role is further weakened by their passive, reactive role, lack of authority, and absence of power. They have so little influence and no impact that they are

frequently overlooked and bypassed by some HR representatives because they know they will not add value to the process.

“Of course, there are labour offices, but their role is very limited; all they do is reviewing the cases before they are transferred to courts, despite their primary role of mediation and troubleshooting to avoid the cases in the first place. Unfortunately, most or all cases end up in court! As a result, their role is very passive and almost useless. Because they lack competence, they end up transferring cases to court that should have been handled by them in the first place. They are only concerned with the number of foreign workers! We discussed inspection earlier, and I’d like to add that in my many years of service, I’ve seen these offices run solely on the number of expatriates we hire, the work permits they have, and all other activities that only generate income for these offices; as a result, the offices became solely responsible for the collection of fees and tariffs, and lost their essence of providing service and assisting private organisations in understanding the labour act” (Participant Five-SEI)

They are seen to be primarily concerned with matters that generate revenue for the offices, such as collecting fees and tariffs and finding ways to encourage or increase that revenue. Any dispute, error, or problem that occurs and must be discussed and resolved requires a fee, so the more problems there are, the more fees there are, and thus, more money and, hence, more income. Consider this: the administration in charge of compliance profits from non-compliance and probably favours any conflict which generates revenue. Moreover, they are neglected by the government and, surprisingly, are under-resourced. They are not trained, equipped, or invested in human resources or facilities, nor do they have the necessary competence or potential to lead this vital role!

“Furthermore, the labour offices’ role is very passive; they have no authority and, most of the time, make no difference. All they do is receive complaints and collect fees. Furthermore, their decisions are not legally binding and must be challenged in court (they have no binding power). To be honest, they are usually more of a hindrance, and sometimes we do not even consider it as a step because we know they can do nothing and take my problem straight to court, completely ignoring them (without them even knowing). While they should have played a more active role in investigating the issues, checking the standards and specifications to ensure compliance, and acting as a true regulatory body in collaboration with the Industrial Safety and the written act” (Participant Eight-HEH)

Because the labour system is structured so that everyone must work through the labour office, the participants explained they must go to the labour office for everything. And no one reached out to them for follow-up on the issues that arose. The government offices did not

proactively ask or demand that organisations do anything specific to improve or develop the operation; they never shared any preventive measures to safeguard the employee-employer relationship. Confirming the passive and unreceptive role they play. The private sector has more expectations for these offices. Unfortunately, they are not up to the standard compared to similar offices with similar roles in neighbouring countries. They are seen as not sufficiently equipped, empowered, and funded.

“More importantly, the labour offices, there may be some corruption issues, which I cannot confirm but suspect. We recommended, in collaboration with the ILO, that the labour ministry be evaluated to determine if it is capable of carrying out its core functions and is capable of achieving the objectives it is meant to achieve” (Participant Four-LME).

They are also suspected of corruption, observed in several incidents, worsening the situation. In their current state, the labour offices are unfit for the purpose!

“The second problem is the lack of labour offices in many Sudanese provinces, which rely on civil courts to settle disputes, and these courts are not serialised at all. Everything is linked in a vicious circle” (Participant Four-LME)

“... in rural areas, these offices do not exist, so an employee or worker must travel for long distances (7-8 hours) to reach a specialised labour office to obtain the necessary support or information. ...Another example is Article 4 of the 1997 Labour Act, which defined many terms but left the phrase "Competent Authority" vague and generally loose/open (leaving it ambiguous), allowing anyone or any side to consider itself the "Competent Authority. This has caused significant difficulties in the application of labour laws and decision making, particularly in rural areas and provinces where specialised representation of legal authority, such as labour courts or offices, is limited or nonexistent! When a tribal chief makes a decision and rules an order about which he has no knowledge or understanding, he is referred to as the "Competent Authority" (Participant Seven-AAB)

Furthermore, despite their ineffectiveness and inefficiencies, the discussion also revealed that they ***lacked coverage***, leaving many private organisations, particularly upcountry and rural areas, out and entirely out of reach. At this point, the “*competent Authority*” steps in and allows for discrepancies, permitting anyone with little or no knowledge and understanding to step in and pretend to be the competent authority playing the role and deciding on a core issue affecting someone’s life-impacting their future!

6.4.7. Lack of Consistency and Flexibility

“The consistency with which the legislation is applied is a critical success factor; due to the elasticity of the legislation, huge disparities occur all the time. Today, for example, the three main labour offices (Khartoum, Khartoum North, and Omdurman) can handle the same case in three different ways! This disparity creates confusion and unnecessary inconsistencies that are inconvenient for both parties. As a result, I believe that there should be universal legislation that aligns and unifies all locations and sectors, and that should simply mean the same to everyone and be clearly understood by all without any divergence, i.e. reach a common understanding in all relevant concepts without debating any issue” (Participant Two-MZK)

Finally, the fundamental problem of discrepancy arose. The understanding and applications of the 1997 Act by labour offices across the country would lead one to assume that it is consistent across the board; however, this is not the case! The participants’ discussions and stories illuminate the situation and unmistakably point to tremendous disparity and uncertainty. The eccentric thing is that the sole point of reference of all offices nationwide is one universal document, the 1997 Labour Act. However, each office, even in the same city, takes, for example, the offices in the capital Khartoum- (Omdurman, Khartoum North, and Greater Khartoum), three offices with the same mandate interpret the same laws differently and respond differently to the same set of information and the same sequence of events.

“There is no consistency what so ever; everything is based on personal judgement, personality, understanding of the situation, and interpretation of the law. The law is not consistently applied, resulting in fragmented application even at the level of labour law governors themselves. Because the legislations are not specific and clearly defined, the interpretation varies among the various bodies... As a result, the application of the 1997 law becomes even more difficult to follow because the people who created it are unable to follow it because it means different things to different people! Let me give you an interesting example: ...I worked for a multi-company organisation whose HR function I headed and led the company branches across the country. When I first started in 2001, the company was new, and I developed a standardised employee disciplinary procedure that had to be endorsed and approved by the labour office (in accordance with the 1997 labour act), and naturally, I developed one single standard disciplinary action and standard sets of contracts for the three different branches spread across the capital city Greater Khartoum. The Khartoum labour offices then approved it for use by all branches in Khartoum North and Omdurman. I then had to engage with the Khartoum-North Office for verification and show them the

disciplinary procedure and contracts authenticated by the Khartoum office; however, the Khartoum-North Office refused the disciplinary procedure and the contracts and stated that they are unable to recognise them because the Khartoum office regulations are incompatible with their applications (note that both offices apply the same regulatory body which is the 1997 Labour Act)...It was shocking to hear that and created a real dilemma for me at the time; I was referring to the application of the 1997 act within the capital city of Khartoum! I then gave them the disciplinary procedure and contracts to review, and I made all of the changes they requested in order to best suit the requirements of the Khartoum-North office. The same thing happened at the Omdurman office, with various changes made to meet various criteria and measures. Of course, I had to follow the rules of all three offices, which resulted in three different disciplinary procedures for three branches of the same company. This meant that in core disciplinary actions across three geographic locations in the same city, I would have to treat many employees working for the same company under one payroll differently! This was an obvious injustice and contradiction that I did not understand; keep in mind that all three offices use the same labour law!!! So I had to go a step further and bring all three offices together with the help of a senior director, including the minister, and with and under very special considerations, the three offices agreed to one consistent disciplinary procedure for the three branches. All of the work done went above and beyond what was required; however, if we had not taken this extra step and gone the extra mile, we would have been all over the place with three inconsistent disciplinary procedures for employees working for the same company!" (Participant Three-MOS)

They all have one underlying benchmark: a national act that advocates for nationwide uniformity. However, the interpretations are never the same; the parties seldom agree and are primarily in dispute or conflict, debating matters and seeing things differently. All participants attribute this predicament to the lack of clarity in the 1997 Act, which leaves room for ambiguity and broad interpretations (lack of clarity is discussed further in the next chapter).

In addition, the labour offices operate rigidly in a way that is not flexible enough to accommodate all the requirements of the different types of work. They also lack the sound judgement required to think creatively and find organisational solutions that adhere to logic and best practices. This is evident in the two examples discussed above: the three different disciplinary procedures for the three branches of the same company and the regulations required to govern tardiness and safety in aviation.

The discussions revealed that the labour offices lack the necessary flexibility to accommodate the diverse organisational needs across the country. They tend to interpret the laws as they

see fit, without the duty of care and careful consideration of diverse businesses' needs. The reasonable argument made by the respondents is that the Labour Act should not have to be interpreted, clarified, or explained to start with. It should be clear, simple, self-explanatory, and easy to understand. It is argued that the ministry benefits from the ambiguity and the creation of conflict rather than focusing on enhancing its technical capabilities and developing the necessary measures for safeguarding and strengthening the inspection process. Arbitration costs organisations money, but it is a guaranteed source of income for the labour offices and, thus, the Ministry of Labour.

6.5. Conclusion

The authorities have not revised the 1997 Labour Laws of Sudan to suit the current issues and requirements. These rules originated in the 1960s and 1970s and are inadequate for addressing the challenges of the current century. Small companies are disproportionately affected by the regulations, which cripple them and deter entrepreneurs from starting new ones since they apply to all businesses, regardless of size. The document itself exhibits ambiguity, a lack of clarity, and inconsistency. The leading cause of the lack of conformance is the oversight of an essential component, namely the regulatory procedures section. The 1997 Act consolidates four distinct legislations, but neither the previous four acts nor the 1997 Act included regulations. The process of inspection, which is a vital requirement of the 1997 Act and is presumed to occur, is dormant. Additionally, crucial provisions such as the presence of "Public Employment Offices," "Specialty Committees," and "Regular Health Checks" are now not operational.

Furthermore, there are no sanctions or repercussions, and the labour offices, the leading authority responsible for implementing the Act, are an ineffective institution with little or no influence and insufficient coverage. They lack power, competency, and consistency and are not accountable to the Labour Ministry, which has exclusive responsibility for formulating and implementing labour legislation. The Ministry of Labour is now experiencing a state of despair, making it unable to make proactive decisions to bring about the necessary change. This situation exemplifies an outdated system incapable of fulfilling the country's urgent requirements. The institution responsible for guiding the recovery, creating the vision, leading the transformation, facilitating collaboration among parties, and supervising the enforcement of labour laws is now in life support.

Corruption and power struggle divert attention from successfully executing equitable, impartial, and dependable initiatives. Financial restrictions significantly burden and hinder the capacity to enforce labour rules effectively. Additional obstacles include the absence of competence and core technical expertise and the presence of knowledge, skills, and behaviours. Since its establishment, the Tripartite Committee has not implemented a systematic approach for examining, evaluating, and revising the 97 Act. Over the last 25 years, there has been a complete absence of any substantiated changes in the legislation.

CHAPTER SEVEN: ANALYSIS & DISCUSSION THEME

II (Major Issues & Challenges)

7.1. Introduction

In this chapter, you will find a detailed analysis and comprehensive discussion of the second theme, “Major Issues & Challenges”. Within the table below, the second column consolidates another thirteen subthemes around which the debate evolves. The central theme of the discussion is around areas where significant challenges stand and problematic areas that are causing issues, such as the lack of clarity, the missing measures, remuneration, social protection, equality, diversity, inclusion, and employment contracts.

Table 7.1 Final Refined Themes & Subthemes II

<i>Theme One: Key Aspects and Features</i>	<i>Theme Two : Major Issues & Challenges</i>	<i>Theme Three: Strategic Direction & Way Forward (Meeting the Twenty-first Century Needs)</i>
A Historical Perspective	How well is the Act coping?	Fundamental Principles and Rights at Work
Private Sector Organizations: Application & Abidance	Lack of Clarity Consistency and Alignment	International Standards
The Practical Application	“What doesn’t get measured doesn’t get managed”	Protecting workers from Unacceptable Forms of Work
Organizational Compliance: Abidance and Inspection	Remuneration	A Decent Work Strategy
Government & Governance	Minimum Wage	Understanding & Measuring Decent Work
The Role of the State	Salary Breakdown, Overtime & Other Benefits	What effort is needed to establish decent work in Sudan?
A Ministry in Limbo	Social Protection (Safety Nets)	A Communication Strategy
The Tripartite Committee	National Pension and Social Insurance Fund	Occupational Safety and Health
Incompetence and Corruption	Beyond the Formal Sector	
Underdeveloped Reform	Protecting the Most Vulnerable	
The Labour Offices	Workplace Boundaries	
Role, Ability and Credibility	Equality Diversity and Inclusion	
Lack of Consistency and Flexibility	The Employment Contract	

Source: (Original)

7.2. How well is the Act coping (is it equipped for the twenty-first-century challenges)?

The participants collectively agreed that the 1997 Labour Act is not meeting the needs of businesses and is unprepared for the challenges of the twenty-first century. Additionally, as discussed earlier, it was emphasised that it was unsuitable even in 1997. The current laws are mostly a continuation of old ones, with minimal modifications and little consequential impact. It is understood that the economic constraints and political challenges confronting Sudan had so much to do with the significant impact on the country's progress; however, these are not the only obstacles; there are others, such as incompetence, corruption and beyond.

“No, it is not equipped at all. My answer is straightforward: Sudan has stagnated primarily due to the autocratic style of the previous president Omer Al-Bashir; they did not focus on what was important for the employees....with anything said it was fine 20-25 years ago, but now we are dealing with and facing international challenges from the International Labour Organization.... and if we benchmark other countries within Africa, a lot needs to be done” (Participant Nine-RFU)

“Even in 1997, the 1997 copy was not convincing to anyone (including its custodians), labour unions, the government, or anyone else. And the proof is that they always make proposals and attempts at change but never achieve anything. This clearly demonstrates the true flaws of the 1997 Act and provides an answer to the question” (Participant Six-MAK)

“The answer is defiantly not; I personally, as a practitioner, have faced huge challenge with this law for years; I was struggling with certain gaps and areas in the legislation 20 years ago (note that other new challenges have risen in-between); so without hesitation, I know for certain that the current law, in its current state, does not fulfil all of our needs; and this has been proven even more after the Covid19 Pandemic, when we as HR professionals realised that there are no laws that support flexible work such as working from home, online work engagements, and even part-time work. As a result, I can simply state that the labour law of 1997 does not support Sudan's current contemporary work environment” (Participant Three-MOS)

To further support this argument, the researcher faced difficulties working with the Labour Act of 1997 when she started working in the private sector in 2003. She felt it was outdated as core fundamental gaps needed to be bridged right away. She recalls speaking with the head of HR and asking if a new version or update would be released because the current one is seven years old and should be modified to cope with the existing business needs. He said it would almost certainly be updated in two years. We neither expected it to remain "untouched" for another twenty years! Let us take, for example, the UK revises its labour laws and updates them regularly. To simplify matters for employers, the UK Government

aims to introduce new employment legislation in April and October of each year. However, employment law changes can occur anytime during the year because of tribunals and occasional government initiatives deviating from the October-April milestones. CIPD predicts that there will be significant legal changes in the UK in 2023, which will have far-reaching consequences for workers and HR.

“I would like to first highlight the fact that there were several attempts made to upgrade the Act of 1997 in a number of different years (2002, 2006,2007,2013,2018) none of which were successful as there was no agreement from the Tripartite Committee, every time the projects take shape. Still, the three partners never agreed to anything... the most recent copy of 2018 focused on the approach of combining all labour laws into a single unified act. The 1997 copy was unclear in emphasising the fundamental labour law rules of public order, which may not be violated (just like all other countries in the world). The concept of employment equality appears in the 2018 proposal, which did not appear in the 1997 copy.....To summarise and answer your question, none of these copies, including the proposed latest version of 2018 update, are sufficient to solve the problems/issues of the third millennium or meet the needs of Sudanese people in the twenty-first century; it will be similar to the 1997 version with very little impact (Participant Six-MAK)

The Sudanese business environment has changed significantly over the past two decades, as has the level of awareness and understanding among the workforce, and the 1997 Act is lagging and is not meeting today’s business needs. This is evident in the current terminology and language used to address the issues raised in the Act and the many gaps. It was created to serve a different generation and an industry that no longer exists. In this context, and because it was apparent to decision-makers a long time ago that the Act needed updating, several unsuccessful attempts were made on various occasions. Whenever a critical need arose, the Tripartite Committee would assemble and make a recommendation or development to upgrade.

However, none of the attempts succeeded in issuing an official document except for some proposals witnessed by a few people, such as “Participant Six-MAK,” who had access to and knowledge of these failed schemes. Furthermore, it is unclear why none of these attempts were successful other than a lack of consensus and agreement among the three parties that comprise the Tripartite Committee.

7.3. Lack of Clarity and Alignment

According to “Participant Two-MZK,” *Sudan does not have one set of consolidated comprehensive legislation that covers all working people within the society and very well includes all the different proceedings in one place. There are separate scattered laws here and*

there, besides the many other stand-alone laws, such as work injuries, minimum wage, and social security. Even expats working in Sudan have separate stand-alone laws.

In addition, today in Sudan, so many different governmental organisations are exempt from these laws and follow separate laws! This is evident at the start of the legislation, where there is a long list of government and other groups that are exempt and follow different individual laws, such as civil servants, members of the armed forces, domestic servants, agricultural labourers, employer's family members, casual employees, and so on (nine different categories).

“Scattered legislation: The Minimum Wage Act of 1974 (Seven Articles) is a separate law that should have been incorporated into the laws themselves due to its importance and significance, as well as for clarity. Some relevant effective articles remain part of the Civil Transaction Laws but govern the employment contract (when they contradict, the Labour Law takes precedence/priority over the other). Why not combine and unify all of these Articles into a single Act known as "The Labour Act"? All of the Acts must be in harmony and synchronisation. Unify the meaning and thus the understanding...they are inconsistent, lack uniformity... There is no common ground- there is a lack of consistency in interpretations and applications- each location has its own points of view and interpretations!” Participant Eight-HEH)

Therefore, the country lacks a well-consolidated and well-collaborated consistent set of rules. Laws are scattered all over the place, not aligned, sometimes contradicting, and simply don't speak to each other, creating huge inconsistencies and discrepancies across the board. “Participant Two-MZK” highlights the importance of developing one comprehensive act that covers and includes all workers. It explains further that at the end of the exemption section, the Act states: “any class of persons, the Ministry Council may declare by an order that they are exempt from the provisions of this Act entirely or partially”.

“Personally, I believe that this is a very bad decision” (Participant Two-MZK)

Meaning that the ministry can declare someone (anyone) or an organisation exempt from the Act at any point in time as it sees fit! This leads to significant inconsistencies, unnecessary discrepancies, and complete unfairness. It was further explained by “Participant Eight-HEH” that the level of inconsistency and disparity has even extended to the level of the Supreme Court!

*“There is no alignment no harmony; they don’t speak the same language!”
(Participant Six-MAK)*

“For example, the Sudanese Labour Act of 1997 grants children the right to work at the age of 16, whereas the Sudanese Child Act of 2010 considers anyone under the age of 18 to be a child and should not work without permission - resulting in two laws operating concurrently that contradict one another” (Participant Seven-AAB)

“Occupational Health, Industrial Safety, and Decent Work are all linked to one another and to the employment regulations - if aligned and in harmony, they can reduce the number of labour court disputes” (Participant Six-MAK)

“Participant Three-MOS,” “Participant Five-SEI,” and “Participant Eight-HEH” contended that the 1997 Act clauses are primarily vague and ambiguous. As a result, each labour office and court interpret the same set of laws differently. The same case can be interpreted in three different ways, each meaning differently. Professionals at the same level can disagree on the outcomes of the same cases because it means something different to each of them. The issue is that there is no standard set of rules and regulations accompanying the Act, as there should have been from the beginning.

For the laws to be easily understood by all and to have common grounds, measures, and standards across the board, the regulations require explanations and interpretations of the meanings of every Article in the Set of Laws. As seen earlier and discussed, the labour offices across the country lack consistency in the application. “Because the legislations are not specific and clearly defined, the interpretation varies among the various bodies”, the researcher was told by “Participant Five-SEI”, and hence, applying the 1997 law becomes even more difficult to follow even for the people who created it.

“So to conclude, there are no consistent measures that everyone understands, and this disparity creates huge discrepancy and haphazardness across the country. The same case can be handled differently by two different HR representatives working for the same company in different timeframes, and as I explained in my example, each labour office interprets the same legislation differently and creates a separate rule for it, expecting you to apply three different rules for people in the same organisation. And, depending on the timing, the situation, or the person in charge, the same case and scenario will be handled and governed differently many more times! The law is highly subjective; the measures are arbitrary, lack objectivity, and are based solely on personal judgement” (Participant Three-MOS)

7.4. “What doesn’t get measured doesn’t get managed.”

Measures are certainly lacking from the formula; according to “Participant One-EOS”, they are simply missing. There are no measures in place, follow-up, audit, or any checks or review of the Labour Act implementation in any organisational setting. It was previously understood that the “Inspection” process is missing; it exists only on paper but is not activated in practice. “Participant One-EOS” explains that HR managers nationwide had to rely on their integrity to follow up, remind themselves of what needed to be done, and do their governance, except for a few multinational corporations that followed their home country’s policies and were self-regulated.

All HR functions oversee upholding labour regulations; they took the initiative; therefore, it was up to them to do the right thing; no one came back to challenge or audit their application.

“The only KPIs or measures in place are the amounts of money collected from penalties, such as when violating health and safety regulations, as well as other fees and charges for work permits, registrations, and other payments such as clarifications. Essentially, sales/commission and the official labour office representatives in charge of these sales are paid an annual bonus based on the volume of sales they manage to generate. They measure their success based on the amount of money collected rather than the impact they have made” (Participant Four-LME)

According to “Participant Four-LME”, the most recent workforce census survey was conducted in 2011 and never again; this is the only official data available today and is over a decade old! It is out of date and out of touch, as the interviewee called it “*obsolete*”. Nothing has happened since; there is a massive problem in Sudan; generally, there is an evident lack of data across the board, and lack of measures is an everlasting predominant problem.

“There is no data - nothing (we were in the dark)! We attempted to assist families during the Covid19 crisis and determine how many families are there in each region; however, we were unable to do so due to a lack of reference data. How can you make policies when you don’t have the basic information...We don’t even know how many people are employed!”

Another issue is the availability and accessibility of data. There are no records or evidence to rely on to help support the decision-making process. A considerable challenge “Participant Four-LME” faced as someone who relied on data and evidence in making changes and decisions. Furthermore, research and development (R&D) is another significant factor missing.

There is no research and development in labour issues. There are no statistical records and no data (Participant Seven-AAB)

When you think about it, how can you research something you know little about? Participants agree there are no measures, no data, and, thus, no tracking. William Thomson, the Scottish physicist who was also known as Lord Kelvin, said about measurements that when you can measure what you're talking about and express it in numbers, you know something about it, but when you can't, your knowledge is weak and unsatisfactory; it may be the beginning of knowledge, but you've barely advanced to the stage of scientific knowledge, whatever the matter may be.

There are no measures in place that have been developed by the ministry or government to support the application of the labour act... Nothing; everything is dependent on the employer's integrity! (Participant Five-SEI)

The famous saying or principle attributed to the management expert Peter Drucker, “*What gets measured gets managed*”, is flawless and applies well to all business scenarios. It implies that assessing an activity alters it by forcing us to pay close attention. It may well indicate that gathering data about the activity gives a solid grip on it and allows us to improve it (Al Bredenberg, 2012).

No one cares about the workers' interests or problems in order to follow or measure anything; the labour offices exist solely to collect money from organisations. (Participant Seven-AAB)

Suppose the government is serious about properly managing the application of labour laws. In that case, clear metrics should have been established and tracked with the respective business units nationwide so that they could be assessed regularly. Unfortunately, none of the people interviewed for this study said they were aware of any predefined government measures concerning the implementation of the 1997 Labour Act.

7.5. Remuneration & Minimum Wage

According to the ILO, the minimum wage is the lowest that must be paid to most of a nation's workers, typically hourly, daily, or monthly. Considering the national economic and social climate at the time, it is ideal for this wage to be set to meet the worker's and their family's essential needs. In Sudan, the Minimum Wage Act was initiated in 1974; it has separate legislation (Seven Articles), but it is mentioned in the 1997 Act, and some

participants referred to this point as part of the scattered legislation that should have been incorporated in one single act for ease and clarity. The government and the tripartite committee set it, and it is currently at two different rates: SDG 425 (USD 0.73) per month for the private sector and SDG 3,000 (USD 5.17) per month for civil servants. Both rates are far below any reasonable living wage sufficient for one person to live, let alone one for a worker with family responsibilities. It has quite a few limitations.

“For the private sector, the minimum wage was last updated in 2014. In 2014, the official exchange rate for the USD was 6 Sudanese Pounds; today, the official rate is 560 Sudanese Pounds! Last December, the minimum wage in the public sector increased to SDG 12,000 and remained 425 Sudanese Pounds (less than a cost of a basic local meal which costs 700 SDG). The same government agency that updated the minimum wage for the public sector is in charge of changing it in the private sector (a very unjustified discrepancy)” (Participant Seven-AAB)

All participants unanimously agreed that the minimum wage poses a significant challenge. Participant Five-SEI explains how the minimum wage in Sudan is incompatible with the workers’ actual needs and emphasises the importance of measuring and basing it on people’s exact needs, which is not currently happening. Participant Three-MOS clarifies the missing governmental role in conducting regular reviews and constant assessments to ensure that the minimum wage reflects the reality surrounding the community.

And that the workers’ livelihood must reflect their daily reality rather than being wholly unreasonable and out of touch. The numbers we have seen and what the minimum wage represents are far from realistic, and one participant mentioned that even if the government multiplies the current figures by 100, it still won’t be enough to secure a decent life. Sudan has struggled with high inflation rates for years, but this is no excuse for decision-makers to be so out of touch and indifferent to such a fundamental issue.

“The minimum wage set by the government is not based on a realistic benchmark and is far below any reasonable/rational measure; and has through time consistently failed to meet the expectations of the Sudanese people, resulting in a threshold that constantly keeps workers below the poverty line. True, the high drastic level of inflation plays a role, but the measures used to calculate it are not reliable enough, and the government is simply not paying enough attention to the issue. Minimum wage should be reviewed and assessed on a regular basis...some leading companies are currently taking the initiative to review their minimum wage every quarter to cope with high inflation and skyrocketing living costs... These are the few who want to be at the top of their game while also retaining and protecting their employees. However, the regulatory body is falling behind, which is very unfortunate” (Participant Three-MOS)

“Participant Six-MAK” argues that the Sudanese government ignores all important socioeconomic matters, focusing only on military and political issues at the expense of people’s livelihood and that it should be noted that the revolution was founded on rebellion and protest against the minimum wage, which was the reason the people of Sudan protested in the first place and lost innocent lives to seize a better life.

This negligence has compelled other bodies that are not directly responsible to take matters into their own hands and begin making decisions, such as the social insurance body has recently decided that they will not insure any employee earning less than SDG12,000, thus creating a threshold for the socially insured, giving organisations room not to send all those earning less than SDG12,000, they may have made this decision with good intentions. Still, it is firing back at low earners and making things worse.

On the other hand, some leading companies are taking the initiative to review the cost of living regularly, even revisiting salaries every quarter to stay ahead of the competition.

“A new article published recently by the social insurance says that companies should not bring in contributions of wages below a threshold of SDG 12,000 that they have determined on their own calling it a minimum wage (just something they have decided on their own), which leaves a lot of room for disagreement” (Participant Eight-HEH)

Sudan is an Islamic country that has claimed for years to follow Islamic governance rules and has attempted to implement many Islamic directives. However, the obvious thing to all Sudanese people is that the government uses the name of Islam to manipulate the people and enforce half-baked plans, taking what suits its form but not with the genuine intention of solving a problem, helping those in need, or improving people’s lives.

This is clear, for example, when implementing Zakat as a compulsory taxation method and deducting the Zakat contribution from the earnings of employees above a certain threshold. Islam has established Zakat as a core part of Sharia (Islamic Laws) that requires all Muslims to adhere to. According to (Azeez, 2003), zakat is “that portion of a man’s wealth designated for the poor”. Zakat is one of Islam’s five pillars, so it is obligatory for every Muslim who has the financial means (nisab). “*Nisab*” is the amount required to meet a person’s or a family’s basic needs for one year. Food, clothing, housing, medical treatment, and transportation for oneself and dependents are all basic needs. Dependents include spouses, children who cannot work, and parents in need.

In many modern societies, “*nisab*” is the same as a government-determined poverty line or threshold (Ali and Hatta, 2014). Nisab, according to Investopedia.com, is a term frequently used in conjunction with zakat. It is a criterion referring to the minimum wealth and possessions a Muslim must possess before being required/ obliged to pay zakat. In other words, no zakat is due if personal wealth falls below this threshold during a lunar year. The nisab is worth 87.48 grams of gold or 612.36 grams of silver.

The value of Nisab has been measured through time using the value of Gold and Silver; these two metals have been known to keep their real value throughout history. Another precise measure is *Zakat al-Fitr*. Every financially able Muslim must pay **zakat al-fitr**, or “*alms on feast*”, which is a small amount equivalent to the price of one day’s worth of food for a person in need. Zakat al-Fitr, which is due before the Eid prayer at the end of Ramadan, is estimated to cost each person the cost of a day’s meal (Atia, 2011), which is usually determined by each country based on actual food prices and varies from one nation to the next.

This is not left to chance or determined by outdated figures but by Islam as a specific measure of barley *Sa’a of barley*, which is equivalent to around 2.41 kg in the decimal system. Therefore, the measures are there and have been through time. As a result, they are not invalid or obsolete criteria, but rather real-life active estimates or precise values determined right now by the same government that sets and defines the unrealistic minimum wage: the minimum wage, which should provide for the employee’s family and ensure that they can live a decent, comfortable life. It should cover every essential requirement.

Some Western countries consider the cost of Internet access a basic need and include it in the food basket. Why can’t Muslim decision-makers use tangible measures to determine the minimum wage, as Islam did thousands of years ago, using active measures like gold, silver, and the actual cost of a meal or Sa’a (you can’t go wrong with these measures)? When the Sudanese government talks about implementing Islamic regimes, why can’t they use Islamic values that have adequately covered everything and have not left any stone unturned? Why are they looking the other way when everything is crystal clear?

“Despite the fact that Sudan was ruled by a so-called Islamic Regime (pretending to be Islamic) for 30 years, they did not manage to align Islamic practices into labor issues in a fair or just manner, despite their knowledge and understanding of every point in Islam. Consider the following: Wages and Salaries are related to “Primary Need.” The primary need for an employee in 2020 was more than one million Sudanese pounds per year (more than the entire income of a worker on minimum wage for five years)...because it is based on the value of gold... The worker must earn 98,000 per month to reach the Zakat threshold (Nisab)... which makes it the Primary Need threshold, after which Zakat taxes apply. If there was justice, the minimum wage should be equivalent to the same threshold (98,000 SDG), not 425 SDG (Participant Seven-AAB)

Participant Seven-AAB showed that the government in Sudan uses the value of gold to determine the thresholds for compulsory income Zakat deductions (taxation), relying on Islamic rules that it can only be deducted after exceeding the “Primary Need” (الحوائج الاصلية) or basic needs. The primary need threshold is 230 times the minimum wage, the same minimum wage defined as the primary need! The problem is that the minimum wage is a fraction of the Primary Need! This is not a case of ignorance or lack of knowledge, but instead of a deliberate strategy.

In addition, Participant Seven-AAB explains that the “*Collective agreement to address the minimum wage Sudan*” was the only recognised Collective Bargaining initiative. The committee, over time, had two functions; to be more specific, they met twice: first in 2004 and predetermined the minimum wage for the next three years (2005, 2006 and 2007) and then met again in 2014 and did the same thing to determine the minimum wage for the following three years (2015, 2016 and 2017), and that was the last time they met since. The astonishing thing is that Sudan’s inflation levels and enormous political and economic instabilities make it extremely difficult to plan for a year, let alone three years!

7.6. Salary Breakdown, Overtime & Other Benefits

According to participants Three, Six, Seven, and Eight, the salary breakdown structure is not equitable, and its structure allows for significant manipulation and exploitation. Basic pay is at the employer’s discretion and is not governed by a formula or standard ratio, which is frequently abused. The labour law allows the employer to calculate almost everything from the basic pay, which can be as little as a quarter, if not less, of the take-home salary. As a result, the worker receives a fraction of their pay-check for everything that matters, such as wrongful termination compensation, after-service benefits, and the cost of overtime work, basically a rip-off.

Furthermore, participants Six and Five raise three significant concerns, including flat monthly rate salaries that do not account for hourly rates, creating unfairness, particularly for groups such as nurses, who end up working very long hours, sometimes up to 16 hours, with very little compensation and don't even have time to file a complaint. The second issue is the gender pay gap, visible in all industries nationwide.

Finally, there is the performance management issue, which is used as a criterion for annual salary increases based on labour law, which states that organisations must review salaries annually and provide a 5% yearly raise based on satisfactory performance. The problem is that the act leaves the definition of “**Satisfactory**” vague without defining what it stands for.

*“The six-month compensation for unfair dismissal is calculated based on the Basic Salary (Salary + Cost of Living), which could end up being as little as three months if not less. This is an obvious gap and weakness in the law that everyone recognizes. It also allows the employer to skirt the benefit "legally" without repercussions. A significant gap and weakness in the law that requires urgent attention; **After-service Benefits** are also calculated from (Salary + Cost of Living), which can be as little as a quarter of the wage. This results in injustice at a pivotal moment in time. And the way **overtime** is calculated creates huge injustice and of course affects the most vulnerable. Basic Salary (Salary + Cost of Living) which can constitute around 25% of the take-home salary; this amount is used to calculate the overtime cost; it is so unfair and unjust for someone to work in their own valuable leisure time and receive very little compensation for it even though the law determines the overtime hour should cost 1.5 hours during weekdays and 2.0 hours during weekends. However, when it is calculated from this minimum rate salary (supported by the labor law), it amounts to nothing because it was based on nothing!”(Participant Three-MOS)*

7.7. Social Protection (Safety Nets)

Numerous jobs are unstable. Work may be irregular or temporary, and earnings may fluctuate. Work may be physically hazardous or cause disease vulnerability. There are various other causes of job-related and life insecurity. Socio-economic security is a strong need that can be met in several ways, such as by strengthening social insurance systems, investing in workplace health and safety, and improving living and working conditions, as well as by strengthening labour market institutions and policies that safeguard workers against changes in employment and work conditions. Social protection is a critical automatic stabiliser in the global economy (Juan Somavia ILO, 2004).

The need for social protection has been recognised by fundamental international human rights agreements. Article 22 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, adopted in 1948, affirms that “everyone, as a member of society, has the right to social security.” Article 9 of

the International Covenant on Economic, Social, and Cultural Rights of 1966 also mentions “everyone’s right to social security, including social insurance.”

The International Labour Organisation defines social protection as “the set of public measures that a society provides for its members to protect them against economic and social distress caused by the absence or substantial reduction of income from work as a result of various contingencies (sickness, maternity, employment injury, unemployment, invalidity, old age, or death of the breadwinner” as well as the provision of health care and benefits for families with children.

7.8. National Pension and Social Insurance Fund

The Government Pension Law established the National Pension Fund 1904 during the colonial era. It applies to civil servants, but the army, police, and security forces have their pension funds (World Bank, 2016). The government enacted the Social Insurance Law in 1975 to balance the public and private sectors. Several laws have been enforced since the establishment of the two funds; however, the 2016 law superseded all previous legislation and established a single fund:

“The National Pension and Social Insurance Fund” (NPSIF) was established by the Social Insurance and Pensions Law of 2016 to offer pensions and social insurance to the public, private, and government sectors. The former includes all government employees paid through the Ministry of Finance, while the latter comprises all private and public organisations. Although the two funds were legally merged in September 2019, in practice, they remain divided into two distinct bodies, and their financial merger is still underway (Bilo, 2020)

Social Insurance is mandatory for all employees in the public and private sectors, as well as in the government, under the Pensions and Social Insurance Law of 2016. Professionals and craftspeople are also covered. Foreigners on diplomatic or international missions, agricultural workers (except those working in agricultural machine maintenance and agriculture-related factories), household workers, family labourers, and trainees (unless for more than three months) are excluded. The eligibility criterion includes and is not limited to work injuries, Old-age pension, Onetime pension, disability pension (for health reasons), Survivor-pension, Death-grant, and End-of-service.

“When calculating social insurance based on a very low basic salary... This means that social insurance will eventually be low, which means that in a time of genuine need, when the worker has retired and is unable to work, his/her social protection will be insufficient to provide him/her with the dignity they require. Due to the depreciation of the Sudanese pound, social insurance is a major issue in Sudan today, and much work is required... The system/policies themselves are fine; in fact, they are in accordance with best practices; however, the problem, like all other policies, is in the application itself” (Participant Two-MZK)

As the participant mentioned earlier, the issue of salary breakdown and reduced basic pay once more haunts the social insurance fund, resulting in inadequate contributions and recovery when needed. The insurance fund is financed by 25% of monthly wages/income, divided as follows (based on the 2016 law): the insured worker pays 8% of the gross monthly wage; the Employer pays 17% of the gross monthly payroll (of which 2% is assigned to cover work injury insurance).

The Government contributes as an employer. In addition, contributions from craftspeople and those who work in free trades, any additional sums paid by the insured to make up for previously uninsured employment periods over time, and any gains from the investment of these contributions. The funds operate on a “pay as you go” basis, which means that contributions from those making contributions today are used to pay today’s pensioners. There are no individual accounts, and funds are typically invested (Bilo, 2020).

“Imagine that in 2004, pensioners received roughly 500 Sudanese pounds- less than \$1 per month! Where is the social protection in this?!” (Participant Seven-AAB)

“Participant Four-LME” contended that social insurance should cover everyone, including the informal sector, and health insurance should do the same; however, practically speaking, they do not (informal groups, part-timers, etc. are not accounted for). But the question is, why is this happening, and why isn’t the government doing anything about it; why are the people not backed up or covered? The continued analysis states that this could be because the program is new and there is a lot to do, or it could be because the country is falling behind and a lot needs to be done. Furthermore, participant Six-MAK stated that when employed people stop working, they are not covered by social insurance and are only covered as long as they are engaged.

*“Let me share with you a very peculiar fact: in 2011 the Industrial Survey (and according to the Employment Policies Report 2017) revealed the following”:
 The Total Number of paid working people nationwide are= **5,500,000**
 The Number of working people registered in the National Pension and Social Insurance Fund are=less than one million (around **750,000**)
 Following the revolution in 2019, they updated the figure to = **1,000,000**
 Meaning more than **4,000,000** working people are not registered in pensions, social insurance, or have medical insurance (medical insurance is one of the polices under the labor Act of 1997)
 Membership in the Sudan Trade Union Confederation is supposed to come from registered workers (all working people have by default automatic membership)
 The membership stands at **1,200,000** (on the day the revolution occurred and the Union fell/was dissolved)
 “These figures, I can tell you, are based on official government reports issued by the ministry and discussed in the Ministerial Council and National Council. I have the reports in my office drawers right now! I raised these concerns in numerous forums, and questioned all these issues and no one responded; instead, they just remove me from my position!”*

(Participant Six-MAK)

Participant Eight-HEH also argued that with the 2016 update, it is now impossible to get the timely compensation one needs when unemployed, so social insurance does not offer workers the security they need when they are out of work or most vulnerable. They will have to wait three years to get their money. Why should they wait, or do they want people to wait until their cash value deteriorates and falls significantly?

How can they take the people’s money when it has value and give it back to them when it is worth nothing?! Similarly, Participant Four-LME believes that social insurance is unjust because of its breakdown and ease of manipulation, as well as the fact that people cannot collect it if they have worked for less than three years and questioned who gave them this power to do so, and once more inquired if they intend to devalue the currency.

According to Participant Six-MAK, working people in the upcountry provinces have been cheated out of their social insurance rights, and their money has been diverted for other purposes without their knowledge or consent. About all the issues raised above, almost all participants agree unanimously that the National Pension and Social Insurance Fund is a corrupt establishment, and this was read between the lines. Still, Participants Five-SEI and Six-MAK say it loud and clear: *“Social Insurance is corrupt!”*

Finally, Participant Six-MAK suggests that, for fairness, sustainability, and future advancement, the National Pension and Social Insurance Fund could be linked with other

payments, such as unfair dismissal and paying women their rights to maternity leave, among other things. All these payments, rather than burdening the employer and creating opportunities for corruption, can be addressed with the assistance of the social insurance fund (parties contributing, employer and employee, with the same logic). And emphasizes that, while this is a crucial step, if we are serious and want sustainable social protection, nothing will happen if we leave these things hanging.

7.9. Beyond the Formal Sector

Since it was first acknowledged in the early 1970s, Sub-Saharan Africa's informal economy has grown to be a significant source of employment for many young people as well as older workers who are pursuing their business ventures and others adjusting to structural changes in the region's employment market (Bangasser, 2000, ILO 2002). Although it was initially viewed as a safety net for individuals who could not find work in the organised sector, the image of the informal sector has begun to shift over time, along with the education of those entering it. More workers view it as a preferred destination for those seeking to become entrepreneurs rather than a temporary stop while looking for work in the formal wage economy (Adams, 2009).

During the last five decades, the informal economy has been interpreted and debated, and it has gone in and out of favour in international development circles. Despite the debates and criticisms, many policymakers, activists, and researchers have found the informal economy to be a useful concept because it captures a large share of sectors of the economy and workers who linger outside the world of regulated economic activities and protected employment relations has become so vast and significant. Currently, the informal economy is gaining more attention across the globe. This resurgence of interest stems from two fundamental facts. First, despite predictions of its demise, the informal economy has not only expanded in many countries but also emerged in new and unexpected forms and locations. Second, despite the ongoing debates about its distinguishing characteristics, supporting informal enterprises and improving informal jobs are increasingly recognised as critical pathways to promoting growth and alleviating poverty (Alter Chen, 2005).

Throughout the African continent, especially in countries like Sudan, where employment growth in the official wage sector has stalled, making it challenging to absorb the growing numbers of new labour force entrants, self-employment has created opportunities for youths chasing higher levels of education and skills (Fox and Gaal, 2008). According to the

International Labour Organisation, it accounts for a sizable but largely unnoticed portion of the global economy and workforce. It accounts for 61% of global employment, 67% in emerging markets/countries, and 90% in developing countries. In 2011, informal employment in Sudan was estimated at around 87%.

Although nearly everyone works, not everyone is employed in Sudan. The interviewees were involved to practically understand how Sudanese labour laws demonstrate concern for and acknowledge workers outside the formal labour market (unregulated wage workers, the self-employed and home workers). Participants Two, Three, Six and Seven informed the researcher that in Sudan, workers outside the formal labour market, such as independent workers, self-employed individuals, home workers, and all unregulated wage workers, are not protected by the Sudanese Labour Act of 1997.

The legislation, on the other hand, covers any official work involving any intellectual effort that is compensated by pay. Furthermore, the legislation does not cover essential working groups such as farmers, shepherds, and farm labourers. If they encounter difficulties, they have no grounds for complaint because the law does not support or include them unless they seek civil laws and courts, which may or may not protect them.

“How will they cover the unofficial sector if the official sector is not covered? There are many people who work part-time in multiple places, students, and others who are not recognised by the laws and are considered unemployed. Some people work in both the official recognised sector and the unofficial sector, but they are not recognised in the latter” (Participant Six-MAK)

In addition, the 1997 Act does not apply to business owners or their families, but it does to anyone who works for them! Even if no contract exists! Additionally, the Act excludes several occupations in Khartoum, the capital city, that unquestionably employ regular workers, including:

- Employees at gas stations
- Loading and unloading
- Bakers in bakeries

To manipulate and exploit their pay, the government created stand-alone *Pay Orders*. It excluded them from the right to be governed under the Labour Act 1997 (because they put in

a lot of extra time- to avoid paying their overtime). As Participant Seven-AAB pointed out, businesspeople are once again being protected at the expense of the weaker party, the worker.

7.10. Protecting the Most Vulnerable

According to the ILO, recent political developments in Sudan have created a genuine need for, and opportunity for, establishing a social protection system that benefits all Sudanese residents. *Social insurance* covers only some categories of pensions and work-related injuries; however, coverage is limited to the formal economy only, with informal employment estimated at around 87% in 2011. This means the number of people covered constitutes only around 13%. The National Health Insurance Fund was established in 1995 to achieve universal coverage; however, official statistics (37.3% in 2014) fall far short of this goal, and the system is overburdened and under-supplied in a country facing significant challenges.

“The informal sector is not represented at all, despite the fact that it accounts for a significant portion of the economy, and that life is changing in Sudan, as it is throughout the world, with people seeking flexibility in their jobs (freelancing and entrepreneurship), particularly among young people”
(Participant Four-LME)

Social assistance in Sudan is provided through both government and humanitarian programmes. According to the ILO, the most important of these is the Zakat fund, which offers a variety of benefits to 1.9 million households (2014). Zakat is one of the five pillars of Islam and is considered a religious duty for wealthy people to help those in need through financial or in-kind contributions. In Muslim-majority countries, it has a long tradition of being part of the provision of social welfare. Countries vary significantly in the institutionalisation of zakat, ranging from obligatory to voluntary contributions. In some countries, the state supervises the collection and management of funds, and Sudan zakat contributions are mandatory (Machado *et al.*, 2018).

Muslims in Sudan earning approximately more than USD 3,575 annually must pay 2.5% of their annual income to the Zakat Fund. Non-Muslims pay an equivalent rate of social solidarity tax. The zakat laws of 1986 and 1990 authorise the state to collect these taxes on wages and salaries. The law also requires that 61% of the revenue collected be transferred to poor and needy households (Kjellgren *et al.*, 2014). Furthermore, in July 2020, a new cash transfer scheme was launched, financed by a World Bank loan, to reach 80% of all households and provide them with only 9 USD/month.

According to Machado et al., 2018 Sudan's existing safety net programmes are inadequate regarding coverage, coordination, monitoring, and evaluation. Given the limitations in the existing monitoring mechanisms and the lack of a unified registry, there is room for improvement in the Fund's programming, especially in equity, adequacy, scalability, transparency, and accountability (Kjellgren *et al.*, 2014).

“What I realised is that there is a very old ineffective social security system. Second, governments are made up entirely of military and police personnel who have no idea what is going on in business and don't care; they only look after themselves. Unfortunately, Sudan has no social security system, which is why there is so much unrest in the country. The extremes are too far apart”
(Participant Nine-RFU)

7.10.1. Is it Protection or Exploitation?

To examine the current Sudanese labour laws in protecting society's most vulnerable workforce, “Participant Five-SEI” began by highlighting a crucial point. There are no work opportunities to start with, especially for those with special needs or vulnerabilities. The rest of the participants agreed that there are no vulnerable and marginalised groups- they are not even mentioned anywhere in the 97Act or any other separate document. The reality is that there is no equality Act to support the Labour Act.

“To begin with, there are no job opportunities here! And the Act does not promote anything in this regard. People with disabilities and vulnerabilities are the most impacted by this, as they require opportunities that are almost invisible! I wish the Act of 1997 had mentioned anything promoting or supporting this segment, but it did not. There are no equal opportunities acts or equality acts to go along and work hand in hand with the labour act”
(Participant Five-SEI)

According to Participant Seven-AAB, the 1997 Act is too broad and lacks a specific focus on society's most vulnerable workforce. A separate act protects domestic workers but is very lax regarding protection and coverage, especially for overtime hours and unlawful termination. It was modified for the province of Khartoum only in 2009, after previously being a federal law across Sudan.

According to Participant Six-MAK, agriculture workers are not entirely covered; in the reviews, they are sometimes included and sometimes excluded, and garbage collectors have nothing; they are disregarded! Participant Three also agrees that it does not protect the most

vulnerable; it has enormous challenges that affect most workers and significantly impact the most vulnerable in society. The 1997 act has vast, apparent flaws that, in the end, create colossal injustice, and it considers three significant factors that negatively affect the most vulnerable: *minimum wage, overtime, and unfair dismissal*.

“I could have evaluated it if it was applicable to the most vulnerable workforce; however, it is not. To illustrate further, consider domestic workers such as housemaids, personal drivers, and gardeners (or any hired help): the law mentions them briefly and applies in legal terms; however, it is not realistically applied, enforced, or monitored in any way. As a result, you cannot truly say that the law protects the most vulnerable” (Participant One-EOS)

All MENA nations mistreat their citizens, not just workers; they are all dictatorships that are horrifying in their practices and highly exploitative of their citizens, according to Participant Seven-AAB; he believes Sudan bears no resemblance to them...they are primarily controlled by greedy, parasitic capitalism with corruption and opportunism profiting on the backs of exploited workers and are simply incapable of functioning without it. Despite this vow, participants One, Five, Seven, and Eight all agree that, in general, these current laws do not protect anyone, vulnerable or not. It is missing the protective element at every level!

Additionally, minorities and workers with special needs are not protected in any way, that is, if they exist at all! In big companies, this is done for purely image-related reasons and publicity. However, the law does not protect these groups; it is fundamental and incompatible. Moreover, they explain that labour laws were created to safeguard weaker groups that cannot defend themselves against exploitation and the might of capitalism, in contrast to the Act of 1997, which was designed to benefit and protect employers. They claim that these laws governing labour protect the employer and favour the employer over the employee.

The minimum wage, for instance, is absurdly low; how are workers protected with a minimum wage of SDG425 plus all other allowances added up to a total of SDG 3000 (president award), equivalent to an overall total of USD 5.9 per month? Furthermore, the level of negligence and lack of duty of care has reached the point where some well-known large Sudanese companies with vast financial resources do not provide drinking water to their workers and employees! And if the workers want to drink, they must go outside and buy their water”.

“If we talk about people with special needs, it did not cater for this category at all, people with vulnerabilities such as disabled and workers with special needs cover (the law does not cover this area... it is neglected). Important things like disabled-accessible facilities, such as wheelchair ramps and special toilets.... all of this is not covered by the Labour Act of 1997, which is nowhere mentioned! As I previously stated, the law was not equipped even in 1997. As you are aware, all of these developments are dependent on the country’s economic situation, and you are also aware that Sudan is currently struggling in this area” (Participant Five-SEI)

7.10.2. Unemployment Protection

On June 21, 1988, the ILO General Conference adopted ILO Convention No. 168 Concerning Employment, Promotion, and Protection against Unemployment, according to Social Protection and Human Rights, 2015. The Convention’s primary goal is to protect unemployed people by providing benefits through periodic payments and promoting employment. As a result, Convention No. 168 recognises the significance of linking social security to broader social and economic policies that promote full, productive, and freely chosen employment. Ratifying countries must also take the appropriate steps to coordinate their unemployment protection system and employment policy and provide unemployment benefits at a minimum replacement rate of 50% of the reference wage.

“Unemployed workers are not protected...because no social protection exists. Despite the fact that Sudan previously endorsed International Agreements to protect unemployed workers, there is no unemployment protection. The government should take the lead in insuring/providing unemployment insurance” (Participant Seven-AAB)

Unemployment protection schemes provide income support to unemployed individuals who can work for a set period. Their goal is to provide at least a partial income substitute for lost earnings due to temporary unemployment, allowing the beneficiary to maintain a certain standard of living during the transition period until they find suitable employment, and, progressively, to assist in finding employment through a variety of initiatives and services, such as assistance, counselling, and advice in looking for work, and facilities for enhancing, upgrading and acquiring new skills for job seekers (Social Protection and Human Rights, 2015).

Figure 7.1 Sudan Unemployment Rates

Source: (www.macrotrends.net, n.d.)

Sudan has extremely high chronic unemployment rates. The World Bank projected a 19.81% unemployment rate in 2020 (statistically speaking, not as high as one would imagine compared to other countries). Ironically, low unemployment rates can conceal significant poverty in a country, whereas high unemployment rates can occur in countries with high economic development and low poverty rates. In countries like Sudan, where unemployment or welfare benefits do not exist, people make a living in volatile employment. Workers in developed countries can afford to wait for suitable or desirable jobs; nevertheless, a high and persistent unemployment rate points to severe inefficiencies in the distribution of resources (Worldbank.org, 2019). The youth unemployment rate in Sudan remained around 35.62 per cent in 2021, with no significant changes from the previous year (Statista, n.d.).

“There are no social protections for unemployment because the country lacks financial capability, and unemployment rates are extremely high throughout the country. National Employment Policy (which is currently drafted). In Sudan, we have the National Social Security... National Pension Plans... Health Insurance-Unfortunately, none of these are feasible in light of the needs. Due to high inflation rates and the devaluation of the Sudanese pound, you end up with a pension rate that is far below the basic minimum wage. A pensioner will pay his or her entire monthly pension for transportation to collect his or her money” (Participant Four-LME)

Understanding Sudan’s youth unemployment is critical because the country has an extremely young population, with a median age of 18.9 as of 2015, and 61.5% of the population is

under the age of 25 (CHALLENGE FUND FOR YOUTH EMPLOYMENT Sudan Scoping Report, 2021). Hafiz Ismail, an economist and former banker, claimed in an interview with Radio Dabanga that the unemployment rate among young people and recent graduates in Sudan has been between 80-90% over the past ten years! Ismail attributed the country's massive unemployment among youths and graduates to the country's recent economic crisis, as well as the former regime's educational and employment policies based on "empowerment" or "Tamkin", a term that the overthrown government of Omar Al Bashir endorsed its followers by awarding them far-reaching privileges, such as jobs in government functions and big businesses set up by high-level associates.

According to Ismail, most Sudanese graduates do not find employment in the private or public sectors. Many end up working in construction, blacksmithing, or driving rickshaws and minibuses. He estimated that the federal Employment Committee and its state branches employ less than 1% of all university graduates (Radio Dabanga, n.d.). Based on the responses of participants Five, Six, Seven, & Eight, there is absolutely nothing on unemployment support. A government responsibility that does not exist in Sudan, and no one even mentions, "Participant Eight-HEH" sarcastically mentioned that if protection for workers does not exist, how on earth would it exist for non-workers? Of course, this is not possible for a country like Sudan, which is currently experiencing economic challenges and constraints, and one would doubt it could act soon.

The only active social protection for working people is the previously discussed pensions & social insurance, and it does not cover workers if they lose their jobs unless they have earned their pensions through years of contributions (other than a lump sum payment that does not provide a safety net). Participant Seven-AAB wonders where the social protection is in a government that takes your hard-earned money for decades and then gives a pensioner less than a dollar per month (SDG 500) in times of vulnerability and utmost need, calling this "institutionalised injustice" and continues by stating that it seems as though the government is working against the general population.

Finally, a summary of this tragedy Participant Six-MAK stated the following words below, which the researcher believes is an overstatement: Many people care; all those the researcher interviewed do care and beyond; some genuine people want to make a difference but always seem to hit a brick wall when they try:

“By the way, no one cares, and if we searched the entire county for two people who did care, only two people who shared our concern...you and I might be the only two, and we might not find another!” (Participant Six-MAK)

7.10. Workplace Boundaries: “Bullying and Harassment”

“Bullying” and “Harassment” are frequently used interchangeably (CIPD, 2022), two forms of brutality and injustice that are constantly struggled, resisted and escaped in the workplace. However, *Harassment* is defined as “unwanted conduct related to a relevant protected characteristic, with the purpose or effect of violating an individual’s dignity or creating an intimidating, hostile, degrading, humiliating, or offensive environment for that individual” in the British Equality Act of 2010. ACAS, 2021 defined *bullying* as “offensive, intimidating, malicious, or insulting behaviour, an abuse or misuse of power through means that undermine, humiliate, denigrate, or injure the recipient”.

It can take many forms and shades, have multiple causes on multiple levels, and differing perspectives on its very nature (Agervold, 2007). However, at its most basic, it refers to the systematic mistreatment of an employee, a colleague, or a superior, which, if sustained and long-term, can result in severe social, psychological, and psychosomatic problems in the target. Exposure to such treatment has been stated to be a more crippling and devastating problem for employees than all other types of work-related stress combined, and it is viewed as a severe type of social stress at work or even a traumatic event by many researchers and targets alike (Einarsen *et al.*, 2010).

Harassment and bullying are entirely unaddressed in the Act of 1997 or any other legislation in Sudan, according to every single participant interviewed (unanimously); nothing is covering these behaviours...no clauses at all. According to “Participant Five-SEI”, sexual harassment was taboo at the time this act was created... no one even talked about it. Furthermore, it was scarce and almost non-existent in the workplace and society, so there was no need to address it then.

Furthermore, Bullying and harassment are two words that do not exist in the Arabic dictionary and have only recently been coined (new terms). There are no preventive measures; the only thing that can happen is that people will act or try to solve the problem when it occurs, not before. And if it occurs, it may be limited to physical assault and nothing else. Bullying and harassment are not legally recognized!

However, Participant Five states that change is unavoidable, and people require vivid, transparent regulations to regulate workplace behaviours safely. Because these practices do exist today despite the upbringing and culture of most of the population, decision-makers must hence stop relying on what the culture dictates and instead take all necessary precautions to prevent these unwelcome behaviours in the workplace through clear policies and effective enforcement and zero tolerance for any form of such behaviour.

“Harassment” and “Bullying”- Nothing in the law prohibits any of these... The problem is that none of the parties are aware of these issues; those in charge of labour policies, those in charge of organisations, and even the workers and employees who need to be protected are unaware of them!! As a result, we are significantly behind in these areas” (Participant Two-MZK)

According to Participant Eight-HEH, the labour law gave the employer the right to terminate the employment contract if the worker or employee committed a moral crime that touched someone’s dignity and honour on particular occasions; the only problem is that Article links this to court conviction (there must be a police case first) and considers the incident a criminal case. This route or course of action involves various issues and complications that victims usually avoid and avoid acting. It breaches confidentiality and harms reputation (especially for women). It also necessitates witnesses from the workplace (which is difficult to obtain) and, of course, requires solid evidence.

Unfortunately, because the system and law do not provide clear, targeted protection, most victims prefer to leave the workplace and avoid acting to protect their reputations and themselves. As explained by Participant Eight, once again, when the law was written in 1997, this was not an issue back then; however, over the last 25 years, there has been a gradual decline in moral standards and ethical behaviours, and it is now clear that people need to investigate this area more deeply. Previously, if someone had committed such a violation, that person would be too ashamed to stay on the job.

“You cannot end a work relationship if an employee was evidently proved to have committed a violation such as sexual harassment. As an employer I do not have the right to terminate this employment...the process is very tedious and impractical (note: Sexual Harassment is not mentioned specifically in the Act as a standalone violation but can be implied (as it requires a court condemnation and very long processes); the employer is not empowered to take an action in this issue. So if he or she decides to terminate the contract it would be considered in the eyes of law “Unlawful Termination” that must be compensated!” (Participant Eight-HEH)

According to Participant Three-MOS, some local businesses have become aware of these issues in recent years and have begun to make a difference by developing internal policies that address these areas. The Participant has observed and recognised that there are tiny minorities who fully comprehend the true meaning of such behaviours and their impact on workers (such as multinational companies). Unfortunately, most people who are supposed to create policies to protect the vulnerable from such injustices cannot comprehend the value of doing so! They are simply ticking boxes but are not convinced themselves. As a result, my interviewee believes that Sudan lacks the necessary culture and awareness to support driving workplace boundaries.

“There is absolutely nothing! I have worked in this field for many years; the law does not cover anything in this area, so we had to rely on our own internal policies to govern these areas; for example, Shell relied heavily on their own internal policies” (Participant One-EOS)

Furthermore, *Sexual Harassment* is not taken seriously, and women lack trust in the internal systems because they understand they do not protect them and frequently judge them when they are victims following Participant Three-MOS’s description. As a result, they do not complain when terrible things happen to them or when things go wrong, preferring to maintain a low profile instead. They will be judged most of the time, and sometimes by those who are supposed to protect them and look after their well-being.

“Sexual harassment has no basis for complaints or reporting because it is not supported by any regulation; as a result, women do not complain when they suffer; instead, they just keep it to themselves. Furthermore, they are terrified of the community and how they are perceived; as the community is not just in such circumstances and usually blames the women for any incident, and most would argue that she had it coming or in some way encouraged such behaviour (extreme inequality and injustice); whether intentionally or unintentionally, as a woman you are always viewed as part of the problem” (Participant Five-SEI).

In addition, Participant Three-MOS disclosed that once was asked by a reputable consultant representing a reputable company that wants to develop an internal sexual harassment policy; the strange thing is that in their briefing, they mentioned that they do not want to make it clear that it was a sexual harassment policy; they want the policy but do not want the women who work for the company to understand what it exemplifies! This was one of the awkward practices that leading companies might want to engage in. Transparency is lacking in such

vital matters. Participant Three-MOS continues, and in terms of **bullying**, the approach and precedence are very informal!

“Regarding bullying things take a very informal approach and precedence and a very serious issue is taken very lightly casually with a light sprit of joking, mocking and with huge informality that usually dilutes the essence of the problem losing its significance; as if this is just a normal behaviour that should not be even taken into consideration and sometimes the people involved make you feel you are making a big fuss out of nothing” (Participant Three-MOS)

According to Participant One-EOS, women cannot complain because there are no channels for filing claims or reporting wrongdoing (whistleblowing). Since there are no guidelines, boundaries, or regulations, things happen and pass by. Furthermore, Sudan has recently witnessed new manifestations of aggression and violence in addition to all the above. Sudanese doctors were beaten by police after responding to the pandemic during the Covid-19 crisis.

The medical staff has complained that plainclothes and uniformed police officers have repeatedly attacked doctors while they were carrying out their duties. Some doctors have gone on strike after being assaulted by officers while trying to do their jobs (Middle East Eye, n.d.). Having the laws in place provides security and will undoubtedly alleviate much distress. Unfortunately, according to Participant Six-MAK, this area is lacking, and there is a significant gap in Sudanese legislation that is far from being filled.

“Bullying and harassment are not currently covered by the 1997 Act. This was one of the disagreements that occurred between members of the tripartite committee in the new proposal (2018 proposal); they never reached an agreement on this point” (Participant Six-MAK)

Sudan must develop trusted and reliable channels, allowing victims to channel their concerns and receive the protection and justice they need. The ILO has recognised the importance of eliminating violence and harassment in the workplace and has established new global standards aimed at ending workplace violence and harassment. The ***ILO’s Convention No. 90*** is the first international treaty to recognise everyone’s right to a workplace free of violence and harassment, including gender-based violence and harassment. ILO Conference adopted the Convention in June 2019 and entered into force on June 25, 2021. Governments that ratify it will be required to implement the necessary laws and policy measures to prevent

and address workplace violence and harassment. The Convention represents a once-in-a-generation chance to shape a future of work based on dignity and respect for all.

7.11. Equality, Diversity and Inclusion (EDI)

Equality of opportunity and treatment is a fundamental social justice principle at the heart of the ILO's work since its early development in 1919. Equality means equal access, treatment, outcomes, and impact on employment and service delivery. The Equality Act of 2010 in the UK emphasises every person must have an equal opportunity to make the most of their lives and talents; it is based on principles of justice and fairness and upholds them. It is also the belief that no one should be denied equal opportunities because of their background, personal identity, or experience (CIPD, 2022). Differences in colour, ethnicity, abilities, age, gender, beliefs, interests, socioeconomic (class), marital or partnership status, sexual orientation, geographic, academic/professional backgrounds, opinions, backgrounds, thinking, experiences, and many other characteristics are referred to as **Diversity** by the (CIPD, 2022).

Having a diverse organisation is frequently a goal to strive for. According to the (ILO, 2021) interpretation, diversity improves organisational performance or is an end goal motivated by equity concerns. The workforce in companies and other organisations is expected to reflect society, either because doing so is believed to be essential for boosting profits, or because it is *fair* that everyone should have access to equal opportunities and employment or for both reasons. It is occasionally stated that the business case for diversity should not be confused with the moral case or equity considerations. Whereas the latter is frequently linked to laws against discrimination and equal employment opportunities or the legal framework, the business case is typically connected to the management of diversity by businesses. It suggests benefits that impact their performance. However, as (Monks, 2007) notes, **legislation strongly influences how diversity is handled.**

Inclusion is the practice of including people in a way that is fair to all, respects everyone's differences, and empowers and enables everyone to be themselves, achieve their full potential, and thrive at work. An inclusive workplace culture is one in which all employees feel valued and safe in being themselves, that their contributions matter, that policies and practices are fair, and that diverse individuals are encouraged to collaborate successfully (CIPD, 2022). Centuries of human rights movements and decades of political, demographic, and social change have fuelled the agenda for workplace EDI. During this long period of

transformation, traditionally excluded and marginalised groups gained significant access to previously barred fields such as education and employment.

These positive changes in access to learning and work in many industrialised countries have led recent generations of young women and men to believe that equality of opportunity has been mostly achieved. As a result, batches of students in higher education believe that their job and employment prospects are free of bias and prejudice. Some even regard conversations of inequality and discrimination as irrelevant to their future careers. Much of the time, this is not the case. Despite a long history of progress toward EDI at work, people continue to face multiple forms of inequality, discrimination, and exclusion throughout their lives (Özbilgin, *et al.*, 2009). This, of course, is tremendously magnified in countries like Sudan.

“Everyone who has worked in Sudan knows that there is a lot of disparity between different groups of people, from different regions and ethnicities in Sudan; the law does not have anything on that does not mention anything to protect marginalised groups, minorities, or people with disabilities in any way”. Women and children are the only two groups that are specifically mentioned or touched on in the legislation (in general terms), leaving out all other groups” (Participant One-EOS)

The researcher is interested in determining the extent to which Sudanese Labour Laws regulate inequalities and vulnerabilities and how they govern the workplace regarding discrimination and inconveniences that Sudanese workers face.

“Unfortunately, the Labour Act of 1997 says nothing about any of this; not one single article on : discrimination, inequality in recruitment (equal opportunities), the rights of disabled people, people with special needs and gender balance in the work place (quotas)” (Participant Seven-AAB)

According to Participant Seven-AAB, discrimination may not be blatant, but it is widespread in Sudan, both officially and off the record. Significant racial discrimination exists in the workplace that may be hidden. For example, in recruitment, interview questions highlight discrimination based on gender, age, family background, colour, and religion all the time. There is no gender balance in the workplace, and women face discrimination when it comes to pregnancy and maternity rights. Certain ethnic minorities are treated as second-class citizens and with contempt. In addition, certain tribes/minorities are not recruited at all or are only given minor jobs and never senior positions, effectively denying certain racial groups or tribes fair representation and equal employment opportunities.

Participant One-EOS clarifies that freedom of belief and expression is somewhat restricted, tribal and racial discrimination is widespread, and nepotism and favouritism are also common and well-established in most organisations. Furthermore, gender and sexuality, which are not socially acceptable for religious and cultural reasons, are by default off the agenda.

“There is nothing to protect the Sudanese workplace from high levels of inequality, discrimination, and social injustice; and we must work on incorporating these areas as well as promoting diversity and inclusion matters” (Participant Four-LME)

Racism is prevalent in Sudan, according to Participant Five-SEI, and the Labour Act contains no provisions to protect workers and employees in this regard, leaving a significant gap. Fair representation, equality, and diversity are lacking in law; the participant tells the researcher that we must develop them in the new act promoting these principles and values. Firstly, there is no employment opportunity, which is quite a fundamental issue! And the Act does nothing to encourage this. People with disabilities and vulnerabilities are disproportionately affected, as they require nearly invisible opportunities! There are no equal opportunities or equality acts to accompany the Labour Act. There are cultural issues that the act does not address, such as opportunities for women in senior positions and promotion; there is nothing specific to address these inequalities, if any exist (gender inequalities).

“Diversity, equal opportunities, and gender representation are not supported or covered by Sudanese labour law (nothing is stated in this perspective and there are no mechanisms to protect these standpoints). Even today, a large number of organisations openly advertise for ordinary jobs that do not require any sort of positive discrimination, requesting “Male Only” applicants for positions that a female is perfectly capable of commissioning just as well, if not better! I believe it is a problem of no rules, no measures, and no consequences, rather than a lack of knowledge of best practises (nothing happens as there are no retrospective actions). Diversity and equality should be explicitly stated, protected, and governing mechanisms put in place. And there are numerous other issues of inequality that require immediate attention” (Participant Three-MOS)

Participant Six-MAK strongly believes that there is a considerable level of inequality and a long list of marginalised groups, both male and female, who do the same work but are paid differently. Sudanese women face twofold restrictions. They not only experience barriers to employment, where only a few professions are deemed appropriate for women, but also discrimination in the labour market (Tønnessen, 2019). These limitations originate from

gender stereotypes, which are based on a conception of gender disparity in which physical differences between men and women are assumed to translate into variances in their social and intellectual capabilities (Hale, 1997).

Tønnessen, 2019 described these constraints as crucial realities in the labour law that limit women's access to employment. While it is true that the Islamist administration assured women equal rights to work and pay, many other government laws severely limit women's economic agency, access, and practice. The legal and regulatory environment is contradictory; it recognises women's constitutional right to equal pay while also granting male guardians the power to approve or deny work for female family members under the Muslim Family Law of 1991.

The Sudanese Labour Law 1997 imposes two significant restrictions on women's employment. First, women are forbidden from performing hazardous work that requires physical exertion and could harm their health. This includes any work that exposes women to toxic materials or high temperatures. Second, with few exceptions, women are not permitted to work between 10 p.m. and 6 a.m., except for office jobs in public or private organisations or the health sector (nurses, doctors). These legal restrictions significantly impact women working in the informal sector, for example, selling food and drinks in public places at night (issuu.com).

To sum up, Participant Seven-AAB summarised below some missing gaps, i.e. essential protections that need to be covered, as follows:

- *Diversity and Inclusion Supported by the Legislation*
 - *Right for Decent Treatment without Bullying or Harassment of any kind.*
 - *Equal Treatment without Discrimination and Biases of any kind*
 - *Gender balance in the work place (quotas)*
 - *Right for Equality*
 - *Harassment & Sexual Harassment Act*
 - *Discrimination Laws Act*
 - *Disability Protection Act*
 - *Equal Opportunities in Employment*
- The Law does not protect any of the above! (Participant Seven-AAB)***

Nonetheless, Participant Eight-HEH informs the researcher that he has never faced any form of discrimination on a personal level. Even though the Act did not contain any articles specifically addressing inequality and discrimination, they are supposedly implied in some

articles. It states that the law is written to suggest that all issues will be dealt with fairly and equally. However, problems may arise during the implementation process. In addition, the Labour office/s is not monitoring and inspecting organisations to ensure that none of this happens.

7.12.1. Gender Equality and Culture Issues

Participant Five-SEI believes that Sudanese laws are meaningful because they speak to the culture, religion, and society, and this should be credited. Sudanese labour laws incorporate laws unique to society and culture that address the needs of women, such as the four-month and ten days fully paid Mourning leave granted to women following the death of their husbands (a grieving period) following Islamic rituals. In addition to maternity leave, women are entitled to one hour off per working day for the first 24 months after giving birth to breastfeed their newborn child.

All organisations allow mothers to choose when they take that hour during the day. Participant Five believes these flexibilities and other options make the Act progressive regarding women's rights compared to international practices. And the ability to accommodate women's needs is a sophistication that must be celebrated.

“There are distinct practises endorsed by the Sudanese labour act that will surprise people in the West; they go far beyond for example: Mourning Leave for four months and ten days; Maternity & Pregnancy Leave; and 1 hour off every working day after birth for 24-month (for child breastfeeding). In addition to the right to refuse overtime hours and the Right not to work at night” (Participant Five-SEI)

Furthermore, the participant emphasises that Sudanese labour law does not discriminate against women based on religion; for example, Christian working widows who are not required by religion to be confined to their homes after the death of their husbands are equally granted the whole four months and ten days fully paid leave as a better condition with all of its privileges without prejudice or discrimination of any kind.

This is another instance where credit must be given to the Act. Nevertheless, Participant Six emphasises that, despite all of this, women continue to face discrimination in the workplace; they are discriminated against in recruitment based on gender because of their maternity rights. And because of the above leaves, organisations prefer hiring men.

“There is no gender equality or balance; employers fail to accept women’s rights to special leave such as maternity leave, and other benefits and are hesitant to pay for women’s rights; as a result, they avoid recruiting women in the first place!” (Participant Six-MAK)

The issue of maternity leave appears to be a predicament for recruiters in Sudan, although it is well established. Moreover, it is sadly overlooked from the father’s perspective, and men are discriminated against because they have no right to claim paternal leave under the current Act, as explained by Participant Seven. Denying someone’s privileges, opportunities, or rights because of their gender is known as gender discrimination (Abbas *et al.*, 2021).

“Men are not given the same consideration during maternity and prenatal leaves as women” (Participant Seven-AAB)

Based on the responses of all participants, the author concluded that there is insufficient gender balance in Sudanese workplaces. Further, the opportunities for women in senior positions are minimal. The researcher recognises that the law neither addresses these imbalances nor advocates for women to break through the glass ceiling with quotas or measures.

“There are cultural issues that that act does not address things like opportunity, for example. The opportunities for women in senior jobs, and promotion, there is nothing specific to tackle these inequalities if any (gender inequalities)” (Participant Five-SEI)

The glass ceiling phenomenon restricts women’s advancement to top positions in organisations, according to Farhat Abbas, Nargis Abbas and Uzma Ashiq (2021). Even in today’s advanced business world, the glass ceiling is widespread in the workplace, and women face numerous career barriers because of its effects. The metaphor “glass ceiling” was created in 1978 by management consultant, author, and diversity activist Marilyn Loden in her famous speech to define the invisible barrier that prevents women from pursuing career progression and growth. It’s a form of discrimination that keeps even the most qualified and experienced women from taking advantage of new prospects (Waters, 2022). Bryant (1984) later used it in her book “The Working Women’s Report” 1984. The author analysed the phenomenon of the glass ceiling as an inaccessible roadblock that keeps women out of senior leadership roles in any organisation.

According to McDonald and Hite (1998), only two women worked as chief executives in 1000 companies, accounting for 0.2% of those in positions of power. Despite the massive efforts over the last three decades to bring more women to the executive table, women continue to lag behind men. There is a variety of reasons for this, which vary by culture. The good news is that a significant global effort is underway to bridge this gap.

The action plan for women on boards was boosted in June 2022 when the EU passed a bill establishing quotas for women on boards. By the middle of 2026, listed firms in all twenty-seven European countries must have 40% female representation on boards or 33% of executive and non-executive positions. The legislation represents an optimistic commitment to fostering gender leadership in Europe’s top companies. Setting specific timeframes for goals is a firm commitment, and we know what gets measured gets accomplished (Forbes, 2019).

Figure 7.2 Changes in the Proportion of Women in Senior Management Across Regions (Five-year view)

Source: (Thornton, 2021)

The proportion of women in senior management roles in Sudan is not precisely quantifiable; however, Grant Thornton data collected in the years leading up to 2022 can be used as an indicator. According to the data, Africa is consistently one of the best-performing regions for female leadership and has maintained its upward trend. The region’s figures have improved

significantly over the past six reporting cycles, rising from 29% in 2017 to 39% in 2021 and 40% in 2022. Africa continues to be a success story for female leaders, with 40% of overall senior roles held by women, far exceeding the global average (Thornton, 2022).

Figure 7.3 Regional Proportion of Leadership Roles Held by Women in 2022

Source: (Thornton, 2021)

Culturally, women in Sudan are well respected in the workplace, according to Participant Five-SEI and EOS. They broke down barriers in the workplace a long time ago, and since independence, they have had equal education opportunities; becoming judges, doctors, and ministers, they dominated all sectors and excelled. They are well-educated, qualified for all jobs, refined at a young age and empowered to compete successfully with men. SEI believes that because of this, it may not have been necessary to explicitly mention gender representation in labour regulations when the act was initially developed in the 1960s when Sudanese women were already members of parliament and had a strong voice in the community.

“In Sudan, there are huge inequalities between working people; this is a widely seen and felt issue, particularly racial discrimination, which is widespread. In comparison to other countries, one thing that stands out is the small or nonexistent pay gap between male and female workers/employees doing the same job (for example Canada & the US). This, I believe, is a significant issue that stems from the Sudanese cultural framework and composition, in which there is little distinction between men and women in employment” (Participant One-EOS)

However, the participant believes it is necessary to address this issue now to strengthen and improve the laws, even if there was no pressing need for them to do so in the past, adamant that the document should be comprehensive enough to reflect the culture and best practices and be documented and governed. The best practice is well-tailored to the people's heritage, cultural needs, and requirements.

“The Sudanese culture itself did not require much work in the area as by nature the culture has addressed this issue very well throughout history. Sudanese women proved themselves in the workplace, they broke barriers a very long time ago, and since the independence, they had equal chances for education they became judges, doctors, and ministers. If there was no pressing need then for the laws to focus on or tackle this area maybe by nature; nevertheless, I believe it does need to be addressed now to strengthen and enhance it (Participant Five-SEI)”

Still, male dominance in senior leadership and decision-making positions is prevalent in Sudanese culture, as it is throughout the world (Titkow, 2010). There is no denying that Sudan is a “male-dominating society” despite all this, and it is argued that a culture of male dominance is one of the main factors to blame for the lack of women in senior leadership positions in organisations (Longman and Lafreniere, 2011).

(Al-Manasra, 2013) conducted a study to investigate the effect of glass ceiling barriers on women's career advancement in Jordan and reported that male executives in the workplace prefer male employees for senior managerial positions over female employees because they believe men perform better than women! Sudanese female managers are frequently confronted with organisational circumstances favouring male employees over them, and they struggle to find a way to fit within these male-oriented contexts (Kargwell, 2008).

Women in Sudan are not just held back by men in the workplace but also by men at home because of the double-workload dilemma and conflicting roles of family and professional responsibilities. This is a significant setback for Sudanese women as the majority opt to sacrifice their careers, giving priority to motherhood, raising their youngsters, and looking after families. Most surrender despite the recognized support working moms receives from their extended families. The problem is that men and women don't rightfully share the burden at home, and women carry both loads if they elect to progress in the workplace. The impact of the interplay between family and work helps create the “glass ceiling” that Sudanese

women managers must overcome, resulting in their underrepresentation at the executive level (Kargwell, 2008).

7.13. The Employment Contract

Employment flexibility has become a management slogan, and there is evidence that different forms of employment flexibility have become more prevalent in advanced industrial societies in recent years. Although many types of employment flexibility exist, contract flexibility seems particularly appealing to organisations (Guest, 2004). In most developed economies over the past years, downsizing, new employment trends, and new corporate groupings have all become vital work-life features. Nonstandard work contracts have been on the rise worldwide, i.e., contracts deviate from the standard contract form, which is full-time, permanent, and relatively secure. These characteristics have been referred to as the standard norm, as opposed to nonstandard employment, commonly perceived as part-time or temporary (Aronsson, 2001).

This entails using fixed-term or temporary contract arrangements to employ a substantial part of the workforce. There seem to be advantages in quickly adjusting the workforce size as the demand for the company's goods or services changes (Guest, 2004). Von Hippel *et al.* (1997) summed up the advantages for organisations in terms of cost savings, increased flexibility, and avoidance of restrictions. Matusik and Hill (1998) emphasised the importance of contingent workers as a source of intellectual capital within organisations. Participant Five-SEI informed the researcher that employment contracts are a massive problem in Sudan! The Sudanese Labour Law of 1997 does not allow room for this kind of flexibility compared to other countries, making it difficult for employers to balance their workforce requirements.

Lack of contract flexibility is a very serious problem! There are only a few contract and employment options. In a way that does not serve the community's or employers' economic needs. It is inadequate in this regard, and I consider it a major flaw (the types of contracts and types of employment and the flexibility required). Life in Sudan has changed dramatically in recent years, as have employment requirements; however, the types of contracts supported by the labour act do not meet this critical need (Participant Five-SEI)

Participant Eight-HEH further elaborated that the practical application of the 97 Act over the last 25 years has demonstrated that it is currently inadequate for meeting business needs. That is evident from his experience with all the non-governmental organisations he was involved

in. The law does not meet these organisations' needs and expectations, especially regarding the employment relationship and the required types of contracts.

Given the nature of their operations and the resources they employ globally, the Act does not support the contracts they typically need; hence, the struggle occurs. This has also affected their financial capacity and budgets. Other large private-sector companies and organisations also criticise the Act's inability to meet their needs and the massive injustice it holds, particularly in the employee-employer relationship, which is treated as a Catholic Marriage that cannot be broken unless very complex arrangements are made.

"From a contractual standpoint, the employer cannot find a way to create the type of relationship they desire. What I mean is that the 1997 act has created rigid and fixed standard moulds as a baseline for the relationship (contracts)...and the means mechanisms for ending this contractual relationship are insufficient, making the relationship very rigid" (Participant Eight-HEH)

Participant Six-MAK highlights that the nature of work has changed in the past few years, shifting from traditional work to other modern and more flexible ways. Despite the apparent necessity dictated by the labour market, Sudanese employment laws have not reflected that need. According to Participant Six, the tripartite committee recognised the need for part-time work and discussed and approved it for the anticipated 2016 proposal. Still, it did not appear in the 2018 draft!

The concept of working from home is not an option, nor is job rotation, and all other contemporary employment contracts and relationships are also missing! This was especially problematic following the pandemic, when these gaps were greatly exacerbated.

"So, without hesitation, I know that the current law, in its current state, does not meet all of our needs, and this was demonstrated even more after the Covid19 Pandemic, when we as HR practitioners realized that there are no laws to support flexible work, such as working from home, online work engagements, and even part-time work. As a result, I can simply state that the labour law of 1997 does not support Sudan's current contemporary work environment" (Participant Five-SEI)

Moreover, Participant Three-MOS told the researcher that Part-time jobs are still not recognised by the 1997 law and that the act says nothing about them! For example, she once needed to hire a social insurance specialist to assist her in preparing new employee social insurance registrations and handling end-of-work claims; in fact, she did hire someone to come in once a week on a part-time basis. She was then surprised to receive a rejection letter

from the labour office for the position, stating that there is no such thing as a part-time employee and that anyone who comes to work is considered a full-time employee regardless of the setup, agreement or naming and is entitled to all of the same benefits of a full-time employee in terms of salary, annual leave, health insurance, and so on.

Of course, and following what Participant Three says, this places a significant burden on organisations and has numerous disadvantages, the most important of which is that it creates disparity and unfairness among employees by allowing part-time workers to receive the same benefits as full-time workers additionally, it discourages organisations from offering part-time jobs, thereby failing many people who are looking for flexible working conditions.

Furthermore, Outsourcing Services, although almost all businesses in Sudan nowadays seek to outsource, according to Participant Three-MOS, a variety of services and prefer to focus on their core business and strategic issues, the Sudanese labour law of 1997 does not recognise the idea of outsourcing business/workers. It does not support it in all ways. Being cynical, Participant Three claims that the law regards outsourcing as slavery or enslavement of workers! One cannot have employees working for them and outsourced somewhere else (unless one provides a service); otherwise, this will create a huge dilemma with the labour office and is one of the areas with no practical solutions with the current legislation because it is missing.

7.13.1. Contractual Manipulation: The Three-Month Probation Period!

According to Sudanese labour legislation, any contract lasting more than three months must be written and issued in three copies (employer/employee copy and a copy for the labour office) and made through the labour office:

“Any employment contract exceeding three months shall be put in writing by the employer. The contract of employment shall be drawn up in three copies and shall be signed by the two parties who shall keep a copy each, and the third copy shall be kept with the Employment Agency or Labour Office”

(Article 28-Labor Act 1997)

Unfortunately, according to Participant Eight-HEH, these procedures are not being implemented as effectively as they should and are missing from day-to-day operations. The labour office’s missing role, no copies are sent there, and no regular reviews of contracts are performed unless a dispute arises; a process that should have occurred at the start of the relationship.”

“The labour act of 1997 has proven to fail the most vulnerable in our society,” says Participant Two-MZK, citing the three-month probation period as an example. The participant explained that employers abuse the probation period to recruit short-term workers for electricity projects, sugar farming, and seasonal jobs while violating their rights. According to the **Probation Act**, both parties (employer and employee) can terminate the contract without legal obligations. Employers nationwide recruit those innocent workers for three months and then terminate their contracts, claiming they did not fulfil the job requirements and failed the probation period just a week before the three-month trial period ends.

And then, of course, the workers are released without any notice or compensation and replaced with new workers. After about two weeks, the same worker returns to the same employer, knowing that they will almost certainly be reinstated with a new contract and a new probation period, only to be fired before the end of the three months, and so on.

The same dilemma repeats itself with the same set of people for years at a time (using a one-year contract with a three-month probation period). In one case, the participant tells the researcher that he knows a specific company without naming names, and this practice continued for 18 years!

*“Many industries and manufacturing companies follow a horrible practice of three month hiring, firing (for one week or two), and rehiring (for another three month) and so on and so forth- and this continues for years – it is used to exploit the workers, confiscate, and exclude them from all deserved rights! This is what I call **Modern Day Slavery**” (Participant Seven-AAB)*

This is hard to believe: 18 years on a probation contract!! According to Participant Two-MZK, this worker later took this company to court; initially, the labour office/inspector officer did not consider this case; as the labour offices investigated the situation from a technical standpoint, and practically speaking, nothing was wrong, the company did follow the labour act and did nothing wrong! However, when the worker took his case to the Labour Court, the judge ruled in his favour and considered him a full-time worker for the 18 years this poor practice has been going on, and made the company compensate him for every year he spent doing this on and off service with them.

The difference between the labour office and the labour court, according to participant Two-MZK, is that the labour court investigates issues from a justice standpoint, which is much

deeper than the mere technical & blind application of the legislation. These companies exploit the law to increase their profits and revenues while making minor financial investments in human capital and incurring the slightest tax/social insurance burdens. The preceding practice resulted in the organisation's eventual downfall.

"It would be a shame if we did not have inclusive and actual representation (via the proper channels) in the workforce; and ended up presenting something that had little impact and did not serve its purpose (relevant stakeholder engagement). If it is not reflecting people's true needs, as we face rapid change (freelancing, entrepreneurship, part-timers, flexible work). Employees are now working three jobs at a time and all of this change must be reflected in the way our laws and policies are written" (Participant Four-LME)

7.14. Conclusion

The 1997 Act lacks clarity, consistency, and cohesion, leading to varying interpretations and situational judgments. Measures are absent from the equation, and there are no follow-ups, audits, checks, or reviews of the Labour Act implementation. The only KPI in place is the amount of money collected from fines and penalties, and government officials are rewarded by commissions and annual bonuses based on the volume of penalties they generate. The Minimum Wage Act of 1974 is one example of scattered legislation that could be well incorporated into a single act for clarity, consistency, and convenience. The foundation of the Sudan revolution was opposition to the minimum wage, causing the loss of innocent lives in the pursuit of a better Sudan, yet the minimum wage remains unresponsive. The gender pay gap is widely visible in all industries. Performance management is vaguely used as a criterion for annual salary increases without explicitly defining or establishing clear performance indicators.

Sudan's social protection system is inadequate and often non-existent. The 2016 National Pensions and Social Insurance Fund requires all public and private sector employees to have social insurance, which includes medical coverage. However, only about one-fifth of working people in the formal sector are registered with the Social Insurance Fund, and reduced basic pay rates, constant devaluation of the Sudanese Pound, and corrupt practices render the Social Insurance return worthless. Unemployed workers in the informal sector are excluded from social/health insurance coverage. The informal economy in Sudan was estimated to have been around 87% in 2011. The Sudanese Labour Act of 1997 does not protect independent workers outside the formal labour market. It excludes several occupations that unquestionably employ regular workers, such as agriculture workers, garbage collectors,

loaders, and bakers. Job opportunities are severely scarce, and people with disabilities and vulnerabilities are disproportionately affected.

The 1997 Sudanese Labour Act fails to promote equality, diversity, and inclusion (EDI), leaving workers facing disparities and discrimination in the workplace. The law does not explicitly advocate for fair representation, equality, or diversity. Discrimination is prevalent in the Sudanese workplace, both officially and unofficially, and it does not address the needs of women, such as addressing culture, religion, and society. Sexual harassment is a taboo subject that no one discusses, and there are no preventive measures in place. Sudanese labour laws address culture, religion, and society but do not explicitly advocate for fair representation, equality, or diversity. Women's rights are not adequately addressed, and they face gender discrimination in recruitment because of their maternity and pregnancy rights. The law does not address these imbalances or advocate for women to penetrate the glass ceiling through quotas or forced measures.

The employment relationship in Sudan is inadequate and does not meet the diverse business's needs. Part-time jobs are still not recognised by the 1997 Act, putting a significant burden on organisations and discouraging them from offering flexible working conditions. Working from home and remote work engagements is not a legitimately recognised option. This was especially problematic in the aftermath of the COVID-19 pandemic, when these gaps were significantly aggravated. The 1997 Act failed the most vulnerable of Sudanese society, as evidenced by the three-month probation period. Employers nationwide are manipulating the probation period to hire short-term workers for projects while violating their contractual rights. They follow the heinous practice of three-month "Hiring, Firing, & Rehiring," exploiting workers with no legal repercussions.

CHAPTER EIGHT: ANALYSIS & DISCUSSION THEME

III (Strategic Direction & Way Forward: Meeting the 21st Century Needs)

8.1. Introduction

In this chapter, you will find a detailed analysis and comprehensive discussion of the third theme, “Strategic Direction and Way Forward...*Meeting the Twenty-first Century Needs*”. In the table below, the third column consolidates eight subthemes in which the discussion evolves. The central theme of the discussion evolves around the fundamental principles and rights at work, best international standards, decent work and occupational safety and health in the workplace.

Table 8.1 Final Refined Themes & Subthemes III

<i>Theme One: Key Aspects and Features</i>	<i>Theme Two : Major Issues & Challenges</i>	<i>Theme Three: Strategic Direction & Way Forward (Meeting the Twenty-first Century Needs)</i>
A Historical Perspective	How well is the Act coping?	Fundamental Principles and Rights at Work
Private Sector Organizations: Application & Abidance	Lack of Clarity Consistency and Alignment	International Standards
The Practical Application	“What doesn’t get measured doesn’t get managed”	Protecting workers from Unacceptable Forms of Work
Organizational Compliance: Abidance and Inspection	Remuneration	A Decent Work Strategy
Government & Governance	Minimum Wage	Understanding & Measuring Decent Work
The Role of the State	Salary Breakdown, Overtime & Other Benefits	What effort is needed to establish decent work in Sudan?
A Ministry in Limbo	Social Protection (Safety Nets)	A Communication Strategy
The Tripartite Committee	National Pension and Social Insurance Fund	Occupational Safety and Health
Incompetence and Corruption	Beyond the Formal Sector	
Underdeveloped Reform	Protecting the Most Vulnerable	
The Labour Offices	Workplace Boundaries	
Role, Ability and Credibility	Equality Diversity and Inclusion	
Lack of Consistency and Flexibility	The Employment Contract	

Source: (Original)

8.2. Fundamental Principles and Rights at Work

According to the ILO, the International Labour Conference adopted the Declaration on *Fundamental Principles and Rights at Work* in June 1998. Over the next twenty-four years, it became a critical international labour standard benchmark. It contains the core principles ILO Member States are obligated to uphold under their membership, even if they have not ratified the ILO Conventions in which they are expressed. It expresses governments', employers', and workers' organisations' commitment to upholding fundamental human values - values critical to our social and economic lives.

When adopted, the Declaration covered freedom of association and the effective right to collective bargaining, the abolition of all forms of forced and compulsory labour, the effective abolition of child labour, and the abolition of employment and occupation discrimination.

<i>Freedom of association and the effective right to collective bargaining</i>
<i>The elimination of all forms of forced and compulsory labour</i>
<i>The effective abolition of child labour</i>
<i>The elimination of discrimination in respect of employment and occupation.</i>

The International Labour Conference then amended this Declaration on the 11th of June 2022 by adding a:

<i>A safe and healthy working environment</i>

As a fifth principle and right, this historic decision directly addresses all working women and men in all occupations and workplaces worldwide. The loss of life, accidents, and diseases caused by inadequate workplace safety and protection remains a dire reality in every country, from the poorest to the richest. The consequences in terms of lost or damaged lives, as well as the economic costs to businesses and the economy, are enormous.

Workplace health and safety is an ever-changing goal. While some progression is made, new occupational hazards emerge because of technological advancement or organisational change. Physical hazards can be aggravated by mental health issues, as well as workplace harassment and violence. Increased distance work and different types of labour contracts present new challenges for health and safety regulations and their implementation. Workplace safety and health are frequently jeopardised during economic downturns or health emergencies. The

COVID-19 pandemic has once again shown how closely intertwined a healthy and safe workplace is with clean air, water, and the preservation of a suitable living environment. A safe and healthy working environment proved essential to the pandemic response and long-term recovery (ILO Declaration on Fundamental Principles and Rights at Work and its Follow-up, 1998).

According to the ILO's global figures, the average pay gap between men and women is 23%, and in many nations, women are essentially barred from certain professions. Hundreds of millions of people face workplace discrimination because of their skin colour, ethnic background or social origin, religion or political opinions, age, gender, sexual identity, disability, or HIV status. 152 million children aged 5-17 are employed in child labour: 72 million are engaged in hazardous work and other forms of child labour, while 80 million are under the legal working age and are just too young to work. Millions of children, primarily girls, must perform intense household chores that prevent them from attending school. Forced labour affects 25 million individuals, 25% of whom are children. Furthermore, at least 15 million people, primarily women and girls, are subjected to forced marriage, which could amount to forced labour.

This cannot and must not be allowed to continue. Fundamental principles and rights at work are the foundation for establishing equitable and just societies. Neither the ILO's Decent Work Agenda nor the 2030 Sustainable Development Agenda can be realised unless implemented in law and practice. Over 40% of the world's population currently lives in nations that have not ratified either ILO Convention No. 87 on *freedom of association* or Convention No. 98 on *collective bargaining*, and even in many countries that have, these protections continue to be violated, both the law and in daily life (Integrated Strategy on Fundamental Principles and Rights at Work, 2017)

8.3. International Standards

Sudan has been a member of the ILO since its independence in 1956; it joined the international organisation on the 12th of June of that same year. Since then, it has ratified 18 of the 190 Conventions and one of the 6 Protocols. Sudan ratified 8 out of the 10 Fundamental Conventions, convention No. 87 on freedom of association being the most recent ratification, which took place on 17 Mar 2021.

*“The good news is that we have finally ratified the 1948 Convention on Freedom of Association and Protection of the Right to Organize (C087... (This should have happened at least 50 years ago!!!). And it takes precedence over everything else (one of the basic Human right principles). It went into effect about a year ago, and now the government can be held accountable if it violated the agreement, and sanctions can be imposed if it does... This was a fundamental requirement if we were to champion change and follow the revolution's slogans of **Freedom**. The first thing we had to ensure was that these freedoms were secured for people, and that in order to create transformation and reform in the sector, we needed to give them capacity and empower the various bodies, unions, and institutions that represent the people and advocate for freedom of association... These bodies were very weak (over 30 years of dictatorship had destabilized them; it was critical to get them back on their feet and assist them in fighting for the interests and rights of the people... A new law has been drafted but has not yet been approved; this law will cover the right to collective bargaining and will be incorporated into labour law in the future” (Participant Four-LME)*

The International Labour Organisation issued the Declaration of Fundamental Principles and Rights at Work in 1998, in which member nations pledged to observe and promote the ILO's conventions, which are legally binding international treaties (Flanagan and Gould, 2003). Sudan is one country that has pledged to do so. So, we can comfortably say that Sudan as a government is familiar with International Labour Standards and best practices in employment regulations. Most people (workers and employers) may not be as aware as they should be, but the government, which has the lead role in creating awareness, is not doing its job.

“By the way, all best practice international laws exist in Sudan (all these nice to have practices we read about); the problem is that these laws are not implemented; they are dormant! If I align all of the labour laws and employment regulations to comply with international laws and standards in a single package, the problem will be solved” (Participant Six-MAK)

The ILO communicated its groundbreaking five-year strategy (Fundamental Principles and Rights at Work Strategy 2017-2023). The researcher asked the participants where Sudan stands concerning this strategy and what efforts are being made to align Sudanese labour policies and practices in the right direction. Almost all the participants said they had no idea and had never heard of it. According to Participant Nine-RFU, fundamental principles and workplace rights do not exist in Sudan, and people do not even understand what they mean.

Participant Eight-HEH assures the researcher that Sudan is a member of the ILO and the ALO (Arab Labour Organisation) and that best practices are theoretically studied but not implemented. Participant Six also supports this argument that if we implement what we

know, the problem will almost certainly be solved. The problem, according to Participant Six, is that we leave these documents to gather dust and do not put what we know into practice.

“This strategy was approved in 2017 (I saw it and occasionally read it because it contains some interesting data); the document was then placed in one of the drawers and that was the end of it. Nobody in the ministry knows anything about it!”
(Participant Six-MAK)

According to the ILO, international labour standards are supported by an exclusive global oversight system to ensure that all countries implement their ratified conventions. The ILO regularly examines the implementation of standards in member countries and identifies areas where they could be improved. If there are any issues with standard implementation, the ILO seeks to assist countries through dialogue and technical assistance.

Following adopting Conventions and Recommendations by the International Labour Conference and ratification by countries, the ILO has established several methods for monitoring their deployment in laws and practice. The ILO follows two types of supervisory techniques:

- ***The Regular Supervision System:*** an examination of periodic reports submitted by Member Countries on the steps they have taken to incorporate the provisions of the ratified conventions.
- ***Special Procedures:*** a general representations and complaints procedure, as well as a special procedure for freedom of association

Like all other state members, Sudan is obliged by the association to send periodic reports to the ILO regularly. The Ministry of Labour is the primary custodian of this. The labour offices throughout the country are in direct contact with all organisations and businesses. As previously stated, there is no reporting link between the ministry and the Labour offices. According to Participant Four-LME, because the labour offices do not report to the ministry, they are slashed off from what is happening; they lack the necessary links, measures, and statistics to draw on.

Furthermore, there may be some instances of corruption that cannot be confirmed but are suspected. They recommended, in collaboration with the ILO, that the labour ministry be evaluated to see if it can carry out its core functions and meet the challenges and goals that have been set for it.

“I read all the reports the reports we send to the UN, they are all lies nothing is true! The reports are simply full of lies; a couple of people from the ministry of foreign affairs and the ministry of labour sit down, cook these reports and send them. Because the organizations that are supposed to fill out their data and return it are not involved in the first place, all of the data is forged” (Participant Six-MAK)

8.4. Protecting workers from Unacceptable Forms of Work

The ILO has defined unacceptable forms of work (UFW) as work in conditions that deny fundamental principles and rights at work, endanger workers’ lives, health, freedom, human dignity, and security, or keep households in poverty (ILO, 2013). This concept of UFW has emerged as a severe issue for the Organisation in the run-up to the ILO’s centennial. Whereas UFW is new in ILO discussions, the numerous and interconnected policy areas that address it are not. These include measures to promote freedom of association and the right to effective collective bargaining, the abolition of child labour and forced labour, the promotion of non-discrimination and equality, occupational safety and health measures and working time arrangements that protect workers’ health and safety, and well-structured minimum wage regulation coupled with effective wage protection measures that protect workers and their families (Fudge and McCann, 2017).

According to Participant Eight-HEH, there is no specific information on UFW in Sudan. The government has never mentioned it. The law speaks vaguely about **Health and Safety** issues in governing the working relationship, and the only solution it leaves the worker with is the right to terminate the contract if things go wrong, which may be a relief to the employer or something they welcome on some occasions, but there is no protection.

Participant Nine RFU expresses his dismay to the researcher at seeing unacceptable forms of work when employers expect employees to perform their jobs without the necessary tools. Workers don’t have the required safety protections and tools; they are welding and grinding with dangerous equipment, and they don’t have safety garments, gloves, goggles, earplugs, or safety shoes, as an example from Soba, one of his previous work locations. He was terrified to see drivers sitting under faulty trucks, risking their lives to change a flat tyre and frequently injuring themselves. When fatigued drivers drive for 14 hours straight without stopping, they are at risk of being killed. And when nothing happens, when they do get killed!

“Unacceptable forms of work are all over the place. Mine workers die every day for no reason; they have no health checks or health protections of any kind. Garbage collectors have nothing to worry about because they are completely ignored. Every day, you hear about work - related accidents. Some industries have some protections, while others, such as the petroleum and gas industries, have limited protections. In general, no laws are specified in the Act to cover these points” (Participant Six-MAK)

Participant Seven-AAB informs the researcher that the current problems are not being addressed and asks the researcher to imagine a large plant with 500 workers on one shift operating without a nurse or medical representative with first aid certification in the event of an emergency. Because of the ignorance of modern production techniques, there are many disputes in labour offices and courts today about different diseases and health issues. Many modern machines and equipment emit laser and atomic radiation, which they are unaware of, causing severe health problems. Factors like ultraviolet rays, prolonged computer use, screen sitting, and ergonomics are not taken into account in the laws regarding workplace injuries and protections. This also applies to the list of risks outlined in the 1997 Act, which includes outdated concerns like dust. The underprivileged workers usually pay the price and lose their protective rights.

“Frankly speaking, I would consider Sudan as one of the most prominent examples of a country in the world that implements 100% “Indecent work” (Participant Seven-AAB)

8.5. A Decent Work Strategy

At the turn of the millennium (ILO, 1999), the ILO suggested the concept of “Decent Work” (DW) and has since enhanced and refined it to become an operational goal for all. Since 1999, the ILO has tried to introduce and promote the concept of decent work, making it its sole focus and centre of attention:

“Opportunities for women and men to obtain decent and productive work in conditions of freedom, equity, security and human dignity”

(ILO, 1999, p. 3)

Decent work encapsulates people’s aspirations in their working lives, according to the (ILO, 2019). It entails opportunities for productive work that pays a fair wage, workplace security and social protection for all, improved opportunities for personal development and social integration, freedom for people to voice their concerns, organise and take an active part in

decisions that influence their lives, and equality of opportunity and treatment for all women and men. The ILO has created a work agenda for the community of work, with gender equality as a cross-cutting goal, and it examines social protection, social dialogue, rights at work, and, on top of all, job creation.

International policymakers have felt an increased urgency, particularly in the aftermath of the 2008 global financial and economic crisis, to provide quality jobs alongside social protection and respect for workers' rights to achieve sustainable, inclusive economic growth and eradicate poverty (ILO, 2019).

Decent Work is described in 11 substantive elements in its updated formulation, also recognised as the Decent Work Agenda (ILO, 2013). Each of the 11 substantive elements of decent work relates to the principles underlying the concept on the one hand and to a set of implications for practice at various levels of analysis and interpretation on the other.

Though these elements are highly interdependent, they can be individualised, as the ILO's indicators have been. Despite the detailed description of the decent work agenda, enhancing the concept and finding ways to promote it globally remains unfinished (Ferraro and Dos Santos, 2015).

Table 8.2 11 Substantive Elements Proposed in the Decent Work Agenda

Employment opportunities
Adequate earnings and productive work
Decent working time
Combining work, family and personal life
Work that should be abolished
Stability and security of work
Equal opportunity and treatment in employment
Safe work environment
Social security
Social dialogue, workers' and employers' representation
Economic and social context for decent work

Source: (ILO, 2013)

The new 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development was adopted during the UN General Assembly in September 2015, and it included decent work and the four core principles/pillars of the Decent Work Agenda: *employment creation, social protection, rights at work, and social dialogue*. Goal no. 8 of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development calls for

promoting sustained, inclusive, and sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment, and decent work. It will be a significant engagement area for the ILO and its stakeholders (ILO, 2019).

After the revolution, it was important for the transitional government in Sudan to demonstrate sincerity by revisiting all its laws, according to Participant Four-LME, to express its seriousness about bringing about the longed-for change resulting from the revolution. The interviewee tells the researcher that the Ministry of Labour was especially eager to achieve social justice and secure a life of dignity for all Sudanese people.

“We have started a good and active partnership with the ILO, and there is a good opportunity, if taken seriously in the next stage (after a bit of political stability), to make a difference in the issue of decent work... Most importantly, an effort must be made to focus on communication and awareness across the board in order to inform the people and create a common understanding of the concept of decent work, as well as to roll out information campaigns to raise awareness among Sudanese people” (Participant Four-LME)

According to Participant Four, the ILO has reviewed the decent work program strategy for Sudan because it is outdated. They (Ministry Officials) reviewed the decent work strategy and policy considering the rapid pace of change in Sudan, and the recommendation is that both be aligned with these changes. The participant emphasises that they pushed hard for the ILO to review it and were successful.

“...we did some good work in revisiting it. You could say it is there theoretically, but to be honest, we are not ready from a practical standpoint...We are a long way from it” (Participant Four-LME)

However, so many interconnected components should be in place for decent work policies to take effect, and other ministries should also be involved. The committee included many people from various disciplines, not just the labour ministry and a lot of other groundwork needs to be put in place to ensure success.

8.6. Understanding & Measuring Decent Work

Every person at work or looking for work, regardless of country, occupation, or skill level, knows what decency at work entails. Given the importance of work in terms of total time, social integration, and individual self-esteem, decent work is a fundamental dimension of life quality. Productive work is also the primary source of income for many people and the driving force behind long-term development (Mehran *et al.*, 2002). It is abundantly clear

from the respondents' arguments that working people in Sudan have drifted away from decent work. Most people certainly have no idea what it stands for.

"Unfortunately the concept of decent work does not exist to start with" (Participant Seven-AAB)

Participant Five-SEI argued that decency is subjective and that most Sudanese people struggle to meet their basic needs and cannot think about anything else (Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs). The people of Sudan are overwhelmed by the day-to-day struggles of feeding their families and survival and cannot think beyond these challenges. In contrast, other nations moved away from the day-to-day struggles of basic labour regulations, focusing on work-life balance, equality, diversity, and inclusion.

Participant Four-LME tells the researcher that a lot of work needs to be done to raise awareness and educate people about what decent work entails and what they are entitled to, such as having enough toilets in the workplace! And claims that the government is suffering from a lack of resources, telling the researcher that the ministry operates on a 20% overhead budget, essentially an unrealistic budget to manage and deliver what it should.

*"You are referring to something that doesn't exist in Sudan... It's not even on the table! These are international standards that Sudan does not have. If you mention **"decent work"**, you must put it in brackets and define it first. The problem is the level of understanding; most of those responsible for this do not even understand it. Before we do anything, we should first educate the people and raise awareness and understanding of the concept" (Participant Six-MAK)*

Everyone who participated in the discussion agreed that decent work is not well-established in the Sudanese labour market and is neither prioritised nor raised in any forum. The concept is discussed behind closed doors among decision-makers and only serves the purpose of filling out forms or presenting ILO reports. This is evident from the participants' feelings of isolation and disengagement in the subject matter with the labour ministry and the level of expertise the labour offices possess and represent.

The researcher then tried to determine whether the government had attempted to measure decent work. Still, the response was unanimously negative, which was not surprising given that the concept did not exist in the first place.

"Of course not! They are not measuring any type of work, let alone decent work!" (Participant Six-MAK)

Measurements are essential for monitoring and assessing where we are with what we need to achieve, and while this is not always easy, it should always be considered. Monitoring and measuring performance towards a decent work agenda is a top priority for ILO members. Yet, because of the concept's multifaceted nature, measuring it is pretty challenging. In light of this, the 2008 International Labour Conference passed the ILO Declaration on Social Justice for a Fair Globalisation, which urges member states to consider the development of appropriate indicators or statistical measures, if need be, with the assistance of the ILO, to monitor and evaluate progress made on "*decent work*"(www.ilo.org).

Using the ILO's recommended eleven indicators and sub-indicators is a good starting point, and these indicators can be customised to suit local requirements best. The ILO also recommends developing unique, relevant required domestic indicators and has demonstrated a willingness to extend its partnership and support.

8.7. What effort is needed to establish decent work in Sudan?

The participants recommended various means for establishing decent work in Sudan; they all had good ideas and strategies. However, most were conscious of the problems and what held Sudan back. According to Participant Five-SEI, Sudan's financial situation is severely damaged, as evidenced by the absent basics and vital necessities not being available even in service areas such as hospitals, schools, and transportation, let alone in other institutions, simply because the law does not enforce these issues and the economic situation does not permit it; thus, they become more like luxuries rather than necessities! So, asking someone at work to provide such a level of care appears to be a daft idea!

"Decency at work is part of the decency of the whole country and cannot be separated" (Participant Five-SEI)

Participant Seven-AAB and Participant One-EOS argued that a significant setback is the considerable level of worker ignorance about their rights and what they should receive from their employers regarding their work relationship. Furthermore, the government's failure to provide adequate support for increasing awareness and understanding of the laws and their interpretations exacerbates the situation. Without their knowledge, employers can easily abuse and exploit their employees.

The ministry does not utilise pamphlets, leaflets, sessions, or posters to promote awareness. The government (at the ministry level) must set an example and increase awareness to

strengthen this area. According to Participant One, the unfortunate thing is that there is no contact from the ministry. And sadly, the ministry's website contains nothing helpful for working people. Participant Six was very frank, expressing his predicament and unsure where to start.

I really don't know...To be honest, I don't have an answer to this question!
(Participant Six-MAK)

However, to establish decent work, Participant Seven-AAB argues that the country's labour laws must be transformed and modernised to address workers' needs and offer the protection they deserve rather than just focusing on the employers' needs. Participant One-EOS stressed that focusing on and promoting the minimum wage is a critical starting point as it dramatically determines. And she goes on to say that there needs to be a general cultural shift, particularly in the workplace.

Participant Eight recommends activating trade union roles in organisations to represent the workers, reflect on their troubles, protect their collective bargaining rights, and empower and strengthen the Labour Offices by providing them with the necessary capabilities, resources, and authority. To make a difference, Participant Seven-AAB recommends that Work & Labour Professionals of Sudan take matters into their own hands in collaboration with international organisations.

"Because the government's role is so limited, we recommend that people take action on their own to make a difference. Independent bodies can bring these issues to the ILO or ALO (Arab Labor Organization) and launch a movement highlighting the amount of abuse, discrimination, and struggle that working people in Sudan face! If there is a visible movement championed by Sudanese workers, international organisations can be very supportive and even impose sanctions" (Participant Seven-AAB)

8.8. A Communication Strategy

According to (Baguley, 1994), communication is the process by which ideas, information, and feelings are expressed between people or groups for clearly intentional purposes. It is not only about information transformation but also about the transition of feelings, opinions, needs, and observations. One significant issue surfaced during the conversation was the lack of communication and dialogue between the government and professional stakeholders across the country.

“...it would be a shame if we didn't have inclusive and actual representation (right channels) in the taskforce and ended up presenting something with very little impact and will not serve as it should (relevant stakeholder engagement)” (Participant Four-LME)

Almost all the candidates interviewed expressed frustration with the lack of involvement and engagement. Participant Eight-HEH tells the researcher that they, as specialists in the field, struggle with the lack of information and the communication gap. They express frustration at the significant efforts required to obtain crucial information that should be readily available.

“There is a lack of information (no communication at all you have to struggle to find it and it is not trusted.” (Participant Eight-HEH)

As hands-on legal experts in the field, they should be consulted and involved as they are aware of the issues and know the consequences of the decisions taken without diverse consultation, discussion, and effective dialogue. Communication is essential in any long-term plan or strategy, both internally and externally. People must express themselves internally to create strategies and applications for sustainable actions. After completing the internal function, expressing oneself outside the institution is essential. To clarify, to plan and promote effective and sustainable practices, people must express themselves internally and externally through appropriate modes of communication (Genç, 2017).

“The discussions are devoid of transparency and communication. There has been very little effort, and there has been no social dialogue” (Participant Six-MAK)

To enhance or develop the situation, Participant Four-LME suggests that the government broaden its scope of engagement and include more people in the dialogue. They must identify the stakeholders, whether they are engaging the appropriate people/stakeholders, whether everyone who needs to participate is involved, whether they genuinely have the relevant people on board, and whether they are listening to the appropriate people. Most importantly, efforts must be made to focus on communication and awareness to inform everyone, create a shared understanding and launch information campaigns to raise awareness among Sudanese people.

“We are the legal experts who should be consulted; we are never asked nor involved is (our input is missing). And we just wake up to decisions and are constantly surprised.we must create a dialogue among and between all intended stakeholders. Involve the Experts and broaden our social circle” (Participant Eight-HEH).

The participant, a former government official, believes this is important to ensure that decisions are made when updates are made. They truly honour and reflect what the people genuinely need, as Sudan faces rapid change and enormous challenges that require immediate attention and reinforcement. Freelancing, entrepreneurship, part-time workers, and flexible work are all examples of new working methods that lack backup legislation. Employees now work three jobs simultaneously, and all this change must be reflected in the Sudanese laws and policies.

8.9. Occupational Safety and Health

According to Participant Five-SEI, health and safety issues in Sudan are severely overlooked and not given the attention they deserve. Each participant expressed their resentment and deep frustration in the area. Participant Seven-AAB claims that Sudanese organisations have very poor Health & Safety systems; there is no industrial health & safety environment or facilities, and basic amenities such as adequate restrooms, ladies/ privacy rooms, and toilets are lacking.

Participant Six-MAK informed the researcher that while the act mentions safety, it does not say it sufficiently or is not supported by strict regulations. Some industries have some safeguards in place, while the majority have very few, and the tragedy is that they hear about workplace accidents every day.

“The Act mentions hazardous jobs, but nothing is done about it; it simply exists without any value or effectiveness for workers who work in dangerous and hazardous work environments. (Participant Six-MAK)

Participant One-EOS confirms and attributes the problem to outdated regulations incompatible with modern industrial needs. Contemporary health and safety issues such as computer screen protectors, ergonomic seating, and furniture, as well as how employees should protect their spine, are not included in the safety measures.

Furthermore, Participant Seven-AAB explains that workplace injuries have a stand-alone regulatory body based on a tabulated chart with a list of workplace injuries and

occupational hazards developed in 1981 and has never been updated since. It refers to a list of injuries caused by methods and techniques that no longer apply in any industrial site and do not meet modern industrial requirements.

The issue is that the courts have endorsed these charts as their only reference source. In addition, the Act has not addressed some critical environmental problems. Moreover, specific offices are meant to oversee “Industrial Safety” but are not responsible for providing any support or protection!

“Exposure to poisons and hazardous materials is mentioned, but in very outdated terms and guidelines that do not deal with or cover everything that is happening today (applicable to materials and techniques used and followed more than 25 years ago)” (Participant One-EOS)

Both participants, Four and Six, raised the issue of outsourcing-related safety matters. Most organisations outsource both the burden and the workforce. Unfortunately, the Act does not mention “outsourcing workers” or how the process works, its legality in terms of duration, or the necessary protections that must be in place because the law does not recognise them and doesn’t know who to blame for their misfortune. Outsourced workers are exploited, suffer from negligence, and have no rights under the Act.

“Many workers have unresolved claims of work incidents hanging in courts for years and some have even died before they reached any resolution” (Participant Six-MAK)

Participant Three-MOS suggests that health and safety issues be addressed in all workplaces, not just manufacturing (as they are now in the current Act), with clear measures and regular monitoring. Participant Nine-RFU explains that financial constraints are a significant factor in the neglect and that it all comes down to finances; if everyone is required to have personal protective equipment and health and safety measures are covered, it will be costly!! Because most private enterprises want to make money at the end of the day and make maximum profits, they don’t want to spend money even if the law requires it.

And they don’t because there is no accountability and no consequences. Workers in Sudan are exposed and exploited as employers fail to provide them with the necessary personal protective equipment. Nothing will happen without education (practical training and development) and someone to enforce the laws. “Health and Safety” are vital,” says Participant Four-LME, and gives the researcher an example of a recent disaster following a

fire explosion in a ceramic manufacturing plant. According to state news agency SUNA, at least 23 people were killed, and over 130 were injured in Sudan in December 2019 after a fire triggered by an explosion at a factory in northern Khartoum. The incident occurred when a gas tanker unloaded a shipment at a ceramics production plant in the city's industrial district (suna-sd.net, n.d.).

These workplace accidents could have been avoided if occupational safety measures had been implemented. The problem in Sudan is that workers are not taken care of, there is no social security, and compensation is unimaginably low if something goes wrong! A worker can lose a limb without repercussions, and penalties are pitiful (and have not been updated in years), negatively impacting the country. "Social protection and insurance require massive work," Participant Four-LME explains.

The ILO Constitution establishes the principle that workers must be guarded against work-related illness, disease, and injury. Nonetheless, the reality for millions of workers, including Sudan, is quite different. Globally, 2.78 million work-related deaths are reported each year, of which 2.4 million are attributed to occupational diseases, per the most recent ILO figures. This, apart from the immense suffering experienced by workers and their families, the corresponding economic costs for businesses, economies, and the entire globe are enormous.

Around 3.94% of the annual global GDP is lost in compensation, missed workdays, disrupted production, training and reconversion costs, and medical expenses. Businesses must also deal with expensive early retirements, losing qualified workers, absenteeism, and high insurance premiums. However, these disturbances can be avoidable by implementing sound preventative measures, reporting, and inspection practices. The ILO standards on occupational safety and health are vital for governments, employers, and workers to develop such policies and practices to ensure optimum workplace health and safety (ILO, 2019).

8.10. Conclusion

Sudan, a member of ILO since its independence in 1956, has ratified 18 conventions and one protocol. The most recent ratification was on March 17, 2021, on the right to organise and bargain collectively. Sudan must promote the right to freedom of association, which is a fundamental requirement for change and adhering to the revolution's slogan of "Freedom, Peace, and Justice." Sudan is well-versed in the Declaration of Fundamental Principles and Rights at Work, which is composed of the five fundamental principles: freedom of

association, the abolition of all forms of forced and compulsory labour, the effective abolition of child labour, the elimination of employment and occupation discrimination, and a safe working environment. However, these principles are not realistically undertaken in Sudan, and people do not understand what they mean.

The ILO supports international labour standards by an exclusive global oversight system to ensure that all countries implement the conventions they ratify. The International Labour Organisation employs two supervisory techniques: the Regular Supervision System and Special Procedures. The ILO requires Sudan to submit periodic reports regularly, with the Ministry of Labour being the primary keeper of this information. The country's labour offices are in direct contact with all organisations and businesses, but they have no reporting relationship because of a lack of necessary links, measures, and statistics. Corruption is suspected, but this research cannot prove it. In collaboration with the ILO, it has been recommended that the Labour Ministry be evaluated to determine whether it can carry out its core functions and meet its challenges and goals.

Health and safety issues should be addressed professionally, with clear measures and regular monitoring. Financial constraints play a significant role in the neglect, and most private enterprises seek to maximise their profits without consequences. Social protection in Sudan requires substantial effort and commitment. Decent Work entails opportunities for productive work that pays a decent living, workplace security and social protection for all, improved opportunities for personal development and social integration, the freedom to express concerns, organise and participate in decisions that affect their lives, and equality of opportunity and treatment for all women and men. Sudan's government must demonstrate its sincerity by revisiting all its laws to bring about the longed-for change brought about by the revolution.

The Ministry of Labour must be eager to achieve social justice and provide a dignified life for all Sudanese citizens. An active partnership with the ILO is necessary to make a difference in decent work. The ILO reviewed Sudan's decent work programme strategy because it is outdated. The Ministry recommended that both be aligned with these changes, but it is not yet ready in practice. Numerous interconnected components must be in place for decent work policies to be integrated, and other ministries must also be involved. To make a real difference, Sudanese workers and labour law professionals should participate and take matters into their own hands in collaboration with international organisations. The ILO

recommends developing unique, relevant required domestic indicators and is willing to extend its partnership and support.

A significant obstacle is the absence of dialogue and communication between the government and industry stakeholders nationwide. Hands-on legal experts should be consulted and involved to ensure that updates and decisions honour and reflect what the people genuinely need.

CHAPTER NINE: CONCLUSION & RECOMMENDATIONS

9.1. Introduction

The Research Direction

Research Aim	Research Questions	Research Objectives
<p><i>The aim of this research is to investigate the current Sudanese Labor Act of 1997 to assess its fitness for purpose.</i></p>	<p><i>What are the key aspects of the Sudanese Labor Act?</i></p>	<p><i>To identify the key aspects of the Sudanese Labor Act.</i></p>
	<p><i>What challenges can be identified within the Act in the context of international best practices?</i></p>	<p><i>To assess the critical challenges the Sudanese Labor Act faces in light of international best practices</i></p>
	<p><i>What strategies can be in place to ensure the Sudanese Labor Act meets the twenty-first century needs?</i></p>	<p><i>To identify the strategies and techniques for updating the Labor Act in order to suit Sudan's current HR needs.</i></p>

Source: (Original)

The research aims to investigate the current Sudanese Labour Act of 1997 to assess its fitness for purpose, and it was set out to do so by answering the above three questions. This chapter aims to synthesise the key findings of the research concerning the research aim, questions, and objectives, as well as their value and contribution. Furthermore, the researcher will make suggestions and recommendations, review the study’s limitations, and propose opportunities for future research.

9.2. THE FIRST QUESTION: What are the key aspects of the Sudanese Labour Act?

The 1997 Labour Laws were designed for a bygone era and have not been transformed or rehashed to address Sudan's current problems and needs. They are a continuation of the old laws, developed in the Sixties and Seventies and even beyond, with no real substantial change and endurance to the challenges they bring. It developed to serve the Sudanese economy during the early 1960s (post-independence) when it was primarily based on the agricultural sector and Agri-processing factories, and it still exists in that. The outdated law cannot deal with the challenges of the twenty-first century.

Despite adherence, the laws are not serving the expectations of small, medium, and large businesses across the country; they are all struggling with the application. Small businesses, on the other hand, suffer the most because the 1997 rules apply to all businesses, regardless of size, crippling small businesses and scaring entrepreneurs away from ventures. Small businesses seek fraudulent practices and manipulation of the articles in enforcement to protect their profit margins. Furthermore, they are not equally accessible to upcountry businesses, as evident negligence is endured. In addition, the articles are vague, lack clarity, and are inconsistent.

One of the primary reasons for the lack of conformity is the lack of an essential component, namely the regulatory procedures section (lacks rules & regulations/procedures/processes). The missing "*Regulations*" document should have accompanied the 1997 Act (it should have been written and included as part of the Act). The 1997 Act is a synthesis of four separate acts, none of which, neither the old four nor the 1997 Act, had regulations! "Inspection", a key provision of the Act and is presumed to take place, is inactivated. Nonetheless, inspection is not the only frozen process, as other necessary articles such as the availability of "Public Employment Offices," "Specialty Committees," and "Regular Health Checks" are all inactive.

Furthermore, there are no penalties (another inactive act) and no consequences; in practice, the laws are not essentially that binding! The Labour offices, the primary authorities in charge of enforcing the Act, governing, and overseeing its day-to-day implementation across the country, are a weak body with little or no impact and lack coverage. They have no authority and don't report to the Labour Ministry (which is solely responsible for the development & application of the labour laws and other corresponding technical knowledge

and expertise). Competence, power, consistency, flexibility, and credibility were significant deficiencies in the labour offices.

The Ministry itself is in despair. Sudan's primary custodian for developing and implementing labour laws is currently in limbo, unable to make active decisions to make the much-needed change. The current situation reflects an ageing system that cannot meet the country's pressing needs. The institution in charge of guiding the recovery, setting the vision, leading the change, bringing parties together, and overseeing labour law implementation is in life support! This is a significant threat to the entire nation. This nation has shed much blood in the name of "*freedom, peace, and justice*," a country that longs for stability and reform, a downhearted nation struggling to make ends meet and desperately needs change. There might have recently been efforts to turn things around; unfortunately, nothing tangible has been seen.

The Ministry of Labour partners in decision-making with two major bodies: the Sudanese Businessmen and Employers Federation (SBEF) & Sudan Workers Trade Unions Federation (SWTUF), forming the "Tripartite Committee". These bodies are meant to represent their respective units independently and freely. However, the representation is political, government-appointed and controlled! Despite its political characteristics and prejudices, its function has been inactive due to the unions' dysfunction since the transitional government occurred. As a result, no official legitimate body represents these faces; hence, no decisions are made (when active, they are never in agreement, rarely reach a conclusion, and cannot create policy, administer reform, and facilitate progress). This, in and of itself, is a further halt and calamity within the more significant crisis.

Corruption and power struggles distract from implementing fair, just, and reliable endeavours. Financial constraints are also an overwhelming burden and a real crippling factor, and a reason for the inability to implement practical labour standards. Knowledge, skills, and behaviours are a further impediment, in addition to the lack of competence and essential technical know-how. Since its inception, the Tripartite Committee has taken no systematic approach to reviewing, assessing, and updating the 97 Act. For the past 25 years, there has been no evidence of change in the laws. The committee responsible for acting, making decisions, and leading the change is rarely in action. The entire reform system is

broken, and the challenge lies not only in the law itself, which requires immediate attention, but also in the institutions in charge of doing so.

9.3. THE SECOND QUESTION: What challenges can be identified within the Act in the context of International Best Practices?

The articles feature vagueness, lack of clarity and inconsistency. With this ambiguity, practitioners are invited to interpret and end up with varying situational and personal judgments. Because the laws are not specific and well-defined, the interpretation varies between the various bodies, resulting in a fragmented application even among labour law governors themselves (labour offices). Hence, the laws are inconsistently applied and muddled. In addition, the government has the power to exempt any entity; the Ministry Council may declare by order that any class of persons is exempt from the provisions of this Act. This adds to the application's inconsistency and injustice. Furthermore, all employment laws lack synergy; they are scattered, not aligned, sometimes contradicting, and do not speak to one another, resulting in massive discrepancies. Sudan, in general, lacks a well-consolidated and well-coordinated set of laws.

The Sudanese business environment has changed dramatically over the past two decades, as has the level of awareness and understanding among the workforce, and the 1997 Act is outdated and no longer meets today's business needs. The terminology and language indicate that it was designed to serve a different generation and an industry that no longer exists. For a long time, it was obvious to decision-makers that the Act needed upgrading; several unsuccessful attempts were made on various occasions. The Tripartite Committee would meet and recommend development or upgrade; however, no official document was issued.

Measures are unquestionably absent from the equation; they are simply missing. In Sudan, there is an evident void and a persistent problem with the availability and accessibility of data and statistical measures that support decision-making at all levels. In any organisational setting, there is no follow-up, audit, checks or reviews of the Labour Act implementation. As previously stated, the "*Inspection*" process does not exist in practice; it is only on paper. The only KPI or measure in place is the amount of money collected from fines and penalties, and government officials are rewarded by commissions and annual bonuses based on the volume of penalties and "sales" they manage to generate.

They judge their success by the amount of money they collect from businesses rather than the impact they make. Suppose the government is genuinely committed to effectively managing the application of labour laws. In that case, it should have established relevant measures and tracked them nationwide to manage and assess them regularly.

The Minimum Wage Act of 1974 is a separate statute mentioned in the 1997 Act as one example of the scattered legislation that could be well incorporated into a single act for clarity, consistency, and convenience. It is currently set by the Government (Tripartite Committee) at two different rates: SDG 425 (USD 0.73) per month for the private sector and SDG 3,000 (USD 5.17) per month for civil servants. Sudan does not compensate workers or compute minimum wage hourly, which is challenging, particularly for workers who work long shifts, such as in the health and hospitality sectors. The minimum wage should be set to meet the workers & their family's basic needs.

Both rates are unreasonably low, far from realistic, and disgraceful by all measures. Regularly, the minimum wage should be reviewed and assessed. Sudan has struggled with high inflation rates for years. Still, there is no excuse for policymakers to ignore such a fundamental issue. It was last reviewed in 2014 and was predetermined for three consecutive years in a volatile country like Sudan. The Sudanese government is only concerned with military and political issues at the expense of people's livelihood. It should be noted that the revolution was founded on rebellion and protesting the minimum wage, which is why the people of Sudan objected and lost innocent lives in pursuit of a better life and a better Sudan.

Although the so-called Islamic Regime ruled Sudan for 30 years, it was unable to align true Islamic Sharia Practices with labour issues for a fair and just distribution of income and wealth. Unfortunately, Islam was taken on the surface and superficially implemented. Sustainable indicators such as "Primary Need" and durable measures like "Nisab" and "Sa'a" were never considered when determining the minimum wage!

The salary structure/breakdown is mainly inequitable, and its setup allows significant deception and exploitation. Basic pay is determined at the employer's discretion and is not governed by a formula or standard ratio, which is widely abused. The employer computes almost everything from the basic pay, which can be as little as a quarter (if not less) of the take-home pay. As a result, the employee receives a fraction of their paycheck for everything that matters, such as wrongful termination remuneration, after-service benefits, and the cost of overtime; basically, a rip-off.

The second issue is the gender pay gap, widely visible nationwide in all industries. Finally, performance management is used as a criterion for annual salary increases under labour law, which states that organisations must review salaries annually and provide a 5% yearly raise based on satisfactory performance. The problem is that it leaves the definition of “satisfactory” vague without explicitly defining it or establishing clear performance indicators.

Fundamental international human rights treaties have recognised the need for social protection. The 1948 Universal Declaration of Human Rights states that “everyone” has the right to social security as a member of society, and the 1966 International Covenant on Economic, Social, and Cultural Rights included Social Insurance for all. Sudan’s social protection system is inadequate and, in many cases, non-existent. It is true that the Sudanese employment regulation somewhat maintains the economic and social distress caused by absence from work due to various contingencies such as sickness, maternity, workplace injury, old age, or death, as well as the provision of health care benefits.

According to the National Pensions and Social Insurance Fund of 2016, social insurance is mandatory for all employees in the public and private sectors (merging the Pension Fund of 1904 and the Social Insurance Fund of 1975). Medical insurance is also covered under the 1997 Act for working people. The challenge, however, is in the implementation and coverage. Only about one-fifth of working people in the formal sector are estimated to be registered with the Social Insurance Fund! Furthermore, the reduced basic pay rates, constant devaluation of the Sudanese Pound, and corrupt practices render the Social Insurance return worthless, even in times of need. Lastly, unemployment and workers in the informal sector are excluded from any social/health insurance coverage.

The informal economy in Sudan employs many young and older adults. Informal employment was estimated to be around 87% in 2011. The informal sector is not represented despite accounting for a sizable portion of the economy. The Sudanese Labour Act of 1997 does not protect independent workers outside the formal labour market, such as self-employed individuals, home workers, and all unregulated wage workers. Furthermore, the Act excludes several occupations that unquestionably employ regular workers, such as agriculture workers, who are not entirely covered, and garbage collectors, who are ignored; loading and offloading workers, as well as bakers in bakeries (to avoid paying overtime). The government created stand-alone “Pay Orders” to exploit and manipulate their pay; it excluded

them from the right to be governed by the Labour Act 1997. The current labour laws' efforts to protect society's most vulnerable workforce are notably missing.

Job opportunities are severely scarce, and people with disabilities and vulnerabilities are disproportionately affected because they require almost invisible opportunities! Vulnerable and marginalised groups are not even mentioned in the 1997 Act or any other separate manuscript; they are ignored. There is no equality Act to supplement the Labour Act. The 1997 Act contains numerous obvious flaws that, in the end, result in massive injustice, considering three major problematic factors that predominantly affect the most vulnerable: *the minimum wage, overtime, and unfair dismissal*. Labour laws were enacted to protect weaker groups who could not defend themselves against exploitation and the might of capitalism. Still, in Sudan, the level of negligence and lack of duty and care has reached record levels.

Sudan has extremely high & chronic unemployment rates. Although Sudan has previously endorsed International Agreements for social security and protection against unemployment, there is no employment promotion or protection against unemployment. With its current economic difficulties and extremely high unemployment rates, Sudan faces a significant challenge, and it must try to take proactive measures to develop an employment protection system. According to the researcher, this has already been attempted and drafted (*A National Employment Policy*). As previously discussed, the only active social protection for working people is Pensions & Social Insurance, and it does not cover workers if they lose their jobs unless they have earned their pensions through years of contributions. However, due to high inflation and the depreciation of the Sudanese pound, the pension and social insurance systems are failing their members.

Bullying and Harassment are not addressed by the 1997 Act or any other legislation in Sudan; nothing addresses these behaviours, and they are not legally sanctioned! Sexual harassment is a taboo subject that no one discusses. There are no preventive measures in place. A significant gap in Sudanese legislation is still far from being filled. In organisations where internal policies may exist, sexual harassment is not taken seriously, and women lack trust in internal systems because they understand they do not protect them and frequently judge them when they are the victims. Most of those tasked with developing policies to protect the vulnerable from such injustices cannot comprehend the value of doing so! As a result, when

things go wrong, women prefer to remain quiet or leave the workplace rather than take action to protect themselves and their reputation.

Astonishingly, an employer cannot terminate a working relationship if an employee has committed a violation, such as sexual harassment. The procedure is tedious and inefficient because sexual harassment is not explicitly mentioned in the Act as a standalone violation, so if he or she decides to terminate the contract, it will be considered “*Unlawful Termination*” and must be compensated! Since there are no channels for filing claims or reporting wrongdoing, women cannot complain (whistleblowing). When it comes to “Bullying,” things take a very informal approach and precedence, and severe issues are treated lightly, casually, and with a great deal of informality, which usually dilutes the essence of the problem and loses its significance.

The 1997 Sudanese Labour Act does not promote Equality, Diversity, and Inclusion (EDI). Sudanese workers face disparities and continue to face multiple forms of inequality, discrimination, and exclusion in the workplace. The labour law does not mention governing the workplace or protecting workers from discrimination or inconvenience. Discrimination may not be visible, but it is prevalent in the Sudanese workplace, both officially and unofficially. Racism is widespread, and the Labour Act makes no provisions for protection, leaving a significant gap. The 1997 Act does not explicitly advocate for fair representation, equality, or diversity.

In recruitment, for example, interview questions frequently highlight discrimination based on gender, age, family background, colour, and religion. Certain ethnic minorities are treated with contempt and as second-class citizens. Furthermore, certain tribes & minorities may not be recruited at all or are only given insignificant jobs and never senior positions, effectively denying fair representation and equal employment opportunities to certain racial groups. Furthermore, freedom of belief and expression is limited, and nepotism and favouritism are common and well-established in most organisations. Moreover, gender and sexuality, which are by definition not socially acceptable for religious and cultural reasons, are automatically excluded from the agenda.

Sudanese labour laws address culture, religion, and society, which should be acknowledged. They include laws that address women’s needs, such as the four-month and ten-day fully paid

Mourning Leave granted to women following the death of their husbands' grieving period under Islamic rituals (irrespective of religion). Besides maternity leave, women are entitled to one hour off each working day for the first 24 months after giving birth. The regulatory environment recognises women's right to equal pay (but does not monitor it).

These flexibilities, combined with other options, make the Act progressive regarding women's rights, and the ability to accommodate their needs is a sophistication that should be commended. Sudanese women are well respected in the workplace; they have dominated and excelled in all sectors. They are well-educated and qualified for all jobs and have the confidence to compete successfully with men. Despite all of this, women continue to face workplace discrimination.

Nonetheless, the Sudanese Labour Law of 1997 restricts women's employment. With a few exceptions, women are not permitted to perform physical labour or work in hazardous or toxic work environments and are not allowed to work between 10 p.m. and 6 a.m. These legal constraints have an impact on working women and limit their opportunities. They face gender discrimination in recruitment because of their maternity and pregnancy rights. Although maternity leave is well established, it appears problematic for recruiters! It is overlooked from the perspective of the father because men are discriminated against and have no right to claim paternal leave under the current act.

Moreover, male dominance in senior leadership and decision-making positions is widespread in Sudanese culture. Sudanese female managers are frequently confronted with organisational conditions favouring male employees over them as they struggle to fit into these male-oriented contexts. Gender balance is insufficient in Sudanese workplaces, and opportunities for women in senior positions are extremely limited. The law does not address these imbalances nor advocate for women to penetrate the glass ceiling through quotas or forced measures.

From a contractual standpoint, the employment relationship is inadequate and does not meet the diverse needs of Sudan's various businesses. These organisations must make difficult decisions to work around their flaws. Employment flexibility, particularly contract flexibility, has become increasingly vital. Nonstandard work contracts have been on the rise all over the world. Contracts that deviate from the standard contract form of full-time, now permanent

employment, have become the norm. Compared to other countries, the Sudanese Labour Law of 1997 does not allow this flexibility, making it difficult for employers to balance their workforce requirements. The employer cannot establish the type of relationship desired. As a baseline for the relationship, the 1997 Act established rigid/fixed standard moulds, and the mechanisms for terminating this contractual relationship were insufficient.

The reality is that the nature of work has changed in recent years, shifting from traditional methods of work to more modern and flexible methods, and the COVID-19 pandemic was the catalyst for Sudanese HR practitioners to recognise the genuine need for absent laws. Despite the apparent labour-market requirement, Sudanese employment laws have not reflected that need. Part-time jobs are still not recognised by the 1997 Act, putting a significant burden on organisations, and discouraging them from offering part-time jobs, thereby failing many people who seek flexible working conditions. Additionally, working from home is not a legitimate, recognised option, nor are online remote work engagements. This was especially problematic in the pandemic's aftermath, when these gaps were significantly exacerbated.

The 1997 Act failed the most vulnerable of our society, as evidenced by the three-month probation period. Employers nationwide are manipulating the probation period to hire short-term workers for projects like electricity, sugar farming, and seasonal jobs while violating their contractual rights. According to the Probation Act, both parties can terminate the contract without legal consequences. Employers nationwide hire innocent workers for three months and then terminate their contracts, claiming they did not meet the job requirements and failed the probation period just days before it ends. The workers are then released without notice or compensation and replaced with new workers or returned after a short time. Many industries and manufacturing companies follow this heinous practice of Three-month "*Hiring, Firing, & Rehiring*", which has been continuing for very long years, exploiting workers, confiscating, and excluding them from all deserved rights; simply "*Modern Day Slavery!*".

9.4. THE THIRD QUESTION: What strategies can be in place to ensure the Sudanese Labour Act meets the "Twenty-first century needs"?

Sudan has been a member of the ILO since its independence in 1956, and it has ratified 18 conventions and one protocol since then (1 out of the 6 protocols, 8 out of the ten fundamental Conventions, 3 of 4 Governance Conventions and only 7 of 176 Technical

Conventions). The most recent ratification was on March 17, 2021, of Convention No. 87 on the right to organise and bargain collectively (which should have happened at least 60 years ago).

Sudan must promote the right to freedom of association. This is a fundamental requirement for change and adhering to the revolution's "Freedom, Peace, and Justice" slogan. To achieve the much-needed transformation and reform, the government must empower the various bodies, unions, and institutions representing the people. Over 30 years of dictatorship destabilised these bodies, and it is critical to get them back on their feet and assist them in fighting for the interests and rights of the people. Since the ratification, a new law has been drafted but not yet approved, which will cover the *right to collective bargaining* and should be incorporated into the labour law soon.

Although most working Sudanese are unaware of the international labour treaties, we can confidently say that Sudan as a "Government" is well-versed in these "*International Labour Standards and Best Practices*". The Declaration of Fundamental Principles and Rights at Work is the foundation for building equitable and just societies. It is composed of five fundamental principles:

- *Freedom of association and the effective right to collective bargaining*
- *The abolition of all forms of forced and compulsory labour*
- *The effective abolition of child labour*
- *The elimination of employment and occupation discrimination*
- *A safe and healthy working environment*

Neither the ILO's Decent Work Agenda nor the broader 2030 Sustainable Development Agenda will be realised unless they are put into law and practice. By membership, Sudan has pledged to uphold and promote these principles. However, these vows are not realistically undertaken; they are artificially pledged and theoretically studied but not executed, and manuscripts are left to collect the dust. In practice, fundamental principles and workplace rights do not exist in Sudan, and people do not understand what they mean.

According to the ILO, international labour standards are supported by an exclusive global oversight system to ensure that all countries implement their ratified conventions. The ILO regularly examines the implementation of standards in member countries and identifies areas

for improvement. If there are any problems with standard implementation, the ILO seeks to help countries by facilitating dialogue and providing technical assistance. The ILO has developed several methods for monitoring their implementation in legislation and practice. The International Labour Organisation employs two types of supervisory techniques:

- *The Regular Supervision System:*
- *Special Procedures*

Sudan, like all other state members, is required by the ILO to submit periodic reports regularly. The Ministry of Labour is the primary keeper of this information. The country's labour offices directly contact all organisations and businesses. The ministry and the Labour offices have no reporting relationship. They are cut off because they lack the necessary links, measures, and statistics. Corruption is suspected, but this research cannot prove it. In collaboration with the ILO, it has been recommended that the Labour Ministry be evaluated to determine whether it can perform its core functions and meet its challenges and goals. The current reports sent to the ILO are not genuine; they do not reflect the accurate picture on the ground because the organisations responsible for filling out the data are not involved in the first place.

Work in conditions that deny fundamental principles and rights at work, endanger workers' lives, health, freedom, human dignity, and security, or keep households in poverty are UFW (ILO, 2013). There is no specific information on UFW in Sudan, and workers are rarely protected. It has never been discussed or measured by the government. Health and safety concerns are widely overlooked and receive inadequate attention. Sudanese organisations lack proper HSE systems, industrial health and safety environments, and essential facilities. While the 1997 Act mentions safety, it does not go far enough in detail and is not supported by strict regulations. It does not address the governing of the working relationship in the first place. The only solution it leaves is the right to terminate the contract if things go wrong, but no protection is advocated.

Workplace injuries have a stand-alone regulatory body based on a tabulated chart listing occupational risks and workplace accidents created in 1981 and hasn't been updated since. It refers to injuries caused by methods and techniques that are no longer used in any industrial setting and do not meet modern industrial standards. Risks include antiquated historical concerns. The problem is that the courts have approved these charts and serve as their sole

reference point. Many workers have unresolved claims of workplace incidents that have lingered in courts for years, and some have even died before their claims could be resolved.

Health and safety issues should be addressed professionally in all workplaces, not just manufacturing (as they are now in the current Act), with clear measures and regular monitoring. Financial constraints play a significant role in neglect, and because there is no accountability or consequence, most private enterprises seek to maximise their profits. Social protection and insurance in Sudan necessitate much effort and commitment. The ILO Constitution states that workers must be protected from work-related illness, disease, and injury. However, the reality for millions of workers, especially those in Sudan, is quite different.

At the turn of the millennium, the ILO proposed the “Decent Work” concept, which has since been enhanced and refined to become an operational goal for all. Since 1999, it has promoted the idea, making it its sole focus and centre of attention (ILO, 1999). In their working lives, people’s aspirations are exemplified by decent work. It entails opportunities for productive work that pays a decent living, workplace security and social protection for all, improved opportunities for personal development and social integration, the freedom to express concerns, organise and take part in decisions that affect their lives, and equality of opportunity and treatment for all women and men. Decent Work is described in 11 substantive elements in its updated formulation, also known as the Decent Work Agenda (ILO, 2013).

The new 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development was adopted during the UN General Assembly in September 2015; it included decent work and the four core principles of the Decent Work Agenda: *job creation, social protection, workplace rights, and social dialogue*. Goal 8 of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development promotes sustained, inclusive, and sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment, and decent work, and it is a significant area of engagement for the ILO and its stakeholders (ILO, 2019).

Following the revolution, the government of Sudan needed to demonstrate its sincerity by revisiting all its laws to show its genuineness in bringing about the longed-for change brought about by the revolution. The Ministry of Labour must be eager to achieve social justice and provide a dignified life for all Sudanese citizens. To make a difference in the issue of decent work, one must develop an active partnership with the ILO.

The ILO reviewed Sudan's decent work programme strategy because it is outdated. Considering Sudan's rapid pace of change, the Ministry reviewed the decent work strategy and policy, and the recommendation is that both be aligned with these changes. It is theoretically present but not yet ready in practice, and it is a long way from being there. However, numerous interconnected components must be in place for decent work policies to be integrated, and other ministries must also be involved. And a lot of other groundwork should be in place to ensure success. Most importantly, an effort must be made to focus on communication and awareness to inform the people, create a shared understanding of decent work, and launch information campaigns to raise awareness among the Sudanese people.

Sudanese people are overwhelmed by the day-to-day struggles of survival and cannot think beyond these challenges. In contrast, other countries have moved away from the day-to-day struggles of basic labour regulations, focusing on work-life balance, equality, diversity, and inclusion. Achieving "decent work" requires significant effort. The country's labour laws need a complete overhaul and modernisation to address the requirements of workers and ensure they receive the deserved protection. Focusing on and promoting the minimum wage is an important starting point because it determines so much. A general cultural shift is required, particularly in the workplace. Trade union roles are used in organisations to represent workers, reflect their problems, and protect their collective bargaining rights. Furthermore, they empower and strengthen the labour offices by providing them with the necessary capabilities, resources, and authority.

To make a real difference, Sudanese workers and labour law professionals should participate and take matters into their own hands in collaboration with international organisations. Using the ILO's recommended eleven indicators and sub-indicators is an excellent place to start, and these indicators can be customised according to local needs. The ILO also suggests developing unique, relevant required domestic indicators and is willing to extend its partnership and support.

The absence of dialogue and communication between the government and industry stakeholders nationwide is one significant problem that has come to light. There is a lack of involvement, engagement, information, and communication; they must make enormous efforts to obtain vital information that they are entitled to without any effort. Hands-on legal experts should be consulted and involved because they know the issues and understand the consequences of decisions without diverse consultation, discussion, and effective dialogue.

To further develop the situation, it is suggested that the government expand its involvement and involve a more significant number of individuals in the conversation. They must identify the stakeholders and determine whether they are engaging the appropriate stakeholders, if everyone who needs to participate is involved, if they genuinely have the relevant people on board, and if they are listening to the right people. Above all, efforts must focus on communication and awareness to inform and create a shared understanding.

This is critical to ensuring that when updates and decisions are made, they truly honour and reflect the people's genuine needs. Sudan is undergoing rapid change and enormous challenges requiring immediate attention and reinforcement. Freelancing, entrepreneurship, part-time work, flexible work, etc., are all examples of new ways of working that do not have legal backup. Employees now work three jobs at once, and this shift must be reflected in Sudanese laws and policies. It would be a shame if we did not have inclusive and actual representation and ended up presenting something that has little impact and will not serve its purpose (relevant stakeholder engagement).

9.5. Recommendations

After answering the following three research questions and based on the findings of this research, the researcher proposes a comprehensive approach to policy reform for the 1997 Labour Act.

1. *What are the key aspects of the Sudanese Labour Act?*
2. *What challenges can be identified within the Act in the context of international best practices?*
3. *What strategies can be in place to ensure the Sudanese Labour Act meets the twenty-first century needs?*

This comprehensive approach will consider three major areas of focus that align with the three main emerging themes from the data analysed.

Theme One: Key Aspects and Features

Theme Two: Major Issues & Challenges

Theme Three: Strategic Direction & Way Forward (meeting the twenty-first century needs)

Institutional reform and policy reform are both needed. The existing employment policies need thorough revision, including technical work, adopting new statutory provisions, and ratifying relevant ILO conventions. The Sudanese government must adopt a holistic view and start by examining the matter from a strategic point of view, reforming the institutions, and then narrowing down to the details of the policies.

These reforms and procedural actions will comprehensively address the issues and challenges. And eventually bridge the gaps currently faced by applying the 1997 Labour Act and its coexisting employment legislation. The idea is to create robust, effective labour laws and regulations to achieve clarity, boost morale and productivity, and enhance business in Sudan.

- 1. *Start by Recognising the Need for Reform & Take Immediate Action.*** Like many African and Middle Eastern countries, Sudan lags in implementing effective labour regulations. Acknowledging the pressing vital need for immediate scrutiny and investigation leading to developing and reforming labour regulations is crucial. These laws have stagnated for decades and are now largely redundant and incapable of meeting labour market expectations and dealing with the current business needs and the challenges of the twenty-first century. According to the Chartered Institute of Personnel and Development (CIPD), all current and new employment law components must be scrutinised regularly to determine their fitness for purpose (CIPD Report, Employment Regulations in the UK 2017).
- 2. *Formulate a Strategic Direction to aid the Ministry of Labour.*** In line with the newly adopted Sudan vision of “*freedom, peace, & justice*” and the International Labour Organisation’s (ILO) fundamental principles and rights at work, the Sudanese Ministry of Labour, in collaboration with the Government, should develop a ten-year strategy with clear short and long-term plans. Integrity should be at the heart of its values, strong, robust driving forces, and the intention to deliver decent work for all Sudanese people while prioritising the people of Sudan and bringing about much-needed change. The Ministry of Labour must be eager to achieve social justice and offer all Sudanese workers a dignified working life. It must lead and enforce this change with vigour, calibre, charisma, gravitas, and, most importantly, integrity because this is a mission unlike any other!

3. ***Address the Twenty-first Century Challenges Strategically.*** To do so, the following international frameworks must be seriously considered and incorporated into the Ministry's values and objectives, as well as in the development of the Ministry's overall "*Strategic Direction*":

a. ***Sudan must Uphold & Promote the ILO's Five Fundamental Principles & Rights at Work:***

- i. Freedom of association and the effective right to collective bargaining
- ii. The abolition of all forms of forced and compulsory labour
- iii. The effective abolition of child labour
- iv. The elimination of employment and occupation discrimination
- v. A safe and healthy working environment

b. ***Promote a Safe and Healthy Working Environment.*** The researcher recommends Sudan adopts contemporary international standards such as OSHA (Occupational Safety and Health Administration) or HSE (Health and Safety Executive) accredited standards to protect the workplace and that these standards be enforced and governed accordingly in the Labour Act. According to the ILO Constitution, workers must be protected from work-related illness, disease, and injury.

c. ***Completely Eradicate Unacceptable Forms of Work (UFW).*** Work in conditions that deny fundamental principles and rights at work, endanger workers' lives, health, freedom, human dignity, and security, or keep households in poverty are UFW (ILO, 2013). Sudanese workers must be protected from UFW.

d. ***Develop & Promote a Decent Work Strategy.*** Goal 8 of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development encourages sustained, inclusive, and sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment, and Decent Work, a central engagement area for the ILO and its stakeholders (ILO, 2019). Because the concept of "Decent Work" is not well recognised and understood in Sudan, it is recommended that the government launches awareness campaigns within its forums and throughout the country to create a shared understanding. Furthermore, decent work as an operational goal for labour issues in Sudan should be at the heart of its strategic mission in collaboration with the ILO. To

make a tangible difference, adopt and customise the 11 substantive elements of the Decent Work Agenda (ILO, 2013) listed in chapter two and develop Sudanese relevant, unique performance indicators in collaboration with the ILO.

- e. ***Entrench the ILO Standards Support & Oversight System with Integrity & Care.*** To ensure the implementation of all ratified conventions and identify areas for improvement, it is advised to seek technical assistance from the ILO and actively engage in productive dialogue and partnership. Sudan should also cooperate with the ILO's supervision systems in periodic reporting with integrity and transparency. And share accurate, realistic results and snapshots of the current situation to reflect an accurate picture. Seek support where necessary, involving suitable people in the process.
 - f. ***Endorse, Create, and Implement a Policy for Convention No. 87 on Freedom of Association and Protection of the Right to Organise.*** Sudan must promote the recently ratified convention on the right to freedom of association and the right to organise. Fundamental transformation is needed for change and adhering to the revolution's *Liberty, Peace, & Justice* slogan.
 - g. ***Consider the Ratification of Additional Conventions.*** Sudan has been a member of the ILO since its independence in 1956, and it has ratified 18 conventions and one protocol since then (one out of six protocols, eight out of ten fundamental conventions, three out of four governance conventions, and only seven out of 176 technical conventions). The researcher suggests that more relevant technical conventions be ratified.
4. ***Rethink & Reinvent the Role of Labour Offices.*** Labour offices must develop the necessary calibre, technical expertise, and legal, interpersonal, and partnership skills to operate with consistency and alignment. It is essential to review its mission statement, restore its reputation, and revamp its entire role to better meet the needs and expectations of the businesses and labour markets it serves and the larger community in which it operates. Should be given enough authority and resources to oversee and govern the day-to-day implementation of labour law nationwide. And connect them to the Ministry of Labour and its overall strategic direction.

5. *Develop Proficient Tripartite Representation & Effective Tripartite Consultation.*

The ILO states that to formulate standards and policies addressing labour issues effectively, the tripartite principle must be based on communication and cooperation between the three parties (government, employers, and employees). At the national level, the researcher recommends Sudan promote free, voluntary, and regular tripartite debates and consultations free of corruption and power struggles. The government is obligated by association to ensure that ILO standards and policies are developed, implemented, and monitored with full participation and without political pressures or influence. The researcher also suggests that all parties show impartiality and sincerity to create a workable framework for effective consultations and ensure greater cooperation among partners and a culture of social dialogue.

6. *Strengthen & Broaden the Scope of Relationships, as well as Diversify Partnerships.*

The researcher recommends strengthening and developing a dynamic international partnership with the ILO for consultation, support, and adequate supervision. Furthermore, many capable and enthusiastic Sudanese professionals are eager to make a difference. They are aware of local issues, gaps, and deficiencies. For example, nine of them have contributed significantly to this research, and the researcher is confident they will do so again. The researcher strongly advises that these individuals, as well as others, become involved. They have no hidden or political agendas, have the potential to make a significant difference, and should be involved in the transformation.

7. *Develop a Communication & Knowledge Sharing Strategy.*

The Ministry should indeed improve communication and dialogue with people all over the country. Participation, engagement, information, communication, and access to information are all essential. Understanding the consequences of decisions can only be accomplished through extensive consultation, discussion, and effective dialogue. It is advised that the government broaden its engagement strategy and engage more people in the conversation to advance the situation. They must identify the stakeholders and ensure that the right people are involved. Furthermore, it is critical to also listen to the right people. Above all, efforts must focus on communication and awareness to inform everyone and build consensus. Respect and reflect what people genuinely need with inclusive and actual representation, i.e. relevant stakeholder engagement.

8. ***Resolve Access & Coverage Issues.*** It is recommended that a strategy be developed to reach and cover all stakeholders in all cities and regions throughout Sudan. It is critical to have labour offices and specialised labour courts throughout the country. The researcher also suggests creating a website or an easily accessible platform to reach, inform, and update all relevant stakeholders. The lack of access and widespread negligence are unjust to those who adhere to, apply, and govern the application.
9. ***Develop Clarity, Consistency & Uniformity.*** First, the 1997 Articles must be rewritten (word for word), revisiting the language and terminology in line with today's business needs, well defined without ambiguity and fully aligned with one another, as well as aligned with speaking to all other relevant employment regulations. All employment laws must be synergistic and not conflict with one another. Accordingly, reviewing, harmonising, and combining all pertinent laws is necessary. Additionally, consistency and fairness should be developed in all applications.
10. ***Create Rules & Regulations to Guide Implementation.*** To achieve the required conformity, the regulatory procedures must be well drafted, documented, and made available to all as part of the Law (accompanying the Act). This will eliminate any potential ambiguity and inconsistency in the applications. And mandate in the Act a requirement for *frequent annual reviews of the Act.*
11. ***Review & Activate the Inspection System as part of a Comprehensive Compliance Strategy & Develop the Necessary Measures.*** Inspection is a crucial provision that must not be overlooked if we are to monitor, regulate, and govern effective implementation. Its function must be updated and reactivated. The ILO believes that inspection is at the heart of effective labour laws, with essential functions such as enforcement and sanctions that must be uniformly applied to prevent violations of labour legislation, as well as providing corrective, developmental, and technical advice, guidance, preventative measures & tools, and promoting workplace best practices. These functions should be regulated and balanced in a comprehensive compliance strategy to ensure decent working conditions and a safe working environment. The Sudanese government must set aside funds to attract, manage and train inspectors. Furthermore, it is strongly advised that appropriate measures and KPIs be in place to support governance and compliance.

- 12. Labour law violations must be legally binding and be linked to actions, consequences, and sanctions.** Currently, all labour laws in Sudan are only associated with penalties, which are not even enforced. As a result, the law is fragile and without consequences; thus, the researcher recommends that the law be legally binding, with consequences ranging from fines to sentencing and a range of prison terms.
- 13. Revisit and Reformulate the Specialty Committees and other Necessary dropped Provisions.** The researcher recommends that the government review and reactivate all previously blocked procedures. Inspection is not the only frozen process; other essential articles, such as the availability of “Specialty Committees,” “Public Employment Offices,” and “Regular Health Checks,” are practically non-existent. The availability of Public Employment Offices with transparent, reliable *Recruitment & Selection* processes in place will add much value.
- 14. Strengthen Learning and Development & Create a Competency Framework.** Lack of knowledge, skills, and behaviours are a real crippling factor and one reason for the inability to implement practical labour standards. To support change, transformation, and sustainability, it is recommended that core, technical, and behavioural competencies must be developed and demonstrated. It is also suggested that the Labour Act and other employment laws be taught as part of university curricula.
- 15. Review, Protect & Regulate Wage & Salary Structures, Breakdown & Overtime & Other Benefits.** Wages and salaries must be protected and distributed equitably to combat deception and exploitation. It is suggested that the government reviews these structures and develop standard just proportions/ratios governed by strict regulations, particularly the basic pay limits, because it serves as the foundation for everything that matters, such as wrongful termination compensation, after-service benefits, and overtime work costs.
- 16. Provisions for Managing & Developing Performance at Work.** Performance is the primary criterion used in the workplace to determine and make significant decisions from the beginning to the end of the working relationship. Beginning with attraction, selection, promotion, development, and termination, and should thus be measured and managed. The 1997 Act vaguely mentions and uses “satisfactory performance” as a criterion for annual salary increases. It fails to explicitly define “satisfactory” or mention the need to develop clear performance measures/indicators and effectively

communicate them to the worker/employee beforehand. It is, therefore, essential that the law encourages regular performance reviews, the identification of poor performance, and the creation of performance improvement/development plans that are accompanied by a structured and fair process.

In addition, an effective disciplinary procedure and a transparent appeals system must be established. Finally, the law must encourage and promote a culture of continuous learning and development within organisations and the designation of budgetary allocations for workforce development.

17. Regulate Workplace Bullying & Harassment. Bullying and harassment in the workplace and beyond must be legally recognised and addressed. Its nonexistence in the 1997 Act or any other Sudanese legislation is unacceptable. Simply disgraceful! These violations must be legally regulated and sanctioned, and this is not debatable. Sexual harassment must be taken seriously, and legislators must not shy away from discussing it to protect women in the workplace and restore their trust. Furthermore, it has recently become increasingly crucial that Sudan acts, particularly in light of the terrible abuse and violence faced by doctors and health workers during the Pandemic. For this reason, among other things, the researcher strongly recommends that the government ratify ILO Convention No. 190 and develop the necessary measures to prevent and eliminate violence and harassment in the workplace to repair dignity and respect.

18. Review the Employment Terms & Conditions & Diversify the Employment Contracts & Agreements. Sudanese labour law should allow flexibility to meet the diverse needs of Sudan's various businesses and organisations, making it easier for employers to balance their workforce requirements. The employer should be able to establish the desired type of relationship and break free from the rigid fixed standard moulds. It is strongly advised that the new Act considers nonstandard work contracts and policies that promote flexible working conditions, such as part-time work, working from home, and online technologies for remote work engagements.

19. Regulate the Three-month Probation Period & Safeguard Workers against Exploitation. The manipulation of the three-month probationary period and the violation of contractual rights are clear examples of how the Labour Act 1997 failed the most vulnerable members of our society. Numerous industries continue to exploit

workers through the shameful practice of three-month “*Hiring, Firing, and Rehiring.*” Regulations must be implemented to restrict the abuse of the probation period, govern the exploitation of workers across the country, and protect the right to fair and just employment conditions.

20. *Safeguard Data Protection, Confidentiality & Information Security.* The Sudanese laws make no mention of governing data protection or confidentiality measures. These regulations must be in place, and the data must be used correctly and legally. Sudan can adopt ideas and principles from the UK Data Protection Act 1998 and The European Union’s General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) 2018. All employers and employees should know their legal obligations and the penalties for breaking these rules (CIPD, 2022).

21. *Promote Maternity & Paternity Rights.* Although maternity leave is legally mandated, women continue to face discrimination in hiring because of their maternity rights. Furthermore, it is overlooked from the father’s perspective, and men face discrimination and have no right to seek paternal leave under the current act. The new law is proposed to refine maternity rights, including shared parental, adoption, and unpaid paternity leave. According to the (CIPD, 2021), both mothers and fathers should have legal rights to maternity, paternity, adoption, shared parental leave, and other family-friendly measures. Employers should also be optimistic and conscientious about supporting and retaining employees who need to balance work and childcare regularly.

22. *Update & align the 1974 Minimum Wage Act & Implement an Hourly Pay Rate.* The researcher suggests incorporating the Minimum Wage Act within a single employment act for clarity, consistency, and convenience. It is currently set at two different rates by the Tripartite Committee; however, for equity and consistency, it is recommended that the threshold be uniform across public and private sectors, with introducing a single standard *hourly minimum wage* set for the entire nation, reviewed, and updated annually. The criteria for determining the minimum wage must also be revisited and updated. The minimum wage must be set to meet the workers and their family’s basic needs, with annual reviews that are bulletproof against inflationary turbulence. It is also suggested that humanitarian principles be derived from Islamic rulings as guidance.

23. *Improve Social Protection (Safety Nets) and modernise & Safeguard the National Pensions & Social Insurance Fund.* The need for social protection has been recognised in fundamental international human rights treaties. According to the 1948 Universal Declaration of Human Rights, “everyone” has the right to social security. Sudan’s social protection system is inadequate and, in many cases, non-existent and thus requires immediate attention and modernisation. It is suggested that the government focus on reinventing the Social Insurance Fund and develop plans to address the coverage issue and the apparent corruption practices. Only about one-fifth of working people in the formal sector are registered with the Social Insurance Fund, which is an excellent place to start!

24. *Think Beyond the Formal Sector.* Although the informal economy in Sudan employs a sizable portion of the workforce (approximately 87% in 2011), the informal sector is not represented. The researcher understands the world’s challenges; however, because of the sector’s vulnerability and scale, the Sudanese government must develop methods and techniques to govern and protect independent workers outside the formal labour market from further drifting from decent work. In doing so, the researcher proposes that the government start by gradually formalising these sectors and embarking on the ILO’s 2015 Recommendations, a powerful tool for guiding the transition from the informal to the formal economy. And then use it to create strategies and policies to ease the transition to formality. The ILO believes that unless the informal economy is formalised, decent work for all and social equity will remain a delusion (ILO, 2019).

25. *Develop a Vigorous Employment Policy/Act.* Sudan has extremely high chronic unemployment rates and urgently requires implementing employment policies/strategies to promote employment and protect against unemployment. It must seriously show that it has endorsed international social security and unemployment protection agreements, i.e., it must walk the talk. Proactive steps must be taken to create an employment protection system (A National Employment Policy). Reactivating the Public Employment Offices will also be beneficial.

26. *Protect the Most Vulnerable.* Neither the 1997 Act nor any other independent document mentions marginalised groups. No equality act exists to supplement the Labour Act. The 1997 Act is a catalogue of apparent flaws that result in massive

injustice. It is suggested that the government seriously considers all problematic factors that primarily affect the most vulnerable. People with disabilities and vulnerabilities, for example, are disproportionately affected because they require almost invisible opportunities! Labour laws must be enacted to protect weaker groups who cannot defend themselves against exploitation and negligence.

27. Bring into Force Provisions of An Equality Act:

- a. **Promote Equality, Diversity, and Inclusion (EDI).** Equality of opportunity and treatment, according to the ILO, is a fundamental principle of social justice that has been at the heart of the ILO's work since its inception in 1919. It is strongly advised that Sudan enact a separate equality Act or incorporate equality provisions into the new labour act. These laws must be explicit and transparent regarding fair representation, equality, diversity, and inclusion. Sudanese workers continue to face multiple forms of workplace inequality, discrimination, and exclusion.

The current labour law contains no provisions governing or protecting workers from discrimination, racism, or inconvenience, denying fair representation and equal employment opportunities, which is unacceptable. Therefore, it is also essential for Sudanese organisations to make fair accommodations so that everyone can function at work. Reasonable adjustments, also known as accommodations by the ILO, are vital in promoting workplace diversity, inclusion, and the right to employment equality.

- b. **Special Disability Provisions.** Disability, which is not negotiable, is absent from the Act and other provisions in Sudan. How can we expect businesses in Sudan to change if the government does not champion or promote disability inclusion? As a result, there must be explicit provisions in that act, or in a separate act to provide employment opportunities for disabled people while making reasonable adjustments and accommodations to ease their life in the workplace. CIPD is a Disability Confident Leader who promotes the elimination of barriers to recruitment, employment, and training for people with disabilities or long-term health conditions. And believes that organisations that take a positive and inclusive approach to disability management will experience numerous benefits, including increased employee

loyalty and commitment, the ability to tap into different ideas and skills that can boost innovation performance, and the ability to recruit and retain good people.

c. Promote Gender Equality & Equity using Measures. Sudanese women, despite their progress, continue to lag behind men. The 1997 Act prohibits them from performing certain jobs and operating during specific times. These impact on working women and limit their opportunities. Furthermore, because of their maternity rights, they face gender discrimination in recruitment. Additionally, male dominance in positions of senior leadership and decision-making is widespread. To make meaningful, long-term progress, the researcher suggests:

- i.* Giving women issues the attention they deserve by researching and studying Sudanese women in the workplace and where they stand.
- ii.* Second, developing labour laws and regulations that reflect the need for conditions that promote women's advancement in the workplace.
- iii.* Third, the government must also establish targets for governing and measuring gender distribution and encourage frequent and regular reporting on the ratios of women at work and women in senior executive roles.

The law must address these disparities and advocate for women to break through the glass ceiling through quotas and other coercive measures. And finally, the gender pay gap must be measured and fairly addressed.

9.6. Research Contributions

This research study produced essential contributions in two areas: *knowledge* and *policymaking*. As a unique endeavour in the field, the researcher believes this study has successfully provided much-required information and understanding that was not previously accessible (knowledge). The researcher can confidently state that there is now a point of reference to depend on in-depth research covering the Sudanese Labour Act of 1997 with reliable findings and solid recommendations.

The second and most significant input is the contribution to policymaking. This study is a reliable source of information for policymakers to use in understanding the issues and using the suggestions as a helpful guide. The researcher is confident that the set of recommendations emerging from this study will be a valuable document for Ministers, Government Officials, Managing Directors, Human Resource Directors, Consultants, and Law Makers in reviewing and developing new employment policies and laws, particularly in creating a new Sudanese Labour Act.

Furthermore, international organisations such as the ILO may also benefit from this research by deepening their knowledge and understanding of the issues and problems and incorporating the suggestions into future engagements, studies, and plans for Sudan and beyond.

9.7. Recommendations for Future Study

Further investigation into the same topic of Sudanese Labour Laws (1997 Act) is highly recommended by the researcher to strengthen and confirm the results of this study. In addition, new fields of inquiry that are similarly scarce have emerged and are suggested for future research.

Here are some recommended topics for further study:

1. The Ministry of Labour (compatibility, leadership, and its strategic direction)
2. The Tripartite Committee (composition, management, and partnership - fitness for purpose)
3. The Labour Offices (effectiveness and fitness for purpose; do these offices have the knowledge and abilities for the job at hand, and are they capable of effectively conducting their responsibilities?)
4. The Social Security Fund (ways to modernise and safeguard the National Pensions and Social Insurance Fund)
5. The Real Value and Sustainability of the Minimum Wage
6. How to Create a Decent Work Strategy for Sudan

7. Sudanese Women in Senior Roles (Measures & Challenges- are women in Sudan Experiencing the Glass Ceiling Effect- what is the Ratio of Women in executive roles)
8. Sudan's Gender Pay Gap (Measures & Challenges)
9. Ratified and Not-ratified ILO Conventions (assessment and the way forward)
10. How Islamic rulings govern the employment relationship.

9.8. Research Limitations

This study is not without flaws and constraints. First and foremost, the lack of previous research has significantly limited the researcher throughout the research process. It would have been beneficial if the researcher had located relevant studies in the area to relate to, challenge, or agree with.

Second, the researcher admits her bias and attachment to the research area and subject matter; despite efforts to eradicate and remove subjectivity, this flaw and weakness may have somewhat influenced the language used and her writing in general.

In addition, the researcher could have benefited from an advisor with expertise in UK and EU employment laws and experience in the area as a backup and advising position, as someone with subject matter knowledge could have significantly impacted the study and added much value. Geographical barriers have also impacted reach; despite the efficacy of contemporary technologies and remote tools to reach others, nothing beats face-to-face interactions and conversation.

Furthermore, the researcher encountered personal challenges throughout the research process, as the study began during the COVID-19 pandemic, and anxiety and uncertainty had a detrimental effect on her welfare, affecting her performance and speed of delivery. Furthermore, the researcher has experienced two tragic events in the last two years, having lost both of her parents, which tremendously impacted the researcher's emotional condition and was a huge constraint and setback.

Finally, the word count restriction was a significant limitation because the researcher created a study that almost doubled the size of the necessary word count and confronted a substantial

challenge in reducing the words to the required size. The researcher worked hard and did her best to reduce the study to a manageable size while retaining its essence.

REFERENCES

Abbas, F., Abbas, N. and Ashiq, U., 2021. Glass Ceiling Effect and Women Career: Determining factors in Higher Education Institutions. *sjesr*, 4(1), pp.1-8.

About Us, *International Trade Union Confederation*, [online] Available from <https://www.itucsi.org/about-us> [Accessed 25 August, 2021].

Abu Dawud, S. (2008). Arabic and English. Translated by Abu Ammar Yasir Qadhi. Riyadh: Darussalam Publishers.

ACAS (2021). *Understanding bullying, harassment and discrimination: Handling a bullying, harassment or discrimination complaint at work - Acas*. [online] www.acas.org.uk. Available at: <https://www.acas.org.uk/handling-a-bullying-harassment-discrimination-complaint>.

Adams, A.V., 2009. Skills development in the informal sector of sub-Saharan Africa. *International handbook of education for the changing world of work: Bridging academic and vocational learning, 1*.

African Business. (n.d.). *African Business - World leading source of analysis & debate on African economic issues*. [online] Available at: <https://african.business>.

African Economic Outlook 2012: Sudan. African Development Bank, OECD, UNDP, UNECA. www.africaneconomicoutlook.org

Agervold, M., 2007. Bullying at work: A discussion of definitions and prevalence, based on an empirical study. *Scandinavian journal of psychology*, 48(2), pp.161-172.

Ahlering, B. and Deakin, S.' 2007. Labor regulation, corporate governance, and legal origin: A case of institutional complementarity? *Law & Society Review*, 41(4), pp.865-908.

Ahmad, M., 2012. Musnad Imam Ahmad bin Hanbal, Arabic and English, Translated by Nasiruddin al-Khattab, Darussalam Publishers, Riyadh.

Al-Hujurat 49: 13, An-Nisaa' 4: 36-37. The Quran, English Translation of the Holy Quran by Abdullah Yusuf Ali.

Ali, I. and Hatta, Z.A. (2014). Zakatas a Poverty Reduction Mechanism Among the Muslim Community: Case Study of Bangladesh, Malaysia, and Indonesia. *Asian*

Al-Manasra, E.A., 2013. What are the” Glass Ceiling” barriers effects on women career progress in Jordan?. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 8(6), p.40.

Alter Chen, M., 2005. *Rethinking the informal economy: Linkages with the formal economy and the formal regulatory environment* (No. 2005/10). WIDER Research Paper.

Al-Tohami, K., 2011. Migration in Sudan: A country profile 2011. *Khartoum: International Organization for Migration*.

Angel-Urdinola, D.F. and Kuddo, A. (2010). Key characteristics of employment regulation in the Middle East and North Africa. World Bank.

Anker, R., Chernyshev, I., Egger, P. and Mehran, F., 2003. Measuring decent work with statistical indicators. *Int'l Lab. Rev.*, 142, p.147.

An-Na`im, A. 1990. Toward an Islamic reformation: *Civil liberties, human rights and international law*. Syracuse. N. Y. Syracuse University Press

Anon, (2014). *The Elephant*. [online] Available at: <https://www.theelephant.info>.

Aronsson, G., 2001. A new employment contract. *Scandinavian journal of work, environment & health*, pp.361-364.

Arshadul, H.K., 2018. Rights of Labourers in Islam: Bangladesh Perspective. *Beijing L. Rev.*, 9, p.345.

Arthurs, H.W. (2011). Labour law after labour. Osgoode CLPE Research Paper(15). at: <https://www.ilo.org/integration/themes/mdw/lang--en/index.htm>.

Atia, M., 2011, December. Islamic approaches to development: A case study of Zakat, Sadaqa and Qurd al Hassan in Contemporary Egypt. In *8th International Conference on Islamic Economics and Finance, Center for Islamic Economics and Finance, Qatar Faculty of Islamic Studies, Qatar Foundation*.

Azeez, W., 2003. Zakat as the Islamic Social Insurance. Azeez, WO (2003),” Zakat as the Islamic Social Insurance” in *Al-Hadarah: LASU Journal of Arabic and Islamic Studies*, 6, pp.30-38.

Babbie, E., 2010. The Practice of Social Research (Twelfth Edition ed.). *Belmont, CA: Wadsworth*.

Baccaro, L. and Mele, V., 2012. Pathology of path dependency? The ILO and the challenge of new governance. *ILR Review*, 65(2), pp.195-224.

Baguley, P., 1994. *Effective communication for modern business*. McGraw-Hill.

Bakr, M., 2019. Localizing Transnationalism: A Struggle for Women's Employment Rights a Narrative from Sudan. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 9(10), pp.78-83.

Baldwin, R., Cave, M. and Lodge, M., 2011. *Understanding regulation: theory, strategy, and practice*. Oxford university press.

Bangasser, P.E., 2000. *The ILO and the informal sector: an institutional history* (pp. 1-64). Geneva: International Labour Organization.

Bardach, E. and Kagan, R.A. (1982). *Going by the book : the problem of regulatory unreasonableness*. Philadelphia: Temple University Press.

BBC (2019). *BBC - Home*. [online] BBC Homepage. Available at: <https://www.bbc.co.uk>.

Bell, E., Bryman, A. and Harley, B., (2011). *Business research methods*. Oxford university press.

Belton, I., MacDonald, A., Wright, G. and Hamlin, I., 2019. Improving the practical application of the Delphi method in group-based judgment: A six-step prescription for a well-founded and defensible process. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 147, pp.72-82.

Bercusson, B. ed., 2006. *European labour law and the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights*. Baden-Baden: Nomos.

Bilo, C., Machado, A., Carolina, Bacil and Fabianna (2020.). *Social protection in Sudan - system overview and programme mapping*. [online] Available at: <https://www.econstor.eu/bitstream/10419/234896/1/RR53-Social-protection-in-Sudan-system-overview.pdf> [Accessed 2 Jan. 2023].

Bird, C.M., 2005. How I stopped dreading and learned to love transcription. *Qualitative inquiry*, 11(2), pp.226-248.

- Blaxter, L., Hughes, C. and Tight, M., 2010. *How to research*. McGraw-Hill Education (UK).
- Boeije, HR and Hox, J.J., 2005. Data collection, primary vs. secondary. *Encyclopedia of social measurement, 1*, pp.593-599.
- Booth, P., 2018. The Enforcement of the Ordinance and Statute of Labourers in Cheshire, 1349 to 1374. *Archives: The Journal of the British Records Association*.
- Botero, J.C., Djankov, S., Porta, R.L., Lopez-de-Silanes, F. and Shleifer, A., 2004. The regulation of labor. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics, 119(4)*, pp.1339-1382.
- Boyce, C. and Neale, P., 2006. Conducting in-depth interviews: A guide for designing and conducting in-depth interviews for evaluation input.
- Braun, V. and Clarke, V., 2006. Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative research in psychology, 3(2)*, pp.77-101.
- Braun, V. and Clarke, V., 2012. Thematic analysis.
- Braun, V. and Clarke, V., 2012. *Thematic analysis*. American Psychological Association.
- Brekhus, W.H., Galliher, J.F. and Gubrium, J.F., 2005. The need for thin description. *Qualitative Inquiry, 11(6)*, pp.861-879.
- Bricki, N. and Green, J., 2007. A guide to using qualitative research methodology.
- Britannica (n.d.). Encyclopedia Britannica. In: *Encyclopædia Britannica*. [online] Available at: <https://www.britannica.com>.
- Bryant, G. (1984). *The Working Woman Report*. Simon & Schuster.
- Bryman, A., 2016. *Social research methods*. Oxford university press.
- Bukhari, S. Al-B., 1997, Arabic and English. Translated by Dr. Muhammad Muhsin Khan. Riyadh: Darussalam Publishers.
- Burrell, G. and Morgan, G., 2016. *Sociological paradigms and organisational analysis: Elements of the sociology of corporate life*. Routledge.
- Castles, S., 2014. International migration at a crossroads. *Citizenship Studies, 18(2)*, pp.190-207.

CHALLENGE FUND FOR YOUTH EMPLOYMENT Sudan Scoping Report. (2021). [online] Available at: <https://fundforyouthemployment.nl/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/Scoping-Report-Sudan-2021-Challenge-Fund-for-Youth-Employment.pdf>.

Charnovitz, S., 2000. The International Labour Organization in its second century. *Max Planck Yearbook of United Nations Law Online*, 4(1), pp.147-184.

Chartered Institute of Personnel and Development

Chisholm, H. ed., 1913. *The Britannica Year Book*. Encyclopedia Britannica Company

CIPD (2021). *Maternity, Paternity & Adoption Rights | Factsheets*. [online] CIPD. Available at: <https://www.cipd.co.uk/knowledge/fundamentals/emp-law/maternity-paternity-rights/factsheet#gref>.

CIPD (2022). *Bullying & Harassment at Work | Factsheets*. [online] CIPD. Available at: <https://www.cipd.co.uk/knowledge/fundamentals/emp-law/harassment/factsheet#gref>.

CIPD (2022). *Diversity and Inclusion in the Workplace | Factsheets*. [online] CIPD. Available at: <https://www.cipd.co.uk/knowledge/fundamentals/relations/diversity/factsheet#gref>.

CIPD. (2022). *Data Protection and GDPR in the Workplace | Factsheets*. [online] Available at: <https://www.cipd.co.uk/knowledge/fundamentals/emp-law/data-protection/factsheet#gref>.

CIPD. (n.d.). *Disability at work | CIPD Viewpoint*. [online] Available at: <https://www.cipd.co.uk/news-views/viewpoint/disability-work#gref>.

Claes, M.T., 1999. Women, men and management styles. *Int'l Lab. Rev.*, 138, p.431.

Clarke, V. and Braun, V., 2013. Teaching thematic analysis: Overcoming challenges and developing strategies for effective learning. *The psychologist*, 26(2).

Clauwaert, S. and Schömann, I., 2012. The crisis and national labour law reforms: a mapping exercise. *European Labour Law Journal*, 3(1), pp.54-69.

Coslovsky, S.V., 2014. Flying under the radar? The state and the enforcement of labour laws in Brazil. *Oxford Development Studies*, 42(2), pp.190-216.

Country Cooperation Strategy for WHO and Sudan 2022-2025. (n.d.). [online] Available at: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/353562/9789290229698-eng.pdf?sequence=1> [Accessed 15 Nov. 2022].

Cox, R.W., 1980. Labor and hegemony: a reply. *International Organization*, 34(1), pp.159-176.

Coxson, C.R., 1998. The 1998 ILO Declaration on Fundamental Principles and Rights at Work: Promoting Labor Law Reforms Through the ILO as an Alternative to Imposing Coercive Trade Sanctions. *Dick. J. Int'l L.*, 17, p.469.

Creswell, J.W. and Poth, C.N. (2016). *Qualitative inquiry and research design: Choosing among five approaches*. Sage publications.

Crisis Group. (n.d.). *Crisis Group*. [online] Available at: <https://www.crisisgroup.org>.

Dagdeviren, H. and Mahran, H.A., 2004. Trade and industry in Sudan: What role for poverty alleviation. *Final draft, UNDP project on macroeconomic policy and poverty alleviation in the Arab region. Khartoum: UNDP office in Sudan*.

Davidov, G. and Langille, B. (eds) (2011). *The idea of labour law*. Oxford University Press.

Davidov, G. and Langille, B. eds., 2013. *The Idea of Labour Law*. OUP Oxford.

Davis, K.E. and Trebilcock, M.J., 2001. Legal reforms and development. *Third World Quarterly*, 22(1), pp.21-36.

Deakin, S. (2016). *The contribution of labour law to economic development and growth*. Centre for Business Research, University of Cambridge.

Deakin, S., Lele, P. and Siems, M., 2007. The evolution of labour law: Calibrating and comparing regulatory regimes. *International Labour Review*, 146(3-4), pp.133-162.

Deakin, S., Lele, P. and Siems, M., 2007. The evolution of labour law: Calibrating and comparing regulatory regimes. *International Labour Review*, 146(3-4), pp.133-162.

Dickens, L., 2007. The road is long: thirty years of equality legislation in Britain. *British journal of industrial relations*, 45(3), pp.463-494.

Djankov, S. and Ramalho, R. (2009). Employment laws in developing countries. *Journal of Comparative Economics*, 37(1), pp.3-13.

Drucker, P.F., 1954. Management by objectives and self-control. *Practice of management*.

Easterby-Smith, M., Thorpe, R. and Jackson, P.R. (2012). *Management research*. Sage.

Easterby-Smith, M., Thorpe, R., Jackson, P. and Lowe, A., 2008. *Management research*, 3rd edn London.

Einarsen, S., Hoel, H., Zapf, D. and Cooper, C. eds., 2010. *Bullying and harassment in the workplace: Developments in theory, research, and practice*. CRC press.

Ely, M., Anzul, M., Vinz, R. and Downing, M., 1997. *On Writing Qualitative Research: Living by Words* (No. 12). Psychology Press.

Embassy of Sudan. (n.d.). *Home*. [online] Available at: <https://www.sudanembassy.org> [Accessed 12 June 2021].

EnergyNet Corporate Site. (n.d.). *Welcome*. [online] Available at: <http://www.energynet.co.uk> [Accessed 2 May 2023].

Fahey, R.S. and Spaulding, J.L., 2016. *Kingdoms of the Sudan*. Routledge.

Fell, E.V. and Dyban, M., 2017. Against Discrimination: Equality Act 2010 (UK). *The European Proceedings of Social & Behavioural Sciences (EpSBS). Vol. 19: Lifelong Wellbeing in the World (WELLSO 2016).—Nicosia, 2017., 192016*, pp.188-194.

Ferraro, T., Pais, L. and Dos Santos, N.R., 2015. Decent work: An aim for all made by all. *International Journal of Social Sciences*, 4(3), pp.30-42.

Field, S., 1990. Without the Law-Professor Arthurs and the Early Factory Inspectorate. *JL & Soc'y*, 17, p.445.

Flanagan, R.J. and Gould, W.B., 2003. *International labor standards: Globalization, trade, and public policy*. Stanford University Press.

Floyd, L., Steenson, W., Coulthard, A., Williams, D. and Pickering, A.C., 2017. *Employment, labour and industrial law in Australia*. Cambridge University Press.

Forbes (2019). Forbes. *Forbes*. [onlin'] Available at: <https://www.forbe'.com>.

Fox, M.L. and Gaal, M.S., 20'8. *Working out of Poverty: Job creation and the quality of growth in Africa*. World Bank Publications.

Fredette, D., 2019. The United States' Global Ranking Regarding Workers' Rights: Comparing Three Countries' Positions On The Right To Organize And Collective Bargaining. *Government Law Review*, 1(12), p.23762.

Fudge, J. and McCann, D. (2015). *Unacceptable Forms of Work: a global and comparative study*.

Genç, R., 2017. The importance of communication in sustainability & sustainable strategies. *Procedia Manufacturing*, 8, pp.511-516.

Ghauri, P., Grønhaug, K. and Strange, R., 2020. *Research methods in business studies*. Cambridge University Press.

Given, L.M. (ed) (2008). *The Sage encyclopedia of qualitative research methods*. Sage publications

Glaser, B.G. (1992). *Basics of grounded theory analysis: Emergence vs. forcing*. Sociology press.

Goodman, C.M., 1987. The Delphi technique: a critique. *Journal of advanced nursing*, 12(6), pp.729-734.

Gottfried, R.S., 2010. *Black death*. Simon and Schuster.

Guest, D., 2004. Flexible 'memployment contracts, the psychological contract and employee outcomes: an analysis and review of the evidence. *International journal of management reviews*, 5(1), pp.1-19.

Hale, S., 1997. Gender politics in Sudan: Islamism, socialism, and the state. *African Studies Review*, 40(3), pp.186-188.

Halim, A.A., 2019. A Woman's Place: Can international law assist in removing gender disparities in Sudanese Laws?. *Ahfad Journal*, 36(1), pp.33-49.

Hamid, M., Thron, C. and Fageeri, S., 2021. Demographics of Sudanese University Students in Relation to Regional Conflict and Underdevelopment. *Social Sciences*, 10(3), p.89.

Harwood, T.G. and Garry, T. (2003). *An overview of content analysis*. The marketing review -Volume 3(4)

Helfer, L.R., 2006. Understanding change in international organizations: Globalization and innovation in the ILO. *Vand. L. Rev.*, 59, p.649.

Hennink, M.M., Kaiser, B.N. and Marconi, V.C., 2017. Code saturation versus meaning saturation: how many interviews are enough?

Hepple, B., 2010. The new single equality act in Britain. *The Equal Rights Review*, 5, pp.11-24.

Heyes, J. and Rychly, L., 2013. Introduction: The origins and development of labour administration. In *Labour Administration in Uncertain Times* (pp. 1-17). Edward Elgar Publishing.

Hodson, R., 2001. *Dignity at work*. Cambridge University Press.

Holt, P.M. and Daly, M.W., 2019. *The history of the Sudan: from the coming of Islam to the present day*. Routledge.

<https://athinkingperson.com/2012/12/02/who-said-what-gets-measured-gets-managed>
[Accessed '2 Mar. 2022].

<https://www.aesanetwork.org/research-onion-a-systematic-approach-to-designing-research-methodology>[Accessed 15 September 2021]

https://www.ilo.org/wcmsp5/groups/public/@ed_norm/@ipecc/documents/publication/wcms_648801.pdf [Accessed 2 Feb. 2023].

Htun, M., Jensenius, F.R. and Nelson-Nuñez, J., 2019. Gender-discriminatory laws and women's economic agency. *Social Politics: International Studies in Gender, State & Society*, 26(2), pp.193-222.

Hughes, S. and Haworth, N., 2013. *International Labour Organization (ILO): Coming in from the Cold*. Routledge.

Hughes, S. and Haworth, N., 2013. *International Labour Organization (ILO): Coming in from the Cold*. Routledge.

Human Rights Watch (2021). *Sudan: Events of 2021*. [online] Human Rights Watch. Available at: <https://www.hrw.org/world-report/2022/country-chapters/sudan>.

Hussmanns, R. and Jeu, B.D., 2002. *ILO compendium of official statistics on employment in the informal sector*. International Labour Organization.

Hyde, A. (2006). What is labor law?

Hyde, K.F. (2000). Recognizing deductive processes in qualitative research. *Qualitative market research: An international journal*.

ILO (1999) Decent Work: Report of the Director General, International Labour Conference, 87th Session. Geneva: International Labour Office

ILO (2019). *International Labour Standards on Occupational Safety and Health*. [online] Ilo.org. Available at: <https://www.ilo.org/global/standards/subjects-covered-by-international-labour-standards/occupational-safety-and-health/lang--en/index.htm>.

ILO Declaration on Fundamental Principles and Rights at Work and its Follow-up. (1998). [online] Available at: https://www.ilo.org/wcmsp5/groups/public/---ed_norm/---declaration/documents/normativeinstrument/wcms_716594.pdf.

Ilo.org. (2019). *ILO Declaration on Fundamental Principles and Rights at Work (DECLARATION)*. [online] Available at: <http://www.ilo.org/declaration/lang--en/index.htm>.

Imf.org. (2012). *IMF -- International Monetary Fund Home Page*. [online] Available at: <https://www.imf.org>.

Integrated Strategy on Fundamental Principles and Rights at Work. (2017). [online] Available at: International Labor Organization. (2014). A roadmap toward a national employment policy for Sudan, Cairo, Egypt: Author, Retrieved from <https://www.ilo.org> [Accessed 15 July, 2021].

INTERNATIONAL LABOUR OFFICE (2021). *FUTURE OF DIVERSITY*

International Labour Organization (2019). *Decent Work*. [online] Ilo.org. Available at: <https://www.ilo.org/global/topics/decent-work/lang--en/index.htm>.

International Labour Organization (2019). *Informal economy*. [online] Ilo.org. Available at: [https://www.ilo.org/global/topics/employment-promotion/informal-economy/lang--en/index.htm](https://www.ilo.org/global/topics/employment-promotion/informal-economy/lang-en/index.htm).

International Labour Organization (2019). *International Labour Organization*. [online] Ilo.org. Available at: <https://www.ilo.org>.

International Monetary Fund (IMF), Sudan: 2013 Article IV Consultation.

International Trade Union Confederation, Global Rights Index: *The World's Worst Countries for Workers* (2021) [online] Available from <https://www.ituc-csi.org> [Accessed 25 August, 2021].

Internet Archive. (2018). *Holy Quran - Yusuf Ali's Translation - 1946 Edition : Free Download, Borrow, and Streaming : Internet Archive*. [online] Available at: <https://archive.org/details/HolyQurAnYusufAliTranslation1946Edition> [Accessed 12 Jul. 2019].

Investopedia. (n.d.). Zakat: The Basic Rules for One of the Five Pillars of Islam. [online] Available at: <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/z/zakat.asp#> [Accessed 29 Dec. 2022].

issuu. (n.d.). *SUDANESE LABOR LAW*. [online] Available at: https://issuu.com/halayassin/docs/bgs_report_2020_final_design/s/11774067 [Accessed 18 Jan. 2023].

Kargwell, S., 2008. Is the glass ceiling kept in place in Sudan? Gendered dilemma of the work-life balance. *Gender in Management: An international journal*, 23(3), pp.209-224.

Kelly, G., 1955. *The psychology of personal constructs* (New York, WN Norton and Company Inc).

Kirchner, J. and Morgenroth, S., 2018. German Employment and Labour Law. In *Key aspects of German employment and labour law* (pp. 1-23). Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg.

Kjellgren, A., Jones-Pauly, C., El-Tayeb Alyn, H., Tadesse, E. and Vermehren, A., 2014. Sudan social safety net assessment.

Kothari, C.R., 2004. *Research methodology: Methods and techniques*. New Age International.

- Kuruvilla, S. and Verma, A. (2006). International Labor Standards, Soft Regulation, and National Government Roles. *Journal of Industrial Relations*, 48(1), pp.41–58.
- La Porta, R.L., Lopez-de-Silanes, F., Shleifer, A. and Vishny, R.W., 1998. Law and finance. *Journal of political economy*, 106(6), pp.1113-1155.
- Labor Management Procedures (LMPs). (n.d.). [online] Available at: <https://documents1.worldbank.org/curated/en/278381620060009583/pdf/Labor-Management-Procedures-Sudan-Family-Support-Project-P173521.pdf> [Accessed 1 Nov. 2022].
- Lapadat, J.C. and Lindsay, A.C., 1999. Transcription in research and practice: From standardization of technique to interpretive positionings. *Qualitative inquiry*, 5(1), pp.64-86.
- Lee, T., Geiger, M., Alamir, M. and Nishiuchi, T., 2013. Sudan Economic Brief: Recent Economic Developments. *World Bank, Issue*, (2012-02).
- Lockwood, G., Henderson, C. and Thornicroft, G., 2012. The Equality Act 2010 and mental health. *The British Journal of Psychiatry*, 200(3), pp.182-183.
- Longman, K.A. and Lafreniere, S.L. (2011). Moving Beyond the Stained Glass Ceiling. *Advances in Developing Human Resources*, 14(1), pp.45–61. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/1523422311427429>.
- Machado, A.C., Bilo, C. and Helmy, I., 2018. *The role of zakat in the provision of social protection: A comparison between Jordan, Palestine and Sudan* (No. 168). Working Paper.
- Maguire, M. and Delahunt, B., 2017. Doing a thematic analysis: A practical, step-by-step guide for learning and teaching scholars. *All Ireland Journal of Higher Education*, 9(3).
- Majah, I., and Muhammad, A. A., 1993. Sunan Ibn-i-Majah. Translated by Tufail Ansari, Lahore, Kazi Publication.
- Mason, J., 2002. *Qualitative researching* Sage Publications Limited.
- Matusik, S.F. and Hill, C.W., 1998. The utilization of contingent work, knowledge creation, and competitive advantage. *Academy of management review*, 23(4), pp.680-697.
- McCann, D. and Fudge, J., 2017. Unacceptable forms of w'rk: A multidimensional model. *International labour review*, 156(2), pp.147-184.

- McDonald, K.S. and Hite, L.M., 1998. Exploring the glass ceiling: An exploration of gender differences in management-development experiences. *Journal of Management Education*, 22(2), pp.242-254.
- Meehan, T., Vermeer, C. and Windsor, C., 20'0. Patients' perceptions of seclusion: a qualitative investigation. *Journal of advanced nursing*, 31(2), pp.370-377.
- Melnikovas, A., 2018. Towards an explicit research methodology: Adapting research onion model for futures studies. *Journal of Futures Studies*, 23(2), pp.29-44.
- Middle East Eye. (n.d.). *Coronavirus: Sudan's doctors beaten by police after responding to pandemic*. [online] Available at: <https://www.middleeasteye.net/news/coronavirus-responding-crisis-sudanese-doctor-still-under-attack> [Accessed 15 Jan. 2023].
- Mishra, L., 2012. History of labour rights. *Social Change*, 42(3), pp.335-357.
- Mitchell, R., Petra, M.A.H.Y. and Gahan, P., 2014. The evolution of labor law in India: an overview and commentary on regulatory objectives and development. *Asian Journal of Law and Society*, 1(2), pp.413-453.
- Monks, K., 2007. *The Business Impact of Equality & Diversity: the international evidence*. National Centre for Partnership & Performance.
- Mukhopadhyay, S., Gupta, R, A. (2014) *Survey of Qualitative Research Methodology in Strategy Research and Implication for Indian Researchers*. Vol 1
- Musannaf , 2017. *The Musannaf of Abd al-Razzaq*, Translated by Abul Ulamuhi Uddin Jehangir
- Mustafa Özbilgin, Anne-Marie Greene and Gill Kirton (2009). *Equality, Diversity and Inclusion at Work*. Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Namie, G. and Namie, R., 2009. *Bully at work: What you can do to stop the hurt and reclaim your dignity on the job*. Sourcebooks, Inc..
- Oette, L. and Babiker, M.A., 2014. The Rule of Law and Human Rights in Sudan: challenges and prospects for reform. *Institutional Reforms Series*, (2).
- Patton, M.Q., 2002. Two decades of developments in qualitative inquiry: A personal, experiential perspective. *Qualitative Social Work: Research and Practice*.

Patton, M.Q., 2002. *Qualitative research & evaluation methods*. sage.

Piore, M.J. and Schrank, A., 2008. Toward managed flexibility: The revival of labor inspection in the Latin world. *International Labor Review*, 147(1), pp.1-23.

Pires, R., 2008. Promoting sustainable compliance: Styles of labor inspection and compliance outcomes in Brazil. *International Labor Review*, 147(2-3), pp.199-229.

PROMOTING EQUITY PROMOTING DIVERSITY AND INCLUSION THROUGH WORKPLACE ADJUSTMENTS A PRACTICAL GUIDE. (n.d.). Available at: https://www.ilo.org/wcmsp5/groups/public/---ed_norm/---declaration/documents/publication/wcms_536630.pdf.

Pusch, T. and Braeckeler-Kogel, V. 2021. Employment Law Overview Germany (2021-2022) Available at <https://knowledge.leglobal.org/> Accessed 7 July 2021

Quiriosity (2012). *Who says, 'What gets measured gets managed'?* [online] A Thinking Person, a.k.a. Cogit8R. Available at:

Radio Dabanga. (n.d.). *Massive youth unemployment in Sudan*. [online] Available at: <https://www.dabangasudan.org/en/all-news/article/massive-youth-unemployment-in-sudan>.

Riessman, C.K., 1993. *Narrative analysis* (Vol. 30). Sage.

Rodgers, G., Lee, E., Swepston, L. and Van Daele, J., 2009. The International Labour Organization and the quest for social justice, 1919-2009.

Rowe and Wright (1999): *The Delphi technique as a forecasting tool: issues and analysis*. *International Journal of Forecasting*, Vol 15

Rowe, G. and Wright, G., 2001. Expert opinions in forecasting: the role of the Delphi technique. In *Principles of forecasting* (pp. 125-144). Springer, Boston, MA.

Saunders, M., Lewis, P. and Thornhill, A., 2015. *Research Methods for Business Students*.

Saunders, M., Lewis, P. and Thornhill, A., 2019. *Research Methods for Business Students*.

Sayer, A., 2007. Dignity at work: Broadening the agenda. *Organization*, 14(4), pp.565-581.

Sekaran, U. and Bougie, R. (2016). *Research methods for business: A skill building approach*. John Wiley & Sons.

Sennett, R. and Cobb, J., 1973. *The Hidden Injuries of Class*, NY: Alfred K.

Sidahmed, A.S. and Sidahmed, A., 2004. *Sudan*. Routledge.

Singh, A. and Zammit, A., 2004. Labour standards and the 'Race to the Bottom': Rethinking globalization and workers' rights from developmental and solidaristic perspectives. *Oxford review of economic policy*, 20(1), pp.85-104.

Skulmoski, G.J., Hartman, F.T. and Krahn, J. (2007). *The Delphi method for graduate research*. *Journal of Information Technology Education: Research*, 6(1), pp.1-21.

SLFS, draft Report, 2011.

Social Protection and Human Rights. (2015). *Unemployment protection - Social Protection and Human Rights*. [online] Available at: <https://socialprotection-humanrights.org/key-issues/social-protection-systems/unemployment-protection/>.

SOCIAL PROTECTION MATTERS PREVENTION AND PROTECTION PROMOTING OPPORTUNITIES ACCESS TO ESSENTIAL GOODS AND SERVICES 3. (2004). [online] Available at: <https://www.ilo.org/public/english/protection/download/newsletter/2004/spring-e.pdf>.

Social Work and Policy Review, 8(1), pp.59–70. doi:10.1111/aswp.12025.

Solomon, C. (2021). *Inside Arabia*. [online] Inside Arabia. Available at: <https://insidearabia.com>.

Saunders, M., Lewis, P. and Thornhill, A., 2007. *Research methods for business students*

Spaulding, Jay L. , Sikainga, Ahmad Alawad , Collins, Robert O. , Sabr, Mohy el Din , Al-Shahi, Ahmed S. and Unit, Economist Intelligence. "Sudan". *Encyclopedia Britannica*, 9 Jul. 2021, <https://www.britannica.com/place/Sudan>.

springmag.ca. (n.d.). *Home - Spring*. [online] Available at: <https://springmag.ca> [Accessed 22 May 2022].

Standing, G., 2008. The ILO: An agency for globalization?. *Development and Change*, 39(3), pp.355-384.

Stati'ta. (n.d.). *Sudan - unemployment rate 1999-2019*. [online] Available at: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/727151/unemployment-rate-in-sudan/>.

Sudan Labour Act (1997)

Sudan.unfpa.org. 2018. *Sudan Gender Justice & The Law*. [online] Available at: <https://sudan.unfpa.org/sites/default/files/pub-pdf/Sudan> [Accessed 28 August 2021].

Sudan's Workers on the March for Their Rights, (2020) [online] Middle East Solidarity Magazine Issue 15. Available from https://menasolidaritynetwork.files.wordpress.com/2020/12/mesm_issue15final.pdf [Accessed 25 August, 2021].

suna-sd.net. (n.d.). *SUDAN NEWS AGENCY*. [online] Available at: <https://suna-sd.net/en> [Accessed 17 Feb. 2023].

Ten Have, P. (2004). *Understanding qualitative research and ethnomethodology*. Sage.

Terry, G., Hayfield, N., Clarke, V. and Braun, V., 2017. Thematic analysis. *The SAGE handbook of qualitative research in psychology*, 2, pp.17-37.

The national archives (2019). *Legislation.gov.uk*. [online] Legislation.gov.uk. Available at: <https://www.legislation.gov.uk>.

The World Bank (2022). *World Development Indicators*. [online] Worldbank.org. Available at: <https://datatopics.worldbank.org/world-development-indicators/>.

Thesismind, 2019. *Analysis of Saunders Research Onion*. [online] <https://thesismind.com>. Available at: <https://thesismind.com/analysis-of-saunders-research-onion/> [Accessed 3 September 2021].

Thompson, E.P., 1963. *The Making of the English Working Class*.

Tønnessen, L., 2019. Women at work in Sudan: Marital privilege or constitutional right? *Social Politics: International Studies in Gender, State & Society*, 26(2), pp.223-244.

Trading Economics (2022). *TRADING ECONOMICS | 20 million INDICATORS FROM 196 COUNTRIES*. [online] Tradingeconomics.com. Available at: <https://tradingeconomics.com>.

Tranfield, D. and Starkey, K., 1998. The nature, social organization and promotion of management research: Towards policy. *British journal of Management*, 9(4), pp.341-353.

Turner, D. and Pirie, E. (2016). *Problems of involvement and detachment: a critical approach to researching live event experiences*. London: Palgrave Macmillan [online], pages 17-35. Available from: <https://doi.org>

United Nations (1948). *Universal Declaration of Human Rights*. [online] United Nations. Available at: <https://www.un.org/en/about-us/universal-declaration-of-human-rights>.

United Nations, Department of Economic and Social Affairs, Population Division (2009). Trends in International Migrant Stock: <http://esa.un.org/migration>

United States Institute of Peace. (n.d.). *42 Months on, How Does Sudan's Democracy Movement Endure?* [online] Available at: <https://www.usip.org/publications/2022/10/42-months-how-does-sudans-democracy-movement-endure>.

UWS -University Ethics Committee-*Guidelines for Ethical Practice in Research and Scholarship* (Revised September 2016)

Von Hippel, C., Mangum, S.L., Greenberger, D.B., Heneman, R.L. and Skoglund, J.D., 1997. Temporary employment: Can organizations and employees both win?. *Academy of Management Perspectives*, 11(1), pp.93-104.

Vosko, L.F. and Andrew, C., 2002. Temporary Work: The Gendered Rise of a Precarious Employment Relationship. *The American Review of Canadian Studies*, 32(1), p.162.

Vosko, L.F., 2002. Decent Work' The Shifting Role of the ILO and the Struggle for Global Social Justice. *Global Social Policy*, 2(1), pp.19-46.

WageIndicator.org. (2018). *Salary Checks -World Wide Wage Comparison*. [online] Available at: <https://wageindicator.org>.

Walliman, N., 2005. *Your research project: a step-by-step guide for the first-time researcher*. Sage.

Waters, S. (2022). *How to Break the Glass Ceiling at work and Unleash Your Potential*. [online] www.betterup.com. Available at: <https://www.betterup.com/blog/breaking-glass-ceilings>.

Weiss, M., 2017. Introduction to European Labor Law. *Edizione GENNAIO*

Weiss, M., 2017. The future of labour law in Europe: Rise or fall of the European social model?. *European Labour Law Journal*, 8(4), pp.344-356.

Whitworth, S., 1994. *Feminism and International Relations*, New York: St.

Wilkinson, D. and Birmingham, P. (2003). *Using research instruments: A guide for researchers*. Psychology Press.

Wilson, J. (2014). *Essentials of business research: A guide to doing your research project*. Sage.

World Bank (2014), Doing Business (2015). *Going Beyond Efficiency* (Washington, DC: International Bank for Reconstruction and Development).

World Bank. (2019). *World Bank Group - International Development, Poverty, & Sustainability*. [online] Available at: <https://www.worldbank.org>.

Worldbank.org. (2019). *Unemployment, total (% of total labour force) (modeled ILO estimate) - Sudan / Data*. [online] Available at: <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/SL.UEM.TOTL.ZS?locations=SD>.

www.ilo.org. (n.d.). *Applying and promoting International Labour Standards*. [online] Available at: <https://www.ilo.org/global/standards/applying-and-promoting-international-labour-standards/lang--en/index.htm>.

www.ilo.org. (n.d.). *Eliminating Violence and Harassment in the World of Work (Violence and Harassment in the World of Work)*. [online] Available at: <https://www.ilo.org/global/topics/violence-harassment/lang--en/index.htm>.

www.ilo.org. (n.d.). *Inclusive Labor Markets, Labor Relations and Working Conditions Branch (INWORK) (INWORK)*. [online] Available at: <http://www.ilo.org/public/english/protection/condtrav/pdf/infosheets/w-1.pdf> [Accessed 28 Dec. 2022].

www.ilo.org. (n.d.). *Labour inspection systems, policies and methods (Labour administration and inspection)*. [online] Available at: <https://www.ilo.org/global/topics/labour-administration-inspection/areasofwork/policies-and-methods/lang--en/index.htm#:~:text=Labour%20inspection%20is%20a%20public> [Accessed 16 Mar. 2023].

www.ilo.org. (n.d.). *Measuring decent work (MULTILATERALS)*. [online] Available

www.macrotrends.net. (n.d.). *Sudan Unemployment Rate 1991-2022*. [online] Available at: <https://www.macrotrends.net/countries/SDN/sudan/unemployment-rate#:~:text=Unemployment%20refers%20to%20the%20share>.

www.oecd.org. (n.d.). *Regulatory policy - OECD*. [online] Available at: <http://www.oecd.org/gov/regulatory-policy/>.

www.oxfamamerica.org. (n.d.). *Oxfam America*. [online] Available at: <https://www.oxfamamerica.org>.

www.salaryexplorer.com. (n.d.). *Salary Explorer | Salary and Cost of Living Comparison*. [online] Available at: <http://www.salaryexplorer.com>.

www.social-protection.org. (n.d.). ILO | Social Protection Platform. [online] Available at: <https://www.social-protection.org/gimi/ShowCountryProfile.action?iso=SD> [Accessed 17 Dec. 2022].

2012-2017.usaid.gov. (n.d.). *Archive - US Agency for International Development*. [online] Available at: <https://2012-2017.usaid.gov>. [Accessed 22 Mar. 2022].

APPENDICES

Appendix 1-Information Sheet

Participation Information Sheet(s)

Name of School: Business and Creative Industries

Degree: Doctor of Business Administration (DBA)

Research Title: *“Sudanese Labour Act 1997... Beyond Two Decades In-action”: A Critical Gap Analysis*

I would like to kindly invite you to participate in this research study. Before you make a decision, you should know why the study is being undertaken and what it entails. Please take the time to thoroughly read the following information. Please do not hesitate to ask questions if anything you read does not make sense to you or if you require additional information. Take your time to consider whether or not you wish to participate.

❖ **Confidentiality, Anonymity and Protection Agreement:**

All participants in this study will stay anonymous, and any information provided by the respondents, such as names, will not be revealed. Any information provided by the participant will be encrypted and protected by a pass code, with only the research team having access.

❖ **Please read all details below to take part:**

My name is Sulafa M. Gawish and I am a Doctor of Business Administration student at University of the West of Scotland (UWS). I am conducting a research project for my doctorate qualification, and I’ve decided to focus on: *“The Sudanese Labour Act of 1997: Beyond Two Decades In-action: A Critical Gap Analysis- to Suit a Contemporary Era of Employment Regulations & Best Practice Equality Acts”*. The School of Business and Creative Industries at the University of the West of Scotland has agreed to let me conduct the research.

❖ **What is the investigation purpose?**

The aim of this research is to critically investigate the current Sudanese Labour Act of 1997 last updated in the year 1997 to assess its fitness for purpose for the purpose of obtaining the professional doctorate degree *“Doctor of Business Administration”* (DBA) from the University of the West of Scotland.

The research questions and objectives are as follows:

Research Questions:

- What are the key aspects of the Sudanese Labour Act?
- What challenges can be identified within the Act in the context of international best practices?

- What strategies can be in place to ensure the Sudanese Labour Act meets the twenty-first century needs?

Research Objectives:

- To identify the key aspects of the Sudanese Labour Act.
- To assess the critical challenges the Sudanese Labour Act faces in light of international best practices
- To identify the strategies and techniques for updating the Labour Act in order to suit Sudan's current HR needs.

❖ **Do you have to take part?**

Engagement in this research study is completely voluntary. As a result, interviewers are not obligated to respond to the questions. A permission (consent) form will be given to all participants to complete, confirming their agreement to participate in the study and their willingness to withdraw at any point in time without any repercussions.

❖ **How will you take part?**

Interviews will take place using face discussions and the conversation will be recorded. Due to Covid19 restrictions the conversation may take place virtually.

❖ **What is your role in this project?**

The questions are based on your knowledge and experience of the Sudanese labour Act of 1997. Its applicability in a contemporary employment world and what are the evident gaps you believe to encounter in relation to your knowledge and understanding of best practices and global employment Laws and Equality Acts; and your suitable suggestions to bridge these gaps. Answering these questions will take place in around 2-3 sessions/cycles each constituting a duration of approximately 30-40 minutes to complete. Privacy, confidentiality, preventing risk and harm to both sides (interviewer and interviewees), and information integrity have all been taken into account in line with the **Social Research Association's (2003) guidelines**. Furthermore, if any inconvenient inquiries arise during questioning, the participants are not obliged to respond.

❖ **Why have you been invited to take part?**

You have been chosen as the primary study participants because of your professional expertise in Human Resources Management and your understanding of the practical implementation of the Sudanese Labour Act of 1997. And you are believed to have the relevant knowledge and experience to answer those questions.

❖ **What are the potential risks you may face in taking part?**

The questions are designed in a way that ensures your privacy and identity are protected, and there are no obligations for you to answer all or any questions you don't want to answer. In addition, no physical, legal, or psychological issues will be revealed throughout the research.

❖ **What happens to the information you give?**

The information you provide will be kept in a safe, password-protected file. Unless the respondents request it, any references to individuals will be removed. Furthermore, once the research has been effectively submitted, all of the

information gathered throughout the research will be deleted. The University of the West of Scotland is registered with the Information Commissioner's Office, which oversees the implementation of the Data Protection Act 2018. All personal information concerning participants will be handled in compliance with the Data Protection Act of 2018. Thank you for taking the time to carefully read the entire document. You are encouraged to contact us should you have any questions or concerns about the form.

❖ **What happens next?**

If you agree to take part in this study, a consent form will be sent to your email address, and you will need to sign it and return it to confirm your participation. However, if you do not choose to participate, you do not need to sign, and we appreciate you for taking the time to read the entire form. If you have any comments or suggestions, please feel free to email them as soon as the investigation is over.

The School of Business and Ethics Committee at the University of the West of Scotland granted ethical approval to the study. If you have any questions, concerns, or would want to contact an independent body that is part of the university Ethics Committee during or after the research, please feel free to contact the following address:

School Ethics Committee
School of Business and Creative Industries
Paisley Campus
University of the West of Scotland,
High Street, Paisley. PA1 2BE

Researcher's email: [REDACTED]

Supervisor's e-mail: [REDACTED]

Participant Consent Form

School of Business & Creative Industries

Doctor of Business Administration

(DBA)

Student Name: *Sulafa M. Gawish*

**Research Title: “*Sudanese Labour Act 1997... Beyond Two Decades In-action*”:
*A Critical Gap Analysis***

- ❖ I..... freely consent to participate in this research study.
- ❖ I certify that I have read and comprehended the *Participant Information Sheet* presented for the above study, and that the researcher has adequately answered any questions I may well have.
- ❖ I acknowledge that, even if I agree to take part right now, I can withdraw at any point of time or decline to answer any question without any repercussions.
- ❖ I consent to participate in the interview and that my conversation will be recorded.
- ❖ I acknowledge that I have the right to withdraw consent to use data from my conversation at any moment of time throughout the research project, and that the material will be deleted if I choose to do so.
- ❖ I was given written explanations of the study’s objectives and purpose, as well as the chance to ask questions about it.
- ❖ I am aware that my participation in this study will not benefit me directly or personally.
- ❖ I am aware that any information I offer to this study will be kept private and confidential.
- ❖ I acknowledge that my identity will be kept anonymous in any report based on the findings of this study. This will be achieved by altering my name and concealing any information that may expose my identity or the identities of those I speak about.
- ❖ I accept that if I advise the researcher that I or someone else is in danger, they may be compelled to disclose

this to the appropriate authorities - they will consult with me first, but they may be obligated to report with or without my approval.

- ❖ I understand that under the **General Data Protection Regulation** (GDPR), signed consent forms will be kept in the University data storage department until the examination board certifies the thesis results.
- ❖ I recognise that a transcript of my interview, with all identifiable information deleted, will be maintained under GDPR policy until the exam board approves and confirms the thesis results.
- ❖ I understand that, under the **Freedom of Information Legislation**, I have the right to access the information I've submitted at any point of time while it's being retained in the manner illustrated above.
- ❖ I recognise that I am free to contact any of the persons engaged in the research project to obtain more clarity and further information.

Participant's Signature

Signature:

Date:

Researcher's Signature

To the best of knowledge, I believe that the participant has provided informed consent to take part in this study.

Signature:

Date:

Appendix 3-Participant Invitation Email

Information Sheet and Consent Form

Sulafa Gawish

To: [Redacted]
Cc: [Redacted]

Mon 21/03/2022 16:15

SG-Participation Information ... 381 KB
SG-Participant Consent Form... 889 KB

2 attachments (1 MB) Save all to OneDrive - University of the West of Scotland Download all

Dear Mawahib,

I would like to take this opportunity to thank you for agreeing to take part in this research study; your participation and valuable contributions are highly appreciated. I am confident that your knowledge and experience will add great value to this project and will make a huge difference.

Please find attached the Information Sheet and the Consent Form for your kind reference, information, and consent.

The consent form is a University requirement, without your official consent and endorsement, I am not authorized to conduct the interview session.

Once you agree we can set a Zoon Meeting at your convenience to kick off our discussion.

Thanks again and your support is very much appreciated.

Kind regards,
Sulafa Gawish

Appendix 4- The Interview Guide

HOW EQUIPPED IS IT FOR THE OF 21st CENTURY CHALLENGES
1. Sudan's labour act of 1997 has been static for more than two decades (<i>a quarter of a century</i>) in your opinion how equipped is it for the challenges of 21st century with all its significant changes and developments (is it the answer to the current Sudanese labour market and employment challenges)
2. Evaluate the current Sudanese Labour Laws in terms of <i>protecting the most vulnerable workforce</i> ?
3. Describe the Sudanese Labour Act Legislations on <i>collective issues</i> ?
4. To what extent do you believe that the Sudanese Labour Act of 1997 is <i>abided</i> by in both public and private sectors and what measures are in place to govern its day-to-day application?
5. Almost everyone works, but not everyone is employed. How does the Sudanese Labour Laws show concern for and acknowledge workers beyond the formal labour market (<i>Scope- unregulated wage workers, the self-employed and home workers</i>).
6. From your experience to what extent is the current Sudanese Labour Act serving the Sudanese people?
EVALUATE THE CONCEPT OF <i>DECENT WORK</i> IN SUDAN
7. A global comparative report argues that it has become evident that in some countries around the world <i>there are obvious patterns of working people who struggle and are overwhelmingly drifted away from "decent work"</i> ... how would you assess the situation in Sudan?
8. Describe the levels of inequality, discrimination and social injustice faced in the Sudanese workplace and what issues do you believe need urgent attention?
9. To what level/degree does the Sudanese labour law cater for such inequalities and vulnerabilities and is it robust enough to align <i>global objectives</i> and priorities to Sudanese workforce.
10. Drawing workplace boundaries can be challenging particularly <i>understanding and influencing</i> what happens in the workplace in terms of <u>discrimination and inconveniences</u> ... can you explain how this is covered by the Sudanese labour Act?
11. Every person is at work or is looking for work (whatever his or her country, occupation or skill level) has a notion of what "decency" at work and what it stands for... <i>do you believe that that all Sudanese workers understand the notion of decency at works and what it stands for?</i>
12. Is the Sudanese government measuring " Decent Work "? And if yes, how is it doing that?
13. In Sudan what protections are in place championed by the government that covers <i>unemployment hazards, trade union representations, social protection systems</i> (such as social support systems, unemployment insurance and other social protection policies)?

14. To enjoy a *decent fulfilled life* people, need to have *dignity at work*. Let's take for example "Bulling" and "Harassment" two forms of brutality and injustice that are constantly struggled, resisted and escaped in the workplace. *How well are these two behaviours governed by the Sudanese Labour Act of 1997?*

UNACCEPTABLE FORMS OF WORK (UFW)

15. In June 2013, the ILO (International Labour Organisation) recognised protecting workers from *unacceptable forms of work* as one of the most important practices and a top priority of the organisation in the years 2014 & 2015, what is your knowledge and observations on the efforts made to fulfil this goal of protecting Sudanese workers from "*Unacceptable Forms of Work (UFW)*."*

16. The ILO has made an effort to introduce and promote the concept of "*decent work*" and has made it its sole focus and centre of attention since 1999: "*Opportunities for women and men to obtain decent and productive work in conditions of freedom*."

17. In 2017 the ILO communicated to the world its breakthrough five-year strategy (*Fundamental Principles & Rights at Work Strategy 2017-2023*)-where is Sudan from this strategy?

WHAT EFFORT HAS TAKEN PLACE TO DEVELOP THE SUDANESE LABOUR ACT IN THE PAST 2.5 DECADES?

18. Explain *how frequently is the Sudanese Employment Laws examined and assessed* in terms of applicability is and fitness for purpose and what process does it follow? (E.g. *Min Wage Limit*)

19. What *efforts have been made to address the shortcomings* of the Sudanese Labour Laws in terms of equality and discrimination

20. How is Sudan re-evaluating and *tighten enforcement mechanisms*

WHAT ARE THE EVIDENT GAPS

21. As a practitioner and based on your application (of the 1997 Act) in the workplace, what *difficulties* AND *challenges* have you encountered and what *obvious fundamental gaps* have you experienced which you believe are not backed up by the legislation.

22. From your exposure to best practice (International Laws, Standards, and Equality Acts) and your individual assessment of the Sudanese Labour Act of 1997, how comparable is it and why?

23. *Sound Labour Regulations* constitute an important foundation for *a favourable healthy investment climate*... how do you feel about this statement when you think of Sudan? How favourable is the investment climate and how sound are the Labour regulations?

24. A study conducted by the World Bank confirms that all MENA (Middle Eastern and North African Countries) firms surveyed believe *their labour regulations are a major setback in doing business*, how do

you feel about this statement and how does Sudan relate to it (bear in mind Sudan was not part of the mentioned survey).

**WHAT ARE YOUR SUGGESTIONS & RECOMMENDATIONS
TO BRIDGE THE EXISTING GAPS**

25. In terms of *context and application* what lessons have you learned from other countries that you believe are applicable to the Sudanese case?

26. In your opinion what are the *general characteristics of work* that people from Sudan consider as fundamental and essential (*characteristics that are relevant to and easy to communicate to the average person in the street*).

27. How do you propose that Sudan refrains from the *antiqued laws* that reflect priorities and realities of a bygone era and how could Sudan focus on providing a *better match with the modern contemporary character of today's employment world*?

28. In your opinion how can we *upgrade and revive the 1997 Act to best suit the 21st century needs* of the Sudanese work force?

29. How *could best practice global laws be applied to Sudan* and what components are most needed and why?

30. What *legislative options do you recommend* for promoting fair representation, equality, and diversity in the Sudanese Act?

31. What effort is needed to *establish decent work* in Sudan?

32. How can we *assess and measure decent work* in Sudan?

33. What are your suggested *statistical indicators* to measure decent work?

Appendix 5- Sample Transcript (Candidate SEI)

HOW EQUIPPED IS IT FOR THE OF 21ST CENTURY CHALLENGES		
	Question	
1.	<p>Sudan's labour act of 1997 has been static for more than two decades, in your opinion how equipped is it for the challenges of 21st century (<i>is it the answer to the current Sudanese labour market and employment challenges</i>)?</p>	<p>SEI: First of all, I would like to make a very important remark, from my personal observation, I believe the current Sudanese labour Act of 1997 has not been in action for just 25 years in fact it has been around since the 1960's, it is proceeding with the same legal sprit that was initiated in the 1960! The name was different but all the articles and all the standards and all the orders are the same as the 1970s act, the same! You can say that what happened 25 years ago was just a renewal for the 1974 Manpower Act! Actually, as a character or sprit of law you shouldn't say that it has been there for 25 years, no it has been almost the same for more than 50 years!</p> <p>SG: This is an eye opener and explains a lot of issues...it does talk about production, assembly and manufacturing, isn't that right?</p> <p>SEI:</p> <p>Yes it addresses industries that are no longer functioning and talks about things that are obsolete... all the amendments that were made the least that I can say were just appearances and touch-ups and nothing more and nothing core! Reorganising the numbers, removal or change of wording (some words were removed because the meaning was different or not clear). But genuine amendments as such for the laws to cope or match the needs of the era never happened!</p> <p>SG: You mean to tell me it was not equipped at that time in 1997 when it was launched?!</p> <p>SEI: Yes not equipped for 1997 let alone equipped for 2022!</p>

		<p>Even the wording and the way it was edited talks about an era that has long departed a bygone era in Sudan when Sudan was heavily reliant on industries such as cotton, sugarcane, and fabrics production. When it was updated in 1997, I believe it was done with very little effort, the people in charge of these so called amendments 25 years ago made no study no effort to it cope with the needs back then in 1997! All that happened was a change in naming, numbers, built points, scheduling, change in names of committees, reordering; but a core change or amendment to the essence of the regulations or new updates needed did not take place even back then in 1997!</p> <p>Authors Note:</p> <p>To support this point, I personally faced difficulty with the labour act way back when I started working in the private sector in 2003 and felt it was missing a great deal back then and that there were core fundamental gaps not covered and needed to be covered urgently back then. And I remember speaking to our head of HR and asking him when will a new version or update will be made as this one is seven years old and should be updated. He said in two years' time probably, we both never thought it will be around for another twenty years!</p>
2.	<p>Evaluate the current Sudanese Labour Laws in terms of <i>protecting the most vulnerable workforce in our society?</i></p>	<p>SEI: If we talk about people with special needs it did not cater for this sector at all, people with vulnerabilities such as disabled and workers or workers with special needs cover (the law does not cover this area ...It is neglected). Important things like facilities fit for the disabled for example wheelchair ramps, special toilets.... Etc. All these are not regulated by the labour act of 1997 it is not mentioned anywhere! As I said before the law was not equipped even back then in 1997. As you know all these developments in fact depends on the economic situation of the county and you know that Sudan is a nation which is currently struggling in this area.</p>

The financial situation in Sudan is severely damaged and you can see that these basic requirements we spoke about are not available even in the service areas like hospitals, schools and transport let alone in other organisations, simple because the law does not enforce these issues and the economic situation does not permit it; hence it becomes more like luxuries rather than necessities! So, to ask someone in the workplace to provide such a thing becomes more like a dream!

Despite that fact, I strongly believe that the Sudanese labour act is advanced in human rights areas and particularly women's rights even when compared to international practices. Areas like pregnancy & maternity leaves, breast feeding time concessions (one hour off for two consecutive years); in addition to the mourning /grief period for a woman who has lost her husband a fully paid 4 month and 10 days is a paid leave determined dictated by the labour Act of 1997; the law speaks to the culture, religion, and society and this is credit for it. There are laws that take care of women's needs which are advanced and must be credited and acknowledged as they are rarely this sophisticated in other societies. In addition to gives women flexibility and choice when it comes to overtime (it gives women full autonomy and does not compel them by all means). Giving her the option to refuse working overtime, the concept of choice in itself is credit to the law.

SG: This is great and what else?

SEI: Furthermore, and to give it more credit the Sudanese labour law does not differentiate between women on the bases of religion; for example, Christian women do not have the 4 month and 10 days mourning period in their religion, but the Labour act of 1997 gives her the same right fully paid as a

		<p>better condition with all its privileges without prejudice or discrimination of any kind.</p> <p>Generally speaking, all the laws perceive the employee as the weak party in relation to the employer.</p> <p>Employment of children (under aged) min 16-17- replay</p>
3.	Describe the Sudanese Labour Act Legislations on <i>collective issues</i> ?	<p>SEI: Collective issues are politicised in Sudan; it depends on the governments go ahead... Typically in Sudan the government is slowing down their activities for political reasons. They fully control their activities and can instantly remove their authority and incriminate any activates or proceedings. Despite the fact that the labour unions in Sudan are the main stake holders of the labour act and they are one of three main pillars that constitute the Tripartite Committee in charge of developing the Act! This is a very strange setup in Sudan when the presidential power cancels/prohibits the role of a main legal pillar (currently inactive), it is quite astonishing; the problem is that Sudan is a nation that is politically instable and has been governed by Emergency Laws for years!</p> <p>Emergency laws where one person only decides everything basically a cruel dictatorship. Therefore, the law is crippled by all measures!</p> <p>Generally speaking initially there was very strong law for collective bargaining and Sudan was very advanced in this area and one day there were very strong labour unions in Sudan. You can't imagine the strength of the Railway Union and how powerful they were (they were a standalone empowered state and legislator). But now, not having the right laws and the political instabilities and interferences weakened the area very much and you can easily say that they are non-existent.</p>

		<p>Note: Which means Sudan was progressing in the 1960s far beyond what is takes place today! Once again Sudan was way advanced in the creation of laws to the extent it was exceeding the Arab world especially the Gulf nations and contributed massively in drafting their laws back then</p>
4.	<p>To what extent do you believe that the Sudanese Labour Act of 1997 is <i>abided</i> by in both public and private sectors and what measures are in place to govern its day to day application?</p>	<p>SEI: From my experience I can say that all the big companies and organisations were committed and were abiding by the legislation, despite the fact that it was crippling and handcuffing in so many ways; especially for me as it was ambiguous and lacked clarity. However the specialised authority responsible for its governance it was relatively strong and had presence especially when it comes to disputes and conflict resolutions between employers and employees (the laws were abided by and respected to a great extent). Big companies were brand conscientious and were very careful in the implementation of the laws; they have strong legal departments that were keen not to break these laws for the sake of their reputation.</p> <p>SG: What about the small companies?</p> <p>On the other hand, small companies in the private sector had so many ways for fraud and room for manipulating the laws; and honestly speaking I do not blame them for that...The labour act of 1997 does not support the economic needs of small businesses employers and entrepreneurs under the challenges of the economic situation in Sudan. I saw many small companies crumbled with former employee entitlements and payments, some of which were miss managed to start with due to their lack of understanding and experience with the legislations and others were genuine as the laws do not differentiate between a small start-up or a well-established business and has no support whatsoever for small businesses, in terms of concessions or financial support.</p>

		<p>Important Note: We have a problem of contracts in the Sudanese labour laws, there is no room for flexibility in comparison to other countries and best practices which makes it very complicated for employers to balance their requirements.</p> <p>Finally, I can say for myself and the majority of companies in Sudan, the law is abided by as no one wants to go to court and face all the hassle and waste of time.</p> <p>SG: What about the measures, were there any?</p> <p>There are no measures whatsoever in place developed by the ministry or government to support the application of the labour act...Nothing; it all depends on the integrity of the employer! In addition, the lack of governance from the government the weakened or absent labour unions in the past played this role and did the auditing on behalf of the government for each organisation (if only they knew the value of collective bargaining).</p> <p>But what can I say this probably the least priority for the government right now if the auditing health and education are not a priority why would it audit private employers on the implementation of the labour act?! It is sequence or chain of corruption with a domino effect ...you stopped the unions; you stop the inspection ...you lose people's rights.</p>
5.	<p>Almost everyone works, but not everyone is employed. How does the Sudanese Labour Laws show concern for and acknowledge workers beyond the formal labour market (scope- <i>unregulated wage workers, the self-employed and home workers</i>).</p>	<p>There is nothing, they have not been mentioned or acknowledged in any place. They are not looked after at all.</p>

EVALUATE THE CONCEPT OF DECENT WORK IN SUDAN

Decent Work according to the (ILO) involves 4 pillars:

Employment, Social protection, Workers' rights and social dialogue

Decent work the 8th Goal in the UN 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development

6.	<p>A global comparative report argues that it has become evident that in some countries around the world <i>there are obvious patterns of working people who struggle and are overwhelmingly drifted away from “decent work”</i> ... how would you assess the situation in Sudan?</p>	<p>To start with the opportunities for work in itself is not here! And the Act does promote anything at all in this regards. And the most impacted sector by this is the people with disabilities and vulnerabilities who most need the opportunities that are almost invisible! I really wished the Act of 1997 mentioned anything promoting or supporting this segment, unfortunately it did not. Things like equal opportunities act and equality acts to work hand in hand with the labour act are missing.</p> <p>Decency at work is part of the decency of the whole country and cannot be separated.</p>
7.	<p>Is the Sudanese government measuring “Decent Work”? And if yes, how is it doing that?</p>	<p>No, to my knowledge it is not even in its agenda.</p>
8.	<p>Every person is at work or is looking for work (whatever his or her country, occupation or skill level) has a notion of what “decency” at work and what it stands for...<i>do you believe that that all Sudanese workers understand the notion of decency at works and what it stands for?</i></p>	<p>No</p> <p>The definition of decency is relative... Most people in Sudan are struggling to meet the necessities of life and are unable to think of anything other than their basic needs (Maslow’s Hierarchy of Needs). People in Sudan are overwhelmed by the troubles of day to day challenges of meeting the basic living needs of feeding their families and survival... no more, so they are unable to think beyond these struggles they have no room to think of anything else; while other nations have actually moved away from the day to day challenges of the basic labour regulations and have are focusing in things like work life balance, equality, diversity, and inclusion.</p>

<p>9.</p>	<p>Describe the levels of inequality, discrimination and social injustice faced in the Sudanese workplace and what issues do you believe need urgent attention? And to what level/degree does the Sudanese labour law cater for such inequalities and vulnerabilities</p>	<p>There are cultural issues that act does not address things like an opportunity for example the opportunities for women in senior jobs, promotion, there is nothing specific to tackles these inequalities if any (gender inequalities). However, despite the gap of articles in this area and despite the fat of not being addressed, the Sudanese culture itself did not need require much work in the area as by nature the culture has talked this issue very well throughout history. As Sudanese women proved them themselves in the workplace, they broke barriers a very long time ago and since independence they had equal chance for education they became judges, doctors, and ministers. It there was no pressing need for the laws to focus or tackle this area maybe by nature; nevertheless, I believe it does need to be addressed to strengthen and enhance it. Culturally women are well respected in the workplace they have dominated all sectors and excelled well. They are well educated and qualified for all jobs and were cultured form a young age (from home) to compete well with men and so there was no need to explicitly mention it in the labour regulations as when the labour act was develop in the 1960 women were already parliament members! And had strong impact and say in the community.</p> <p>Note:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yet we still strongly believe that the document should be inclusive to reflect the culture and practices and should be documented (best practice is the practice that is customised with the cultural needs and requirements). • • There are distinct practices supported by the labour act that in favour of women that will shock people in the west; they are far beyond the <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 4 months and 10 days fully paid Mourning
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		<p>Leave</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Pregnancy and Maternity Leave ○ 1 hour off daily for 24-month child nursing (breastfeeding) ○ Right to refuse overtime ○ Right not to work at night ○ Etc
10.	<p>In Sudan what <i>protections</i> are in place championed by the government to cover <i>unemployment, trade union representations, social protection systems (such as social support systems, unemployment insurance and other social protection policies)</i>?</p>	<p>No there is nothing on unemployment; absolutely nothing, this is a government responsibility which does not exist.</p>
11.	<p>Drawing workplace boundaries can be challenging particularly <i>understanding and influencing</i> what happens in the workplace in terms of <u>discrimination and inconveniences</u>...</p> <p>Let's take for example "Bulling" and "Harassment" two forms of brutality and injustice that are constantly struggled, resisted and escaped in the workplace.</p> <p><i>How well are such behaviours governed by the Sudanese Labour Act of 1997?</i></p>	<p>Not addressed at all...there is nothing...no clauses.</p> <p>When this act was initially developed harassment is a taboo... no one even talk about it. In addition, it was very rare and almost non-existent in the workplace and in society as a whole and for that reason there was no need to address it back then.</p> <p>In the Arabic language both bulling and harassment are two words that do not exist in the Arabic dictionary and have been recently developed (new terms)</p> <p>There are, no preventive measures at all; the only thing that can happen is people may take action or try to solve the problem when and after it happens not before; and if it happens it may be only related to physical assault only ...Nothing else. Bulling and Harassment are out of Scope!</p> <p>However, change is inevitable, and people need to have vivid transparent regulations to safely regulate the behaviours in</p>

		<p>the workplace. As these practices do exist despite the upbringing and culture of the people, and for that reason we must not rely on what our culture dictates us, but we must take all the necessary steps and measures to prevent such behaviours in the workplace with clear clauses and genuine enforcement, with zero intolerance for all kinds of such behaviours.</p> <p>Important Facts:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Racism is high in Sudan and there is nothing in the labour act to protect workers and employees whatsoever in this respect and this is a huge gap. • Going back to harassment and specifically sexual harassment has no base for complains or reporting as it is not supported by any regulation, consequently women do not complain when they suffer, they just keep it to themselves. Furthermore, they are petrified of the community and how they are perceived; as the community is not just in such circumstances and usually blames the women for any incident and most would argue that she had it coming or encourage such behaviours one way or another (extreme inequality and injustice); intentionally or unintentionally as a woman you are viewed as part of the problem.
12.	What effort is needed to <i>establish decent work</i> in Sudan?	Government efforts needed
13.	<i>Assessing and measuring decent work</i> in Sudan... are there any statistical measures/indicators that you know of to measure decent work in Sudan? And what are they?	No measurements –governments

14.	In June 2013, the ILO (Sudan in a member of the ILO) recognised protecting workers from <i>unacceptable forms of work</i> as one of the most important practices and a top priority of the organisation in the years 2014 & 2015, what is your knowledge and observations on the efforts made to fulfil this goal of protecting Sudanese workers from “ <i>Unacceptable Forms of Work (UFW).</i> ”*	
15.	In 2017 the ILO communicated to the world its breakthrough five year strategy (<i>Fundamental Principles & Rights at Work Strategy 2017-2023</i>)-where is Sudan from this strategy and how far is it?	

**WHAT EFFORT HAS TAKEN PLACE TO DEVELOP THE SUDANESE LABOR ACT
IN THE PAST 2.5 DECADES?**

16.	Explain <i>how frequently is the Sudanese Employment Laws examined, re-evaluated, and assessed</i> in terms of applicability and fitness for purpose and what process does it follow? (E.g., <i>Min Wage Limit</i>), and What <i>efforts have been made to address the shortcomings</i>	<p>There is no process, no assessment, no revisiting, no re-evaluation, and the biggest proof for that is that the Act has been still for the last 25 years without any change whatsoever! One of the mechanisms for measuring is at least have a data base for the number of court cases and their precedence; unfortunately, there is nothing objective realistic to rely on for lessons learned and precedence! There are no records or statistics and most of all there is no medium for media and other mechanisms to educate and create awareness.</p> <p>What about the labour offices?</p> <p>Of course, there are labour offices their responsibility is very limited, all they do is view the cases before they are transferred to the courts; despite their main role of mediation and troubleshooting to avoid the cases to start with.</p> <p>Unfortunately, most or all cases end up going to court anyway!</p>
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Which makes their role very passive and almost useless? They are not competent and so they end up transferring the cases to court, which should have been handled by them in the first place. They only focus on counting the foreign workers! We talked about inspection earlier and want to say that in my long years of service I have seen these offices only running after the number of expatriates we hire, the work permits they have and all other activities that only generate income to these offices; hence the offices become responsible for the collection of fees and tariff only and lost its essence of service providing and supporting private organisations gain understanding of the labour act.

The labour office is a preliminary stage before the labour court; if these offices were competent, they could have reduced the number of cases going to court and saved organisations hell of money and time.

Notes:

- One might argue why should the labour act need interpretation, explanation, and clarification; why isn't it straight forward and clearly understood in the first place?! Why do you need an intermediate to function?!
- Another important fact is that these offices do not report the ministry (labour ministry) and report to the state offices. Let just think about it for a moment if the ministry wants to build a relationship with the ILO and effectively develop international standards in Sudan, how can they work with the labour offices and enforce these strategies if they do not report to them.
- So the income is the problem as they do not want the income to go to the ministry!

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Same applies to government schools (<i>Adil Almadaris</i>) ...dividing the schools renting the classes as shops...Government schools that are acres wide have been cut and rented to make money and the funny thing this money does not go back to the school it goes to the state offices!
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WHAT ARE THE GAPS

17.	<p>As a practitioner and based on your application (of the 1997 Act) in the workplace, what <i>difficulties</i> AND <i>challenges</i> have you encountered and what <i>obvious fundamental gaps</i> have you experienced which you believe are not backed up by the legislation.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Lack of flexibility in contracts is a very big issue! Very limited contract types and employment types. In a way that does not serve the economic needs of the community or the employers. It is inadequate in this particular aspect; I consider it to be a major pitfall (the types of contracts and types of employment and the flexibility required). Life in Sudan changed drastically in the past years and the employment requirements have changed drastically however the types of contracts supported by the labour act do not serve this critical need. ● Probation period is too short; three month is too short for a country like Sudan where the economic situation is dreadful and where most projects fail in their first stage. This will support employers (especially for start-up employers); the current 3-month probation period is a heavy burden on most start-ups and new investors it overwhelms them with payments entitlement they are not able to fulfil (and this is why most small organisation manipulate the laws and play around it). ● Very long sick leaves: do you know that the labour act requires the employer to pay sick leave for up to 9 months. This is another heavy burden that must be
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		<p>sponsored by the government and social protection. This is not logical.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There are other awkward leaves that are not applicable today things like road/travel leave; this was in a time when travelling from one city to another took ages due to the type of transport available, these do not make sense anymore. • Annual leave is also very long comparison to other countries, it starts at 20 and goes up 30 days. • Vague and ambiguous interpretation of most of the clauses (not all). Every labour office, every court has its own interpretation to the same set of laws. • Minimal wage is not compatible with the real needs of the people. The common thing is to calculate the minimal wage on the bases of people's needs this is not happening in Sudan! • Health and Safety is not given enough room. • Social Insurance is corrupt!
18.	<p>* <i>Sound Labour Regulations</i> constitute an important foundation for <i>a favourable healthy investment climate</i></p> <p>A study conducted by the World Bank confirms that all MENA (Middle Eastern and North African Countries) firms surveyed believe <i>their labour regulations are a major setback in doing business</i>, how do you feel about this statement and how does Sudan relate to it (bear in mind Sudan was not part of the mentioned survey).</p>	<p>A lot of investors discontinue their projects because of the labour laws; it is not flexible at all.</p>
<p>WHAT ARE YOUR SUGGESTIONS & RECOMMENDATIONS TO BRIDGE THE EXISTING GAPS</p>		

19.	<p>In your opinion what general characteristics of work that people from Sudan consider as core and essential (<i>characteristics that are relevant to and easy to communicate to the average person in the street</i>).</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wage and salary enough for a decent living (enough income) • Work suitable for my skills. • Training to support me d mu job. • Decency and respect for his/her humanity • Safety in the workplace • Work life balance. <p>Note: Why should we reinvent the wheel, why shouldn't we start where others stopped and build on it?</p>
20.	<p>In terms of context and application what lessons have you learned from other countries that you believe are applicable to Sudan?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hours pay/rate; base for contracts should be hourly based and hourly rate; this is in favour of both employer and employees. It helps measure and boost productivity. • Two days off: by the way this is currently not in the law, the current practice is lead and is operating by the companies own their own but not law as the law says people must work a 48-hour week not 40!
21.	<p>How could best practice global laws be applied to Sudan and what components are most needed and why?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • We need studies, research, statistics, data measures what is there in place. •
22.	<p>In your opinion how do propose that we upgrade the 1997 Act to best suit the 21st century needs of the Sudanese work force?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Flexibility in contracts –Review the contracts and introduce and support flexibility. • Healthy work environment, which is social responsibly that is everybody's responsibility to change our way we do things and change of our attitude and behaviours. • Transparency of jobs and job requirements in everything across all provinces • Information availability • Stakeholders' involvement in all work-related issues including schools, universities, and the entire

		<p>educational system.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collect information about what is going on. • Study best practice. • Keep updated and aware of • We need to go back to the labour unions (collective bodies), they know more they understand the community, they know the gaps and missing skills as they are closer to the community and their empowerment. • Youth development and employment • Schools' engagement, collages, technical schools, qualification, and diplomas that support employment. • Government must champion this change
23.	<p><i>What legislative options do you recommend for promoting fair representation, equality, and diversity in the Sudanese Act?</i></p>	<p>All these laws are missing; we need to develop them in the new act promoting fair representation, equality, and diversity all should be in the new Sudanese Act?</p>

Appendix 6- The Thematic Analysis

Participant/Sub Theme	Theme One: Key Aspects
Sub-Theme/Code	Key Aspects and Features : A Historical Perspective
Participant One-E.O.S	<p><i>“In my opinion, it has the basics- a good foundation and the attributes for a very good labour law in terms of the rights given to employees in any organisation very well written; however, it is very clear that it has been written to serve an industrialised sector, the old cotton factories, Aljazeera Agricultural project and other manufacturing and assembly lines. I believe it does not cater for the diverse sectors that we currently have in Sudan. Let’s take for example the laws governing shifts in Sudan they are different for Women & Men (putting in mind the intention to protect women workers from night shifts ...etc); but how can these laws be applied to other sectors that demand women working night shifts by profession; for example the medical sector (not just doctors and nurses but other supporting administrative and back office staff) and other sectors that cannot afford to do that such as telecommunication and other wide service sectors. So the foundation is there but it was made for a different time and environment, to apply it, therefore, needs to be updated & customised to suit the needs and challenges of today”</i></p>
Participant Five- S.E.I	<p><i>“First of all I would like to make a very important remark, from my personal observation, I believe the current Sudanese labour Act of 1997 has not been in action for just 25 years in fact it has been around since the 1960’s, it is proceeding with the same legal spirit that was initiated in the 1960! The name was different but all the articles and all the standards and all the orders are the same as the 1970s act, the same! You can say that what happened 25 years ago was just a renewal for the 1974 Manpower Act! Actually as a character or spirit of law you shouldn’t say that it has been there for 25 years, no it has been almost the same for more than 50 years!”</i></p> <p><i>“Generally speaking, initially, there was a very strong law for collective bargaining and Sudan was very advanced in this area one day there were very strong labour unions in Sudan. You can’t imagine the strength of the Railway Union and how powerful they were (they were a standalone empowered state and legislator). But now, not having the right laws in place and the political instabilities and interferences weakened the area very much and you can easily say that they are non-existent. This means Sudan was progressing in the 1960s far beyond what it takes place today! Once again Sudan was way advanced in the creation of laws to the extent it was exceeding the Arab World, especially the Gulf Nations and we contributed massively in drafting their laws back then”</i></p>

	<p><i>Yes, it addresses industries that are no longer functioning and talks about obsolete things... all the amendments that were made the least that I can say were just appearances and touch-ups and nothing more and nothing core! Reorganising the numbers, removal or change of wording (some words were removed because the meaning was different or not clear). But genuine amendments as such for the laws to cope with or match the needs of the era never happened!</i></p> <p><i>“When it was updated in 1997, I believe it was done with very little effort, the people in charge of the so-called amendments 25 years ago made no studies, no effort to manage or cope with the needs back then in 1997”...All that happened was a change in naming, numbers, built points, scheduling, change in names of committees, reordering; but a core change or amendment to the essence of the regulations or new updates needed did not take place even back then in 1997”</i></p>
<p>Participant Six- M. A. K</p>	<p><i>“You have to understand that 1997 Laws are a continuation for the laws that were initiated in 1948; they are almost the same thing, with just very little changes here and there, nothing major. Changes in the number of days, wages...etc but nothing in the heart. It was targeting the old labours, manual workers & industry workers; has nothing to do with modern employment (does not serve doctors, engineers, teachers, and bankers....they have no place in the law...).The law applies to them but the laws are irrelevant to them”</i></p>
<p>Sub-Theme/Code</p>	<p>Key Aspects and Features: The Practical Application</p>
<p>Participant Five- S.E.I</p>	<p><i>“I can say that all the big companies and organisations are committed and abiding by the legislation, despite the fact that it is crippling and handcuffing in so many ways; especially for me as it was ambiguous and lacked clarity. However, the specialised authority responsible for its governance was relatively strong and had a presence especially when it comes to disputes and conflict resolutions between employers and employees (the laws were abided by and respected to a great extent). Big companies were brand conscientious and were very careful in the implementation of the laws; they have strong legal departments that were keen not to break these laws for the sake of their reputation...”</i></p> <p><i>“On the other hand, small companies in the private sector have so many ways for fraud and room for manipulating the laws; and honestly speaking I do not blame them for that...The labour act of 1997 does not support the economic needs of small businesses, employers and entrepreneurs under the challenges of the economic situation in Sudan. I saw many small companies crumble with former employee entitlements and payments, some of which was miss managed to start due to their lack of understanding and experience with the legislation and others were genuine as the laws do</i></p>

	<i>not differentiate between small start-ups or well-established businesses and have no support whatsoever for small businesses, in terms of concessions or financial support”</i>
Participant Six- M. A. K	<p><i>“For example, in Sudan, there are around 1000 Private Recruitment agencies (just over 1000), and 241 are registered under the Sudanese General Intelligence Agency (all of these companies 241 are exempt by a presidential decree from the application of the Act of 1997. I witnessed a case where they terminated all their staff with no legal rights and when the workers came to take legal action, they discovered that they had no legal rights as the company employing them is exempt from the implementation of the law by a letter from the president! This is all happening today in Sudan so many companies; so many companies are invited and have permission to do what they like!!!”</i></p> <p><i>“The thing that happens in Sudan is that foreign investors by law can be exempted from the Sudanese national labour laws, take for example the African University they are exempt!! By a presidential decision, because you can do that, the Sudanese laws support these exemptions”.</i></p>
Participant Seven- A.A.B	<p><i>“International organisations and big companies abide by the laws to avoid reputation damage (as they have big numbers and of workers and employees and any issue can be repeated and cause reputational damage they can’t afford), however other small companies are not restricted, one or two cases can go on in court and drag for 7-8 years as the law does not compel its implementation”.</i></p> <p><i>“Inspection is not functioning, I worked for 20 years and saw no one inspecting. May be if there is a big fire they may visit and issue a report but nothing else... That is all, they cannot impose anything else!”</i></p>
Participant Eight-HEH	<i>“The Practical application over the past 25 years has proved that the 97 Act is currently not coping with the needs. I can see that from my personal experience with all the NGOs I am working with. The law is simply not coping with the needs and expectations of these organisations. Especially when it comes to the employment relationship and the type of contracts needed. The types of contracts they usually require are based on the nature of activities they run and normally use across the world-are not supported by the Act. And hence the struggle occurs. This has even affected their budgets and their ability to provide finance to make the necessary compensations that they owe the workers legally in courts (due to their lack of understanding and the gaps in the Act). Regarding other big companies and organizations in the private sector, they are also dreadfully complaining of its incompatibility with their needs (not coping) and the huge injustice in</i>

	<i>the Act especially in the relationship between the employee and employer relationship as if it was a Catholic Marriage that is not possible to break unless with very complex arrangements”</i>
Sub-Theme/Code	Key Aspects and Features: Organisational Compliance (Inspection & Abidance)
Participant Two-MZK	<i>“I can’t say that the 1997 Act is fully abided by because the legislation provides the minimum requirements in the working relationship between the employer and employee, this minimum is a bare minim that is not sufficient for a decent life hence, taking, for example, the minimum wage; it is a disgrace and is far way far from being realistic by all measures, so in this context, it is not practical for any successful business to follow this absurd measure and guarantee sustainability, it just doesn’t make sense. Even these measures as I said before are meant to be inspected regularly by the labour office inspectors (which integral part of the legislative procedures) but this process itself is not activated for economic reasons”</i>
	<i>“In addition, part of the legislation the Act mentions the necessity of Inspection and regular checks (auditing) across all organisations (Article 69) ... Again, this is a legislation that never takes place in fact you can easily say it does not even exist!”</i>
Participant Three-MOS	<i>“Of course, I was obliged to abide by the regulations of all three offices”.</i>
Participant Four- LME	<i>“There is no inspection-this activity is not operational... the Inspection is not activated in the Ministry of Labour; blamed under the umbrella of lack of resources”</i>
	<i>“It has another major problem the 1997 labour law’s executive regulations have not been issued up to this date (this is a core document which must accompany any set of laws). This in itself is a major flaw and setback”</i>
Participant Five- SEI	<i>“Finally, I can say for myself and the majority of companies in Sudan, the law is abided by as no one wants to go to court and face all the hassle and waste of time”.</i>

Participant Six-MAK	<i>“In my opinion, it is all on paper, I cannot say it is abided by! Practically speaking it is not applied; and how could it be if two important aspects required for its application are completely missing from the process: the employment offices and the mechanism of inspection? These two elements define and regulate the implementation and they are completely missing in the field!”</i>
	<i>“Let’s take Recruitment, for example, according to the legislation the candidates must be selected through the public labour recruitment office, the applicants must be registered there in the labour offices initially and if chosen then the recruiter needs to go back and confirm their appointment if successful. And if the recruiter was failed to find suitable candidates an opening must be advertised in the newspapers and finally, biannual reports are issued ...none of these activities takes place in reality they by no means did!”</i>
	<i>“Public Employment Offices (not one office was ever established since 1997); Inspection not practices (non-functional); Specialty Committees (non-existent) ...”</i>
	<i>“Another example, is that regular health checks, are not practiced and the government must have a role in this...but nothing is happening”</i>
	<i>“...and most important the Regulations are not in place.... The regulation part should be drafted and part of the Act –it was never done when it should have to accompany the 1997 Act “</i>
	<i>“The labour act is missing an important component which is the regulatory part (lacks regulations). The 1997 act is a combination of four different acts (none of which has regulations neither the old four nor the 1997)!”</i>
Participant Seven –AAB	<i>“There is no obligation to apply the laws and the labour offices have no authority and their decisions are not binding”</i>
	<i>“Big companies and organisations have processes in place to and do abide by as they are concerned about their reputation. Small offices and businesses don’t abide by that much and can frequently and easily diverge and drift away. Most workers don’t have adequate knowledge of the</i>

	<p><i>labour laws that will allow them to understand their rights and responsibilities –there is an obvious lack of awareness in this sense ... For this reason, we have developed a network of volunteers (professionals) who have devoted their time to educate as many people as possible ... help them understand their rights and responsibilities...many forums and platforms”.</i></p>
	<p><i>“Since I have started working with this Act for more than 20 years, I have realised that there are certain Articles at the end of the Act (Articles related to the penalties) which are completely frozen (not in use at all) and are just written there without any activation. I asked all the lawyers I know and even Judges why these Articles are not activated no one has an answer”</i></p>
<p>Participant Eight-HEH</p>	<p><i>“Missing role of the labour office-no contract copies sent; no regular reviews done to the contracts unless a dispute happens –a process that should have taken place at the very beginning of the relationship.... They only come at the end when the relationship breaks (Divorce-Stage) but have done nothing in-between. The inspection role is not effective; when a dispute happens, they ask to check if they have a copy of the contract and happens most of the time if not all”</i></p>
	<p><i>“Any contract for more than three months should be written, and three copies issued (employee copy, employer copy and a copy for the labour office) and made through the labour office. Which is part of the legislation (Article 28) - unfortunately in the practical sense these procedures are not practically implemented as they should; they are missing from the actual day-to-day implementation... The job itself should not have been advertised unless it was done through the labour offices, all of that does not happen””</i></p>
	<p><i>“In addition, the role of the labour offices is very passive, they have no authority and most of the time makes no difference. All they do is receive the complaints and collect the fees. And their decisions are not binding and must still be taken to court (they have no binding power). To be honest, they are usually more of an obstacle, and sometimes we do not even consider taking it as a step as we know they can do nothing, and I take my problem straight to court and completely overlook them (without them even knowing). While they should have played an active role in investigating the issues, checking the standard and specifications to make sure everything is in line and acting as a real regulatory body in collaboration with the Industrial Safety and the written act”</i></p>
<p>Participant Nine-RFU</p>	<p><i>In my experience to a degree, we followed it and ensured that we complied with it even though it was old and outdated”.</i></p>

Sub-Theme/Code	Key Aspects and Features: Government & Governance: The Role of the State
Participant Six-MAK	<i>“With the current conditions in Sudan, the labour ministry should be the top priority; however, it is at the bottom of the priority list! Economic rights are neglected, but political issues are addressed (for example the Electoral Commission is in place)”</i>
Participant Seven –AAB	<i>“The government’s role is very weak, and as a result, we recommend that people take action and achieve something on their own. Independent bodies can raise these issues with the ILO or ALO (Arab Labour Organisation) and launch a movement highlighting the amount of abuse, discrimination, and struggles that Sudanese workers are forced to endure! If there is a visible movement championed by Sudanese workers, international organisations can be very supportive and even impose sanctions.</i>
Participant Eight-HEH	<i>“In general, ministries take the lead in initiating any updates and creating the vision; in this case, the Ministry of Labour takes the lead and, in collaboration with the Ministry of Justice, creates the necessary legal context; unfortunately, I believe this has been missing in the last 30 years... Before that, and especially at the beginning/middle of the 1990s, there was a very active period in which all of these laws and many more were written, and then everything came to a halt! For example, criminal laws from 1991, personal status laws from 1991, and then 1997 the labour law...now everything is a mess and there is huge disparity...even the states are inconsistent in their application of laws and are developing their own laws! Some have even opted to repeal the 1997 Labour Act (for example in South Darfur)”</i>
	<i>“The Ministry of Labour (a strategic and very important Ministry) is overlooked and not given the attention it deserves. From the moment you enter, you can see that it is obviously neglected, and this reflects the neglect of the entire function...this is obvious from the calibre of people there.... we do not say they are incapable</i>
Sub-Theme/Code	Key Aspects and Features:

Government & Governance: A Ministry in Limbo	
	<i>“During my tenure as Labour Minister, we were all very eager to revisit all of the laws and update them to comply with International Standards and Treaties. It was critical for the transitional government to revisit all laws in order to achieve social justice and secure a life of dignity in Sudan if it was to bring about change and a revolution. The transitional government was committed to social development in order to affect this change”</i>
Participant Four- LME	<i>“.....In terms of the Labour Ministry, the biggest obstacle to change was the ministry itself, which lacked the capacity and aptitude to make the change happen. The second issue was the decision makers, who were represented by the Tripartite Committee (this is a committee responsible for everything related to any kind of change in legislation) and the relationship between all three parties, who never agreed, and the sudden political change which diluted their composition beyond doubt affected the relationship”.</i>
	<i>“.... Furthermore, prior to the pandemic, there was a major setback that slowed things down, and that was the following: part of the transitional government task was to get rid of all previous bodies through the Dismantling Committee, which was in charge of dismantling all previous established unions, and part of that was the Tripartite Committee body. This slowed progress because there was no official body representing these faces other than the assigned steering committees established by the government, and these bodies were not elected bodies (not legitimate delegated committees -selected by the new government and were not elected) and thus could not represent the people and hence were unable to take any actions”.</i>
Participant Seven –AAB	<i>“Ministry of Labour has no Minister since October 2021” (Participant Seven-AAB)</i>
Participant Eight-HEH	<i>“The most recent official publication we received was on the minimum wage in 2016... Since 2019, the tripartite committee has been dissolved; leaving us in a state of uncertainty... basically, no one is in charge” (Participant Eight-HEH)</i>
Sub-Theme/Code	Key Aspects and Features: Government & Governance: Incompetence and Corruption
Participant Four- LME	<i>“The problem is that the people working in the ministry have become so complacent that they are unwilling to change even the most basic things around them. Let me tell you a story that happened</i>

	<p>during one of my first rounds in the ministry. I received a complaint from one of the departments that they have a huge problem...all the files have been eaten by rats, and they want me, the minister, to solve this problem for them. I couldn't believe my ears when I heard the request! I inquired as to when the administration manager was available and why you had allowed this to happen for so long until you had lost all the files. This is an incredible level of content and passivity. It was difficult for me to comprehend how the ministry in charge of working conditions could not ensure a healthy and safe working environment for itself" (Participant Four-LME)</p>
<p>Participant Six-MAK</p>	<p>"Government officials are corrupt in many ways; they take advantage of their positions and use their power to levy taxes and impose regulations on simple labourers such as wagon manual workers in open markets and kiosk sellers with no repercussions" Participant Six-MAK</p>
<p>Participant Seven –AAB</p>	<p>"Unfortunately, the majorities of Ministers assigned to the Ministry of Labour are politically appointed and lack the technical background or competence required to make a difference and lead the much needed and deserved change. All they care about is hiring new employees and firing existing ones" (Participant Seven-AAB)</p> <p>"The problem is that the government, ministers, and members of the National Council are all traders and businessmen!!! A true model of capital control over the state" (Participant Seven-AAB)</p> <p>"Generally speaking, the Sudanese Businessmen and Employers Federation (SBEF) possess enormous influence and are abusing their power manipulating the laws to their advantage-the situation in Sudan, in my opinion; can be simply described as modern-day slavery! Sudanese businessmen are aggressively taking control of the labour market... Why should they decide the minimum wage when it is a completely irrational and wrong practice that does not exist in any country in the world (conflict of interest)?" (Participant Seven-AAB)</p> <p>"The tripartite committee relationship is an exploitative relationship that benefits these businessmen, and it is in their best interests that the labour act remains in limbo. There is clear evidence that the tripartite committee is not impartial and is biased towards the businessmen's association (Employers Union), as well as evidence that the committee's office is located in the facilities of the Employers Union, despite the fact that it should have been a stand-alone independent entity functioning without prejudices. In any case, no one knows who is in charge for the time being and after 2019 (after the revolution) and the committee has been dissolved! As a result, nothing tends to happen!" (Participant Seven-AAB)</p>

<p>Participant Eight-HEH</p>	<p><i>“Savage aggressive capitalism” that presses and burns people out while making huge profits on the backs of hardworking people and offering them crumbs!!! The Quran contains a clear verse referring to those who deal in fraud that is used for merchants or in trade and it applies to business as well:</i></p> <p style="text-align: center;"><i>وَيْلٌ لِّلْمُطَفِّفِينَ * الَّذِينَ إِذَا اكْتَالُوا عَلَى النَّاسِ يَسْتَوْفُونَ * وَإِذَا كَالُواهُمْ أَوْ وَزَنُواهُمْ يُخْسِرُونَ“</i></p> <p><i>“Woe to those who give less in measure (and weight). “When they buy by measure, they are good to people (“they measure righteously); and when they measure out “to others or weight out for them, they are deficient“ (they give less than its due (83/Al-Mutaffifin” (Participant Eight-HEH)</i></p>
<p>Sub-Theme/Code</p>	<p>Key Aspects and Features:”Gov“rnrment & Governance: Underdeveloped Reform</p>
<p>Participant Two-MZK</p>	<p><i>““almost every few years o” so, the government holds ““review sessions and meet” with the Tripartite committee to actively discuss “he legislation, make recommendations, and in fact d”d create several new rough “drafts, but when it come” time to approve and final“se the updated versions, they never agree on anything and nothing happens!”</i></p>
<p>Participant Three-MOS</p>	<p><i>“I know there was a committee formed eight or nine years ago to review the 1997 Act, and I know it has made some effort to upgrade the labour act, possibly more than once; I believe they have created a draft (but I have not seen anything). I can’t say they have a specific structure or mechanism for doing so, and we haven’t seen any findings, and nothing has been communicated to us, so I’m not sure what it has accomplished. My guess is that the initiative came from the private sector, but this is just my personal speculation”.</i></p>
<p>Participant Four- LME</p>	<p><i>“Any work in this area is heavily reliant on the Tripartite Committee; they determine any progress, change, or development in this area. The problem is things take longer than they should because they never see eye to eye and are frequently faced with challenges or in conflict! As a result, they do not progress and have no set routine for updates and development. In theory, they should have constant regular reviews, but in practice, this is not the case! And the evidence is that the 1997 act has remained unchanged since 1997!”</i></p> <p><i>“At some point, some changes have been proposed; however, the Tripartite Committee never agreed to anything, and thus no change occurred over time. We tried to bring people together recently during my tenure and form task forces or review current laws and make the necessary</i></p>

	<i>changes. In fact, there was a very productive initiative made by the Sudanese HR Managers Association and they came up with good proposals for change, and we welcomed their suggestions and contribution and said why not make them part of the committee task force, which we did; unfortunately, their initiative was unsuccessful”</i>
Participant Five- SEI	<i>“There is no process, no assessment, no revisiting, or re-evaluation, and the biggest proof is that the Act has remained unchanged for the last 25 years! One mechanism for measuring is having a data base for the number of court cases and their precedence; unfortunately, there is nothing objective realistic to rely on for lessons learned and precedence! There are no records or statistics, and there is no medium for media or other mechanisms to educate and raise awareness”.</i>
Participant Six-MAK	<p><i>“There have been a few attempts to review more than once, but these attempts lack key components such as labour court judicial representation (they have been involved in so many issues throughout time and tacked many disputes that are not covered by the labour act-of course, if they were covered, there would be no dispute). They should be involved in the discussions, but they are not. Aside from the civil court judges, there is no link or communication among or between all of the relevant parties”</i></p> <p><i>“There is nothing hidden everything was absolutely clear from the begging. Economic liberalisation polices have not started in 1997, no they have been around since 1978 and grew and spread in 1992; so in the 1997 there were so many core issues that were not catered for then. Everyone knows that; and I have been working on it since 1978. The problem is that the private sector does not want it, they claim that it holds them back in production , they claim that it stands with the worker at the expense of the employer (basically doing its job-we all know labour laws worldwide were initiated to protect workers). The Tripartite Committee must be partners in developing and upgrading...and these old mentalities and ideologies must be eliminated, and each party must compromise in order to achieve a common understanding and a wider benefit”.</i></p>
Participant Seven -AAB	<i>“The 1997Act has not seen any changes despite the fact that it contains numerous mistakes, print mistakes, gaps, and is incapable of coping with global changes or even the local legal reforms that have occurred in Sudan over the years. Of course, from a legal perspective, having the laws for a long period of time is not a problem; the issue is having them without any amendments or updates”</i>
Sub-Theme/Code	Key Aspects and Features: Government & Governance: Labour Offices
Participant Four-LME	<i>“More importantly, labour offices are part of the state/province offices rather than the Ministry of Labour (which is a huge contradiction and huge challenge). This distances it from what is going on</i>

	<i>there; it lacks the necessary links, measures, and statistics to refer to”</i>
Participant Five-SEI	<i>“Another significant fact is that these offices do not report to the ministry (Labour Ministry), but rather to the state offices. Let’s just think about it for a moment: if the ministry wants to establish a relationship with the ILO and effectively develop international standards in Sudan, how can they work with labour offices to implement these strategies if they do not report to them? The same is true for government schools (I know that from Adeel Almadaris-the CSR Corporate Social Responsibility initiative lead for several years)... dividing the schools and renting out the classrooms as shops; government schools with acres of land have been cut and rented to make money, and the funny thing is that this money does not go back to the school; it goes to state offices!”</i>
Sub-Theme/Code	Key Aspects and Features: Government & Governance: Labour Offices - Role, Ability and Credibility!
Participant Two-MZK	<i>“My recommendation is that all labour office inspectors have legal backgrounds, and the benchmark should not be just technical but legal from the start; can you believe that none of the inspectors have legal backgrounds, and as a result, they administer the law with technical abilities rather than legal understanding, which is why most cases end up in labour courts for resolution”.</i>
Participant Four-LME	<i>“More importantly, the labour offices, there may be some corruption issues, which I cannot confirm but suspect. We recommended, in collaboration with the ILO, that the labour ministry be evaluated to determine if it is capable of carrying out its core functions and is capable of achieving the objectives it is meant to achieve” (Participant Four-LME).</i>
	<i>“The second problem is the lack of labour offices in many Sudanese provinces, which rely on civil courts to settle disputes, and these courts are not serialised at all. Everything is linked in a vicious circle”</i>
	<i>“Of course, there are labour offices, but their role is very limited; all they do is reviewing the cases before they are transferred to courts, despite their primary role of mediation and troubleshooting to avoid the cases in the first place. Unfortunately, most or all cases end up in court! As a result, their role is very passive and almost useless. Because they lack competence, they end up</i>

<p>Participant Five-SEI</p>	<p><i>transferring cases to court that should have been handled by them in the first place. They are only concerned with the number of foreign workers! We discussed inspection earlier, and I'd like to add that in my many years of service, I've seen these offices run solely on the number of expatriates we hire, the work permits they have, and all other activities that only generate income for these offices; as a result, the offices became solely responsible for the collection of fees and tariffs, and lost their essence of providing service and assisting private organisations in understanding the labour act"</i></p>
	<p><i>"The labour office is a preliminary stage before the labour court; if these offices were competent, the number of cases that went to court could have been reduced, saving organisations a huge amount of money and time" (Participant Five-SEI)</i></p>
<p>Participant Seven-AAB</p>	<p><i>"Labour offices have no power whatsoever, and foreign organisations are unaware that they are powerless (these offices sometimes take advantage of their ignorance). The labour offices give the employer two weeks to act (their only level of power-nothing else), then tell the employee to take his or her case to court, which can drag for years! The labour offices exist solely to collect fees from organisations"</i></p>
	<p><i>"No one cares about the workers' interests or problems in order to track or measure anything. Even in rural areas, these offices do not exist, so an employee or worker must travel for long distances (7-8 hours) to reach a specialised labour office to obtain the necessary support or information".</i></p>
	<p><i>"Another example is Article 4 of the 1997 Labour Act, which defined many terms but left the phrase "Competent Authority" vague and generally loose/open (leaving it ambiguous), allowing anyone or any side to consider itself the "Competent Authority. This has caused significant difficulties in the application of labour laws and decision making, particularly in rural areas and provinces where specialised representation of legal authority, such as labour courts or offices, is limited or non-existent! When a tribal chief makes a decision and rules an order about which he has no knowledge or understanding, he is referred to as the "Competent Authority".</i></p>
	<p><i>"Furthermore, the labour offices' role is very passive; they have no authority and, most of the time, make no difference. All they do is receive complaints and collect fees. Furthermore, their decisions are not legally binding and must be challenged in court (they have no binding power). To be honest, they are usually more of a hindrance, and sometimes we do not even consider it as a step</i></p>

<p>Participant Eight-HEH</p>	<p><i>because we know they can do nothing and take my problem straight to court, completely ignoring them (without them even knowing). While they should have played a more active role in investigating the issues, checking the standards and specifications to ensure compliance, and acting as a true regulatory body in collaboration with the Industrial Safety and the written act”</i></p> <p><i>“Labour offices: I do not want to diminish their role, but frankly, the labour offices should be analysing, researching, and delivering solutions to recurring problems that they are well aware of... They are not fixing anything; they are just firefighting all the time... It is not enough to bridge the gaps and develop the employer/employee and government relationships”</i></p> <p><i>“Labour offices/officers are also deserted, and their role is diminished, especially when compared to Social Insurance Workers, who are empowered and have the necessary resources to take action because they are properly funded and are empowered to take action”</i></p> <p><i>“Labour offices in Oman and Saudi Arabia for example have leading roles are very capable and empowered; they have full authority and can make decisions and take actions (based on the laws) and solve any problem without going to court. The courts then become a device for implementing the decisions made by the offices; and are reduced to a very small percentage of issued cases, which are often extremely rare”.</i></p>
<p>Participant Nine-RFU</p>	<p><i>“That office is antiquated; you do not have a labour office to run everything, and that office does not even understand labour laws. I only saw them twice in three years, and both times we had to phone them because there was a disagreement with an employee and we needed to highlight something or show them something, so we had to call them and remind them of their job...”</i></p> <p><i>“No, I don’t think they are equipped enough in terms of skills in terms of knowledge and in terms authority, and I’m sorry to say that but you just give someone 200 Sudanese pounds and the problem goes away, yeah, this is horrible corruption, a lot of corruption is going on, I mean, this is a really big problem, and there are so many other issues”(Participant Nine-RFU)</i></p>
<p>Sub-Theme/Code</p>	<p>Key Aspects and Features: Government & Governance: Labour Offices- Lack of Consistency & Flexibility</p>
<p>Participant</p>	<p><i>“The consistency with which the legislation is applied is a critical success factor; due to the elasticity of the legislation, huge disparities occur all the time. Today, for example, the three main</i></p>

Two-MZK	<p><i>labour offices (Khartoum, Khartoum North, and Omdurman) can handle the same case in three different ways! This disparity creates confusion and unnecessary inconsistencies that are inconvenient for both parties. As a result, I believe that there should be universal legislation that aligns and unifies all locations and sectors, and that should simply mean the same to everyone and be clearly understood by all without any divergence, i.e., reach a common understanding in all relevant concepts without debating any issue”.</i></p>
Participant Three-MOS	<p><i>“There is no consistency whatsoever; everything is based on personal judgement, personality, understanding of the situation, and interpretation of the law. The law is not consistently applied, resulting in fragmented application even at the level of labour law governors themselves. Because the legislations are not specific and clearly defined, the interpretation varies among the various bodies... As a result, the application of the 1997 law becomes even more difficult to follow because the people who created it are unable to follow it because it means different things to different people! Let me give you an interesting example: ...I worked for a multi-company organisation whose HR function I headed and led the company branches across the country. When I first started in 2001, the company was new, and I developed a standardised employee disciplinary procedure that had to be endorsed and approved by the labour office (in accordance with the 1997 labour act), and naturally, I developed one single standard disciplinary action and standard sets of contracts for the three different branches spread across the capital city Greater Khartoum. The Khartoum labour offices then approved it for use by all branches in Khartoum North and Omdurman. I then had to engage with the Khartoum-North Office for verification and show them the disciplinary procedure and contracts authenticated by the Khartoum office; however, the Khartoum-North Office refused the disciplinary procedure and the contracts and stated that they are unable to recognise them because the Khartoum office regulations are incompatible with their applications (note that both offices apply the same regulatory body which is the 1997 Labour Act)...It was shocking to hear that and created a real dilemma for me at the time; I was referring to the application of the 1997 act within the capital city of Khartoum! I then gave them the disciplinary procedure and contracts to review, and I made all of the changes they requested in order to best suit the requirements of the Khartoum-North office. The same thing happened at the Omdurman office, with various changes made to meet various criteria and measures. Of course, I had to follow the rules of all three offices, which resulted in three different disciplinary procedures for three branches of the same company. This meant that in core disciplinary actions across three geographic locations in the same city, I would have to treat many employees working for the same company under one payroll differently! This was an obvious injustice and contradiction that I did not understand; keep in mind that all three offices use the same labour law!!!! So I had to go a step further and bring all three offices together with the help of a senior director, including the</i></p>

	<i>minister, and with and under very special considerations, the three offices agreed to one consistent disciplinary procedure for the three branches. All of the work done went above and beyond what was required; however, if we had not taken this extra step and gone the extra mile, we would have been all over the place with three inconsistent disciplinary procedures for employees working for the same company!”)</i>
Participant Four-LME	<i>“We have a major issue in this area, particularly in arbitration (mediation). Some believe the ministry is slowing things down. Some disputes could be easily resolved, but it is believed that the ministry of labour (via the labour offices) benefits from the delays and ambiguity through the income/fees generated by the labour offices’ arbitration... Furthermore, the necessary measures are not in place; the ministry should have data on things like the number of cases/disputes, but none are available to relate to. Furthermore, there is no inspection-this activity is not in operation!”</i>
Participant Five-SEI	<i>“One might argue that why should the labour act require interpretation, explanation, and clarification in the first place; why isn’t it straightforward and easily understood in the first place?! Why do you require an intermediary in order to function?! So income is a problem... because they want the money to go to the ministry!</i>
Participant Eight-HEH	<i>“Labour offices are not performing their duties of monitoring and inspecting organisations to ensure that none of this (discrimination) occurs. Furthermore, they lack the common sense that allows them to think outside the box (and comply with best practise standards), and they operate rigidly in a way that is not flexible enough to accommodate all of the needs of the various types of work. Consider for example how work tardiness (being late) is handled in the same manner across all industries; for example, I work in the aviation industry, where being late has a significant impact on the job, as opposed to other industries where the implication may be less severe. If I want to develop a regulation that reflects this significance, the labour office will not support it because all they understand is that there is only one fixed standard that cannot be avoided by any means (and cannot work around it). Another example: a worker smoking in a gas station should not be treated the same as a worker in a non-smoking office because of the potential consequences!”</i>
Participant/ Sub Theme	Theme Two: Major Issues & Challenges

Sub-Theme/Code	Major Issues & Challenges: How well is the Act coping, and is it equipped for the twenty-first century challenges?
Participant Two-MZK	<p><i>“It is not coping at all and has not been equipped for a very long time; 2.5 decades is quite a long time. The change in Sudan’s social, economic and political environment has been rapid in the past decades and the labour Act has not matched this move by all measures. It is not effectively serving the employer or the worker (employee of today). The 1997 law was developed with a bygone mentality in mind, when workers were much weaker and less informed; however, today’s workers are more knowledgeable and have a broad understanding of their rights and how the law must protect them-both as workers and employers” (Participant Two-MZK)</i></p>
Participant Three-MOS	<p><i>“The answer is defiantly not; I personally, as a practitioner, have faced huge challenge with this law for years; I was struggling with certain gaps and areas in the legislation 20 years ago (note that other new challenges have risen in-between); so without hesitation, I know for certain that the current law, in its current state, does not fulfil all of our needs; and this has been proven even more after the Covid19 Pandemic, when we as HR professionals realised that there are no laws that support flexible work such as working from home, online work engagements, and even part-time work. As a result, I can simply state that the labour law of 1997 does not support Sudan’s current contemporary work environment” (Participant Three-MOS)</i></p>
Participant Four-LME	<p><i>“It is defiantly outdated, and this is a problem with all Sudanese laws—we have many other laws that are mostly outdated, such as (Domestic Workers Laws) and many others (Participant Four-LME)</i></p>
Participant Five-SEI	<p><i>“Yes, it is not equipped for 1997, let alone equipped 2022! Even the wording and editing speak of a long-gone era in Sudan when the country was heavily reliant on industries such as cotton, sugarcane, and fabric production” (Participant Five-SEI)</i></p>
	<p><i>“Even in 1997, the 1997 copy was not convincing to anyone (including its custodians), labour unions, the government, or anyone else. And the proof is that they always make proposals and attempts at change but never achieve anything. This clearly demonstrates the true flaws of the 1997 Act and provides an answer to the question” (Participant Six-MAK)</i></p> <p><i>“I would first like to first highlight the fact that there were several attempts made to upgrade the Act of 1997 in a number of different years (2002, 2006,2007,2013,2018) none of which were</i></p>

<p>Participant Six-MAK</p>	<p><i>successful as there was no agreement from the Tripartite Committee, every time the projects take shape. Still, the three partners never agreed to anything. The 2013 copy actually made it to the National Council for approval but was suddenly withdrawn. The final copy of 2018 was the only copy that the three members fully endorsed it was completed before the revolution, this copy should have comprehensive and should have been approved, and there was no reason to hold it back. All the aspects needed for the 3rd millennium should have been incorporated in this copy. However, what was obvious to us is that it was no” (Participant Six-MAK)</i></p>
	<p><i>“The most recent draft, made in 2018, and the one before it, both have some positive aspects. But, to answer your question, the most recent copy of 2018 focused on the approach of combining all labour laws into a single unified act. The 1997 copy was unclear in emphasising the fundamental labour law rules of public order, which may not be violated (just like all other countries in the world). The concept of employment equality appears in the 2018 proposal, which did not appear in the 1997 copy.....To summarise and answer your question, none of these copies, including the proposed latest version of 2018 update, are sufficient to solve the problems/issues of the third millennium or meet the needs of Sudanese people in the twenty-first century; it will be similar to the 1997 version with very little impact (Participant Six-MAK)</i></p>
<p>Participant Nine-RFU</p>	<p><i>“No, it is not equipped at all. My answer is straightforward: Sudan has stagnated primarily due to the autocratic style of the previous president Omer Al-Bashir; they did not focus on what was important for the employees.... with anything said it was fine 20-25 years ago, but now we are dealing with and facing international challenges from the International Labour Organization... and if we benchmark other countries within Africa, a lot needs to be done” (Participant Nine-RFU)</i></p>
<p>Sub-Theme/Code</p>	<p>Major Issues & Challenges: Lack of Clarity Consistency and Alignment</p>
<p>Participant Two-MZK</p>	<p><i>The first and foremost the most important and impactful upgrade would be to have one consolidated comprehensive legislation that covers all working people in our society and covers all different proceedings instead of all those separate laws scattered here and there ...Note: we now have all those different governmental organisations exempted and following separate laws in addition to the many stand-alone laws like for example: Work Injuries...Minimum wage. Social Insurance...Expatriates working in Sudan.... And my recommendation is that all these laws come together in a well-coordinated collaborated legislation and be consistent with one another as having them scattered the way they currently sometimes create contradictions and inconsistencies.</i></p>

	<p><i>At the opening of the legislation, there is a wide range of government groups and other groups that are exempt from the legislation and follow different individual legislations such as civil servants, members of the armed forces, domestic servants, agricultural labourers, employer’s family members, casual employees...etc (nine different categories). My first recommendation would be to have one single comprehensive act that covers and includes all workers. In addition to that and at the very end of the exemption section the act also says the following “any class of persons, the Ministry Council may declare by an order that they are exempted totally or partially from the provisions of this Act”. This means the ministry can at any point in time declare someone or some association exempt. This creates huge inconsistencies and creates unnecessary discrepancies and unfairness! I personally believe that this is a very unwise decision to take.</i></p> <p><i>“Personally, I believe that this is a very bad decision”.</i></p>
Participant Three-MOS	<p><i>“So to conclude, there are no consistent measures that everyone understands, and this disparity creates huge discrepancy and haphazardness across the country. The same case can be handled differently by two different HR representatives working for the same company in different timeframes, and as I explained in my example, each labour office interprets the same legislation differently and creates a separate rule for it, expecting you to apply three different rules for people in the same organisation. And, depending on the timing, the situation, or the person in charge, the same case and scenario will be handled and governed differently many more times! The law is highly subjective; the measures are arbitrary, lack objectivity, and are based solely on personal judgement” (Participant Three-MOS)</i></p>
Participant Five-SEI	<p><i>“Because the legislations are not specific and clearly defined, the interpretation varies among the various bodies... As a result, the application of the 1997 law becomes even more difficult to follow even for the people who created it are unable to follow it because it means different things to different people!”</i></p>
Participant Six-MAK	<p><i>“There is no alignment no harmony; they don’t speak the same language!”</i></p> <p><i>“Occupational Health, Industrial Safety, and Decent Work are all linked to one another and to the employment regulations - if aligned and in harmony, they can reduce the number of labour court disputes”</i></p>
Participant Seven-AAB	<p><i>“For example, the Sudanese Labour Act of 1997 grants children the right to work at the age of 16, whereas the Sudanese Child Act of 2010 considers anyone under the age of 18 to be a child and should not work without permission - resulting in two laws operating concurrently that contradict one another”</i></p>

Participant Eight-HEH	<i>“The legal applications (inconsistencies) are at the level of the Supreme Court!”</i>
	<i>“Scattered legislation: The Minimum Wage Act of 1974 (Seven Articles) is a separate law that should have been incorporated into the laws themselves due to its importance and significance, as well as for clarity. Some relevant effective articles remain part of the Civil Transaction Laws but govern the employment contract (when they contradict, the Labour Law takes precedence/priority over the other). Why not combine and unify all these Articles into a single Act known as “The Labour Act”? All the Acts must be in harmony and synchronisation. Unify the meaning and thus the understanding...they are inconsistent, lack uniformity... There is no common ground- there is a lack of consistency in interpretations and applications-each location has its own points of view and interpretations!”</i>
Sub-Theme/Code	Major Issues & Challenges: “What doesn’t get measured doesn’t get managed”
Participant One-E.O.S	<i>There were no measures, and no one followed up with you or audited your implementation. When I was working, I had to do the follow-up and remind the companies I worked for, as well as govern myself; except for Shell, which was very keen not to break the laws and did not want to get into any disputes because they were already in enough trouble. The HR function was in charge of enforcing labour regulations; they took the initiative, so it was up to them to do the right thing; no one came back to challenge their application or audit them.</i>
	<i>The Ministry of Labour has no follow-ups on the labour law’s implementation.</i>
Participant Four-LME	<i>The most recent workforce census/survey was in 2011 (now obsolete), so everything is out of date! And nothing has happened since; we don’t even know how many people are employed! We have a major problem here; there are no records or evidence on which to rely or base your decisions. This was the most difficult challenge for me as someone who can and needs evidence to rely on; there is no data - nothing (we were in the dark)! We attempted to assist families during the COVID-19 crisis and determine how many families are there in each region; however, we were unable to do so due to a lack of reference data. How can you make policies when you don’t have basic information?</i>
	<i>“The only KPIs or measures in place are the amounts of money collected from penalties, such as</i>

	<i>when violating health and safety regulations, as well as other fees and charges for work permits, registrations, and other payments such as clarifications. Essentially, sales/commission and the official labour office representatives in charge of these sales are paid an annual bonus based on the volume of sales they manage to generate. They measure their success based on the amount of money collected rather than the impact they have made”.</i>
	<i>There are no measurements, no statistics, and no measurements at all... There is no data at all)</i>
Participant Five-SEI	<i>At the very least, having a data base for the number of court cases and their precedence is one of the mechanisms for measuring. Unfortunately, there is no objective realistic basis for lessons learned or precedent! There are no records or statistics, and there are no mediums, media, or other mechanisms to educate and raise awareness.</i>
	<i>There are no measures in place that have been developed by the ministry or government to support the application of the labour act... Nothing; everything is dependent on the employer’s integrity!</i>
Participant Seven-AAB	<i>There is no research and development in labour issues. There are no statistical records and no data</i>
	<i>No one cares about the workers’ interests or problems in order to follow or measure anything; the labour offices exist solely to collect money from organisations.</i>
Participant Eight-HEH	<i>No, the Sudanese government does not measure anything. They are really not tracking or measuring anything.</i>
Sub-Theme/Code	Major Issues & Challenges: Remuneration-Minimum Wage
Participant Two-MZK	<i>“The minimum wage; it is a disgrace and is far way far from being realistic by all measure”.</i>
	<i>“The minimum wage set by the government is not based on a realistic benchmark and is far below any reasonable/rational measure; and has through time consistently failed to meet the expectations of the Sudanese people, resulting in a threshold that constantly keeps workers below the poverty line. True, the high drastic level of inflation plays a role, but the measures used to calculate it are not reliable enough, and the government is simply not paying enough attention to the issue. Minimum wage should be reviewed and assessed on a regular basis...some leading companies are currently taking the initiative to review their minimum wage every quarter in order to cope with high inflation and skyrocketing living costs... These are the few who want to be at the top of their</i>

	<i>game while also retaining and protecting their employees. However, the regulatory body is falling behind, which is very unfortunate”</i>
Participant Three-MOS	<i>“Minimal wage is not compatible with the real needs of the people. The common thing is to calculate the minimal wage on the bases of people’s needs this is not happening in Sudan!”</i>
Participant Six-MAK	<i>“All major socioeconomic issues receive no attention. It should be noted that the revolution was based on a rebellion and protest against the minimum wage”.</i>
Participant Eight-HEH	<i>“The minimum wage law is a separate law that should have been incorporated into the laws themselves due to its importance and clarity”</i>
	<i>“A new article published recently by the social insurance says that companies should not bring in contributions of wages below a threshold of SDG 12,000 that they have determined on their own calling it a minimum wage (just something they have decided on their own), which leaves a lot of room for disagreement”.</i>
	<i>“One living in Sudan will not be able to subsist on 100 times the current minimum wage”.</i>
Sub-Theme/Code	Major Issues & Challenges: Remuneration- Salary Breakdown, Overtime and other Benefits
Participant Three-MOS	<i>“The six-month compensation for unfair dismissal is calculated based on the Basic Salary (Salary + Cost of Living), which could end up being as little as three months if not less. This is an obvious gap and weakness in the law that everyone recognises. It also allows the employer to skirt the benefit “legally” without repercussions. A significant gap and weakness in the law that requires urgent attention; After-service Benefits are also calculated from (Salary + Cost of Living), which can be as little as a quarter of the wage. This results in injustice at a pivotal moment of time. And the way overtime is calculated creates huge injustice and of course affects the most vulnerable. Basic Salary (Salary + Cost of Living) which can constitute around 25% of the take-home salary; this amount is used to calculate the overtime cost; it is so unfair and unjust for someone to work in their own valuable leisure time and receive very little compensation for it despite the fact that the law determines the overtime hour should cost 1.5 hours during weekdays and 2.0 hours during weekends. However, when it is calculated from this minimum rate salary (supported by the labour law), it amounts to nothing because it was based on nothing!”</i>
	<i>“There are significant pay issues. Nurses work long hours and are underpaid; they don’t even have time to complain or file a claim!”</i>

Participant Six-MAK	<i>"I can tell you there is a huge amount of inequality. I have a list of marginalised groups, both male and female, who do the same work but are not paid the same".</i>
Participant Seven-AAB	<i>"Salary breakdown in the contract (basic pay is very low, around 20%) to avoid paying large termination allowances (the 6-month basic pay compensation)"</i> <i>"When discussing annual salary reviews of 5% of the basic salary provided the worker shows satisfactory performance, the Sudanese labour act (minimum wage) only mentions performance once, in a very vague phrase without explaining what satisfactory means"?</i>
Participant Eight-HEH	<i>"Basic pay is not governed by any formula or percentage and is left to the employer's discretion...which is widely abused"</i>
Sub-Theme/Code	Major Issues & Challenges: Remuneration- National Pension and Social Insurance Fund
Participant Two-MZK	<i>"When calculating social insurance based on a very low basic salary... This means that social insurance will eventually be low, which means that in a time of genuine need, when the worker has retired and is unable to work, his/her social protection will be insufficient to provide him/her with the dignity they require. Due to the depreciation of the Sudanese pound, social insurance is a major issue in Sudan today, and much work is required... The system/policies themselves are fine; in fact, they are in accordance with best practices; however, the problem, like all other policies, is in the application itself".</i>
Participant Four-LME	<i>"Social insurance should cover everyone, including the informal sector; the same applies for health Insurance however, in practice, they do not (informal groups, part-timers etc are not accounted for). But why aren't we doing so is the question. Neither supported nor covered! You could say that the program is new, that there is so much to do, that we are far behind, and that much needs to be done.</i> <i>"Social insurance is unjust because of its breakdown and the ease with which it can be manipulated, as well as the fact that people are not allowed to collect it if they have worked for less than three years... Who gave them the authority to do so (are they hoping for a devaluation?!)"</i>
Participant Five-SEI	<i>"Social Insurance is corrupt!"</i>

<p>Participant Six-MAK</p>	<p><i>“Let me share with you a very peculiar fact: in 2011 the Industrial Survey (and according to the Employment Policies Report 2017) revealed the following:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>❖ The Total Number of paid working people nationwide are= 5,500,000</i> <i>❖ The Number of working people registered in the National Pension and Social Insurance Fund are=less than one million (around 750,000)</i> <i>❖ Following the revolution in 2019, they updated the figure to = 1,000,000</i> <i>❖ Meaning more than 4,000,000 working people are not registered in pensions, social insurance, or have medical insurance (medical insurance is one of the polices under the labour Act of 1997)</i> <i>❖ Membership in the Sudan Trade Union Confederation is supposed to come from registered workers (all working people have by default automatic membership)</i> <i>❖ The membership stands at 1,200,000 (on the day the revolution occurred and the Union fell/was dissolved)</i> <p><i>These figures, I can tell you, are based on official government reports issued by the ministry and discussed in the Ministerial Council and National Council. I have the reports in my office drawers right now! I raised these concerns in numerous forums, and questioned all these issues and no one responded, instead, they just remove me from my position!”</i></p> <p><i>“Even employed people are not covered by the social insurance when they stop working”.</i></p> <p><i>“Working people in the upcountry/province have been cheated out of their social insurance rights, and their money has been diverted for other purposes without their knowledge and consent”.</i></p> <p><i>“Unfair dismissal and paying women their rights to maternity leave among both among other things can be addressed with the help of the social insurance fund (both parties contributing). We should connect them for sustainable social protection.... But nothing will happen if we leave it hanging”.</i></p> <p><i>“Social Insurance is corrupt!”</i></p>
<p>Participant Seven-AAB</p>	<p><i>“Imagine that in 2004, pensioners received roughly 500 Sudanese pounds- less than \$1 per month! Where is the social protection in this?!”</i></p>

Participant Eight-HEH	<i>“Social insurance does not provide you with the protection you require when you are most vulnerable...the 2016 update makes it impossible to obtain the timely compensation you require when you are out of work! You must wait three years... Why should I wait...or must I wait for its value to deteriorate? They invest my money and I receive nothing in return!”</i>
Sub-Theme/Code	Major Issues & Challenges: Remuneration- Beyond the Formal Sector
Participant Two-MZK	<i>“Workers outside the formal labour market are not covered by the Sudanese Labour Act of 1997, including independent workers, self-employed individuals, home workers, and others. However, the legislation covers any official work involving any intellectual effort that is compensated by pay. Moreover, there are other important groups that are not included in the legislation, such as farmers, shepherds, and farm labourers. If they have problems, they have nowhere to turn to because the law does not support or include them, unless they seek civil laws and courts, which may or may not protect them”.</i>
Participant Three-MOS	<i>“The 1997 act does not cover the informal sector at all those unregulated wage workers, the self-employed and home workers are out of scope”.</i>
Participant Six-MAK	<i>“How will they cover the unofficial sector if the official sector is not covered? There are many people who work part-time in multiple places, students, and others who are not recognised by the laws and are considered unemployed. Some people work in both the official recognised sector and the unofficial sector, but they are not recognised in the latter”</i>
Participant Seven-AAB	<p><i>Informal workers, self-employed, owners, and their families are not covered by the 1997 Act, but anyone working for the owner is! Even if there is no contract! The Act excludes many employment sectors in Khartoum (the capital city) that clearly employ regular workers, such as:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>• Petrol Station Employees</i> <i>• Loading and Offloading</i> <i>• Bakers in Bakeries (because they work very long hours to exclude them from overtime)</i> <p><i>The government created stand-alone Pay Orders to govern their wages and excluded them from the right of governance under the Labour Act 1997 to manipulate and exploit their pay (once again protecting businessmen at the expense of the weak party, the worker))</i></p>

Sub-Theme/Code	Major Issues & Challenges: Protecting the Most Vulnerable
Participant Four-LME	<i>“The informal sector is not represented at all, despite the fact that it accounts for a significant portion of the economy, and that life is changing in Sudan, as it is throughout the world, with people seeking flexibility in their jobs (freelancing and entrepreneurship), particularly among young people”</i>
Participant Nine-RFU	<i>“What I realised is that there is a very old ineffective social security system. Second, governments are made up entirely of military and police personnel who have no idea what is going on in business and don’t care; they only look after themselves. Unfortunately, Sudan has no social security system, which is why there is so much unrest in the country. The extremes are too far apart”</i>
Sub-Theme/Code	Major Issues & Challenges: Is it Protection or Exploitation?
Participant One-E.O.S	<i>“I could have evaluated it if it was applicable to the most vulnerable workforce; however, it is not. To illustrate further, consider domestic workers such as housemaids, personal drivers, and gardeners (or any hired help): the law mentions them briefly and applies in legal terms; however, it is not realistically applied, enforced, or monitored in any way. As a result, you cannot truly say that the law protects the most vulnerable”.</i>
	<i>“Minorities are not protected; it is only for image and publicity purposes; however, the law does not protect these groups; it is extremely basic”.</i>
Participant Three-MOS	<i>“No, it does not protect the most vulnerable; it has huge challenges that affect most workers and, of course, has a greater impact on the most vulnerable in society; the act of 1997 has vast obvious flaws that ultimately create huge injustice; let us consider three important elements that have a negative impact on the most vulnerable: Minimum wage, overtime, and unfair dismissal”</i>
Participant Five-SEI	<i>“To begin with, there are no job opportunities here! And the Act does not promote anything in this regard. People with disabilities and vulnerabilities are the most impacted by this, as they require opportunities that are almost invisible! I wish the Act of 1997 had mentioned anything promoting or supporting this segment, but it did not. There are no equal opportunities acts or equality acts to go along and work hand in hand with the labour act”</i>
	<i>“If we talk about people with special needs, it did not cater for this category at all, people with vulnerabilities such as disabled and workers with special needs cover (the law does not cover this area... it is neglected). Important things like disabled-accessible facilities, such as wheelchair</i>

	<i>ramps and special toilets.... all of this is not covered by the Labour Act of 1997, which is nowhere mentioned! As I previously stated, the law was not equipped even in 1997. As you are aware, all of these developments are dependent on the country's economic situation, and you are also aware that Sudan is currently struggling in this area".</i>
Participant Six-MAK	<i>"There are no protections whatsoever as most vulnerable groups are not included in the Act to begin with, and thus have nothing to protect them (marginalised groups are not covered in these laws)"</i>
	<i>"Agricultural workers are not covered; in the reviews, they are included in some cases and removed in others...they are unable to decide whether to include or remove them. And Garbage collectors have nothing; they are completely overlooked"</i>
Participant Seven-AAB	<i>"The 1997 Act is very general and does not demonstrate a specific focus on our society's most vulnerable workforce. There is a separate Act that covers domestic workers that was modified for the province of Khartoum only in 2009 (it used to be a federal law across Sudan but was then modified for the province of Khartoum only), but it is very weak in terms of protection and coverage, particularly for overtime hours and unlawful termination".</i>
	<i>"MENA countries abuse people in a variety of ways, not just workers; they are highly exploitative dictatorships... and have horrific practises... I don't believe Sudan resembles them in any way...they are mostly controlled by greedy parasitic capitalism—with corruption and opportunism profiting on the backs of exploited workers—and are simply incapable of functioning without it"</i>
	<i>"It was designed to serve and protect employers, whereas labour laws were designed to protect vulnerable groups who are unable to protect themselves and save them from exploitation and the strength of capitalism".</i>
	<i>"All labour laws protect the employer and work in the employer's favour rather than the worker's"</i> (Participant Seven-AAB)
	<i>"I know very large Sudanese companies with enormous financial resources that do not provide drinking water to their workers and employees! They must go outside and purchase their own water if they want to drink"</i>
Participant Eight-HEH	<i>"In general, these current laws do not protect anyone, vulnerable or not... At every level, it is lacking the component of protection! Consider the minimum wage for example, which is so low</i>

	<i>(SDG3000 less than 7 USD per month), how are workers protected?! SDG425 plus all other allowances brought the total to SDG 3000 (president award)!"</i>
Sub-Theme/Code	Major Issues & Challenges: Unemployment Protection
Participant Four-LME	<i>"There are no social protections for unemployment because the country lacks financial capability, and unemployment rates are extremely high throughout the country. National Employment Policy (which is currently drafted). In Sudan, we have the National Social Security... National Pension Plans... Health Insurance-Unfortunately, none of these are feasible in light of the needs. Due to high inflation rates and the devaluation of the Sudanese pound, you end up with a pension rate that is far below the basic minimum wage. A pensioner will pay his or her entire monthly pension for transportation to collect his or her money".</i>
Participant Five-SEI	<i>"No, there is absolutely nothing on unemployment; this is a government responsibility that does not exist".</i>
Participant Six-MAK	<i>"Even employed people are not protected by social insurance when they stop working".</i>
	<i>"By the way, no one cares, and if we searched the entire county for two people who did care, only two people who shared our concern...you and I might be the only two, and we might not find another!"</i>
Participant Seven-AAB	<i>"Take into account that since 2004, pensioners have received around 500 Sudanese pounds per month, which is less than one US dollar per month! The government's role in protection is "institutionalised injustice"! You have the impression that the government is working against the people! Where is the social protection in this?"</i>
	<i>"Unemployed workers are not protected...because no social protection exists. Despite the fact that Sudan previously endorsed International Agreements to protect unemployed workers, there is no unemployment protection. The government should take the lead in insuring/providing unemployment insurance".</i>
Participant Eight-HEH	<i>"Protection for unemployment (social protection); unfortunately, there is nothing...working people are not getting the protection they deserve!!!"</i>

Sub-Theme/Code	Major Issues & Challenges: Workplace Boundaries - <i>Bulling and Harassment</i>
Participant One-E.O. S	<p><i>“There is absolutely nothing! I have worked in this field for many years; the law does not cover anything in this area, so we had to rely on our own internal policies to govern these areas; for example, Shell relied heavily on their own internal policies”.</i></p> <p><i>“Women are unable to complain because there are no channels for filing claims or reporting wrongdoing (whistleblowing). There are no guidelines, no boundaries, and no regulations, so things just sort of happen and pass by”.</i></p>
Participant Two-MZK	<p><i>“Harassment” and “Bullying”- Nothing in the law prohibits any of these... The problem is that none of the parties are aware of these issues; those in charge of labour policies, those in charge of organisations, and even the workers and employees who need to be protected are unaware of them!! As a result, we are significantly behind in these areas”.</i></p>
Participant Three-MOS	<p><i>“The law has nothing on Bulling and Harassment there is absolutely nothing mentioned. But in the recent years some companies have started to be aware or these issues and want to make a difference in the area by creating their own internal policies that cover them. The problem I have seen these very marginal group not fully able to grasp the true meaning of these behaviours and their impact on workers and employees; and sadly, they themselves who are meant to create polices to protect the vulnerable form such injustices do not have the capacity to comprehend the real value in doing so! They are just ticking boxed but are not convinced themselves. So I believe we do not have the right culture in place or the awareness level to support us in driving workplace boundaries”</i></p> <p><i>“Sexual harassment is not taken seriously, and women do not trust the internal systems as they know they do not protect them; and frequently judge them when they are the victims. Hence, they do not complain when things happen to them, or things go wrong preferring to keep a low profile instead. They will be judged most of the time and sometimes by the people who are meant to protect them and are in charge of their wellbeing. I was asked once by a reputable consultant representing a reputable company that wants to develop an internal sexual harassment policy, the strange thing is that they briefed me that they do not want to make it clearly visible that it was a sexual harassment policy; they want the policy but don’t want the ladies in working for the company to understand what is represents! This was one of the awkward practices leading companies can</i></p>

	<p><i>actually want to do...lack of transparency in such fundamental issues”.</i></p> <p><i>“ Regarding bulling things take a very informal approach and precedence and a very serious issue is taken very lightly casually with a light sprit of joking, mocking and with huge informality that usually dilutes the essence of the problem losing its significance; as if this is just a normal behaviour that should not be even taken into consideration and sometimes the people involved make you feel you are making a big fuss out of nothing”</i></p>
Participant Four-LME	<p><i>“Bulling” and “Harassment” ...Nothing!!</i></p>
Participant Five-SEI	<p><i>“Returning to harassment, sexual harassment has no basis for complaints or reporting because it is not supported by any regulation; as a result, women do not complain when they suffer; instead, they just keep it to themselves. Furthermore, they are terrified of the community and how they are perceived; as the community is not just in such circumstances and usually blames the women for any incident, and most would argue that she had it coming or in some way encouraged such behaviour (extreme inequality and injustice); whether intentionally or unintentionally, as a woman you are always viewed as part of the problem”.</i></p> <p><i>However, change is inevitable, and people require vivid, transparent regulations to safely regulate workplace behaviours. Since these practises exist despite people’s upbringing and culture, we must not rely on what our culture dictates, but rather take all necessary steps and measures to prevent such behaviours in the workplace through clear clauses and genuine enforcement, with zero tolerance for all types of such behaviours (Participant Five-SEI)</i></p>
Participant Six-MAK	<p><i>“Bullying and harassment are not currently covered by the 1997 Act. This was one of the disagreements that occurred between members of the tripartite committee in the new proposal (2018 proposal); they never reached an agreement on this point”.</i></p>
	<p><i>“The labour law gave the employer the right to terminate the employment contract if the worker/employee on certain occasions if he/she committed a moral crime that touches someone’s dignity and honour, the only problem is that Article links this to a court convection (there must be one first-a police case) and considers it a criminal case. This route or course of direction involves so many issues and complications that most of the time the victims tend to refrain from it and avoid taking action: breaches confidentiality, affects reputation negatively (especially for women). It also requires witnesses from the workplace (which is difficult to secure) and requires very strong evidence”</i></p>

<p>Participant Eight-HEH</p>	<p><i>“Unfortunately, because the system /law does not protect in clear targeted ways most of the victims tend to escape the workplace and prefer not to take any action to protect their reputation and themselves. You can simply say that when the law was written in 1997 this area was not an issue back then; however, in the last 25 years there has been a gradual decline in the morals and behaviours, and it is now evident that people need to look into this area with more depth. In the past if someone was known to have committed a violation of such a kind this person will be too ashamed and will immediately leave the job (will run away without any question).</i></p>
	<p><i>“You cannot end a work relationship if an employee was evidently proved to have committed a violation such as sexual harassment. As an employer I do not have the right to terminate this employment...the process is very tedious and impractical (note: Sexual Harassment is not mentioned specifically in the Act as a standalone violation but can be implied (as it requires a court condemnation and very long processes); the employer is not empowered to take an action in this issue. So, if he or she decides to terminate the contract it would be considered in the eyes of law “Unlawful Termination” that must be compensated!”</i></p>
<p>Participant Nine-RFU</p>	<p><i>“I don’t recall seeing that because there is a lot of bullying going on; managers believe they are masters and their employees are slaves, so they treat them as such. I did not notice any specific quotes or legislations”.</i></p>
<p>Sub-Theme/Code</p>	<p>Major Issues & Challenges: Equality Diversity and Inclusion</p>
<p>Participant One-E.O.S</p>	<p><i>“In Sudan, there are huge inequalities between working people; this is a widely seen and felt issue, particularly racial discrimination, which is widespread. In comparison to other countries, one thing that stands out is the small or non-existent pay gap between male and female workers/employees doing the same job (for example Canada & the US). This, I believe, is a significant issue that stems from the Sudanese cultural framework and composition, in which there is little distinction between men and women in employment”</i></p> <p><i>“Considering the rights of existing marginalised groups, everyone who has worked in Sudan knows that there is a lot of disparity between different groups of people, from different regions and ethnicities in Sudan; the law does not have anything on that does not mention anything to protect these marginalised groups, minorities, or people with disabilities in any way”. Women and children are the only two groups that are specifically mentioned or touched on in the legislation (in general terms), leaving out all other groups”</i></p>

	<p><i>“You mean a Discrimination Act? There isn’t one! And, of course, all other freedoms and rights associated with things like:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>• Freedom of belief and expression</i> <i>• Tribal and Racial discrimination</i> <i>• Gender and sexuality which are by definition not socially acceptable for religious reasons.</i> <i>• Nepotism and Favouritism – is common and well established in most organisations”</i>
<p>Participant Three-MOS</p>	<p><i>“Diversity, equal opportunities, and gender representation are not supported or covered by Sudanese labour law (nothing is stated in this perspective and there are no mechanisms to protect these standpoint). Even today, a large number of organisations openly advertise for ordinary jobs that do not require any sort of positive discrimination, requesting “Male Only” applicants for positions that a female is perfectly capable of commissioning just as well, if not better! I believe it is a problem of no rules, no measures, and no consequences, rather than a lack of knowledge of best practices (nothing happens as there are no retrospective actions). And there are numerous other issues of inequality that require immediate attention”</i></p> <p><i>“Diversity and equality should be explicitly stated, protected, and governing mechanisms put in place”.</i></p>
<p>Participant Four-LME</p>	<p><i>“There is nothing to protect the Sudanese workplace from high levels of inequality, discrimination, and social injustice; and we must work on incorporating these areas as well as promoting diversity and inclusion matters”.</i></p>
<p>Participant Five-SEI</p>	<p><i>“Racism is prevalent in Sudan, and the labour act contains no provisions to protect workers and employees in this regard, leaving a significant gap”</i></p> <p><i>“Fair representation, equality, and diversity.... all these laws are missing; we need to develop them in the new act promoting fair representation, equality, and diversity all should be in the new Sudanese Act”</i></p> <p><i>“There are cultural issues that act does not address things like opportunity, for example, the opportunities for women in senior jobs, and promotion, there is nothing specific to tackle these inequalities if any (gender inequalities). However, despite the gap in articles in this area and despite the fact of not being addressed, the Sudanese culture itself did not need to require much work in the area as by nature the culture has addressed about this issue very well throughout history. As Sudanese women proved themselves in the workplace, they broke barriers a very long time ago, and since the independence, they had equal chances for education they became judges, doctors, and ministers. If there was no pressing need then for the laws to focus on or tackle this area maybe by nature; nevertheless, I believe it does need to be addressed now to strengthen and enhance it. Culturally women are well respected in the workplace they have dominated all sectors</i></p>

	<p><i>and excelled well. They are well educated and qualified for all jobs and were refined from a young age (from home) to compete well with men and so there was no need to explicitly mention it in the labour regulations as when the labour act was developed in the 1960 women were already parliament members! And had a strong impact and say in the community. Yet we still strongly believe that the document should be inclusive to reflect the culture and practices and should be documented (best practice is the practice that is customised with the cultural needs and requirements)”</i></p>
	<p><i>“To begin with, there are no job opportunities here! And the Act does not promote anything in this regard. People with disabilities and vulnerabilities are the most impacted by this, as they require opportunities that are almost invisible! I wish the Act of 1997 had mentioned anything promoting or supporting this segment, but it did not. There are no equal opportunities acts or equality acts to go along with the labour act”</i></p>
<p>Participant Six-MAK</p>	<p><i>“I can tell you there is a lot of inequality. I have a list of marginalised groups, both male and female, who do the same work but are not paid the same”</i></p>
<p>Participant Seven-AAB</p>	<p><i>Diversity and Inclusion Supported by the Legislation</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Right for Decent Treatment without Bullying or Harassment of any kind.</i> • <i>Equal Treatment without Discrimination and Biases of any kind</i> • <i>Gender balance in the workplace (quotas)</i> • <i>Right for Equality</i> • <i>Harassment & Sexual Harassment Act</i> • <i>Discrimination Laws Act</i> • <i>Disability Protection Act</i> • <i>Equal Opportunities in Employment</i> <p><i>The Law does not protect any of the above!</i></p> <p><i>“Unofficially/off the records, discrimination is widespread in Sudan. There is significant racial discrimination in the workplace that may not be obvious...for example, in recruitment, the interview questions highlight discrimination based on gender, age, family background colour, and religion. There is no gender balance and when it comes to pregnancy and maternity rights for women there is discrimination. Certain ethnic minorities are treated as second-class citizens and are treated with contempt. Certain tribes/minorities are not recruited at all or are only given minor jobs in senior positions; basically, not providing equal employment opportunities to certain racial groups or tribes”.</i></p> <p><i>“Unfortunately, the Labour Act of 1997 says nothing about any of this; not one single article on the following: discrimination, inequality in recruitment (equal opportunities), the rights of disabled people, people with special needs and gender balance in the workplace (quotas)”</i></p>

Participant Eight-HEH	<i>“Personally, I have never faced any form of discrimination. The law did not include explicit articles addressing inequality and discrimination; however, they are implied in some articles. However, the law is written in such a way that it implies that all issues will be addressed fairly and equally. However, issues may arise during the practical implementation. Labour offices do not play their proper role of monitoring and inspecting organisations to ensure that none of this occurs”.</i>
Participant Nine-RFU	<i>“I didn’t see anything in the labour law that caters to inequality or anything of the sort”</i>
Sub-Theme/Code	Major Issues & Challenges: Gender Equality and Cultural Issues
	<i>“There are cultural issues that that act does not address things like opportunity, for example. The opportunities for women in senior jobs, and promotion, there is nothing specific to tackle these inequalities if any (gender inequalities)”</i>
	<i>“However, despite the gap in articles in this area and despite the fact of not being addressed, the Sudanese culture itself did not need to require much work in the area as by nature the culture has addressed about this issue very well throughout history. As Sudanese women proved themselves in the workplace, they broke barriers a very long time ago, and since the independence, they had equal chances for education they became judges, doctors, and ministers. If there was no pressing need then for the laws to focus on or tackle this area maybe by nature; nevertheless, I believe it does need to be addressed now to strengthen and enhance it”</i>
	<i>“Culturally women are well respected in the workplace they have dominated all sectors and excelled well. They are well educated and qualified for all jobs and were refined from a young age (from home) to compete well with men and so there was no need to explicitly mention it in the labour regulations as when the labour act was developed in the 1960 women were already parliament members! And had a strong impact and say in the community”)</i>
	<i>“Yet we still strongly believe that the document should be inclusive to reflect the culture and practices and should be documented (best practice is the practice that is customised with the cultural needs and requirements)”</i>
Participant Five-SEI	<i>“There are distinct practises endorsed by the Sudanese labour act that will surprise people in the West; they go far beyond for example: Mourning Leave for 4 months and 10 days; Maternity & Pregnancy Leave; and 1 hour off every working day after birth for 24-month (for child breastfeeding).In addition to the right to refuse overtime hours and the Right not to work at night”</i>
	<i>“Furthermore, and to its credit, Sudanese labour law does not discriminate against women based on religion; for example, Christian women do not have the 4 month and 10 days mourning period in their religion, but the Labour Act of 1997 grants her the same right fully paid as a better</i>

	<p><i>condition with all of its privileges without prejudice or discrimination of any kind”</i></p> <p><i>“Despite this, I am convinced that the Sudanese labour act advances human rights, particularly women’s rights, when compared to international practises. Pregnancy and maternity leaves, breast feeding time concessions (one hour off for two consecutive years); in addition to the mourning/grief period for a woman who has lost her husband, a fully paid 4 month and 10 days is a paid leave mandated by the Labour Act of 1997”</i></p> <p><i>“The law speaks to the culture, religion and society and this is credit for it. There are laws that address the needs of women that are advanced and should be credited and acknowledged because they are rarely this sophisticated in other societies. Furthermore, it provides women with flexibility and choice when it comes to overtime (it is gives women full autonomy and does not compel them by all means). Giving her the option to refuse working overtime is a credit to the law in and of itself”</i></p> <p><i>“However, change is inevitable, and people require vivid, transparent regulations to safely regulate workplace behaviours. Since these practises exist despite people’s upbringing and culture, we must not rely on what our culture dictates, but rather take all necessary steps and measures to prevent such behaviours in the workplace through clear clauses and genuine enforcement, with zero tolerance for all types of such behaviours</i></p>
<p>Participant Six-MAK</p>	<p><i>“Inadequate gender balance in opportunities”</i></p> <p><i>“There is no gender equality or balance; employers fail to accept women’s rights to special leave such as maternity leave, and other benefits and are hesitant to pay for women’s rights; as a result, they avoid recruiting women in the first place!”</i></p>
<p>Participant Seven-AAB</p>	<p><i>“Men are not given the same consideration during maternity and prenatal leaves as women”</i></p> <p><i>“Women face discrimination because of their maternity and pregnancy rights”</i></p>
<p>Sub-Theme/Code</p>	<p>Major Issues & Challenges: The Employment Contracts/Agreements</p>
	<p><i>“18 years on probation contracts!!!!!!This particular worker later took this company to court; initially the labour office/inspector officer did not consider his case as they look into the situation form a technical point of view and practically speaking nothing is wrong-the company did follow the labour act and did nothing wrong. But when the worker took his case to Labour Court the judge ruled in favour of the worker and considered him as a full-time worker for the 18 years this poor practice has been going on. And made the company compensate him for every year he spent with them doing this on and off service. The difference between the labour office and the labour court is that the labour court looks into issues from justice point of view which is much deeper than the mere technical application of the legislation. These companies abuse the law to secure greater</i></p>

<p>Participant Two-MZK</p>	<p><i>financial retunes and revenues with the least financial investments in the human capital and the tax/social insurance burdens that they must incur, the above practice actually led to the collapse of that particular corporation”</i></p> <p><i>“Unfortunately, the labour act of 1997 has obviously proved to fail the most vulnerable in our society. Let’s take for example the 3-month probation period which employers are abusing to recruit short term workers in projects like the electricity, sugar farming and seasonal works without being lawful to their rights. The probation act says that both parties (employer and employee) can terminate the contract without any legal obligations and these employers all around the country recruit those innocent workers for three month and terminate their contract claiming they have not fulfilled the job requirements and failed the probation period just a week or so before the end of the three month trial period and releases them of course without any notice period or compensation; and then replace them with new workers. Later after two weeks or so the same worker returns to the same employer knowing that he/she will be certainly returned to work with an new contract and a new probation period and once again terminated before the end of the 3 months period and so on and so forth. The same dilemma repeats it’s self with the same set of people over and over again for years sometimes (using a one year contract with the 3 probation period) and in one particular case I know for certain a specific company without mentioning names did this with one worker for 18 years!”</i></p>
<p>Participant Three-MOS</p>	<p><i>“Part time jobs are also not recognised by the law of 1997 the, the act simply says nothing on them! For example, I needed to hire a social insurance specialist to support me with preparing the social insurance registrations of new employees and handle the end of work claims, in fact I did appoint someone once a week on part-time bases. I was then surprised with a rejection form the labour office for the position saying there is no such thing as part-time employee and anyone who comes to work is considered a full time employee irrespective of the set-up, agreement or naming and is entitled to all the benefits of full time employee for salary, annual leave health insurance ..Etc. This is a huge burden on the organisation and has so my disadvantages, most of all it creates discrepancy and unfairness among employees to have part-time worker getting the same benefits equivalent to full-time workers (unfair practice); furthermore, it discourages organisations from offering par-time jobs and this fails a huge number of people who are looking for flexible work”</i></p> <p><i>“Outsource Services, the Sudanese labour law of 1997 does not accept the concept of outsourcing business/workers and does not support it by all measures, despite the fact that almost all businesses in Sudan nowadays seek to outsource a lot of services and like to focus on their capabilities on their core business and strategic issues. To be a bit cynical the law perceives the concept outsourcing as slavery or enslaving workers! You cannot have employees working for you and outsourced somewhere else (unless you provide a service) otherwise ...this will create a huge dilemma with the labour office and is one of the areas that has absolutely no practical solutions</i></p>

	<i>with the current legislation as it is missing”</i>
Participant Four-LME	<i>“It would be a shame if we did not have inclusive and actual representation (via the proper channels) in the workforce and ended up presenting something that had little impact and did not serve its purpose (relevant stakeholder engagement). If it is not reflecting people’s true needs, as we face rapid change (freelancing, entrepreneurship, part-timers, flexible work). Employees are now working three jobs at a time and all this change must be reflected in the way our laws and policies are written”</i>
Participant Five-SEI	<i>“Lack of contract flexibility is a very serious problem! There are only a few contract and employment options. In a way that does not serve the community’s or employers’ economic needs. It is inadequate in this regard, and I consider it a major flaw (the types of contracts and types of employment and the flexibility required). Life in Sudan has changed dramatically in recent years, as have employment requirements; however, the types of contracts supported by the labour act do not meet this critical need”</i>
	<i>“In Sudanese labour laws, there is no room for flexibility in comparison to other countries and best practices, making it difficult for employers to balance their requirements”</i>
	<i>“So, without hesitation, I know that the current law, in its current state, does not meet all our needs, and this was demonstrated even more after the Covid19 Pandemic, when we as HR practitioners realised that there are no laws to support flexible work, such as working from home, online work engagements, and even part-time work. As a result, I can simply state that the labour law of 1997 does not support Sudan’s current contemporary work environment”</i>
Participant Seven-AAB	<i>“Contract flexibility is needed! Contracts should be reviewed, and flexibility should be introduced and supported”</i>
Participant Eight-HEH	<i>“Many industries and manufacturing companies follow a horrible practice of three month hiring, firing (for one week or two), and rehiring (for another three month) and so on and so forth- and this continues for years – it is used to exploit the workers, confiscate, and exclude them from all deserved rights! This is what I call Modern Day Slavery”</i>
Participant Eight-HEH	<i>“The practical application of the 97 Act over the last 25 years has demonstrated that it is currently incapable of meeting the needs. That is evident from my personal experience with all the non-governmental organisations with which I am involved. The law simply cannot meet these organisations’ needs and expectations. Especially when it comes to employment relationships and the type of contracts that is required. The Act does not support the types of contracts they typically require based on the nature of the activities they run and use around the world. As a result, the struggle occurs. This has even impacted their budgets and their ability to provide financing to make the necessary compensations that they legally owe the workers in court (due to their lack of understanding and the gaps in the Act). Other large companies and organisations in the private sector are also dreadfully complaining about its incompatibility with their needs and the huge</i>

	<p><i>injustice in the Act, particularly in the relationship between the employee and employer relationship, which is treated as if it were a Catholic marriage that cannot be broken unless very complex arrangements are made”</i></p> <p><i>“From a contractual standpoint, the employer cannot find a way to create the type of relationship they desire. What I mean is that the 1997 act has created rigid and fixed standard moulds as a baseline for the relationship (contracts)...and the means mechanisms for ending this contractual relationship are insufficient, making the relationship very rigid”</i></p> <p><i>“Any contract more than 3 months should be written, and 3 copies issued (employee copy-employer copy and a copy for the labour office) and made through the labour office. Which is part of the legislation (Article 28) - unfortunately in practical sense these procedures are not practically implemented as they should in fact, they are missing from the actual day to day implementation. Missing role of the labour office-no copies sent; no regular reviews done to the contracts unless a dispute happens –a process that should have taken place at the very beginning of the relationship”</i></p>
Participant/ Sub Theme	Theme Three: A Strategic Direction & the Way Forward
	A Strategic Direction & the Way Forward: <i>Fundamental Principles and Rights at Work & Sudan & International Standards</i>
Participant Four-LME	<p><i>“The good news is that we have finally ratified the 1948 Convention on Freedom of Association and Protection of the Right to Organise (C087... (This should have happened at least 50 years ago!!!). And it takes precedence over everything else (one of the basic Human right principles). It went into effect about a year ago, and now the government can be held accountable if it violated the agreement, and sanctions can be imposed if it does... This was a fundamental requirement if we were to champion change and follow the revolution’s slogans of Freedom. The first thing we had to ensure was that these freedoms were secured for people, and that in order to create transformation and reform in the sector, we needed to give them capacity and empower the various bodies, unions, and institutions that represent the people and advocate for freedom of association... These bodies were very weak (over 30 years of dictatorship had destabilised them; it was critical to get them back on their feet and assist them in fighting for the interests and rights of the people... A new law has been drafted but has not yet been approved; this law will cover the right to collective bargaining and will be incorporated into labour law in the future”</i></p> <p><i>I have no idea... Perhaps, but I don’t know about it!</i></p> <p><i>“Furthermore, the labour offices do not report to the ministry, which distances it from what is going on there; it lacks the necessary links, measures, and statistics to refer to. Furthermore, there may be some corruption issues, which I cannot confirm but suspect. We recommended, in collaboration with the ILO, that the labour ministry be evaluated to determine if it is capable of</i></p>

	<p><i>carrying out its core functions and achieving the goals set for it”</i></p> <p><i>“Furthermore, the labour offices do not report to the ministry, which distances it from what is going on there; it lacks the necessary links, measures, and statistics to refer to. Furthermore, there may be some corruption issues, which I cannot confirm but suspect. We recommended, in collaboration with the ILO, that the labour ministry be evaluated to determine if it is capable of carrying out its core functions and achieving the goals set for it”</i></p>
Participant Six-MAK	<p><i>“By the way, all best practice international laws exist in Sudan (all these nice to have practices we read about); the problem is that these laws are not implemented; they are dormant! If I align all of the labour laws and employment regulations to comply with international laws and standards in a single package, the problem will be solved”.</i></p> <p><i>“This strategy was approved in 2017 (I saw it and occasionally read it because it contains some interesting data); the document was then placed in one of the drawers and that was the end of it. Nobody in the ministry knows anything about it!”</i></p> <p><i>“I read all the reports the reports we send to the UN, they are all lies nothing is true! The reports are simply full of lies; a couple of people from the Ministry of Foreign Affairs and the ministry of labour sit down, cook these reports, and send them. Because the organisations that are supposed to fill out their data and return it are not involved in the first place, all of the data is forged”.</i></p>
Participant Seven-AAB	<i>“I’ve never heard of it before!”</i>
Participant Eight-HEH	<p><i>“We are ILO and ALO members; why don’t we study these agreements’ standards and best practices?”</i></p> <p><i>Nowhere... I have no idea and have never heard of it.</i></p>
Participant Nine-RFU	<i>“No, fundamental principles and rights do not exist. To have them, you must first understand what they are, and they must be mentioned somewhere in the law. Nothing like that exists”.</i>
Sub-Theme/Code	A Strategic Direction & the Way Forward: Protecting Workers from Unacceptable Forms of Work
Participant Six-MAK	<i>“Unacceptable forms of work are all over the place. Mine workers die every day for no reason; they have no health checks or health protections of any kind. Garbage collectors have nothing to worry about because they are completely ignored. Every day, you hear about work - related</i>

	<i>accidents. Some industries have some protections, while others, such as the petroleum and gas industries, have limited protections. In general, no laws are specified in the Act to cover these points”</i>
Participant Seven-AAB	<i>“The problems that exist today are not addressed; imagine a large plant with 500 workers on one shift operating without a nurse or medical representative with first aid certification in the event of an emergency. Today, there are so many disputes in labour offices and courts about diseases and health issues because of ignorance in modern production techniques (a lot of modern equipment and machines have lazier and atomic radiation, that they are unaware of and cause huge health problems.) Other issues such as ultraviolet rays, prolonged computer use, screen sitting, and other ergonomics are not taken into account (not considered in the laws as workplace injuries and protections required). The same is true for the list in the 1997 act - dust and other historic issues. In almost all cases, poor workers lose their right to protection” (Participant Seven-AAB)</i>
Participant Eight-HEH	<i>“There is nothing specific on UFW. The government has never mentioned anything on the subject. The law governs the work relationship and speaks vaguely about safety issues, and the only solution it leaves the worker/employee with is the right to terminate the contract, which may be in some occasions a relief to the employer or something he/she welcomes” (Participant Eight-HEH)</i>
Sub-Theme/Code	A Strategic Direction & the Way Forward: A Decent Work Strategy
Participant One-E.O.S	<i>“Defiantly drifted away, and the evidence for that is everything we’ve just discussed!” (Participant One-EOS)</i>
	<i>“I believe there is an update, but communication is, as usual, lacking” (Participant Four-LME)</i>
Participant Four-LME	<i>“It was essential for the transitional government to revisit all laws in order to achieve social justice and secure a life of dignity in Sudan if it was to bring about change and a revolution” (Participant Four-LME)</i>
	<i>“We have started a good and active partnership with the ILO, and there is a good opportunity, if taken seriously in the next stage (after a bit of political stability), to make a difference in the issue of decent work... Most importantly, an effort must be made to focus on communication and awareness across the board in order to inform the people and create a common understanding of the concept of decent work, as well as to roll out information campaigns to raise awareness among Sudanese people” (Participant Four-LME)</i>
	<i>“The ILO has reviewed the decent work program strategy because it is outdated for Sudan and has not been updated in a long time. We reviewed the decent work strategy and policy, as change is occurring at a rapid pace in Sudan, and both should be aligned with these changes. We pushed for it and for its review, and we did review it with the ILO (we did some good work in revisiting it).</i>

	<i>You could say it is there theoretically, but to be honest, we are not ready from a practical standpoint...We are a long way from it. There are so many interconnected components that are supposed to be in place (groundwork) for decent work policies to take effect that other ministries should be involved (the committee involves a large number of people from various disciplines, not just the ministry of labour) and a lot of other groundwork should have been in place (Participant Four-LME)”</i>
Participant Seven-AAB	<i>“Frankly speaking, I would consider Sudan as one of the most prominent examples of a country in the world that implements 100% “Indecent work” (Participant Seven-AAB)</i>
Sub-Theme/Code	A Strategic Direction & the Way Forward: Understanding & Measuring Decent Work
Participant One-E.O.S	<i>“No defiantly not, they don’t know; most people in Sudan are unaware of their rights! Not that I’m aware of; I haven’t seen anything while working, and I don’t believe there is! There is nothing visible, and I doubt it is even on their agenda! Even if there was something, I haven’t seen anything tangible in all my working years.</i>
Participant Two-MZK	<i>“I have no idea...I have never heard of anything in this regard”</i>
Participant Three-MOS	<i>“No, in all my years of service, I have seen nothing!”</i>
	<i>“No, I do not think so”</i>
Participant Four-LME	<i>“No... A lot of education is needed because people do not understand what decent work entails and what they are entitled to, basic things such as having enough toilets in the workplace. Lack of resources (the ministry operates on a 20% overhead budget, which is essentially an unrealistic budget”</i>
	<i>“There are no measurements”</i>
Participant Five-SEI	<i>“The definition of decency is subjective... Most people in Sudan are struggling to meet their basic needs and are unable to think about anything else (Maslow’s Hierarchy of Needs). People in Sudan are overwhelmed by the troubles of day-to-day challenges of feeding their families and survival... no more, so they are unable to think beyond these struggles; whereas other nations have actually moved away from the day-to-day challenges of basic labour regulations and have been focusing on things like work-life balance, equality, diversity, and inclusion”</i>
	<i>“The definition of decency is subjective... Most people in Sudan are struggling to meet their basic needs and are unable to think about anything else (Maslow’s Hierarchy of Needs). People in Sudan are overwhelmed by the troubles of day-to-day challenges of feeding their families and survival... no more, so they are unable to think beyond these struggles; whereas other nations have actually</i>

	<i>moved away from the day-to-day challenges of basic labour regulations and have been focusing on things like work-life balance, equality, diversity, and inclusion”</i>
	<i>“No, it is not even on its agenda, as far as I know”</i>
Participant Six-MAK	<i>“No, they have no idea!”</i>
	<i>“Of course not! They are not measuring any type of work, let alone decent work!”</i>
Participant Seven-AAB	<i>“Unfortunately, the concept of decent work does not exist in the first place”</i>
	<i>“Unfortunately, the concept of decent work does not exist to start with”</i>
	<i>“Of course, not”</i>
Participant Eight-HEH	<i>“No not at all”</i>
	<i>“No The Sudanese government is not measuring anything, and the biggest proof that it is not measuring decent work is that the minimum wage is far away for decency by all measures - there are no measures...or measures are completely missing”</i>
	<i>“The concept of decent work is completely absent”</i>
Participant Nine-RFU	<i>“Definitely not”</i>
	<i>“No, they don’t; they don’t know how to measure it”</i>
Sub-Theme/Code	A Strategic Direction & the Way Forward: What effort is needed to establish decent work in Sudan?
Participant One-E.O.S	<i>“There must be a shift in culture, particularly in workplace culture, across all industries. To be honest, I don’t think many people understand what decent work is and what it stands for; even HR practitioners who need to apply these themselves, I’m sure very few understand what it means and what it stands for. To strengthen this area, the government (at the ministry level) must lead by example and raise awareness. The unfortunate thing is that there is no contact from the ministry of at all. No one sends anything; no one shares any updates to let you know about any changes, such as the minimum wage or any important updates, in all the years I’ve worked! I had to go there myself to see if there was anything new”</i>
	<i>“Another requirement for decent work is the minimum wage, which was established by a tripartite committee”.</i>
Participant Five-SEI	<i>“Sudan’s financial situation is severely damaged, and you can see that the basic necessities we discussed are not available even in service areas such as hospitals, schools, and transportation, let alone in other organisations, simply because the law does not enforce these issues and the economic situation does not permit it; thus, they become more like luxuries rather than necessities! So asking someone at work to provide such a thing seems more like a dream!”</i>

	<i>"Decency at work is part of the decency of the whole country and cannot be separated".</i>
Participant Six-MAK	<i>"I really don't know...To be honest, I don't have an answer to this question!"</i>
	<i>"You are referring to something that doesn't exist in Sudan... It's not even on the table! These are international standards that Sudan does not have. If you mention "decent work", you must put it in brackets and define it first. The problem is the level of understanding; most of those responsible for this do not even understand it. Before we do anything, we should first educate the people and raise awareness and understanding of the concept"</i>
Participant Seven-AAB	<i>".., there is a huge level of unawareness and ignorance on the part of workers about their rights and what they should receive from their employers in terms of their work relationship, whether it is decent or indecent work. The issue is the government's failure to provide adequate support in order to raise awareness and understanding of the laws and their interpretations (worker training and development). The employer can abuse and exploit the workers without the workers being aware of it. To raise awareness, the ministry does not provide any brochures, leaflets, sessions, or posters. I believe they used to do that before 1997 (مؤسسة الثقافة العمالية), but nothing has happened since then! Unfortunately, the labour ministry's website contains nothing useful to working people"</i>
	<i>"To establish decent work, we need.... Modernisation of labour laws so that they can deal with the needs of workers and the protection they deserve, not just the needs of employers"</i>
Participant Eight-HEH	<i>"Activation of trade unions' roles in organisations to represent workers, reflect on their problems, and protect their rights in collective bargaining; and empowering and strengthening the Labour Offices by giving them the tools, recourses and authority they need"</i>
Sub-Theme/Code	A Strategic Direction & the Way Forward: Communication
Participant Four-LME	<i>"Most importantly, an effort must be made to focus on communication and awareness across the board in order to inform the people and create a common understanding... and to launch information campaigns to raise awareness among Sudanese people"</i>
	<i>"This is important to ensure that when we do make updates, they reflect what people really need; it would be a shame if we didn't have inclusive and actual representation (right channels) in the workforce and ended up presenting something with very little impact and will not serve as it should (relevant stakeholder engagement). Is it reflecting people's true needs, as we face rapid change (freelancing, entrepreneurship, part-timers, flexible work...? Employees now work three jobs at once), and all of this change must be reflected in the way our laws and policies are written")</i>
	<i>"To improve or develop where we stand in these areas, we need to broaden our scope of</i>

	<i>engagement and involve more people in the dialogue. We need to determine who the stakeholders are and whether we are engaging the right people/stakeholders, whether everyone who needs to participate is involved, whether we have the right people on board, and whether we are listening to the right people”.</i>
Participant Six-MAK	<i>“The discussions are devoid of transparency and communication. There has been very little effort, and there has been no social dialogue”</i>
Participant Eight-HEH	<i>“We are the legal experts who should be consulted; we are never asked nor involved is (our input is missing). And we just wake up to decisions and are constantly surprised. There are no workshops and no training at all”.</i>
	<i>“We must create a dialogue among and between all intended stakeholders. Involve the Experts and broaden your social circle”</i>
	<i>“There is a lack of information (no communication at all you have to struggle to find it and it is not trusted.”</i>
Sub-Theme/Code	A Strategic Direction & the Way Forward: Occupational Safety and Health
Participant One-E.O.S	<i>“Exposure to poisons and hazardous materials is mentioned, but in very outdated terms and guidelines that do not deal with or cover everything that is happening today (applicable to materials and techniques used and followed more than 25 years ago). For example, modern health and safety issues such as computer screen protectors, ergonomic seating and furniture, and the way employees should sit to protect their spine are not included in the safety measures”.</i>
Participant Three-MOS	<i>“Health and safety issues should be addressed in all work environments, not just manufacturing (as they are now), with clear measures and regular monitoring”</i>
Participant Four-LME	<i>“Health and safety issues are often outsourced”</i>
	<i>“HSE is very crucial; a recent example is the disaster fire that took place in the ceramic manufacturing plant. Workplace accidents: you are not cared for- there no social security; and compensation is extremely low, unimaginably low! A worker can lose a limb with no repercussions, penalties are pitiful (not updated for years), and this reflects poorly. In general, social protection and insurance require massive work”</i>
Participant Five-SEI	<i>“Health and safety are not given enough consideration”</i>
	<i>“The Act does not refer to “outsourcing workers” or how the process lasts. Many workers have unresolved claims of work incidents hanging in courts for years and some have even died before</i>

<p>Participant Six-MAK</p>	<p><i>they reached any resolution”</i></p> <p><i>“Every day, we hear about workplace accidents. Some industries have some protections, while others, such as the petroleum and gas industries, have limited protections”</i></p> <p><i>“The Act mentions hazardous jobs, but nothing is done about it; it simply exists without any value or effectiveness for workers who work in dangerous and hazardous work environments. All standard associated practises, such as special working conditions, projections, years of service, and pension schemes, are absent”</i></p>
<p>Participant Seven-AAB</p>	<p><i>“Sudan has a very poor HSE system. Basic amenities such as rest rooms, ladies’ privacy rooms, and toilets are missing. There are also no industrial health and safety environments (best practice standards)”</i></p> <p><i>“Another issue is workplace injuries; the stand-alone regulatory body relies on a tabulated chart with the same list of work place injuries and occupational hazards developed in 1981 and never updated since -with a list of injuries based on some outdated methods and techniques (these are the charts endorsed by the courts and their only point of reference), a list of injuries that are no longer applicable (do not comply with modern industrial requirements). And environmental issues that have no place in the Act- there are specific offices in charge of Industrial Safety, but in reality they are not in charge of providing any protection!”</i></p>
<p>Participant Nine-RFU</p>	<p><i>“It all comes down to finances; if everyone is required to have personal protective equipment and health and safety measures, it costs a lot of money, and because a private enterprise and is run by a private business, they want to make money at the end of the day, so they don’t want to spend money that isn’t necessary, even if the law requires it, and because there is no accountability, they don’t”</i></p> <p><i>“Employee health and safety is critical in order for people not to be injured, hurt, or negatively impacted by any aspect of their jobs. When employers fail to provide workers with personal protective equipment or guards for welding or grinding, they are exploited and exposed. It all comes down to education and the enforcement of laws; without someone to enforce the laws, nothing will happen”</i></p>

Appendix 7- A Critical Literature Review

NO	Author's Name & Year	Study Title	Purpose of the Study	Research Type: Empirical/ Conceptual	Theoretical Foundation /Model/ Practices Policies	Concept/ Dimensions/ Variables	Research Questions/ Objectives /Hypothesis	Research Design/ Methodology	Key Findings	Research Contribution /Implication	Observations /Limitations
1	Diego F. Angel-Urdinola and Arvo Kuddo 2011	Key Characteristics of Employment Regulation in the Middle East & North Africa (MENA)	To understand employability constraints in MENA- a response to regional priorities in the context of the Arab World Initiative (AWI). Focusing explicitly on employment creation as a top priority	Conceptual	-Industrial Revolution -Trade Unions -Industrial Regulations theory -Human Rights Theory -Labour Regulation	This study compiles information on available labour laws and other legal acts concerning employment protection regulation.	The objective is to provide policymakers and international organizations with a regional analysis of how labour regulation affects labour market outcomes in the region and to inform governments on strategic approaches to employment creation through labour policy and associated reforms	Providing a general background of the main features of Labour Regulation in the Middle East and North Africa (MENA) and benchmarking them against international best practices (regional comparability)	-Labour market indicators in the Middle East and North Africa (MENA) region are lagging by international benchmarks. -Labour regulation, among other factors, introduces restrictions to employability in MENA. -Employment laws are often ineffective because of evasion, weak enforcement, and failure to reach the informal sector.	Strategic approaches to employment creation through labour policy and reform	Activity comes as a response to regional priorities in the context of the Arab World Initiative (AWI). One of the six strategic themes of the AWI
2	Djankov, Simeon, and Rita Ramalho	Employment laws in developing	To study/understand the effect	Conceptual	-	Three major studies providing evidence on	The objective is to review the recent literature on	A survey of the literature using papers	Developing countries with rigid labour	Contribute to the broader "new	Some studies also find that rigid labour

	2009	g countries	of employment laws in developing countries			the effects of rigid employment laws: *Besley and Burgess (2004) - India *Heckman and Pagés (2004) - Latin America *Botero et al. (2004) - 85 countries around the world	employment laws in the developing countries:	published since 2004 on employment laws in developing countries. The survey is hence supported by cross-country correlation analyses	regulation tend to have larger informal sectors and higher unemployment, especially among young workers.	comparative economic s” literature on why governments regulate markets differently. As labour regulation is relatively new in most countries, some of the existing theories – for example, of the imposition of inappropriate regulation by colonizers – are easily discarded. This allows for a cleaner research design.	regulation results in an increase in urban poverty, fewer business start-ups, foregone benefits from other (particularly trade and licensing) reforms, and in female unemployment. These results need further empirical support, using data for more countries and in the context of reform episodes. Prior to 2004, virtually no studies existed in this area
3	Tzehaines h Tekle` (ed.) 2010	Labour Law and Worker Protection in	An academic discussion to understand	Book-Conceptual	The book follows a historical and contextual	- This study reflects on labour law’s ability, in its current form,	Hypothesis throughout the book is that despite the huge	Originates from research carried out by the	The mismatch between norms and reality can only be	The book opens the door to new questions	There is no chapter on ‘informal work’ and ‘the

		Developing Countries	did if globalization leads to a 'race to the bottom' with respect to employment and working conditions and standards, or to a 'race to the top', or to something in between		zed approach to labour law	to protect workers' rights and secure decent working conditions in the developing world. It identifies and examines structural weaknesses and challenges brought about by globalization and, against this background, explores regulatory and policy responses which have been made at different governance levels to enhance the scope and application of labour regulation, focusing particularly on Latin America, South Asia and southern Africa	diversity in the level of economic development in the regions considered, they all share a structural mismatch between the basic categories of labour law and the socio-economic trends of developing countries	editor at the ILO's (International Institute for Labour Studies). Two theoretical chapters on effectiveness of labour law and on trade liberalization, labour law and development in developing countries; and three regional case studies – Latin America, southern Africa and South Asia	overcome by looking beyond 'standard' employment relationships for protection of workers. Decent work can only effectively be guaranteed worldwide by 'developing jobs as part of a fair globalization' and by decentralized democratic participation in social norm-building in developing countries. The growing diversity has to be encouraged and empowered by a 'mobilization of local knowledge'	on the history, function and perspectives of labour law. It focuses on globalization processes in a concrete and precise manner, taking the point of view of developing countries. This makes it worthwhile and mandatory reading	informal sector' providing clear categories as a base for the empirical case studies and the book would have been better if an integrated approach had been taken
4	Sangheon Lee and Deirdre McCann	Regulating for decent work:	Regulating for decent work	Conceptual	Orthodox economic theory and the ILO's	The book studies the regulatory frameworks	Enriching the academic and policy debates on	The book studies the regulatory frameworks	Central contentions of orthodox economic	The challenge for legal policy is	It identifies a set of contemporary

	(ed.) (2011)	New directions in labour market regulation		Decent Work Agenda	of countries as diverse as Brazil, China, France, Indonesia, Tanzania and the United States, showcasing research from a variety of disciplines including economics, law, industrial relations, sociology and political science highlights certain of the more significant and novel developments in contemporary labour market research	post-recession labour regulation	of countries as diverse as Brazil, China, France, Indonesia, Tanzania and the United States, showcasing research from a variety of disciplines including economics, law, industrial relations, sociology and political science highlights certain of the more significant and novel developments in contemporary labour market research	theory on the impact of labour market regulations have been exaggerated There is an urgent need to find more balanced approaches to labour market regulation. Policy actors must recognize the potential benefits of regulation, and reflect them in the design and evaluation of labour market policies. A proper understanding and assessment of the effects of labour regulations needs robust data A widespread disjuncture between labour force participation patterns and regulatory frameworks is helping to generate	to strike the right balance between growth, employment and worker protection. The experience of a number of countries confirms the important role of government policies in allowing workers to share in the gains of economic growth	challenges for labour market regulation: The role of empirical research in assessing and supporting labour market interventions Historical limitations in the coverage of regulatory frameworks and recent initiatives to extend their reach and the decline of traditional institutional mechanisms and the search for effective regulatory techniques to replace them.
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									<p>precarious forms of employment</p> <p>Traditional institutional mechanisms are in decline</p> <p>The effectiveness of regulatory frameworks is one of the key subjects of contemporary labour market regulation research</p> <p>Dominant analyses of labour markets do not appreciate the complexity of regulatory frameworks.</p>		
5	Jens Lerche School of Oriental and African Studies (2012)	Labour Regulations and Labour Standards in India: Decent Work?	To assess the ILO's decent work agenda in the Global South	Conceptual	United Nations' (UN) International Labour Organization International Labour Rights	Informal Employment The working poor Vulnerable Employment	The ILO had entered into specific bilateral 'decent work' agreements with 61 countries by 2011. The objective of this study is to see how this approach works out in	The article assesses the ILO decent work agenda in the Global South: its objectives and coherence, its impact on labour relations and	In practice the decent work agenda has had little impact on the conditions of informal labour and even its focus on child labour and forced labour is yet to show major results	Important lessons for both the ILO decent work agenda and for Indian labour relations	The lesson for the decent work agenda is that it needs to treat work conditions, employment rights and social policy-related rights as

							<p>relation to developing countries?</p> <p>Case Study: India.</p> <p>To what extent has the Indian version of the decent work agenda and the ILO–India collaboration influenced regulatory frameworks and labour relations?</p> <p>Who are the main social actors and what are the power relations delimiting their influence? What is the impact of the ILO on this?</p>	<p>conditions, and its overall policy direction in relation to alternative labour rights and welfare policy thinking.</p> <p>This is followed by a case study of the Indian version of the decent work agenda and the extent to which the ILO–India collaboration has influenced regulatory frameworks and labour relations.</p>	<p>The development of crosscutting platforms and outright political mobilization is not part of the ILO decent work agenda and therefore leaves this agenda without sustained transformative power.</p> <p>In India, conditions of work and pay are not improving for in formalized labour. Labour finds itself in a very weak bargaining position, while government and employers push for further in formalization. Social floor policies do exist, but so far their impact on informal</p>	<p>interlinked so as to deal with the underlying social and economic inequalities. The absence of policies that can catalyse wider alliances on the ground is a threat to the possibility for political mobilization. The lack of efforts and initiatives seeking to deal with employment-related inequalities and to promote universal welfare programs may well stall the progress of the agenda.</p>
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									workers is patchy. Moreover, they are targeted as opposed to universal programs. There are also no policies aiming at dealing with economic labour market-based inequalities.		
6	Timothy Besley And Robin Burgess	Can Labour Regulation Hinder Economic Performance? Evidence From India	To illuminate the long-standing debates about the role of the state in promoting or hindering economic development	Conceptual	Relative price effect and expropriation effect	-A wide variety of sources covering the sixteen main Indian states -And separate observations for Punjab and Haryana	To investigate whether the industrial relations climate in Indian states has affected the pattern of manufacturing growth in the period 1958–1992	Econometric analysis is based on panel data regressions	-States which amended the Industrial Disputes Act in a pro-worker direction experienced lowered output, employment, investment, and productivity in registered or formal manufacturing. - In contrast, output in unregistered or informal manufacturing increased. -Regulating in a pro-worker direction was also	The study reinforces the growing sentiment that government regulations in developing countries have not always promoted social welfare	Attempts to redress the balance of power between capital and labour can end up hurting the poor

									associated with increases in urban poverty		
7	Heckman, J. and Pagés, C. 2003	Law and Employment: Lessons from Latin American and the Caribbean	To investigate the impact of regulations on labour markets in a wide range of diverse Latin American and Caribbean countries	Empirical	Labour Reforms	Employment /Population Unemployment rate Log GDP Per capita PPP adjusted. GDP growth Share of working age pop. 25-54 Share of working age pop.55-64 Social Security (% wage) Advance notice Indemnities for dismissal Seniority pay Social Security	To summarize the main lessons to be drawn from the studies assembled. To place the Latin American and Caribbean (LAC) regulatory burden in an international context by comparing the level and changes in LAC labour regulation policies with those in OECD countries, as well as providing some historical context about the origins of this regulation And to update the work of Heckman and Pagés (2000) with an expanded	Analysis of pooled time series cross sections of countries under study examining the impact of regulations in Latin America and OECD countries Sensitivity of estimates of the impact of regulation obtained from conventional pooled time series cross sections of countries to alternative choices of samples and models.	Mandated benefits and job security regulations have a substantial allocative impact both in Latin America and in OECD countries. Results suggest that not all regulations have the same effect on employment rates. While social security contributions are negatively associated with employment (and positively associated with unemployment); the effect of job security measures on employment is ambiguous. While in the joint and LAC	The shifts in the policy regimes experienced in the region are dramatic by the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) standards, and many of these regime shifts are exogenous. This large and exogenous variation provides identifying power not available to analysts studying regulation in Europe and North	More precise quantitative estimates would be desirable

							sample and better measures of regulation, providing a cross-country time-series analysis of the impact of regulation on employment and unemployment		samples, advance notice and indemnities for dismissal have positive, although not statistically significant coefficients, the coefficient on indemnities in the OECD sample is negative and statistically significant at conventional levels. Seniority pay is positively associated with employment, and the coefficients on this variable are statistically significant in most specifications.	America	
8	Juan C. Botero, Simeon Djankov, Rafael La Porta, Florencio Lopez-de-Silanes, Andrei Shleifer,	The Regulation Of Labour	To investigate the regulation of labour markets through employment, collective	Conceptual	The Efficiency Theory The Political Power Theory The Legal Theory	Potential consequences of labour regulation: The size of and the employment in the unofficial economy	Efficiency theories predict that heavier regulation of labour markets should be associated with better, and certainly	The study examines the regulation of labour markets in 85 countries through the lens of three broad theories of	Heavier regulation of labour is associated with lower labour force participation and higher unemployment, especially of the young.	The political power of the left is associated with more stringent labour regulations and	This research was supported by the World Bank, the Gildor Foundation, the National Science Foundation,

	2004		relations, and social security laws in 85 countries		<p>Employment Law</p> <p>Collective Relations law</p> <p>Social Security Law</p>	<p>Male and female participation in the labour force</p> <p>Unemployment computed separately for everyone, and for male and female workers aged 20–24</p> <p>The average wage of machine operators relative to that of clerks and workers in craft and related trades</p>	<p>not worse, labour market outcomes. This prediction has been contradicted by a variety of empirical studies from Lazear [1990] to Besley and Burgess [2003]; and this study is to confirm their findings.</p> <p>If the regulation of labour is damaging at least to some workers, then who benefits from it?</p> <p>Is there political support for the heavier regulation of labour, or does legal origin simply provide a politically unsupported “technology” for the social control of labour markets?</p>	<p>government regulations; Efficiency Theories, Political Theories and Legal Theories.</p>	<p>There is some support for the view that countries with a longer history of leftist governments have more extensive regulation of labour, consistent with the political theory.</p> <p>There is strong evidence that the origin of a country’s laws is an important determinant of its regulatory approach, in labour as well as in other markets.</p> <p>Legal origin does not appear to be a proxy for social democracy—its explanatory power is both independent and significantly larger.</p>	<p>more generous social security systems, and that socialist, French, and Scandinavian legal origin countries have sharply higher levels of labour regulation than do common law countries</p>	<p>and the International Institute for Corporate Governance at Yale University</p>
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									This evidence is broadly consistent with the legal theory, according to which patterns of regulation across countries are shaped largely by transplanted legal structures.		
9	Arvo Kuddo 2009	Labour Laws in Eastern European and Central Asian Countries : Minimum Norms and Practices	To focus on internationally accepted labour standards and norms governing the individual employment contracts	Conceptual	Employment Law	The study analyzes relevant provisions in the main labour law of each ECA country: labour code, law or act, law on labour relations, employment contracts act, or law on employment relationships associated with commencing or terminating employment and during the period of employment. It will also analyze the design	This study focuses on internationally accepted labour standards and norms governing the individual employment contract, including ILO conventions and recommendations, EU labour standards (Directives) and the European Community Social Charter (Charter of Fundamental Social Rights of Workers)	The study is based on a comparative analysis of the main indicators/parameters of the individual contract particular to the labour law of each country. It is intended as a sourcebook for practitioners from the ECA region who are working on reforming the labour legislation in their respective countries. It looks into	Despite common roots, each of the ECA countries has its own history of labour law development, with differing labour market conditions and contrasting legal and social security systems. Over the last decade, a second generation of reforms in labour legislation has been carried out in many ECA countries. The minimum content of	Reform of national employment protection legislation in the region in the last two decades has focused on easing existing regulation to facilitate more contractual diversity.	These countries may consider shifting the focus of employment protection from protecting jobs to protecting workers in case of unemployment. In order to make labour legislation more business friendly, the countries may consider adopting a lifecycle approach to work, which

						features of some key issues attached to the individual employment contract. (The list of labour laws from 27 ECA transition countries is presented)	also analyzes relevant provisions in the main labour law of each Eastern European and Central Asian (ECA) country associated with commencing or terminating employment and during the period of employment.	suggested labour norms, regulations and entitlements through the prism of ILO-relevant conventions and recommendations, EU labour standards (Directives) and the European Community Social Charter (Charter of Fundamental Rights of Workers). References are made to practices from EU15 countries.	labour regulations governing the employment contract in most ECA countries coincides, and goes beyond, the requirements of the ILO Conventions, the European Social Charter, or EU Directives even in the countries which are non-signatories of relevant treaties. In most ECA countries, collective bargaining is not very widespread and collective agreements are relatively weak. In many ECA countries, the labour law remains in some important ways too prescriptive for today's realities.		may require shifting from the concern to protect particular jobs to a framework of support for employment security, including social support and active measures to assist workers during periods of transition.
10	Seth D. Harris and Alan	A Proposal for	This proposal would	Conceptual	Social Security Laws and	By extending many of the legal benefits	New and emerging work	The project was designed in	This paper proposes a new legal	Reforms along the lines that	The online gig economy represents a

B. Krueger 2015	Modernizing Labour Laws for Twenty-First-Century Work: The “Independent Worker	address the uncertainty that workers and businesses face in the current legal environment regarding a range of legal protections and benefits that employees receive.		Labour Reforms	and protections found in employment relationships to independent workers, the proposal would protect and extend the social compact between workers and employers, and reduce the legal uncertainty and legal costs that currently beset many independent worker relationships.	relationships arising in the “online gig economy” do not fit easily into the existing legal definitions of “employee” and “independent contractor” status.	part to provide a forum for leading thinkers across the nation to put forward innovative and potentially important economic policy ideas that share the Project’s broad goals of promoting economic growth, broad-based participation in growth, and economic security	category, which the authors call “independent workers,” for those who occupy the gray area between employees and independent contractors.	are proposed would help to protect and extend the hard-earned social compact that has protected workers and improved living standards over the past century, reduce uncertainty, and enhance the efficient operation of the labour market.	Independent workers typically work with intermediaries who match workers to customers. The independent worker and the intermediary have some elements of the arms-length independent business relationships that characterize “independent contractor” status, and some elements of a traditional employee-employer relationship.	small but rapidly growing segment of the workforce, especially in the ride-sharing and food-delivery sectors.
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								options into the national debate			
1 1	Meera Rajah 2019	From Third World to First: A Case Study of Labour Laws in a Changing Singapore	The purpose of this study is to examine the shift in the policy underpinnings of labour law in Singapore	Conceptual		<p>Reviewing the trajectory of labour law in Singapore in four discrete movements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -A collective laissez-faire approach in 1945 to the 1950s -Followed by a sharp turn towards efficiency and flexibility in the Singapore labour market over job security (in favour of the employer) from the 1960s to the 1980s -The introduction of the 'tripartite partnership' model, significantly, the influx of foreign workers in the 1970s, -Since then there appear to have been genuine 	<p>The objective of this article is to examine the shift in the policy underpinning of labour law in Singapore, and how the Singapore legislature appears to have recalibrated the emphasis placed on the competing goals of labour law, to now develop local policies more tilted towards social justice</p>	<p>A case study examining the shift in the theoretical underpinnings of labour law in Singapore over recent years</p>	<p>It is clear that the 21st century has witnessed progressive change, and the legislature and the executive appear to have taken the conceptual foundations of labour law under advisement in re-orienting their approaches towards recognizing and promoting social justice. In contrast to the rather bare, basal policies and regulation enacted during the 'collective laissez-faire' and the early beginnings of the 'tripartite partnership' model between the 1940s to the 1960s, an increasing</p>	<p>It is hoped that this case study will be able to contribute further to the existing debate on the 'purpose' of labour law, in considering how labour law, historically, has been shaped in different jurisdictions. Labour policy in Singapore now appears to have altered its track towards a more social justice-orientated direction, undoubtedly a step</p>	<p>In formulating and applying labour law legislation and policies, the Singapore legislature and government should adopt a Dworkinian, purposive approach by reconciling social protection with economic efficiency, to honour labour law's normative justifications.</p>

						institutional efforts to enhance 'worker protection', most marked in the 21st century. In late 2018, the new Employment (Amendment) Bill 2018 was introduced into Singapore Parliament			amount of 'protective' regulation and rights-oriented discourse has developed in the 21st century. The 2018 amendments that have been proposed to the Employment Act, the establishment of the new ECT and the recent initiatives by the NTUC and the TAFEP against workplace discrimination are some contemporary measures that appear to appreciate the vulnerabilities peculiar to workers who fall outside the traditional employment model, such as contract workers and migrant workers	in the right direction, on a long road ahead.	
1	Ahmad	Are All	The	Concep	Labour	Multiplicity	This paper	The	Labour	While	India must
2	Ahsan	Labour	purpose	tual	Reforms	of data	examines	research	regulations	further	find

and Carmen Pagés 2007	Regulations Equal? Assessing the effects of job security, labour dispute and contract labour laws in India	of this paper is to study the economic effects of legal amendments on different types of labour laws			<p>sources at the state</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Output measures *Person-days lost in industrial disputes *State fiscal Deficit *Population *Development Expenditures *Net Value Added *Productive capital *No of persons employed *Workers *Wages to Workers *Number of factories Registered 	<p>which types of labour laws matter the most for economic outcomes.</p> <p>It also assesses whether de facto deregulation dampened the effect of labour laws.</p> <p>This study follows Besley and Burgess (2004) and identifies the effects of labour reforms on economic outcomes by focusing on reforms at the state level. Since most policies and legislation other than labour laws are set at the national level, this approach allows identifying labour reforms from other contemporaneous policy</p>	<p>follows, with important modification, Besley and Burgess (2004) in exploiting the time variation in state amendments to central labour laws to identify the effect of such changes on economic outcomes. Identifying amendments to two types of laws: (a) laws that regulate the procedures for the resolution of industrial disputes and (b) laws that affect hiring and firing and in consequence, firms' employment adjustment capacity. The study also uses time variation in</p>	<p>are generally introduced to improve the lot of workers. However, these results suggest that in India they are not achieving this goal</p> <p>Not only have regulations created large costs for society, but they have not raised workers' labour share. Instead, workers have been left with an equal share of a much smaller cake.</p> <p>There are important costs associated with regulations that increase the cost of settling industrial disputes. The findings suggest that their costs for society and for registered sector</p>	<p>liberalization of the use of contract labour is likely to create some additional jobs and increase output and investment, it is unlikely to bring back the jobs lost due to inappropriate labour regulations.</p>	<p>alternative way to improve labour conditions for the majority of workers. While traditionally portrayed as labour advances against the abuses of capital, current labour regulations favour no one.</p>
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							and legal changes.	the use of contract labour to capture the effect of de facto labour reforms.	workers may be higher than those associated with job security laws. By reducing investment, employment and wages, they generate pure costs for workers and for the society as a whole. Labour intensive sectors such as textiles are the hardest hit eroding the comparative advantage of India in labour intensive industries, and in the process removing viable job opportunities for a large number of people. The widespread use of contract labour does not seem alleviate the adverse		
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									effects of labour regulations, particularly in regards to employment		
13	Sarah Berens & Achim Kemmerling 2019	Labour Divides, Informality, and Regulation: The Public Opinion on Labour Law in Latin America	The purpose of this study is to look at public opinion on labour laws in Latin America to find out who are potential beneficiaries or losers.	Conceptual	Labour Law policies	Using data on public attitudes towards labour law for 18 Latin American countries Variables: Labour Law Scepticism Employment Status Labour Law	While scholarship on the politics of labour market divides and labour law in Latin America has bloomed in recent years, this literature rarely looks at the role of public opinion, a gap that needs to be filled and this is the objective of this study. What does the public think about these laws, who really benefits or loses, and who supports or vetoes reforms of labour markets in Latin America?	Following the literature on labour market divides to see how far those at the margins of the formal labour market differ in their opinions from the formally employed A focus on public attitudes towards job laws and whether or not people perceive them as protection for workers surveying the literature on labour regulation in Latin America (Labour Market Divides, Informality,	The results of the empirical analysis have revealed three aspects of the politics of labour regulation. First, there are clear cross-country differences in the general perception of labour laws. Second, there are clear differences between employment groups, with the unemployed and those working in the informal sector seeing employment laws differently from the rest of the labour force. Third, there is some indication that the two levels interact with each other in the form of feedback	On the micro level, it is found that individuals at the fringe of the formal labour market (unemployed and informal workers) think laws are less protective. On the macro level, it is shown that feedback effects play a role: labour law shapes the divide in public opinion, since the divide increases in countries with better	Data on perceived vulnerability were stopped in 2005 and do not cover the recent downturn in Latin American labour markets. The operationalisation of labour market divides is naturally limited due to data restrictions. Moreover, some critics may be concerned about the “subjective” nature of the dependent variable. The study of political consequences of insider–outsider dynamics is still in its

								and the Demand for Regulation” section). Using Latino barometer (LAB) data for up to eighteen countries and running a battery of multi-level regressions to understand the determinants of public opinion.	effects from existing labour laws to public perception.	(effective protection.	infancy, especially for Latin America and better (survey or experimental) data will yield stronger conclusions in future research.
14	Ulla Liukkonen 2020	The ILO and Transformation of Labour Law	To explore some of the biggest challenges to the ILO caused by globalization and altering of the collective labour rights scene	Conceptual	Industrial relations Collective bargaining	International labour standards that protect freedom, equality and safety of workers	Globalization has furthered problems relating to transnational social dumping, and the labour dimension of human trafficking still remains largely unidentified. With forms of exploitation that do not have national borders, the narrative of vulnerabilities makes more inclusive regulatory	Examining the recent transformation of collective bargaining regimes at national and transnational level and the consequences for normativities that characterize the relationship between labour law and the system of international labour standards.	Domestic bargaining regimes are influenced by decentralization whereas in a transnational setting, with the phenomena of contractual arrangements between multinational enterprises and trade unions or other employee representatives, transnational collectivization of labour law is occurring.	The ILO Centenary Declaration for the Future of Work of 2019 constructs a commitment to decent work and sustainability by linking social, trade, financial, economic, and environmental policies together. The	Building a perspective on major global challenges to the ILO at the beginning of its second centenary requires an assessment of the labour question in terms of flexibility and vulnerabilities. This raises the question of inclusivity, calling for the ILO decent work agenda,

							responses highly significant to the ILO as an organization whose purpose is to promote social justice universally.		The process of transnationalization of labour law affects the traditional labour law paradigm with profound consequences for our understanding of the purpose and role of labour law. The transformation of labour law highlights regulatory developments that require reinforcement of the role of fundamental labour rights	transformation of labour law highlights developments that deserve attention when we consider the role of the ILO at the beginning of its second centenary	employment creation, social protection, and rights at work and social dialogue, all to be more firmly integrated in global regulatory approaches to work.
15	Kiernan Joliat and Kailing Li 2007	The Law at Work: what you need to know about your rights	The booklet helps answer some of the most frequently asked questions about the laws that cover workers and workplaces	Conceptual	Employment Laws	The information in this booklet comes from several sources, most published by the US Department of Labour or the New York State Department of Labour	The objective of this booklet is to answer all possible questions for all potential workers	A compiled listing /document that includes all legal rights on employment and answering possible questions	Answers to several questions and findings on legal practices and laws related to employment covering on the job, off the job and special groups of workers	Help and support to workers and an understanding of their rights	The authors are not lawyers and the information in this booklet is not professional legal advice
16	Fachry Ahsany	Legal Protection	The purpose	Conceptual	Labour Rights	Primary law and	The objective of this paper	Using the normative	The government	The form of	Welfare can be achieved

	Ahmad Faiz Alamsyah Sholahudin Al-Fatih 2020	n of Labour Rights During the Corona virus Disease 2019 (Covid-19) Pandemic	of this paper is to find legal issues on labour right during Covid-19 pandemic in Indonesia .			secondary law, which primary law refers to Law No. 21 of 2000 concerning Trade Unions, Law No. 13 of 2003 concerning Manpower, Law No. 3 of 1992 concerning Labour Social Security (JAMSOSTEK) , Law No. 1 of 1970 concerning Work Safety, Law No. 2 of 2004 concerning Settlement of Industrial Relations	is to analyses some of the regulation and legal government act to protect labour right who were terminated (Pemutusan Hubungan Kerja/PHK) during Covid-19 pandemic	legal research carried out by examining mere library materials or secondary data- called normative legal research or library legal study,	issued two programs to solve PHK and protect labour rights, namely Pre-Works Card and Cash Incentive Program (Bantuan Langsung Tunai/BLT). It actively helped employees to create a new job and continue their daily life.	protectio n or governme nt programs for workers who have been laid off (PHK) due to the Coronavir us Disease 2019 (COVID - 19) pandemic , namely Pre-Work Card And Cash- Intensive Programs . The two programs have the same goal to overcome the problem of unemploy ment in Indonesia .	by workers when their needs are met, both physical and spiritual needs. In this way an association or labour union is formed which is tasked with channelling the opinions or suggestions of workers to form an industrial involvement by passing through the company. As a form of welfare given to laborers can be realized through the provision of labour rights and decent wages, but that is still often not done well.
17	Malte Reichelt, Kinga Makovi & Anahit Sargsyan 2021	The impact of COVID-19 on gender inequality in the labour	COVID-19 and ensuing changes in mobility have altered	Conceptual	Gender Inequality Employment and Unemployment Index	COVID-related changes in labour market outcomes:	This paper investigates two interrelated questions. First, analysing how men's	Analysing a representative sample of respondents in the US, Germany, and Singapore	Results show that transitions to unemployment, reductions in working hours and transitions to	The long-term consequences will depend on how both men and	These results indicate that gender-role attitudes might adapt to the lived realities.

		market and gender-role attitudes	employment relations for millions of people across the globe. Emerging evidence shows that women may be more severely affected by this change. The pandemic , however, may have an impact beyond the immediate restructuring of employment and shift gender-role attitudes within households as a result of changes in the division of household labour			<p>*Transition to working from home</p> <p>*Reduction in working hours</p> <p>*Transition to unemployment</p>	and women's employment status, their working hours, and their working arrangements (main place of work) changed during the pandemic. Second, focuses on people who experienced such transitions in their household to study the association between these transitions and gender-role attitudes.	These countries were selected because of their different experiences with the unfolding of the corona virus outbreak, governmental responses, and citizens' concerns about the virus.	working from home have been more frequent for women than for men – although not to the same extent across the three countries. Among couples who had been employed at the start of the pandemic, men express more egalitarian gender-role attitudes if they became unemployed but their partners remained employed, while women express more traditional attitudes if they became unemployed and their partners remained employed	women experience further shifts in their employment relations as economies recover. Potential shifts in attitudes toward women's participation in the labour market may also contribute to their economic outcomes for years to come. Contributes to the gender pay gap	To our knowledge, they are the first to study this relationship in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic.
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